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THE RULE OF LAW UNDER SCRUTINY: DISCRETIONARY POWERS AS A NORMATIVE FACTOR OF CORRUPTION IN THE REPUBLIC OF NORTH MACEDONIA

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Abstract

This paper undertakes a normative analysis of the rule of law principle in the Republic of North Macedonia focusing on the critical examination of discretionary powers and their potential role in facilitating systematic corruption. The main focus will be on the regulatory framework governing discretionary powers to identify legal gaps and institutional weaknesses that could be a potential source of corrupt practices.

Methodologically, the paper employs normative analyses, comparative analyses, empirical method and case studies, with a primary emphasis on European Court of Human Rights (ECtHR) judgments.

Additionally, the paper proposes measures to constrain discretionary powers and enhance mechanisms for combating systematic corruption in our country.

Keywords: rule of law, corruption, discretionary powers.

1. INTRODUCTION

The importance of good governance and raising awareness among citizens to demand high professional standards, efficient institutions and successful public administration, as well as greater accountability, is one of the factors for a successful fight against corruption – particularly in situations where discretionary decisions are involved.¹

¹ Discretion (Latin *discretio*, French *diskretion*) is prudence and caution in speech and behavior, attention, restraint; taking into account the sensitivities of others; restraint, silence; discretion, generosity or attention (towards the winner). This term also has additional meanings: to surrender to discretion - to surrender to the mercy and grace of others; discretion, - according to one's own will; discretionary right (law) - the right to make decisions within the legal framework at one's own discretion, against which there is no legal remedy.

Discretionary authority (Latin *discretio*, in contrast, from Latin *discernere* – to distinguish) is a form of weaker legal binding of a state body to a legal norm. The subject of discretionary authority, although less frequently, can also be issues of procedural law in administrative and judicial (civil)

The establishment of a framework for systemic limitation of discretionary powers enables the strengthening of legal certainty for citizens and protection from the arbitrariness of institutions, but also encourages reform in strengthening the control mechanisms for the exercise of these powers by institutions. Discretionary powers, in the simplest terms, represent an opportunity for public sector institutions to freely decide in certain situations. Such powers are held by institutions belonging to all three branches of government (legislative, executive and judicial).²

Discretionary powers are an institute of public law that refer to the ability of public sector institutions to freely decide for the more efficient and effective achievement of certain goals. Discretionary powers of the administration mean freedom in consideration, action and decision-making, which means the ability to choose a solution, to do something or not, and if the option to do something is chosen, to choose one of the possible ways (Breban, 2002, p. 204).

Discretionary powers are not unlimited (Breban, 2002).³ Institutions vested with such authority are required to consider the purpose for which the law confers it, and their decisions must be thoroughly justified and clearly explained.

However, these powers are not resistant to abuse and in the absence of a clear procedure and guidelines for their application and control, they can serve as an instrument for materializing corruption, cronyism and clientelism (employment in the public sector, appointment of management and leadership structures in public sector institutions, allocation of public resources/funds, citizens' access to public services and making certain political decisions.) (Guidelines for the exercise of discretionary powers, p. 5).

So, as Munir, Khan, and Ahmad (2020, p. 183-191) emphasize, certain standards have to be laid down by the legislature, administration and norms of practice to maximize the advantages of discretionary powers and to minimize the susceptibility of their exploitation.

In accordance with Recommendation No. R (80)2 of the CoE Committee of Ministers, an administrative authority, when exercising a discretionary power: 1. does not pursue a purpose other than that for which the power has been conferred; 2. observes objectivity and impartiality, taking into account only the factors relevant to the particular

proceedings, and very rarely in criminal proceedings. It is most often applied in administrative proceedings in the form of discretionary (free) assessment (French: *pouvoir discrétionnaire*: discretionary authority, German: *freies Ermessen*: free assessment), which means the authority of the competent body to choose, between two or more possibilities provided for in the legal norm, that is, to find the most appropriate solution in a specific case.

² Discretionary powers can differ from the perspective of the holder, as follows: executive discretionary powers (which are held by public office holders within the executive branch and are exercised by making an executive decision); administrative discretionary powers (which are used by public officials when resolving cases in administrative proceedings and deciding on the rights, obligations and legal interests of citizens) and judicial discretionary powers (which refer to the powers of public prosecutors and courts - most often referring to the right to free judicial decision-making).

³ In the Barel case, when communist candidates were excluded from the competition for admission to the National School of Administrative Affairs on the basis of the discretionary authority of ministers, lawyer Moro Giaferri emphasized in a parliamentary debate that: "discretionary authority is an authority that should be used with discretion (prudence, attention)". This is a political, not a legal formulation. However, in terms of law, certain restrictions, even when it comes to discretionary authority, mean that the freedom of the administration is not complete, but is subordinated to the principle of legality.

case; 3. observes the principle of equality before the law by avoiding unfair discrimination; 4. maintains a proper balance between any adverse effects which its decision may have on the rights, liberties or interests of persons and the purpose which it pursues; 5. takes its decision within a time which is reasonable having regard to the matter at stake and 6. applies any general administrative guidelines in a consistent manner while at the same time taking account of the particular circumstances of each case.

2. THE NECESSITY OF DISCRETIONARY POWERS

The law, by its very nature, cannot predetermine or regulate every conceivable factual situation that may arise in social and legal relations. To assume that the legislator is capable of prescribing exhaustive and rigid norms for all administrative interactions, thereby eliminating any scope for autonomous decision-making, would be a legal fiction. Inevitably, there exists a residual domain of discretion – a sphere of administrative latitude - within which public authorities, guided by the purpose of the law and the principles of proportionality, legality, and reasonableness, must exercise their decisions in light of the specific circumstances of each case.

However, free assessment must not represent arbitrariness, i.e. arbitrariness of the decision-making body. The body cannot act according to its personal will or mood, but is nevertheless bound by the general rules for the performance of its service and function, which must be performed in accordance with the law and the public interest. Decisions made under free assessment must be made within the limits of the authorization and in accordance with the purpose that was to be achieved with such authorization (Davitkovski B. & Pavlovska Daneva A. p. 279).

According to Hicks (2024, p.365-375), the discretionary powers have three faces: the first face of discretion is the power to decide and distribute; the second face of discretion is the power to interpret and enforce and the third face of discretion is the power to disclose and expose.

3. THEORETICAL AND PRACTICAL DIMENSIONS OF THE EXERCISE OF DISCRETIONARY POWERS

In legal theory, the analysis of discretionary powers is closely tied to the concept of the rule of law, which requires that public institutions operate strictly in accordance with the principle of legality. This implies that their actions must remain within the boundaries established by law, thereby minimizing the scope for arbitrary decision-making. Excessive latitude could otherwise jeopardize both the principle of legality and the legal certainty guaranteed to citizens.

Legal science conceptualizes discretionary powers as inherent in legal norms contained within abstract and general acts (laws, by-laws), which are subsequently concretized through their application to individual cases and materialized in specific administrative acts (decisions, rulings, or solutions). From the perspective of normative construction, discretionary power is frequently indicated by formulations such as “*may*”, which confer upon the competent authority a legally sanctioned margin of appreciation. Nevertheless, such discretion is not unlimited; it remains bounded by the principles of legality, proportionality, and the prohibition of arbitrariness. Norms granting discretionary powers are embedded throughout the hierarchy of legal acts, thereby reflecting a systematic delegation of evaluative authority to administrative bodies.

Legal theorist Grey (1979, p. 114) emphasizes that the limits of discretionary powers are defined in two cases *Boulis* and *Congreve*. According to him, these limits can

be summarized as a duty to act: (a) in good faith, (b) uninfluenced by irrelevant considerations or motives, (c) reasonably, and (d) within the statutory bounds of the discretion.

The Constitution, as the highest general legal act of the state, does not contain such norms. Laws, as second-level acts, contain norms with discretionary powers. At the third level are the by-laws that elaborate parts of the laws, and they are most often adopted by the state administration bodies or the Government of the Republic of North Macedonia (procedures, rulebooks, decrees, decisions, instructions, programs, solutions and conclusions) that have "erga omnes" legal effect.

With specific acts (decisions), institutions decide on the rights, obligations and legal interests of citizens and refer to legal and natural persons, and they have "inter partes" legal effect.⁴

The most important laws in the Macedonian legal system that directly mention discretionary powers are: the Law on General Administrative Procedure (LAAP), the Law on Administrative Disputes (LAD), the Law on Prevention of Corruption and Conflict of Interest (LPCI) and the Criminal Code (CC).

The Law on General Administrative Procedure in Article 5 paragraph 3 states that "if a public authority is authorized by law to decide on a discretionary basis, the administrative act should be adopted within the limits of the law granting the authorization, in accordance with the purpose for which the authorization was granted and be specifically explained".

The Law on Administrative Disputes as a procedural law only determines how administrative courts act when a case related to discretionary powers is brought before them, and Article 6 paragraph 2 of the Administrative Disputes Act stipulates that "an administrative dispute cannot be conducted regarding the correct application of the free assessment by a public authority (discretionary power) when adopting an individual administrative act, but it can be conducted regarding the legality of such an act and the limits of such power". Additionally, Article 60, paragraph 3, line 1, stipulates that "the court cannot decide on the merits in full jurisdiction if the disputed act was adopted with the discretionary authority of the authorities, but the court shall annul the disputed individual administrative act and return it for re-decision to the authority that adopted it".

The Law on Prevention of Corruption and Conflict of Interest recognizes discretionary powers as one of the greatest risks to corruption, and in Article 8, paragraph 6 of the Law on Prevention of Corruption and Conflict of Interest, the term "risk of corruption" means "inappropriate use of discretionary powers".

The Criminal Code in Article 353-c provides for "a prison sentence of three months to three years if an official or responsible person in a public enterprise or public institution violates the legal regulations on conflict of interest or on conscientious conduct in the exercise of discretionary authority, by failing to exercise due supervision or in any other way clearly acts negligently in the exercise of his or her authority and duties and thereby obtains for himself or another some benefit or causes harm to another".

The remaining laws in the Macedonian legal system confer discretionary powers to public sector institutions, either explicitly or implicitly, through vague and broadly interpreted legal norms. The lack of a consistent administrative practice results in arbitrary decision-

⁴ From a legal perspective, all solutions provided for by the legal norm are of equal value, and the competent authority assesses the solution that best meets the reasons for public interest and expediency in that case.

making by authorities, which undermines both the principle of legality and the legal certainty of citizens. (Discretionary Powers Report, p. 10-11).

In practice, the use of discretionary powers is very widespread, and there is no institution that does not use them. Their use is especially problematic in cases where there is no legal basis for their use, where the institution itself decides on its own discretion to decide on a certain "right" (powers that are not provided for by law), determines the criteria for that "right" on its own discretion, decides on its own discretion who will receive and who will not receive that "right", and determines the scope, i.e. the amount of that "right" if it concerns certain financial resources.

Discretionary powers are not resistant to abuse and, in the absence of a clear procedure and guidelines for their application and control, serve as an instrument for materializing corruption (Final report of the project "Assessment of Vulnerability to Corruption in Employment Policies and Procedures, with a Special Focus on Nepotism, Cronyism and Clientelism", 2021).

Professor Wade (Breban, 2002, p.206) points out that the very essence of discretionary power also means the right to make mistakes, which is also accepted in French law, by introducing the concept of a manifest error of assessment, which means that the holder of discretionary power can make an oversight in the assessment, but does not have the right to make a noticeable error.

The choice of the right measure in discretionary powers⁵ is a very important political-legal issue, because the construction of so-called legal gaps depends on its necessary and necessary representation, and its enormous (excessive) application increases the possibilities for their incorrect application and abuse.

However, the right of discretionary decision-making of the administration for certain administrative areas is represented in all legal systems, including the legal system of the Republic of North Macedonia, and the possibilities for its abuse should be reduced (Davitkovski B. & Pavlovska Daneva A. p.279).

Discretionary administrative acts or acts adopted at discretion are those acts whose author is authorized, at discretion, to determine whether in a specific case he will adopt an act at all and, if he does, what the content of the act will be. Discretionary acts contain the authority for the administration to choose between two or more legally equal alternatives.

4. MECHANISMS TO PREVENT ABUSE OF DISCRETIONARY POWERS BY INSTITUTIONS

According to the established institutional system, the acts of the public administration are subject to supervision and control by the higher authorities (ministries), specialized bodies (second-instance commissions) or the courts (Administrative, Higher Administrative and Constitutional Court).

Supervision is exercised over the legality of general acts (rulebooks, statutes, etc.), over specific acts, over the operation and over the material and financial operations of the administration and is carried out by independent institutions such as the Parliament of the Republic of Macedonia, the State Audit Office (SAO), the Ombudsman (OP), the State

⁵ When it comes to discretionary acts, i.e. discretionary decisions, there are certain guidelines and rules according to which the administration must be guided in decision-making: the discretionary authority must be provided for by law; the act must be adopted in a legally prescribed procedure; the form of the act must be respected; the authority must not be exceeded; the authority should not be used contrary to the purpose for which it was granted.

Commission for the Prevention of Corruption (SCPC) and others, whose recommendations have only a consultative role and do not carry legal consequences for the institutions. This is important, because the abuse of discretionary powers can only be determined when their acts are effectively controlled.

With regard to specific acts of the administration, i.e. decisions by which it decides in administrative procedures where it has discretionary powers (discretionary decisions), citizens can:

- file a regular legal remedy, an appeal before the State Commission for Decision-Making in Administrative Procedures and Employment Procedures in the Second Instance and

- if they are not satisfied with the second instance decision, they can initiate an administrative dispute by filing an appeal with the Administrative Court, and further use extraordinary legal remedies with the Higher Administrative Court.

The laws with the vague and poorly defined provisions of the laws and bylaws grant the institutions tacit freedom in certain situations to act as they deem best. This combination of shortcomings in the system provides greater scope for the abuse of discretionary powers violating the principle of legality in the work of the public administration, the legal certainty of citizens and making the rule of law impossible.

Silveira and Ettner (2020) in their paper propose several mechanisms (legislative drafting tools) for limiting discretionary powers: a) clear identification of discretionary powers; b) avoid using discretion as a principle; c) avoid vague legal concepts; d) use discretion when necessary; and e) when possible use non-exhaustive lists of cases.

5. DISCRETIONARY POWERS IN THE JURISPRUDENCE OF THE ECtHR

The ECtHR has addressed the question of discretionary powers in a number of cases. This paper examines several judgments that, either explicitly or implicitly, reveal instances where national authorities abused their discretionary powers, resulting in violations of the ECHR.

The Court consistently holds that broad discretionary powers are not per se incompatible with the Convention - but they must be:

- prescribed by law (clear, accessible, foreseeable) (*Gillan and Quinton v. United Kingdom*, Application no. 4158/05), paras. 76, 77),
- circumscribed by safeguards against arbitrariness (*Case of Kruslin v. France*, Application No. 11801/85),
- be necessary in a democratic society (*Roman Zakharov v. Russia*, Application no. 47143/06), and
- proportionate to the legitimate aim pursued (*ML v. North Macedonia*, Application no. 30206/23, para 56).

Where safeguards are absent, or where discretion is exercised arbitrarily, the Court finds violations.

The case of *Gillan and Quinton v. United Kingdom* (para.87) concerns stop-and-search measures under Terrorism Act 2000 that give powers to police to stop people without reasonable suspicion. In conclusion, the Court considers that:

“the powers of authorization and confirmation as well as those of stop and search under sections 44 and 45 of the 2000 Act are neither sufficiently circumscribed nor subject to adequate legal safeguards against abuse. They are not, therefore, “in accordance with the law” and it follows that there has been a violation of Article 8 of the Convention”.

According to ECtHR, the absence of any requirement of “reasonable suspicion” gave the police “an almost unfettered discretion”. So, the Court found violation of Article 8.

1. In the case of *Kruslin v. France* the applicant’s telephone was tapped in the context of a criminal investigation. French law at the time allowed wiretapping but gave very little guidance on **who could authorize it, for how long, or under what conditions**. The Court’s reasoning reads as follows:

“Above all, the system does not for the time being afford adequate safeguards against various possible abuses. For example, the categories of people liable to have their telephones tapped by judicial order and the nature of the offences which may give rise to such an order are nowhere defined. Nothing obliges a judge to set a limit on the duration of telephone tapping. Similarly unspecified are the procedure for drawing up the summary reports containing intercepted conversations; the precautions to be taken in order to communicate the recordings intact and in their entirety for possible inspection by the judge (who can hardly verify the number and length of the original tapes on the spot) and by the defense; and the circumstances in which recordings may or must be erased or the tapes be destroyed, in particular where an accused has been discharged by an investigating judge or acquitted by a court. The information provided by the Government on these various points shows at best the existence of a practice, but a practice lacking the necessary regulatory control in the absence of legislation or case-law (para. 35)”

So, ECtHR found that the French law did not indicate with sufficient clarity regarding the **scope** of the authorities’ discretion, and the **minimum safeguards** required to prevent abuse. The lack of clear rules meant that the discretion was **not circumscribed by safeguards against arbitrariness**. The Court found violation of Article 8. In the case *Roman Zakharov v. Russia* the Court found violation of Article 8 because Russian law allowed interception of communications with broad discretion and minimal oversight and it lacked adequate safeguards. ECtHR states as follows:

“In view of the shortcomings identified above, the Court finds that Russian law does not meet the “quality of law” requirement and is incapable of keeping the “interference” to what is “necessary in a democratic society”. There has accordingly been a violation of Article 8 of the Convention (paras. 304, 305)”

The case *ML v. North Macedonia* concerns domestic barring order (restrictions on proximity to family members), so the Court examined proportionality and safeguards in the order:

“Lastly, the applicant was not even informed, let alone involved in any such reassessment conducted by the pre-trial judge, and the Government did not argue otherwise. His subsequent request of 25 July 2023 that the barring order be lifted apparently went unanswered. The Court cannot but conclude that, in respect of the mandatory reassessment of whether the need for the barring order persisted, the applicant was not afforded any procedural guarantees capable of enabling him to protect his interest in being reunited with his daughter.

In sum, the insufficient reasoning of the three-judge panel confirming the barring order, together with the absence of formal reasoned decisions, the lack of meaningful scrutiny on the basis of relevant updated information and the failure to involve the applicant in the mandatory periodic reassessment of the barring order, fell short of the procedural requirements under Article 8 of the Convention (paras. 78,79)”.

The Court concludes that there has been a violation of Article 8 of the Convention.

The case of *Grzęda v. Poland* concerns the premature termination of the applicant’s term of office as a judicial member of the National Council of the Judiciary (Krajowa Rada Sądownictwa, KRS) in Poland due to legislative reforms of 2017. The applicant, Judge Jan Grzęda, claimed that the termination of his term of office without the possibility of judicial protection violated his rights under Article 6 § 1 of the European Convention on Human Rights (the right to a fair trial, including access to a court). The ECtHR, in a landmark judgment of 15 March 2022, found a violation of Article 6(1), emphasizing the crucial importance of judicial independence and the need for procedural safeguards against arbitrary interference with judicial functions. According to the Court, the reform granted broad discretionary powers to the Polish legislative and executive authorities to restructure the judiciary, including the termination of judicial mandates without transparent criteria or accountability. The ECtHR criticized this as a threat to judicial independence, as it allowed for unchecked political interference in judicial functions. The absence of judicial protection increased the risk of arbitrary exercise of discretionary powers, a key concern in the context of legal imperfections.

Grzęda v. Poland is a landmark case in the ECtHR’s case law on judicial independence. It reinforces the principle that judges must have access to a court to challenge decisions affecting their status, particularly in the context of legislative or executive interference. The judgment has significant implications for Poland’s judicial system, calling for reforms to comply with Article 6(1). It also adds to international pressure on Poland to address concerns about the rule of law, as reflected in related EU proceedings and Council of Europe reports.

The case sets a standard for all Council of Europe member states, underlining the need for procedural safeguards to protect judicial independence and prevent arbitrary exercise of power. It is particularly relevant for countries undergoing judicial reform or facing problems with political influence over the judiciary.

While the case is specific to Poland, its principles are relevant to any jurisdiction, including North Macedonia, where concerns exist about judicial independence, legal gaps and corruption. For example, reports by the State Commission for the Prevention of Corruption (SCPC) have identified legal gaps and excessive discretionary powers in areas such as urban planning and local government (Annual Report on the Work of the State Commission for the Prevention of Corruption for 2023, p. 63).

In case *Baka v. Hungary*, former President of the Supreme Court of Hungary, was prematurely removed from office in 2011 due to constitutional and legislative changes, partly in response to his criticism of judicial reforms. He was not able to challenge the decision in court. The ECtHR found a violation of Article 6(1) (right of access to a court) and Article 10 (freedom of expression), finding that the removal was retaliation for his criticism and that the legislative changes undermined judicial independence. ECtHR states (Information Note on the Court’s case-law no. 174, 2014, p. 3):

“As regards the proportionality of the interference, the applicant’s term of office as President of the Supreme Court had been terminated three and a half years before the end of the fixed term applicable under the legislation in force at the time of his election. Furthermore, although the applicant had remained in office as a judge of the new Kúria, the premature termination of his mandate had had pecuniary consequences”.

Accordingly, the ECtHR implicitly found that the legislation granted the authorities broad powers to remove Baka without transparent criteria.

In the *Case of Ramos Nunes De Carvalho E Sá v. Portugal* ECtHR also found a violation of Article 6(1) of the ECHR on account of the lack of impartial and independent judicial review of disciplinary sanctions, highlighting systemic problems in the Portuguese disciplinary system. In this case the applicant, a judge in Portugal, was subject to disciplinary proceedings by the High Council of the Judiciary for alleged professional misconduct. She alleged that the proceedings were unfair, with limited access to judicial review and bias in the judicial decision-making. From the perspective of discretionary powers, practically the Supreme Court had considerable discretionary powers, which gave rise to a risk of bias. ECtHR concluded that:

“In the light of the foregoing the Court concludes that, in the circumstances of the present case – taking into consideration the specific context of disciplinary proceedings conducted against a judge, the seriousness of the penalties, the fact that the procedural guarantees before the CSM were limited, and the need to assess factual evidence going to the applicant’s credibility and that of the witnesses and constituting a decisive aspect of the case – the combined effect of two factors, namely the insufficiency of the judicial review performed by the Judicial Division of the Supreme Court and the lack of a hearing either at the stage of the disciplinary proceedings or at the judicial review stage, meant that the applicant’s case was not heard in accordance with the requirements of Article 6 § 1 of the Convention (para.214)”.

CONCLUSION

Discretionary powers represent a vital component of modern legal systems, as they provide the necessary flexibility for institutions to act in situations where rigid adherence to legal norms cannot adequately address the particularities of a case. Yet, this very freedom of decision-making carries the inherent risk of unequal, arbitrary, or even abusive use.

The central challenge, therefore, lies in striking a balance between the need for discretion and the imperative of legal certainty and the protection of civil rights. Legislators must set clear boundaries and criteria for the exercise of such powers, while judicial oversight and adherence to the principles of the rule of law serve as essential safeguards against arbitrary practices.

In this light, discretionary powers should not be regarded as unlimited authority, but rather as a tool which – when exercised in line with the principles of fairness, equality, and proportionality – can enhance both the efficiency and the justice of legal application.

The principles of ECtHR cases shown above offer a roadmap for addressing systemic challenges in the legal system of North Macedonia, as well. By applying these principles, the country can strengthen judicial independence, close legal gaps, regulate

discretionary powers, improve judicial discretion, and strengthen the fight against corruption. Reforms based on these standards will not only bring Macedonian legislation into line with the European Convention, but will also increase public trust in the judiciary and the rule of law.

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EFFECTIVE JUDICIAL PROTECTION FOR THE LAWFUL EXERCISE OF DISCRETIONARY POWERS

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Abstract

This paper highlights the role of the judiciary in ensuring the rule of law in the Republic of North Macedonia, particularly in the lawful exercise of discretionary powers by all holders of public office. The study examines the need to strengthen anti-corruption policies in order to meet the standards of Chapter 23 for North Macedonia's accession to the European Union.

Within this paper, the subject of research is the discretionary powers of holders of public office. Initially, the paper defines discretionary powers, their types, elements, and the principles for applying discretionary powers. The paper identifies institutional weaknesses due to improper use of authority, information, and documentation. This is followed by an analysis of court decisions focusing on administrative judicial control over the limits of such powers. By presenting decisions of the Administrative Court for the period 2015–2025, the paper emphasizes the need for a proportionality test when exercising discretionary powers. Finally, it concludes that there is a need to establish a standard model that North Macedonia must adopt in order to reduce risks and prevent potential adverse consequences arising from the misuse of discretionary powers.

Keywords: rule of law, discretionary power, judicial protection, proportionality test, binding nature of final court decisions

1. INTRODUCTION

The concept of modern democracies is based on the responsible exercise of power. In the modern political community, the hallmark of democracy is the guarantee of freedoms and rights, establishing a rule of law state with zero tolerance for abuses. The division of power into legislative, executive, and judicial aims primarily to prevent the concentration of power. However, it is primarily necessary to pass laws that not only declaratively proclaim rights but can also be functionally applied. The executive power is obliged to implement them through the administrative bodies, and the judicial power, by resolving disputes, implements them in practice to protect the rights of citizens.

This paper highlights the role of judicial power in ensuring the rule of law in the Republic of North Macedonia in relation to the lawful practice of discretionary powers by all holders of public office. By combining normative analysis with empirical methods to explore different legal grounds of final court judgments (case studies) of the Administrative Court (hereinafter: the Court), this paper identifies procedural violations in

the exercise of discretionary powers. By presenting cases from the administrative judiciary through the test of proportionality, a comparative analysis of court decisions for the period 2015-2025 is made. The main goal of this empirical research is to detect weaknesses, all with the aim of reducing risks and preventing possible undesirable consequences due to abuses in discretionary powers.

2. DISCRETIONARY POWERS THROUGH THE PRISM OF NATIONAL LEGISLATION AND CASE LAW

2.1 Legal-Philosophical Conception of Discretionary Powers

In his work *The Laws*, Plato discusses the development of state systems in history and explains the relationship between justice and power (Plato, 1971:521). He believes that the one who enforces the law and is consistent in respect must be authorized to implement and supervise the application of the laws. Unfair conduct is unacceptable from those in power who are obliged to apply the laws and interpret them correctly (Rawls, 1997:269).

Weber created a systemic theory of power and explains it as a "factual situation in which the expressed will is an order from those who rule and influences the actions of others" (Weber, 1976:446). Labović, through the etymological roots and theoretical teachings of the phenomenological forms of power, provides an analysis of the conceptual distinction between the terms power, politics, might, and authority (Labović, 2006:40). In political practice, the division of power into legislative, executive, and judicial branches is generally accepted. However, Loewenstein (as cited in Kitanovski, 1996:30) believes that when dividing power and functions, the control over politics is of essential importance, and this is ensured not only by the division of power but also by applying the principles of political responsibility.

Political might endangers other principles of the rule of law: the principle of legality, free elections, the exercise of public functions, the public interest, an independent judiciary, and the constitutionally presumed legitimacy of the state. The question arises of how the rule of law state can develop its own defence system, and how the rule of law state can be protected "against the state" (Kambovski, 2005:580). Academician Kambovski believes that for self-defence, the state "must embed strong and autonomous instruments of protection, above all, through an independent and powerful judiciary and other institutions for the protection of human rights that will act as a counterweight to the criminal aspirations of political powerful figures" (Kambovski, 2005:59).

The idea of democracy appears in the text of the Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms in three different forms that are used as standpoints and interpreted in concrete cases from the practice of the European Court. It appears primarily as a principle contained in the Preamble, which requires all members of the Convention to interpret the articles in accordance with the general spirit of the Convention as an instrument designed to maintain and proclaim the ideals and values of a democratic society (Omejec, 2013:1089).

According to legal science, the rule of law and the rule of law state seemingly appear to be synonyms and imply issues of constitutionality and judicial control of constitutionality, but etymologically they have a different origin and are not identical, although they have common points. The 'rule of law' is a term that originates from England and was developed by Anglo-American legal theory, while the genesis of the term 'rule of law state' is from German legal thought. Professor of Constitutional Law Svetomir Škarić elaborates on the two concepts and states that the concept of the rule of law state is

based on natural law, more precisely on human freedoms and rights, and is associated with liberal democracy and less with the functions of power and formal legality. On the other hand, the rule of law state implies the functioning of state power and formal legality, and less the quality of the laws. Therefore, the Constitution of the Republic of North Macedonia adopted the term rule of law as a fundamental value from the aspect of limiting power and respecting human rights and freedoms.

In the modern British constitution, the term 'rule of law', according to Dicey, implies the sovereignty of Parliament, and for form, the rule of law is the supremacy of the law (Dicey, 1889:303). The rule of law implies respect for the rights of the citizen: the right to property, existential rights, to work, to a salary, to social and health insurance, and freedoms, ensured security, all in the sense that power should be limited by existing judicial control.

When it comes to the rule of law state, Škarić refers to the concept from three aspects, stating that the concept of the rule of law state encompasses a material, formal, and social aspect (Škarić, 2014:36). The material aspect was developed by Robert von Mohl, the formal by Friedrich Stahl, and the social by Heinz Nauler (as cited in Škarić, 2014:37). The material aspect takes into account the primacy of law over state power. First, this means guaranteeing human rights and freedoms, and personal freedoms and rights; second, ensuring favourable conditions for the development of civil society; and third, determining the legal limits of state power. The formal aspect emphasizes, first, the inviolability, the formal characteristics of constitutionality and legality, and not the goals of the state and the content of laws and other regulations and by-laws. The rule of law state is valued depending on how much constitutionality and legality are realized as formal-legal categories, and as a result, the rule of law state can be a mere formal legality, without the natural-law content of the laws and the guarantee of freedoms and rights.

2.2 Concept, Definition, and Types of Discretionary Powers

According to Recommendation No. R(80)2 of the Committee of Ministers, discretionary powers are defined as "powers that give administrative bodies a certain degree of freedom regarding the decision to be made, allowing them to choose the one they consider most appropriate from several legally acceptable decisions" (Council of Europe, 1980). Additionally, Recommendation CM/Rec(2007) of the Committee of Ministers stipulates that "the administration shall not be arbitrary when using discretionary powers" and that "when the administration uses discretionary powers, it shall maintain a proper balance between any negative effects that its decisions have on the rights or interests of private persons and the goal they pursue" (Council of Europe, 2007).

Discretionary powers represent a right that the law grants to institutions (most often to the heads of institutions or their authorized officials) from the public sector to decide freely in situations that are also determined by law. Legal science first views discretionary powers as a legal norm contained in a general legal act (law, by-law), which must be applied to a real individual case and then transformed into a concrete administrative act (resolution, decision, etc.) (Gjorgievski & Vrglevski, 2023:11).

Discretionary powers can be distinguished in relation to who uses them as:

- Executive discretionary powers (held by the holders of public office within the executive power and exercised by issuing an executive decision).
- Administrative discretionary powers (used by public officials when resolving cases in administrative procedures and deciding on the rights, obligations, and legal interests of citizens).
- Judicial discretionary powers (referring to the powers of public prosecutors and courts – most often referring to the right of free judicial discretion).

Discretionary powers can also be distinguished according to the way they are set up, i.e., formulated: Legal acts may contain legal norms with the so-called explicit or express discretionary powers, which clearly instruct the body to make a free decision (discretionary power) when choosing one of the two or more options contained in the norm. Such discretionary powers are most often found in substantive laws that provide concrete rights for citizens and regulate special administrative procedures in which those rights can be exercised.

2.3 Discretionary Powers in National Legislation

In the Macedonian legal system, discretionary powers are directly mentioned in the Law on Prevention of Corruption and Conflict of Interest (LPCCI), the Criminal Code (CC), the Law on General Administrative Procedure (LGAP), and the Law on Administrative Disputes (LAD). The essence of discretionary powers is the freedom of the official when making a specific decision on behalf of a public institution. The legislation does not directly define discretionary powers, but it nevertheless recognizes them as a legal institute and prescribes how they should be applied by the administration and controlled by the Court. In the legislation, the phrases "discretionary powers" and "resolving by free assessment" are used synonymously.

Measuring the proportionality and reasonableness of the administration's decisions, especially discretionary decisions, is closely related to the purpose of the authorization, which officials can initially perceive in the provisions of the law from which the discretionary power emanates. Specifically, laws usually begin with an article describing the purpose of the law, which should be reflected throughout the text of the law and during its application in specific cases. The words "purpose," "subject," or "function" are commonly used.

The LPCCI recognizes discretionary powers as one of the greatest risks for corruption. Under the term "risk of corruption," a definition of corruption is given, which means abuse of office, public authorization, official duty, or position to gain benefit, directly or through an intermediary, for oneself or another, thus encompassing the concepts of passive corruption and active corruption (LPCCI, 2019, Article 8). The Law contains definitions of several terms: public interest, public authorization, and the term official duty, with the aim of ensuring the lawful, independent, impartial, ethical, responsible, and transparent implementation of the law.

For the exercise of discretionary powers, it is determined that every official is obliged to make decisions conscientiously, taking into account all the facts and circumstances of the specific case and the principle of legality and fairness (LPCCI, 2019, Article 63). A natural or legal person dissatisfied with a decision made on the basis of discretionary power and who believes that the decision was made due to corruptness can

submit a petition to the State Commission. The SCSC is obliged to consider the petition and, within 30 days from the date of receipt, inform the natural or legal person about the action taken on it. Furthermore, it must publish statistical data on the submitted petitions on this legal basis on its website twice a year.

The special form of incrimination is unconscientious work in the service from Article 353-v, paragraph 4 of the Criminal Code (1996). Academician Kambovski gives a definition of "unconscientious conduct" which consists of a violation of a special regulation or the abuse of discretionary powers of the executor, or the omission of due supervision in formal and material abuse (Kambovski,2016:1065). Another way of obviously unconscientious conduct is the conclusion of harmful contracts, a conflict of interest, as well as the consequences of this unconscientious conduct, which exceed the degree of carelessness, sloppiness, or misdemeanour liability in the professional ethics of officials. Consequences of the act include obtaining property benefit, some material or immaterial benefit for oneself or another, and the executor must be proven to have had intent, more precisely, awareness that the law was violated, i.e., the official did not act in accordance with their duties. Punishment for the negligent execution of this form of the act is also provided for in paragraph 5 of the same article.

The LGAP, in Article 5, paragraph 3, stipulates that if the public body is authorized by law to decide by free assessment, the administrative act must be adopted within the limits of the law that grants the authorization, in accordance with the purpose for which the authorization was given, and must be specifically reasoned (2019). In this context, the concept of the LGAP emphasizes that public bodies should be service-oriented in order for citizens to efficiently and effectively exercise their rights, but on the other hand, they are also obliged to protect the public interest.

Other laws in the Macedonian legal system grant discretionary powers to public sector institutions. Elements of discretionary powers exist in decision-making on rights that citizens can exercise. Viewed through the prism of case law, great unprofessionalism is also noted in the commissions formed by the Pension and Disability Insurance Fund (Case *Metastaza*, 2012), as well as in the commissions of the Health Insurance Fund. This is because they are obliged to give an expert opinion on the diagnosis of the disease, the stage of the diseases, and the projection of diagnosing the disease, and not to engage in the interpretation of laws.

Independent institutions that monitor the work of public bodies in practicing discretionary powers within their competencies include: the State Commission for Prevention of Corruption, the Commission for Prevention and Protection against Discrimination, the State Audit Office, and the State Commission for Protection against Discrimination.

2.4 Law Created by European and National Case Law

European administrative procedural law is based on administrative principles (rule of law, transparency, proportionality, impartiality, and efficiency), on European administrative standards that are not determined statically but are developed on the basis of formally prescribed standards (hard law), case law (case law, judge-made law), and on the basis of good practices (soft law) (Koprić, 2014:12). European courts have an active role in interpreting rules and standards and imposing innovations on national courts. Therefore, in 2018, the Law on Courts was intervened again to make the practice of the European Court mandatory; specifically, an addition to Article 18 establishes that "when making a

decision, the court is obliged to apply the positions expressed in the final judgments of the European Court of Human Rights" (Law on Courts, 2006).

2.5 Judicial Protection and Control of Discretionary Powers

Regarding judicial control, there is a difference as to whether it is carried out over concrete acts, over general acts, or whether the responsibility of administrative employees is decided.

- If a general act of the administration is the subject of control, the Constitutional Court of the Republic of North Macedonia decides on its constitutionality and legality.
- If the legality of concrete administrative acts is decided, the authority to annul it is within the jurisdiction of the administrative judiciary.

The Court exerts direct influence on the administration through the authorizations issued by administrative bodies when deciding on the rights and obligations of citizens in the administrative procedure. This is done by annulling the act and instructing the body to adopt a new one in accordance with the court's indications, and in a dispute with full jurisdiction, even by deciding to resolve the administrative matter itself. This achieves two goals: the first is the protection of the rights and interests of citizens from arbitrary and self-willed actions of administrative bodies, and the second refers to the protection of the legal order by removing acts with which administrative bodies violate the principle of legality.

Regarding the control of discretionary powers, the Court can decide on the legality and the limits of the authorization of the public body that decided according to free assessment – the discretionary right (LAD, 2019, Article 6).

However, an administrative dispute cannot be conducted over the correct application of free assessment by a public body (discretionary power) when adopting an individual administrative act, but it can be conducted over the legality of such an act and the limits of such an authorization. This means that the Court is obliged to determine whether the public body was authorized to apply free assessment and whether it adhered to the limits of the given authorizations on that occasion.

To illustrate the case law, we will refer to final court decisions of the Court with the legal basis of control of the lawful use of discretionary power. Decision-making on lawsuits is related to the test of proportionality – *stricto sensu* (Grimm, 2016:171–172)⁶.

1. Initially, the legitimacy is examined—whether the decision was made by a competent body and whether the decision is aimed at achieving the purpose of the law, whether it is lawful and legally sound.
2. Then, it is determined whether there is excessive interference of the public authority in the rights provided by national legislation and the convention. This step represents a balanced analysis where the benefits of the decision made are

⁶ Traditionally, the test of proportionality is applied to measures undertaken by the administration (especially the police) which restrict the fundamental rights and freedoms of citizens. It was established in the 19th century by the Administrative Court of Prussia, and later adopted and developed by the Federal Constitutional Court of Germany. This method has a tremendous influence on European legal systems.

measured against the losses from the restriction of certain rights. All of this must be proportionate and necessary in relation to the public interest and essential in a democratic society.

3. Only if the benefits exceed the burden imposed on the rights will it be considered suitable (Möller, 2023:8).

To illustrate judicial control over discretionary powers, an analysis of the Administrative Court's case law reveals systemic violations in three key areas: procedural jurisdiction, the right to a reasoned decision, and the misapplication of substantive rights.

1. The first case study concerns the discretionary powers of a plaintiff, a former President of the Republic, who challenges the decision of 1. Jurisdictional & Procedural Violations: The Court consistently annuls decisions where strict procedural standards or constitutional boundaries are ignored. In Judgment URP no. 39/2019, it annulled a decision by the State Commission for Prevention of Corruption (SCSC) against the President of the Republic, ruling that Article 87 of the Constitution grants exclusive jurisdiction for presidential accountability to the Assembly. Similarly, Judgment U-5 no. 1452/2018 protected the separation of powers by voiding an Assembly decision to dismiss SCSC members because the Government's involvement infringed upon legislative independence. Procedural strictness was further enforced in Judgment U-5 no. 380/2025, where the Court annulled the election of a Constitutional Judge because the Judicial Council failed to assess candidates' work results or follow voting protocols required by Article 98 of the Law on the Judicial Council.

2. Lack of Reasoning & Transparency: Failure to provide adequate reasoning—a core requirement of the LGAP and Article 6 of the ECHR—is a frequent ground for annulment. In Judgment U-5 no. 316/18 (national security certificates), the Court ruled that withholding classified evidence from the defence prevented a lawful assessment, citing the ECHR precedent *Ljlatifi v. Republic of Macedonia*. The judgment underscored that Article 6 mandates the principle of "equality of arms," requiring that the plaintiff be given a genuine opportunity to challenge the state's assertion that national security is endangered. Consequently, the Court found that denying the party access to the decisive evidence created a procedural imbalance that violated their Convention rights. Likewise, in Judgment U-5 no. 729/14, it found that administrative bodies arbitrarily denied free legal aid without explanation, failing to consider material facts such as the applicant's minor children.

3. Substantive Rights & Social Justice: Judicial intervention is particularly robust when discretionary power affects the welfare of children and vulnerable families. In Judgment U-5 no. 729/14 (free legal aid), the Court expanded the interpretation of the law to include divorce proceedings, reasoning that the protection of the applicant's minor children supersedes rigid administrative lists. Similarly, in Judgment U-5 no. 180/2015, it prioritized protection against domestic violence over bureaucratic hurdles. Furthermore, Judgment U-4 no. 343/20 addressed a discriminatory interpretation regarding parental allowance for a third child, where the administration excluded an adopted child by focusing solely on the "physical act of childbirth." The Court annulled this, establishing that under Article 113 of the Family Law, adoption equates to birth. The ruling emphasized that the state's objective is to support child-rearing and family values, not merely biological

reproduction, thereby strictly prohibiting discrimination against adoptive families. Finally, regarding environmental rights, Judgment USPI no. 2/2024 established that the Government's failure to adopt the National Ambient Air Protection Plan since 2018 directly violated the constitutional right to a healthy environment.

CONCLUSION

We can conclude that states strive to strengthen their position, primarily for the sake of the security of citizens and the fight against crime and the mafia. The fight against terrorism, organized crime, and corruption, as well as the need for the development and maintenance of transnational prevention, are especially important for international law. Legal certainty and protection from the unlawful use of discretionary powers are ensured through the impartial application of the rights and interests of natural and legal persons, regardless of the status and characteristics of the parties. Therefore, consistent provisions for clear discretionary powers are necessary, as is the use of control mechanisms over the implementation of laws. It is necessary to strengthen institutions in the direction of autonomous instruments of protection. Also, raising awareness of the importance of the lawful practice of discretionary powers is very important. The delivery of quality services by the administration and the correct application of discretionary power are ensured through the test of proportionality.

From the analysis of the court decisions, it was concluded that the thorough reasoning and justification of the decisions, i.e., the acts of the public administration, contribute on the one hand to limiting the potential abuse of discretionary powers for corrupt purposes, and on the other hand, to strengthening the legal remedy with which they can potentially be challenged, and thus to the implementation of much more effective control. The relationship between the administration and the judiciary is independent; they are functionally and organizationally autonomous, and the judiciary retains the role of a controller over the legality of the acts and the operation of the administration. The principles of law and the judicial and constitutional-judicial protection based on them are, for now, confirmed as the most suitable instruments for approaching the great ideas and aspirations for freedom, justice, and truth in a contemporary civil and conflicted society.

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SYSTEMIC CORRUPTION IN NORTH MACEDONIA: PHENOMENOLOGY, CRIMINOGENIC FACTORS AND INSTITUTIONAL TRUST

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Abstract

Systemic corruption represents one of the most profound and persistent challenges to the rule of law and public trust in the institutions of the Republic of North Macedonia. It does not stem from isolated cases of bribery but rather reflects a recurring pattern of deviant behaviour rooted in structural weaknesses within public administration and governance mechanisms. This study examines systemic corruption through a combined phenomenological and etiological approach, analysing its structure, dynamics, and the factors that contribute to its persistence. The analysis integrates criminological theory with empirical data from the Ministry of Interior, the State Commission for the Prevention of Corruption, and international assessments by GRECO and Transparency International Macedonia. Findings indicate that corruption in North Macedonia manifests across multiple institutional and societal levels, revealing enduring weaknesses in transparency, oversight, and law enforcement. These deficiencies directly erode public confidence and reinforce the perception of impunity. In conclusion, the study emphasizes that improving the situation requires strengthening institutional integrity, ensuring genuine independence of the judiciary, and consistently implementing anti-corruption policies as prerequisites for restoring trust in the rule of law.

Keywords: systemic corruption; criminogenic factors; institutional trust; rule of law; anti-corruption policy.

1. INTRODUCTION

Systemic corruption remains one of the key challenges shaping the development of institutions and the rule of law in the Republic of North Macedonia. From a criminological perspective, systemic corruption can be understood as a manifestation of institutional anomie – a condition in which political and economic interests prevail over moral and legal norms. This situation produces the well-known gap between “law in books” and “law in action”, where selective enforcement and politically influenced justice cultivate a culture of impunity. As a result, public perception of justice weakens, and legal norms lose their moral authority.

International reports on governance and the rule of law consistently emphasize that, although North Macedonia’s legal framework has been harmonized with European standards, its implementation often remains formalistic, selective, and politically influenced. These findings highlight persistent systemic weaknesses that hinder institutional integrity and the consistent application of justice.

Within this context, the purpose of this study is to provide a criminological analysis of systemic corruption in North Macedonia, by examining:

1. the structure and dynamics of corruption at the institutional level;
2. the criminogenic factors that generate and sustain it; and
3. its impact on public trust, the rule of law, and institutional integrity.

The study integrates theoretical analysis with empirical data from the Ministry of Interior (2020-2024) and reports from international bodies such as GRECO, MCIC, and Transparency International, offering a comprehensive view of the aetiology of systemic corruption and its effects on the institutional and social stability of the country.

2. CRIMINOLOGICAL AND INSTITUTIONAL APPROACH TO SYSTEMIC CORRUPTION

This chapter explores systemic corruption by integrating criminological theory with institutional analysis, highlighting how structural weaknesses, legal frameworks, and governance practices shape its dynamics and persistence.

2.1 Characteristics of Systemic Corruption in North Macedonia

Systemic corruption represents one of the most persistent forms of criminal behaviour in the Republic of North Macedonia. It is not confined to isolated cases of bribery but is deeply embedded within the mechanisms of institutional functioning, where the intersection between public and private interests often creates space for deviant behaviour.

From a criminological standpoint, this phenomenon is closely linked to institutional anomie – the gap between legal norms and actual practice, often referred to as the contrast between “law in books” and “law in action.” This condition fosters a culture of tolerance toward violations and weakens the perception of justice, making punishment appear less inevitable.

According to Heywood (2022), systemic corruption is characterized by institutional capture, where informal rules take precedence over formal legal norms. In practice, this translates into the existence of a “parallel system” in which the enforcement of laws is frequently influenced by personal interests and political hierarchies.

In this sense, systemic corruption should not be seen merely as an individual deviation but as a recurrent pattern of behaviour that undermines the efficiency and credibility of public institutions.

2.2 Theoretical Approaches to Systemic Corruption

Systemic corruption is a complex phenomenon that must be understood not only through legal analysis but also through the lens of social structure, individual motivation, and institutional culture. Criminological approaches help explain how this phenomenon emerges, persists, and adapts to changes within political and administrative systems.

In this sense, systemic corruption is viewed as a form of crime that links individual rationality with the structural deficiencies of institutions. It is not merely the product of occasional moral failures, but rather the result of a distortion in the balance between public and private interests – a point at which law loses its preventive function and personal gain becomes the guiding principle (Mungiu-Pippidi, 2015).

Four theoretical approaches contribute to explaining this process:

1. **The Institutional Anomie and Normative Distortion Approach** - Rothstein (2011) and Mungiu-Pippidi (2015) argue that when political and economic interests prevail over moral norms, institutions lose their equilibrium, and corruption becomes an integral part of everyday administrative functioning.
2. **The Power Conflict and Institutional Domination Approach** - Heywood (2022) and Johnston (2014) interpret corruption as a mechanism for maintaining privilege and control over institutions. In such contexts, law often serves not to limit political influence but to legitimize it.
3. **The Rational Choice Theory** (Clarke & Cornish, 1985) - views corruption as a rational decision made by individuals operating in environments where the risk of punishment is low and potential benefits are high. This dynamic fosters a culture of opportunism in which deviant behaviour becomes a practical strategy.
4. **The Institutional Quality of Government Approach** - Rothstein (2011) and Heywood (2022) emphasize that the credibility of institutions and the impartiality of the public administration are preconditions for effective corruption control. When these are absent, a self-reinforcing cycle emerges in which institutional weakness fuels public distrust, and distrust further weakens institutions.

Taken together, these approaches demonstrate that systemic corruption is not merely a problem of law enforcement but a reflection of the broader relationship between structure, culture, and the individual within the social system.

2.3 Phenomenological Analysis Based on the Ministry of Interior Data (2020-2024)

The phenomenological analysis of systemic corruption relies on official data from the Ministry of Interior of the Republic of North Macedonia for the period 2020-2024. These data provide a clear overview of trends in economic and organized crime, helping to understand the scope and dynamics of offenses with corruptive elements within criminal practice.

For analytical purposes, the information is divided into two main categories:

1. **Direct indicators of corruption** - include criminal offenses such as bribery (both giving and receiving), which represent the classical forms of active and passive corruption.
2. **Indirect indicators** - include offenses such as abuse of official position and authority, failure to perform official duties, forgery of official documents, and money laundering, all of which reflect the supporting mechanisms within the structure of systemic corruption.

From a criminological perspective, these data represent only the discovered and prosecuted crimes – the “visible” part of the phenomenon. A significant portion of latent corruption – cases that are not reported or that never result in criminal sanctions – remains outside the scope of official statistics. This gap between detected and latent crime is characteristic of white-collar offenses and reflects the structural challenges in detecting and prosecuting corruption.

Table 1. Key Corruption-Related Offenses in the Area of Economic Crime (2020-2024)

Year	Abuse of Official Position and Authority	Offenders	Negligent Performance of Duty	Offenders	Forgery of Official Document	Offenders
2020	152	217	23	41	20	29
2021	129	222	34	42	28	59
2022	91	125	25	39	9	10
2023	84	128	41	53	31	31
2024	99	179	70	119	23	25

Source: Ministry of Interior of the Republic of North Macedonia, *Summary Analysis of Total Criminality 2010-2024* (Збирна анализа за вкупен криминалитет 2010-2024 МВР на РСМ). Available at: <https://mvr.gov.mk/mk-MK/analizi-i-statistiki/zbirna-analiza>

The data presented in Table 1 reveal a high level of stability in economic crimes with corruptive elements during the period 2020-2024. This persistence indicates that offenses related to abuse of official position, failure to perform official duties, and forgery of official documents continue to be consistently present within the public administration. These indicators suggest the existence of an entrenched structure of deviant behaviours, where the misuse of authority and public office for personal gain remains a recurrent and institutionally tolerated practice. On a broader level, this stability directly affects citizens' trust in public institutions, reinforcing the perception that punishment for administrative violations and abuse of duty remains limited and selectively applied.

Table 2. Corruption-Related Offenses in the Area of Organized Crime (2020-2024)

Year	Receiving Bribe	Offenders	Giving Bribe	Offenders	Money Laundering	Offenders
2020	5	4	1	1	9	11
2021	4	4	3	5	6	10
2022	11	18	5	5	1	1
2023	11	12	11	12	10	15
2024	12	25	10	11	7	19

Source: Ministry of Interior of the Republic of North Macedonia, *Summary Analysis of Organized Crime 2010-2024*.

The data presented in Table 2 illustrate the most direct indicators of corruption through offenses of bribery, representing the classical forms of *active* and *passive* corruption. During the period 2020-2024, the number of recorded cases remained very low – only a few per year – which contrasts sharply with the widespread public perception of corruption.

A slight increase is observed after 2022, which may be attributed to improved reporting mechanisms and administrative oversight, though not necessarily to an increase in actual accountability or conviction rates. This disproportion reveals the presence of latent corruption – cases that go unreported or fail to result in judicial outcomes.

In this context, the data provided by the Ministry of Interior offer a limited but valuable insight into the dynamics of corruption detection and the institutional challenges related to its documentation. On a broader level, these trends influence public perceptions of the functioning of justice mechanisms and the effectiveness of anti-corruption policies.

2.4 Legal and Institutional Framework for Preventing Systemic Corruption in North Macedonia

The legal framework for preventing and combating corruption in the Republic of North Macedonia has been developed in accordance with international standards and the requirements of the European integration process. The main challenge lies less in the existence of laws and more in their consistent implementation. The gap between what is prescribed by law and what occurs in practice remains one of the most evident indicators of the systemic nature of corruption.

The framework includes key legal acts such as the Law on the Prevention of Corruption and Conflict of Interest and the relevant provisions of the Criminal Code, both harmonized with the United Nations Convention against Corruption (UNCAC) and the Council of Europe's Criminal Law Convention on Corruption. This alignment has helped establish a solid foundation for strengthening public integrity and enhancing institutional transparency.

As Rose-Ackerman (2016) emphasizes, the strength of the law lies not in the existence of norms but in the certainty of their enforcement. When punishment is rare or delayed, the law loses its preventive function and risks being perceived as a formality. This reality highlights the need to strengthen internal integrity mechanisms and ensure the consistent implementation of anti-corruption policies across all levels of public administration.

In conclusion, systemic corruption remains a structurally rooted phenomenon closely tied to the functioning and culture of institutions. While legal and institutional improvements in recent years have produced formal progress, their practical impact depends on sustained enforcement and the continuous reinforcement of integrity within public institutions.

To better understand this dynamic, the following chapter focuses on the etiological factors - the causes and mechanisms that generate and sustain systemic corruption within the country's institutional reality.

3. ETIOLOGICAL ANALYSIS OF SYSTEMIC CORRUPTION

3.1 Socio-Economic Factors

In the economic reality of the Republic of North Macedonia – where the public sector holds significant influence and opportunities for employment in the private market remain limited – economic insecurity and political dependency create fertile ground for the emergence of corruption. Positions within public administration are often perceived as sources of economic stability, linking professional status more to political loyalty than to the individual merit.

The absence of merit-based competition and the persistence of clientelism foster a culture of dependency, in which personal connections are viewed as an acceptable means for professional advancement (MCMS, 2023). This mentality normalizes corruption, framing it not as a moral violation but as a functional tool for survival within an unstable economic system.

Consequently, private interest frequently replaces public responsibility, while adherence to legal rules is perceived as a bureaucratic obstacle. As a result, corruption acquires a self-reinforcing character, becoming an integral part of the daily functioning of the public administration, sustained by political influence, institutional favouritism, and the absence of meritocracy.

3.2 Institutional and Political Factors

The weakness of public institutions and the politicization of justice are among the most significant factors that enable systemic corruption to persist. Political interference in appointments, investigations, and prosecutions has created an institutional dualism in which the “law in books” exists, but the “law in practice” is often shaped by partisan interests and networks of influence (GRECO, 2025).

This situation reflects a lack of institutional impartiality and limitations in the overall quality of governance, which in turn undermines the preventive and educational functions of justice. In practice, punishment often remains selective, while internal control mechanisms are mostly formal and have limited practical effect.

From a criminological perspective, corruption at this level operates as a mechanism for maintaining institutional influence and authority, indirectly affecting the principle of equality before the law and public perceptions of justice. This creates a difficult cycle to break, in which institutional weakness and public mistrust reinforce one another, making the consolidation of integrity and accountability a long-term process.

3.2.1 Analysis of National and International Reports on Systemic Corruption (2024-2025)

To better understand the institutional and political context of systemic corruption, this section analyses key national and international reports published during 2024–2025. These reports provide empirical insight into the effectiveness of anti-corruption mechanisms, institutional integrity, and the overall implementation of good governance principles.

3.2.1.1 Report of the State Commission for the Prevention of Corruption (2024)

The 2024 Annual Report of the State Commission for the Prevention of Corruption conceptualizes the fight against corruption as a systemic and collective process that requires the active engagement of all competent institutions. According to the document, effective prevention can only be achieved through an integrated approach in which transparency, accountability, and public integrity function in a coordinated and sustainable manner.

The report highlights progress at the normative level through the implementation of the National Strategy for the Prevention of Corruption and Conflict of Interest 2021-2025, while noting that practical implementation remains fragmented due to limited resources, insufficient interinstitutional coordination, and the lack of effective oversight. During 2024, efforts began to develop a new Strategy for 2026-2030, aimed at

strengthening public integrity and assessing sectoral corruption risks within public administration.

A particularly important element emphasized in the report is the focus on interinstitutional cooperation and the inclusion of the civil sector through the Platform of Civil Society Organizations for the Fight against Corruption, implemented in partnership with USAID and MCMS within the framework of the “*Citizens Against Corruption*” program. This collaboration has contributed to improving institutional integrity indicators and promoting good governance, encouraging greater transparency and public accountability.

From a criminological perspective, the report reflects the tension between the normative structure and the practical functioning of institutions, illustrating how limited coordination, fragile internal integrity, and political dependency continue to act as criminogenic factors that sustain systemic corruption at higher levels of public administration.

3.2.1.2 GRECO Report (2025)

The 2025 Report of the Group of States against Corruption emphasizes that, despite the legal and institutional reforms undertaken in recent years, their implementation remains limited and uneven. Out of the 23 recommendations addressed to the Republic of North Macedonia, 17 have been fully implemented, while six only partially, pointing to the need for greater institutional consistency and long-term commitment to integrity reforms.

GRECO acknowledges the important role of the State Commission for the Prevention of Corruption (SCPC) in enhancing transparency and monitoring the assets and interests of public officials. However, it also notes that the independence and operational effectiveness of this body continue to face challenges, particularly regarding resource constraints and external influence.

Some of the outstanding recommendations relate to the absence of effective sanctions for breaches of integrity, which reinforces the perception of impunity and weakens citizens’ confidence in the justice system. The report also observes that, while notable steps have been made toward strengthening the operational independence of the police and establishing internal and external oversight mechanisms, issues such as transparency, objectivity in evaluations, and the protection of whistleblowers remain fragile and insufficiently embedded in practice.

In its overall assessment, GRECO concludes that systemic corruption continues to display a deeply rooted structural character, which challenges both the effectiveness of the justice system and the broader legitimacy of the rule of law. The report highlights that a sustainable improvement requires not only an aligned legal framework but also consistent, independent, and transparent enforcement, as a precondition for building institutions with integrity and public trust.

3.2.1.3 Transparency International - Macedonia Report (2025)

The *Corruption Barometer 2024 - Light & Dark* report by Transparency International - Macedonia concludes that corruption in the Republic of North Macedonia remains a deeply systemic phenomenon that directly undermines citizens' trust in public institutions. Although there has been a moderate improvement in institutional transparency and access to public information, the practical effects of anti-corruption policies continue to be limited and fragmented.

Monitoring of cases for 2024 reveals the involvement of high-ranking public officials in corruption scandals, including representatives of the judiciary and the Academy for Judges and Prosecutors. These incidents have negatively impacted perceptions of judicial independence and deepened institutional mistrust, reinforcing the belief that the law is not applied equally to all.

In comparative terms, North Macedonia ranks 88th out of 180 countries in the Corruption Perceptions Index (CPI) with a score of 40 points, indicating that despite undertaken reforms, concrete results in strengthening public integrity and the rule of law remain insufficient.

These findings are directly connected to the criminological dimension of institutional trust, demonstrating that perceptions of impunity and political interference reinforce the self-reproduction of corruption within public structures. From a criminological standpoint, these indicators do not merely reflect public perceptions – they represent the absence of effective justice and the weakness of equality before the law. In this context, both national and international reports converge on a common conclusion: citizens' trust in public institutions in North Macedonia remains fragile, shaped by perceptions of impunity, political influence, and the lack of genuine transparency.

From a criminological perspective, this mistrust is not only a consequence of corruption but also a mechanism that perpetuates it – as it weakens citizens' willingness to report, participate, and engage in public oversight. According to Transparency International (2025), the low level of trust in the judiciary and public administration is directly linked to the absence of effective accountability and to the widespread perception that power operates above the law, not under it.

3.3 Psychological and Individual Factors

At the personal level, corruption often stems from the motivation for individual gain, a low perception of risk, and moral reasoning that makes deviant behaviour appear acceptable. According to Sutherland (1949), perpetrators of *white-collar crimes* rarely perceive themselves as criminals – they view corrupt behaviour as a normal part of their professional environment or as a response to systemic pressures. When punishment is rare and internal institutional control is weak, corrupt behaviour is perceived as a logical, low-risk choice, consistent with rational choice theory (Clarke & Cornish, 1985).

In this sense, corruption does not arise from a lack of morality but rather from a functional adaptation to the unwritten rules of the system, where personal gain and loyalty often outweigh honesty. As Sutherland emphasized, such crimes are not driven by necessity but by *opportunity* and the belief that institutional status provides protection from punishment.

This creates a mutual interdependence: the individual benefits from the system's tolerance, while the system maintains stability through the acceptance of deviant behaviour. This cycle makes corruption not merely a moral or legal issue but also a psychological dynamic that sustains the very structure of institutional functioning.

3.4 Cultural and Moral Factors

One of the most enduring foundations of systemic corruption is the cultural normalization of deviant behaviour. In a society where success is often measured by influence and connections rather than merit, deviation gains moral legitimacy and becomes embedded in everyday culture. As Rothstein (2011) and Mungiu-Pippidi (2015) emphasize, when political interests and personal gain prevail over moral norms and institutional impartiality, the fundamental balance of the system collapses. Corruption is then perceived not as a violation but as a “useful” tool for achieving personal or institutional objectives.

In this context, the values of integrity and accountability are replaced by personal loyalty and clientelist networks, eroding the sense of obligation to the law and the public interest. This fosters a climate of moral relativism, where the boundary between right and wrong becomes blurred and easily shifted. Breaking this cycle requires civic education and professional ethical formation that promote responsibility and honesty instead of conformity and self-interest. Without these elements, legal and institutional reforms remain partial and formal.

In conclusion, systemic corruption in the Republic of North Macedonia results from the interplay of structural, political, individual, and moral factors. Socio-economic factors create the conditions, political and institutional ones sustain the system, while cultural and psychological dimensions justify and normalize it. The interaction of political dependency, lack of meritocracy, and moral relativism reinforces a self-sustaining model of deviation that erodes institutional trust – which, from a criminological standpoint, is both a consequence and a cause of corruption.

Restoring this trust requires the strengthening of institutional integrity and the development of a public ethic centred on accountability and the genuine rule of law.

4. CONCLUSIONS

The theoretical and empirical analysis of systemic corruption in the Republic of North Macedonia for the period 2020-2024 demonstrates that this phenomenon is not merely the result of individual misconduct but rather an expression of a constructed and persistent structure of institutional deviation. It represents a typical form of *white-collar crime*, in which public positions and political influence are used for personal or partisan gain, thereby undermining the rule of law and public trust in justice.

Official data reveal a high degree of stability in offences with corruptive elements, despite ongoing legal reforms and the establishment of specialized institutions. This indicates that systemic corruption is not incidental but deeply rooted within the political and administrative structure, where the line between individual and institutional responsibility often becomes blurred.

The unequal application of the law and political interference in decision-making processes reinforce perceptions of selective justice and impunity. The effectiveness of justice, however, is not measured by the severity of punishment but by its inevitability and impartiality. Only an independent judiciary and institutions with integrity can reduce the level of latent corruption and the so-called “dark number” of crime.

A special role in this process belongs to ethical education and the professionalism of public officials, together with the active engagement of civil society in building a culture of accountability and transparency.

In conclusion, strengthening institutional integrity and restoring public trust in justice remain the fundamental prerequisites for a functional rule-of-law state and for the long-term prevention of systemic corruption in North Macedonia.

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INSTITUTIONAL INTEGRITY IN THE SECURITY SECTOR: ANTI-CORRUPTION APPROACHES IN NORTH MACEDONIA

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Abstract

In transitional democracies with insufficient respect for the rule of law, where institutions are still developing and striving to strengthen their governance, corruption poses a significant threat to the security sector as well. In such conditions, corruption undermines the operational capacities of security institutions and weakens their efficiency, accountability, legitimacy and public trust. This paper aims to investigate, present and analyse the anti-corruption measures that are applied within the security sector institutions in the Republic of North Macedonia. A special focus will be placed on strengthening institutional integrity as an important component of good governance and sustainable reforms. The study analyses the existing legal and strategic frameworks, institutional practices and internal control mechanisms in preventing and countering corruption in key security sector institutions in the Republic of North Macedonia. It is conducted using a qualitative methodology, by reviewing national legislation, strategic documents, official reports and assessments from relevant international organisations. The findings highlight institutional challenges in establishing anti-corruption policies, as well as differences between the institutional approaches, measures and mechanisms adopted by the institutions to address corruption. The paper concludes with the importance of sustained political will and of creating and fostering a professional organisational culture that respects ethical standards, transparency and accountability as core values of the security sector.

Keywords: corruption, institutions, integrity, governance, accountability, security sector

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1. Introduction

Corruption is a phenomenon that seriously undermines the functioning of democratic institutions and the rule of law. Corrupt activities within institutions undermine their efficiency, legitimacy, and reputation, especially if the institutions are not sufficiently resilient and do not detect and deal with them internally.

Institutional corruption (Lessig, 2013) undermines the institution's effectiveness by diverting it from its purpose or weakening its ability to achieve its purpose, including, to the extent relevant to its purpose, weakening either the public's trust in that institution or the institution's inherent trustworthiness. Therefore, Lessig (2013) defines institutional corruption as a state in which institutional integrity has eroded in one or more of a set of relevant dimensions. Wueste (2005) thinks that institutional health depends upon institutional integrity, and institutional integrity depends upon individual integrity. If that's right, "disease" may be manifest at two levels—at the level of institutional or individual integrity. Therefore, Gillian (2014) considers institutional integrity as a baseline for examining the dimensions of institutional corruption. Institutional integrity exists when all four of the following conditions are met: (i) An institution achieves its purposes effectively and equitably; (ii) Insofar as an institution is properly dependent on P (or parties P1, P2, . . . , Pn), is required to promote the interests of P (or parties P1-Pn), or is required to be accountable to P (or parties P1-Pn), it does so and does not improperly depend on or promote the interests of other parties; (iii) Because (i) and (ii) are the case, public confidence in the institution is appropriate. This confidence may assist the effectiveness of the institution; (iv) Public confidence in the institution's practices, operations, and policies can also survive appropriate transparency and accountability tests. By contrast, institutional corruption occurs when all four of the above conditions fail to be the case.

Marks (2019) offers a more demanding account of institutional integrity than public officials tend to employ. A core requirement is consistency among what an institution is obligated to do (its purpose), what the institution says it does (its mission), and what that institution actually does (its practices). If an institution's practices predictably undermine the very goals in terms of which the institution justifies its existence, that institution may be said to lack integrity.

Inspired by this concept, this paper examines the integrity of security sector institutions in North Macedonia with a particular focus on the measures and mechanisms for combating corruption adopted within their legal and strategic frameworks. The aim is to assess the extent to which these institutions demonstrate resilience to corrupt practices and influences, with special focus on their transparency and openness to the public. Specifically, the assessment will draw on all three elements of Marks' definition—namely, the consistency between what institutions are obliged to do in combating corruption within their own ranks (the goal), what they claim to do to prevent, detect and counter corrupt activities (the mission), and what they actually do in practice. These elements will be analysed through the institutional legal and strategic frameworks, that is, the legislation adopted and in force within the institutions, as well as how transparently this is communicated to the public.

2. Institutional Integrity: Theoretical Considerations

Rose and Heywood (2013; 2015), for example, tie the concept of integrity to a concern with public values. These authors point to the conception of integrity as an iterative process: 'integrity is part of a process, not merely something that exists in

temporally specific actions, like corruption' (Heywood & Rose, 2015). Integrity is therefore something that is cultivated, rather than being simply a set of conditions under which corruption does not occur. Certainly, in some cases, this may mean the absence of corrupt behaviour, yet it may also mean that an organisation and its members strive to maintain a commitment to the organisation's legitimate purpose. In such instances, as discussed above, if an organisation possesses integrity, it possesses more than the mere absence of corruption.

Kirby (2018) assumed that the best conception of public integrity, first and foremost, is the one most worthy of the logical, cognitive, and affective associations with the concept of personal integrity, but in the specifically public realm with public actors. It has, therefore, been an exercise in analogy and functional equivalence, fulfilling the key criteria of 'integrity' in general: coherence, consistency, justifiability, praiseworthiness, virtue logic, and trustworthiness. On this basis, the author has argued that the best conception of public integrity is organically, 'institution-first'. A public institution has integrity if and only if it has a robust disposition, through its constitutive parts, to legitimately cohere to its legitimate purpose, consistent with its own commitments, across time and circumstance. And a public officer has integrity if and only if they have the robust disposition to support the integrity of their institution.

From a practical perspective, a better understanding of institutional integrity requires deeper introspection into how an institution functions, what its vision and mission are, its values and goals, priorities, anti-corruption mechanisms, and approaches to ethical behaviour. As Robinson et al. (2008) noted, this change of focus, from preventing unethical behaviour to cultivating good behaviour, highlights the utility of integrity as a concept distinct from other aspects of good governance.

Kirby (2022) puts forward a substantive moral conception of institutional integrity as the robust disposition of an institution to pursue its purpose efficiently, within the constraints of legitimacy, and consistent with its commitments. The author argues that it is important because it provides the strongest grounding for a 'duty of support' owed by citizens to the institution. This conception of institutional integrity also helps advance the ongoing debate regarding institutional corruption, as the integrity of an institution enables it to prevent and resist corruption.

3. Methodology

The research on institutional measures to combat corruption, strengthen integrity, and ensure accountability and responsibility within the existing legal and strategic frameworks covered seven key institutions in the security sector in the Republic of North Macedonia. These institutions are the Ministry of Interior (MoI), the Customs Administration (CA), the Financial Police (FP), the Financial Intelligence Unit (FIU), the National Security Agency (NSA), the Intelligence Agency (IA), and the Directorate for Security and Intelligence in Defence (DSID), which is an entity within the Ministry of Defence (MoD). Three of these institutions form the judicial police in accordance with the Law on Criminal Procedure (MoI, CA, FP). At the same time, the other three constitute the security-intelligence community, as defined in the Law on the Coordination of the Security-Intelligence Community (NSA, IA, DSID). Although the FIU does not belong to any of these groups, it was included in the analysis due to the scope and nature of its mandate – namely, collecting information to detect money laundering, terrorist financing, and other financial crimes – which ensured greater comprehensiveness of the study.

In this process, five indicators were defined to assess institutional preparedness to fight corruption. The indicators referred to the existence of:

- Internal strategy and/or action plan against corruption: existence of strategic documents containing measures and activities to fight and suppress corruption within the institution;
- Code of ethics or conduct: the existence of ethical documents with appropriate rules of conduct intended for employees of the institution to which they should adhere when performing their work;
- Regulations on conflict of interest: existence of such rules that regulate further procedure in case of identified conflicts of interest among employees of the institutions while performing their activities;
- Selection, recruitment and promotion procedures: the existence of such procedures that regulate in more detail all phases of the process of establishing an employment relationship in the institution, which guarantees that appropriate, professional and deserving personnel are employed; and
- Whistleblower protection mechanisms: the existence of such mechanisms in case of reporting of illegal activities in the institution, which may come from external or internal whistleblowers.

The data for the assessment of each of the indicators were collected from the official websites of the institutions (mvr.gov.mk, customs.gov.mk, finpol.gov.mk, ufr.gov.mk, anb.gov.mk, ja.gov.mk, mod.gov.mk). However, not all information was easily accessible due to differences in the structure of the websites, the organisation of the menus and the categorisation of documents. In cases where a large number of documents, especially bylaws, were available but were not systematically grouped, finding the necessary materials proved to be more time-consuming.

A limitation of this research is that not all institutions of the security sector have been analysed, such as institutions which are part of the protection and rescue sector, and in a broader sense, institutions for control and supervision over the security sector. Furthermore, some of the bylaws in the analysed institutions are classified at a certain level and are therefore not publicly available. However, there is no information on their websites confirming whether such acts exist, what their titles are, or what level of classification they carry. This means that certain legal acts may actually exist, but due to secrecy and lack of information, they cannot be included in the research to verify a particular indicator. On the other hand, the indicators were checked only based on the existence of relevant documents and their public availability, without delving into their content and the measures and activities they contain. Thus, by assessing and examining the availability of relevant documents for each indicator separately, the research adds value in terms of assessing the transparency and openness of the institutions of the security sector, by proactively informing the public about the anti-corruption measures they have introduced and are implementing.

4. Findings

In accordance with the established methodology, an examination was made into the websites of the seven researched institutions from the security sector in North Macedonia, and data were collected for each of the selected indicators. In doing so, Table 1 was compiled, which lists the documents that correspond to each indicator.

Table 1. Institutional, Strategic and Legal Framework in the Security Sector Institutions in North Macedonia Regarding Anti-Corruption, Integrity and Accountability

	Existence of Internal Integrity/Anti-Corruption Strategy/Action Plan	Code of Ethics/Conduct	Conflict of Interest Regulations	Recruitment and Promotion Procedures	Whistleblower Protection
MoI	Integrity Plan 2023-2025 Anti-Corruption Programme 2025	Code of Ethics 2021	Guidelines on the Manner of Conduct of Elected and Appointed Persons and Employees in the Ministry of Interior to Prevent Conflicts of Interest 2023	Several bylaws	Rulebook on Internal Protected Reporting in Public Sector Institutions 2016 (Ministry of Justice)
CA	Strategy for Integrity and Fight Against Corruption 2025-2028 Integrity Policy 2023	Code of Conduct 2021 Rules of Order and Discipline 2021	-	-	-
FP	Annual Plan for Prevention of Corruption 2022	Code of Conduct 2014 Code for Public Service Employees 2014	-	Several bylaws	Procedure on Protected Internal and External Reporting 2020
FIU	Annual Plan for Prevention of Corruption 2023	-	-	-	Rulebook on Protected Internal Reporting
NSA	-	-	-	-	Rulebook on Internal Protected Reporting in Public Sector Institutions 2016 (Ministry of

					Justice)
IA	Anticorruption Programme Corruption Risks Register 2022 Annual Plan for Corruption Risks Assessment for 2023	-	-	-	Rulebook on Internal Protected Reporting in Public Sector Institutions 2016 (Ministry of Justice) Rulebook on Protected External Reporting 2016 (Ministry of Justice)
DSI D	Integrity Plan of MoD 2021-2024	Code of Ethics 2025	-	Law on the Defence, Law on the Employees in the Ministry of Defence and several bylaws	Rulebook on the Protection of Whistleblowers 2016

What does the table show? In the following text, the indicators for each institution will be elaborated separately, and in the Discussion section below, they will be cross-referenced and compared with each other.

The MoI carries out activities related to the detection, prosecution, and prevention of criminal acts, maintenance of public order and peace, protection of human rights and freedoms, guarding and controlling the state border, and other activities determined by law (mainly the Law on Internal Affairs and the Law on Police). These legal acts list the duties of employees and the authorisations granted to them, which they may apply while performing their duties. Thus, according to the Law on Internal Affairs, employees of the Ministry are obliged (Article 6) to protect and safeguard the life and property of citizens, to respect human freedoms and rights, and to apply only those measures and means of coercion prescribed by law or other regulation. In performing their duties, employees must maintain high standards of personal integrity, professional ethics, and care for the protection of the public interest, and must comply with the acts regulating these standards (Art. 10). Employees are accountable to the Ministry for the consequences of their actions, inaction, or decisions, as well as for the quality, timeliness, and efficiency of their work (Art. 12). Furthermore, they must not allow their personal material or non-material interests to conflict with the public interest or their professional status, in accordance with the law (Art. 13). To this end, the Ministry, through its specialised unit — the Department for Internal Control, Criminal Investigations and Professional Standards (<https://mvr.gov.mk/mk-MK/ministerstvo/za-oddelot>) — implements a wide range of measures and activities aimed at addressing unprofessional, illegal, and unethical conduct by employees, as well as preventing such conduct through both proactive and repressive measures. The Ministry’s anti-corruption efforts are continuously focused on maintaining

achieved results, improving efficiency, and proactively narrowing the space for corrupt behaviour within the Ministry and the police. These efforts also seek to ensure that every specific case of illegal or unprofessional conduct by employees is detected and appropriately sanctioned. On its website, the MoI has published relevant documents for each indicator. Its current Integrity Plan concludes this year, while the preparation of a new plan for the period 2026–2028 is already underway, supported by DCAF – Geneva Centre for Security Sector Governance. The Ministry has also adopted an Anti-Corruption Programme 2025, which has been in place since 2017. The Ministry of Interior has a Code of Ethics adopted in 2021, as well as Guidelines on the Manner of Conduct of Elected and Appointed Persons and Employees in the Ministry of Interior to Prevent Conflicts of Interest, adopted in 2023. In addition, the Ministry has a bylaw regulating employee behaviour and mutual relations. Regarding employment, selection, and promotion, the Ministry, in addition to its Law on Internal Affairs and Law on Police, has developed detailed bylaws available on its website, covering the procedures for the selection of applicants for Ministry positions and police officers, as well as the assessment of employees' performance and career system. For the protection of whistleblowers, the Ministry has not developed its own bylaws but instead applies the Rulebook on Internal Protected Reporting in Public Sector Institutions, adopted by the Ministry of Justice in 2016. In the MoI, there is a designated person for advising on matters related to integrity, gifts, and conflicts of interest, as well as a person responsible for protected internal and external reporting in the Ministry.

The CA has a wide scope of responsibilities related to customs control, supervision, and customs clearance. On its website, the CA has published cases it has identified as carrying the highest risk of corruption, along with the potential consequences arising from corrupt practices. According to the Law on the Customs Administration, customs officers are required to uphold the highest standards of integrity, both personal and institutional, in the course of their interactions with the public, the business sector, state administration bodies, and other state institutions (Art. 72). Each customs officer bears personal responsibility for the performance of their duties and tasks. In cases of violation of official duty, customs officers may face disciplinary, misdemeanour, or criminal liability (Art. 73). On its website, the CA has published documents for only two indicators. It has adopted a Strategy for Integrity and the Fight Against Corruption (2025–2028), as well as an Integrity Policy in 2023. Regarding employment and promotion, there are no additional bylaws beyond the Law on the Customs Administration. Customs also has a Code of Conduct and Rules of Order and Discipline, adopted in 2021. However, no documents relating to the remaining indicators are available on its website. Customs has a designated person for protected internal reporting.

In accordance with the Law on Financial Police, the FP is responsible for safeguarding the financial interests of the Republic of North Macedonia by detecting and investigating criminal offences such as money laundering, illicit trafficking, smuggling, tax evasion, and other crimes involving unlawful property gain of significant value. It also protects the financial interests of the European Union by detecting and investigating criminal offences related to the misuse of funds from EU programmes received from the Union's budget (Art. 2). Financial police officers are required to perform their duties conscientiously, professionally, efficiently, and in a timely and orderly manner, in accordance with the Constitution, the law, and other regulations governing the Financial Police. They must carry out their work impartially, free from political influence or personal financial interest, and must not misuse their powers or status. Officers are also obliged to

protect the reputation of the Financial Police, to comply with its Code of Conduct and prescribed rules of order and discipline, and to refrain from using privileges or exemptions, or from requesting or accepting material or other benefits in the exercise of their official duties, as stipulated by law (Art. 41). On its website, the FP has published documents for four indicators, except for the conflict-of-interest indicator. It has adopted a single Annual Plan for the Prevention of Corruption in 2022. The FP has a Code of Conduct and a Code for Public Service Employees, both adopted in 2014. Regarding procedures for employment, selection, and promotion, in addition to the provisions in the Law on Financial Police, it has developed two detailed bylaws which regulate the method of assessing working abilities for employment as well as the evaluation of financial police officers' performance. For the protection of whistleblowers, the FP has its own bylaw — the Procedure on Protected Internal and External Reporting, adopted in 2020. The FP has a designated person for protected internal reporting, as well as a person for reporting misconduct, fraud, or corruption.

The FIU was established by the Law on Prevention of Money Laundering and Financing of Terrorism. The mandate of this institution is the collection and analysis of intelligence information on suspicious transactions and other information relevant to the prevention and detection of money laundering and the financing of terrorism. When there are grounds for suspicion of money laundering or financing of terrorism (Article 75), the FIU is obliged to submit the results of its analysis, together with all additional relevant information, to the competent authorities. As with other institutions, financial intelligence officers are obliged to perform their duties conscientiously, professionally, efficiently, promptly, and orderly, in accordance with the Constitution, the law, and other regulations. They must act impartially, without influence from political parties or personal financial interests, and must not abuse their powers or status. Furthermore, they are obliged to protect the reputation of the FIU, adhere to its Code of Conduct, and respect the prescribed rules of order and discipline. Officials may not use privileges or exemptions, nor seek or accept material or other benefits in the course of their official duties, as provided for by law (Article 91). On its website, the FIU has published documents for only two indicators. It has adopted three annual plans for the prevention of corruption covering the period 2021–2023. For the indicator relating to employment and promotion, there are no additional bylaws other than the provisions of the Law on Prevention of Money Laundering and Financing of Terrorism. Regarding the protection of whistleblowers, the FIU has developed its own bylaw — the Rulebook on Protected Internal Reporting — although there is no information available on the date of its adoption. The FIU has a designated person for protected internal reporting.

According to the Law on the National Security Agency, the NSA was established to protect the national security of the state, including the independence, sovereignty, constitutional order, and the fundamental freedoms and rights of citizens guaranteed by the Constitution of the Republic of North Macedonia, as well as other matters of national security (Art. 2). Article 64 stipulates that, to ensure transparent communication with the public, the Agency must publish on its website relevant regulations concerning its work, its organisational structure, publicly available annual reports, surveys and brochures within its scope of activities, public job advertisements, and similar materials. In practice, however, apart from general institutional information and news about the director's participation in events, no regulations or annual reports have been published. The NSA has therefore not provided documents on its website corresponding to the indicators required by law. Nevertheless, the website does contain a form through which citizens can report

misconduct by Agency employees. There are no additional bylaws for employment and promotion, in addition to the provisions in the Law on the National Security Agency. For the protection of whistleblowers, the Agency has not developed its own bylaws but instead applies the Rulebook on Internal Protected Reporting in Public Sector Institutions, adopted by the Ministry of Justice in 2016. There is a designated officer within the Agency responsible for handling protected internal reporting.

The IA was established by the Law on the Intelligence Agency. As a foreign intelligence service, its mandate is to collect intelligence information on threats and risks originating from abroad for the protection of national security, economic and political interests, independence, sovereignty, constitutional order, and the fundamental freedoms and rights of citizens guaranteed by the Constitution of the Republic of North Macedonia (Article 2). The Agency is authorised to collect, process, analyse, evaluate, exchange, store, and protect data and information of importance for the security, defence, foreign policy, and economic interests of the Republic of North Macedonia (Article 3). For transparent communication with the public, the Agency may publish on its website relevant regulations regarding its work, its organisational structure, and its budget and final accounts. It may also inform the public about certain security phenomena and events (Article 24). Employees of the Agency who violate work order and discipline or fail to fulfil their professional duties are subject to disciplinary, misdemeanour, and criminal liability (Article 91). On its website, the IA has published documents related to two indicators. Regarding the anti-corruption documents, the IA has published the Anti-Corruption Programme, the Corruption Risk Register (2022), and the Annual Risk Assessment Plan (2023). Regarding employment and promotion, there is no additional bylaw other than the provisions set out in the law. For the protection of whistleblowers, the IA refers to two regulations issued by the Ministry of Justice in 2016, which regulate protected internal reporting in public sector institutions and protected external reporting. The IA has a designated person responsible for protected internal reporting, although the name of the individual is not publicly disclosed, but an email address is provided for submitting reports.

Defence intelligence comprises measures, activities, and procedures undertaken to collect, document, and analyse intelligence data relevant to the defence of the Republic (Art. 133). Defence counterintelligence comprises measures, activities, and procedures aimed at detecting and preventing intelligence and other subversive activities by foreign military intelligence and security services, whether conducted within the country or from abroad, and directed against the defence of the Republic; detecting and preventing all forms of terrorist activity targeting the defence of the Republic; and ensuring counterintelligence protection of tasks, plans, documents, material and technical resources, areas, zones, and facilities of interest for the defence of the Republic (Art. 134). In performing these tasks, authorised officials have the right to collect data, reports, and information within their scope of work. They are also subject to disciplinary, misdemeanour, and criminal liability. Given that this Directorate is part of the MoD, the Law on Employees of the Ministry of Defence (Article 13) also applies to these employees, according to which they are obliged to maintain high standards of personal integrity, professional ethics, and dedication to the protection of the public and the interests of the Ministry. The law requires them to adhere to the Code of Ethics for Employees of the Ministry and the Army of the Republic of North Macedonia in their work and to ensure the impartial and objective application of laws and other regulations. They must carry out their responsibilities politically impartially and refrain from being influenced by personal

financial interests. Employees of the Ministry are personally accountable for the consequences of their actions, inactions, or decisions, as well as for the quality, timeliness, and efficiency of their assigned tasks (Art. 16). They must not place their personal, material, or non-material interests in conflict with the public interest or with their professional status, in accordance with the law (Art. 17). Furthermore, they may not manage, represent, or act on behalf of a political party, nor serve on its statutory bodies. Membership in a political party and participation in its activities must not compromise professionalism, impartiality, or legality in the performance of their duties within the Ministry (Art. 18). Since the DSID is an entity within the MoD, it does not have its own website; therefore, documents published by the Ministry also apply to the DSID. The Ministry website contains relevant documents for four of the examined indicators. The last available Integrity Plan, covering the period 2021–2024, has already expired, but the preparation of a new plan for 2026–2029 is underway, supported by a foreign partner — the Centre for Integrity in the Defence Sector from Norway. The MoD also adopted a Code of Ethics in 2025, but no documents relating to conflicts of interest are publicly available. With regard to employment, selection, and promotion, the Ministry has developed detailed bylaws that are accessible on its website, covering areas such as recruitment procedure, performance evaluation, and career progression from entry to middle and senior levels. For the protection of whistleblowers, the Ministry adopted its own bylaw, the 2016 Rulebook on the Protection of Whistleblowers. The Ministry has a designated person for protected internal reporting.

5. Discussion

When examining the indicators, it becomes evident that the first indicator—the existence of integrity and/or anti-corruption strategies and plans—is largely met. All institutions, with the exception of the NSA, either currently have or have previously developed integrity and/or anti-corruption documents. At the same time, the institutions demonstrate different approaches in relation to this indicator. The MoI and the DSID, for example, have integrity plans in the form of strategic documents covering a three- or four-year period, from which annual action plans are derived. The CA follows a similar approach, with a four-year strategy addressing both integrity and anti-corruption. By contrast, the remaining institutions (FP, FIU, IA) have only adopted annual plans, which have not been updated since 2022/2023.

An analysis of the indicators reveals notable variations in institutional approaches regarding the Code of Ethics/Conduct. Four institutions (MoI, CA, FP, DSID) have adopted such documents, under different titles such as Code of Ethics, Code of Conduct, and Rules of Order and Discipline. This indicates compliance with the requirement for internal ethical standards.

With regard to conflicts of interest, only the MoI has a publicly available bylaw. This highlights a significant gap in the transparency and regulation of this area in the remaining institutions.

Regarding procedures governing selection, employment, and promotion, the MoI, FP, and DSID have adopted certain bylaws in addition to their laws. In the other institutions, only the respective laws govern these processes. If they have any bylaws, they might be classified. The absence of such publicly available regulations in other institutions raises concerns about the transparency of these procedures and the potential exposure to undue influence.

Whistleblower protection is addressed through two different models: reliance on the Rulebooks issued by the Ministry of Justice (MoJ, IA) or the adoption of institution-specific regulations (FP, FIU, DSID). This variation reflects both an effort to adapt protection mechanisms to institutional needs and a lack of harmonised practice across the security sector.

In summary, the table shows that the judicial police institutions (MoJ, CA, and FP) have better results in terms of the selected indicators; that is, they have a more developed legal and strategic framework concerning integrity, the fight against corruption, ethics, and procedures for employment and promotion. This shows that they are significantly more transparent and open compared to other institutions. However, a deeper analysis of their frameworks also reveals certain gaps, particularly the lack of continuity in the adoption of strategic documents. This means that the process of drafting, adopting, and implementing these documents is not sequential, consistent, or connected. Failure to adopt a new continuation of a strategic document carries the risk of a policy vacuum—the measures are no longer valid, and institutions lack guidelines for action in the specific area. This is mainly because strategic documents are often developed with foreign support (as can be determined by reviewing the documents); thus, after such support ends, the institutions do not continue the process independently. Consequently, the objectives and measures in these documents are, to some extent, no longer relevant or cannot be implemented in the current context and must be upgraded or revised.

In contrast, the security and intelligence institutions are more closed and show less satisfactory results in terms of the indicators. The NSA stands out as particularly non-transparent, as it does not publish any documents or data related to the selected indicators on its newly designed website. By contrast, the DSID shows more positive results, but this is mainly because it is an organisational unit within the MoD, meaning that all rules and procedures adopted by the Ministry also apply to the DSID. However, it is also noticeable that some of these acts are outdated in this institution.

CONCLUSION

The literature review in the paper showed that institutional integrity is a fundamental factor for public trust in institutions and their efficiency, which affects both the prevention of and resistance to corruption. Integrity within an institution must be continuously maintained through a series of established functional mechanisms, and not only assessed by the absence of corrupt behaviour. Therefore, public institutions need to maintain consistency between their goals and mission, on the one hand, and their operational practices, on the other. If an institution fails to meet its goals, problems related to the reduction of control, transparency, accountability, public trust and reputation will arise. Effective institutional integrity depends on two things: both the integrity of each employee in the institution and the systemic protection mechanisms established within it. Therefore, in order to encourage and achieve institutional integrity, through which the occurrence of corruption will be prevented, comprehensive and continuous institutional activities are needed. These include proactively promoting ethical behaviour in all processes and levels of the institution, adopting and establishing clear functional mechanisms and rules against corruption, and practising transparent communication with the public about the institution's work. Broad institutional integrity provides a moral and functional basis for trust and support from citizens, thereby increasing institutional

legitimacy. In the security sector, the integrity of institutions is even more important, given that public trust is particularly vital for supporting their work and activities.

With this in mind, the paper analysed the anti-corruption and ethical standards of security sector institutions in North Macedonia, through five identified indicators. From the mapping and analysis of these indicators, the following conclusions can be drawn:

- Institutional approaches to each indicator differ in the scope, structure and continuity of strategic and legal documents.
- The absence of updated strategic documents creates policy gaps and risks of discontinuity in institutional integrity measures.
- Heavy reliance on foreign assistance for the development of strategic documents limits sustainability, as institutions rarely continue strategic processes independently.
- Judicial police institutions (MoI, CA, FP) demonstrate stronger legal and strategic frameworks for integrity, ethics and the fight against corruption compared to other institutions.
- Security and intelligence institutions are less transparent and show weaker results in fulfilling integrity-related indicators.
- All institutions, except the NSA, have developed strategies or plans for integrity and/or the fight against corruption.
- The NSA remains the least transparent, with no publicly available documents or data.
- The DSID performs better than other intelligence services due to its integration within the MoD.
- Only the MoI has its own publicly available bylaw on Elected and Appointed Persons and Employees in the Ministry of the Interior to Prevent Conflicts of Interest.
- Mechanisms for the protection of whistleblowers exist across institutions, generally using bylaws adopted by the Ministry of Justice, while some have developed their own.

Security sector institutions must align their legal and strategic frameworks with anti-corruption and ethical standards to strengthen overall institutional resilience. In this regard, several recommendations are inevitably imposed in relation to the set indicators:

- Security sector institutions should regularly update their strategies and plans, ensuring continuity between documents without a gap between two periods. In doing so, it is desirable to develop internal capacities for the preparation and monitoring of the implementation of strategies, instead of relying exclusively on foreign support. The model for the preparation and evaluation of integrity plans should ideally be unique and aligned with the recommendations of the State Commission for the Prevention of Corruption and EU standards.
- Existing codes of ethics and conduct should be harmonised in structure and substance throughout the security sector.
- All institutions should adopt and publish special bylaws for the prevention of conflicts of interest, with appropriate internal procedures for reporting and managing potential conflicts. In addition, for the purposes of transparency, it is necessary to ensure public availability of annual reports on reported and resolved cases of conflicts of interest.
- Each institution must have published detailed rulebooks governing all stages of recruitment and promotion, with a transparent performance appraisal system that

will serve as the basis for career progression and advancement. Institutions should enable external oversight or audit of recruitment processes to reduce the risk of nepotism and partisanship.

- Whistleblower protection procedures must be harmonised across institutions, in accordance with the Law on Whistleblower Protection and international standards. Institutions must appoint publicly available internal reporting persons, with clear contact information.

Finally, in terms of improving transparency and communication with the public, it is recommended that all security sector institutions publish documents related to integrity, anti-corruption, ethics, recruitment and reporting on their websites. In addition, they should introduce regular reporting to the public and civil society on the level of implementation of integrity and anti-corruption measures, as well as identified problems. In this way, institutions demonstrate a higher level of professionalism, accountability and commitment to the fight against corruption within their ranks. Furthermore, each institution must, in accordance with the law, establish clear standards for publishing information, especially through annual reports and work plans, which is recommended to be practised even by institutions where the law does not provide for this as an obligation.

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LEGISLATIVE FRAMEWORK AND INSTITUTIONAL MECHANISMS FOR COMBATING CORRUPTION IN SERBIA

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Abstract

Corruption is a phenomenon known from the earliest days of human civilization that has persisted to this day and represents a huge danger to the survival of the community. In the report, the basic concepts and characteristics of corruption, the international and national legislative framework and institutional mechanisms for its suppression in the Republic of Serbia are briefly presented. The place, role and tasks of the newly established specialized authorities of the police, prosecutor's office and the judiciary for the fight against corruption were especially pointed out. Furthermore, an overview of the most important activities and achieved results in combating corruption in Serbia in the last few years is provided. In the final part, some solutions *de lege ferenda* are proposed to improve the legislative framework and improve the work of specialized bodies for combating corruption. Special attention was paid to Serbia's application for admission to the EU and, in connection with that, the need for harmonization of regulations, further development of good practice and construction of functional mechanisms.

Keywords: corruption, corrupt crimes, suppression of corruption, Republic of Serbia, EU.

1. INTRODUCTION

At the beginning of the third millennium, corruption is an indisputable global problem that seriously erodes the foundations of modern society, represents a threat to democracy and the modern rule of law. This is a phenomenon known since the earliest days of human civilization that has survived many changes and has remained until today. In modern society of technical and technological development, corruption has taken on new and more dangerous forms, especially in transition and developing countries. Unfortunately, in many underdeveloped areas, corruption has acquired the right of citizenship and has become a phenomenon that is taken for granted, to which citizens are accustomed and rarely react.

Corruption of members of the public service is particularly present in developing countries, countries in transition and underdeveloped areas. This entails the devastation of public services, state administration bodies and local self-government, which increases citizens' mistrust in these institutions and their officials.

After the fall of the Berlin Wall, the problem of corruption was encountered by many ex-socialist countries that did not have a good normative basis and did not have

built-in mechanisms to fight corruption. Many of these countries, such as Poland, Hungary, the Czech Republic, Slovakia and others, have relatively successfully completed the process of economic and social transition, and have built sustainable mechanisms to fight crime and corruption, as one of the most serious forms of crime. Most Eastern European countries joined the EU after the changes and accepted the standards and mechanisms for fighting corruption and other forms of crime.

The Republic of Serbia and other successor states of the former SFRY also faced economic and other problems after the breakup of the common state, as well as a high rate of crime and especially corruption. Some of them, such as Slovenia and Croatia, had great support from Western countries and successfully completed the economic and social transition, so they were admitted to equal membership of the EU. Other countries from the former SFRY are today still in the process of transition and social reforms, and have applied for EU membership.

Regarding accession to EU membership, Serbia started negotiations even earlier and opened numerous negotiation chapters with the aim of harmonizing legal norms with EU regulations, accepting good practices and prevailing solutions of the EU. Chapters No. 23 and No. 24 are particularly important, which refer to the judiciary and fundamental rights, justice, freedom and security, with which Serbia and other candidate countries need to be aligned. In this part, the fight against corruption, which seriously disrupts the socio-economic system, life in the community and cancels the results achieved in the process of transition and social changes, has a significant place. Suppression of corruption and all its manifestations is also important for strengthening the reputation of the state and its bodies, building citizens' trust in the system and affirming the principle of the rule of law.

2. METHODS

The paper explores the legislative aspects of corruption and accordingly uses methods of legal sciences such as dogmatic, normative and comparative law methods. Using the same methods, institutional mechanisms used in the fight against corruption are abstracted from legal regulations and their analysis is performed. In addition, content analysis of literature and previous research on corruption is used.

3. ABOUT CORRUPTION IN GENERAL

In a historical sense, corruption is a phenomenon known from the earliest days of human civilization in the form of favours, gifts and dole given by subjects to tribal leaders, for the sake of better status and benefits. In Greece, there was a system of *ephoria* – civil servants with judicial and executive powers, which was the most important source of corruption, as 'a crime committed not for the sake of obtaining the necessary, but for obtaining the superfluous' (Aristotle, 1960: 1270). In Rome, Caesar went to war in Gaul to fight against the barbarians, but also to secure income for the state and military service. The Ottoman Empire had a similar form of reward as the sultans allowed judges to receive gifts when applying Sharia law (Aras, 2007: 25-27).

In the Middle Ages, corruption was also present and this phenomenon was criticized by philosophers from the time of humanism and the Renaissance, as well as English philosophers, such as Dante, Machiavelli, Montesquieu, More, Bacon and others. Humanists and philosophers in the US also had a critical approach to corruption, which they believed to be a product of the system, but also influenced by human nature regardless of the geographic component. The society of that time was accustomed to corruption, and

the prevailing attitude was that it was justified to buy public positions, to choose civil servants according to their origin and financial status (Teofilović, 2007: 11-15).

In the new century, especially after the end of World War II, the earlier doctrines and protection system (England), spoils system (USA) and electoral nepotism (France) were abandoned. A new system of professional administration, selection and training of personnel, impartial execution of work, respect for laws and professional standards is advocated (Aras, 2007: 25-27).

4. INTERNATIONAL LEGISLATIVE FRAMEWORK FOR COMBATING CORRUPTION

The international legal framework for combating corruption includes several specialized documents, the most important of which are: UN Convention against Corruption, 2004 (UNCAC), Criminal Law Convention on Corruption, European Treaty Series - No. 173, 1999 (Criminal LCC), Civil Law Convention on Corruption, European Treaty Series – No. 174, 1999 (Civil LCC) and UN Convention against Transnational Organized Crime, 2001, (UNCATOC). The aforementioned conventions were adopted by the Republic of Serbia, i.e. the predecessor states, and solutions from these documents were incorporated into the legal order of Serbia.

The UNCAC imposed the obligation of the signatory states to adopt preventive anti-corruption policy measures and positive practices related to the development, implementation and maintenance of the same policy in their national legislation. Furthermore, it is envisaged to review legal instruments and issued measures with the aim of preventing corrupt actions, establishing preventive independent bodies and hiring specialized personnel for the implementation of anti-corruption activities.

The UNCAC imposes the obligation of the signatory states to criminalize in their national criminal legislation corrupt criminal acts related to: bribery of domestic civil servants, bribery of foreign civil servants and representatives of international organizations; embezzlement; illegal appropriation or similar diversion of property by a civil servant; influence peddling; abuse of official position; illegal enrichment; bribery in the private sector, embezzlement of property in the private sector and laundering of proceeds (money) obtained from a criminal act. In accordance with the above, it is also the obligation of the signatory states to criminalize in national legislation the responsibility of legal entities for the aforementioned actions, then to issue the punishment of accomplices, aides and instigators in committing and attempting to commit these criminal acts, as well as all actions undertaken with the aim of obstructing justice.

The Criminal LCC imposes the obligation of the signatory states to criminalize (corruption) criminal acts related to: active and passive bribery of domestic civil servants in their national criminal legislation; bribery of members of domestic and foreign state authorities, bodies and officials; active and passive bribery in the private sector; bribery of officials of international organizations and members of international parliamentary bodies; bribery of judges and officials of international courts; influence peddling; money laundering, acquired through offences related to corruption and criminalization of accounting criminal acts.

The Civil LCC Imposes the obligation of the signatory states to provide compensation for damages in their national legislation, provided that the defendant committed or approved an act of corruption or failed to take reasonable steps to prevent it from happening, with the existence of damage on the part of the plaintiff and the existence of a causal link between the commission of corruption and the resulting damage.

According to Article 2 of the Civil LCC, corruption is defined as any act that includes asking, offering, giving or receiving a bribe, directly or indirectly, or any other illegal act of obtaining benefits. These are actions that violate the legal and proper performance of duties or that demand illegal behavior from the recipient of the bribe, as well as the acquisition of illegal benefits. It is very important to emphasize that the Civil LCC formed a specialized Group of Council of Europe against corruption called GRECO (<https://www.coe.int/en/web/greco>). The GRECO is in charge of monitoring the implementation of the Civil LCC in the fight against corruption and in this capacity monitors the member states, which visits and prepares evaluation reports on the existence and representation of corruption in each specific country, with a proposal of recommendations for the most successful fight against corruption.

UNCATOC or colloquially ‘The Palermo Convention’, among other things, establishes the obligation of the signatory states to criminalize corrupt criminal acts in their national legislation and to adopt measures to fight corruption. Additional protocols to the Convention are: Protocol for prevention, suppression and punishment of trafficking in human beings, especially women and children, Protocol against smuggling of migrants by land, sea and air and Protocol against illegal production and trafficking of firearms, their parts, assemblies and ammunition (Nikač, 2015: 265-290).

According to the provisions of the Palermo Convention (Articles 8-10), corruption is defined as any promise, offer or giving of an inappropriate benefit to a civil servant, in order to act or refrain from acting in the performance of his official duties, but also any request or acceptance of an inappropriate benefit by a civil servant in order to act or refrain from acting in the performance of official duties. The category of civil servants is broadly defined as all persons who work in public services, which was also accepted by the legislator in Serbia (According to Article 2 of the Civil Servant Law, the Official Gazette of the RS, Nos. 79/05, 81/05)

The obligation of the signatory states to adopt anti-corruption measures and determine the effective action of state authorities in order to prevent, detect and punish corrupt civil servants is foreseen. Accordingly, it is necessary to ensure the independence of professional bodies in order to prevent inappropriate influences on their work. The Palermo Convention is a revolutionary document for the fight against organized crime and provides for the formation of special bodies for the fight against organized crime (court, prosecutor's office, police, prison), then the use of special investigative techniques and measures, the harmonization of the norms of national legislation with the Palermo Convention, etc.

5. NATIONAL LEGISLATIVE FRAMEWORK OF SERBIA FOR COMBATING CORRUPTION

The legislative framework of the Republic of Serbia was amended during 2016, when the current Criminal Code (Official Gazette of the RS, Nos. 85/05, 88/05 – Corrigendum, 107/05 – Corrigendum, 72/09, 111/09, 121/12, 104/13, 108/14, 94/16, 35/19 and 94/24 <https://propisi.pravno-informacioni-sistem.rs/content/126>) was amended, as well as the adoption of the new Law on the Organization and Competence of State Authorities in Suppression of Organized Crime, Terrorism and Corruption (Official Gazette of the RS, No. 94/16 and 10/23 <https://propisi.pravno-informacioni-sistem.rs/content/1610>). In addition to new normative solutions, a new organization of authorities that should participate in the suppression of corrupt criminal acts was also adopted.

The Criminal Code was amended at the end of 2016, when a new composition of felonies against the economy was implemented. The amendments entered into force the following year (June 1st 2017), while one part of the provisions began to be applied later (March 1st 2018). The same amendments to the Criminal Code incriminate more (7) new felonies against the economy, but they are not specifically listed in the section-head under the heading of corrupt felonies. In the period 2002 – 2005, there was a special chapter of Criminal Code called Corruption crimes, which included the following crimes: Corruption in administrative bodies, Misappropriation of funds from the budget, Corruption in public procurement, Corruption in the privatization process, Corruption in the judiciary, Abuse of the function of a defence attorney or attorney, Corruption in health, Corruption in education, and Fixing the outcome of competitions. At the time, the systematics of these felonies were carried out mainly according to the areas where corruption appeared, and a particular problem was the fact that the concept of corruption was not uniquely defined in the text of the law. Therefore, different interpretations were applied in the practice of the authorities, primarily a broader (extensive) and narrower (restrictive) interpretation of which acts belong to the area of corrupt felonies.

According to the current rulings of the Criminal Code, corrupt felonies are considered to be those that mainly relate to the areas (protected object) of the economy and official duties, as well as certain acts from other areas. Within Chapter XXII, felonies against the economy are issued, including corrupt felonies: Tax Avoidance, Abuse of Position of a Responsible Person, Abuse Concerning Public Procurement, Abuse in Privatization Procedure, Accepting Bribes in Conducting of Business Activity, Giving Bribe in Conducting of Business Activity, Causing Bankruptcy, Causing False Bankruptcy, and Money Laundering. Within the framework of Chapter XXXIII, felonies against official duty and among them corrupt felonies are provided: Abuse of Office, Violation of Law by a Judge, Public Prosecutor or his Deputy, Dereliction of Duty, Unlawful Collection and Payment, Improper Use of Budget Funds, Fraud in Service, Embezzlement, Unauthorized Use, Influence Peddling, Soliciting and Accepting Bribes, and Bribery. In other chapters of the CC, there are also certain felonies that are corrupt, such as: within the felonies against electoral rights – Giving and Accepting Bribes in connection with Voting, within the felonies against labor rights – Violation of the Right to Employment and during Unemployment.

Law on the Organization and Competence of State Authorities in Suppression of Organized Crime, Terrorism and Corruption (OCGL) determines which felonies it refers to in terms of corruption, thus adopting mostly identical solutions as stated above. In addition, this is the so-called ‘organizational law’ that issues the organization of public authorities such as the courts, the prosecution and the police in the fight against corruption.

Other laws of importance for combating corruption are also important and among them the following stand out: Criminal Procedure Code (Official Gazette of the RS, Nos. 72/11, 101/11, 121/12, 32/13, 45/13, 55/14, 35/19 and 27/21-CC), Law on Confiscation of Property Derived from Criminal Activity (Official Gazette of the RS, Nos. 32/13, 94/16 and 35/19), Law on the Protection Programme for Participants in Criminal Proceedings (Official Gazette of the RS, No. 85/05), Law on the Anti-Corruption Agency (Official Gazette of the RS, No. 97/08, 53/10, 66/11 – CC, 67/13 – CC, 112/13 – authentic interpretation, 08/15 – CC and 88/19), Law on Whistleblowers' Protection (Official Gazette of the RS, No. 128/14) etc. Corruption is normatively defined in the Law on the Anti-Corruption Agency as ‘a relationship based on abuse of an official, i.e. social position or influence, in the public or private sector, with the aim of obtaining personal benefit or

benefit for another'. The Law on Confiscation of Property Derived from Criminal Activity issues opportunities for the confiscation of property benefits achieved through corrupt actions through the financial investigation process conducted by the police and the prosecutor's office. Law on the Protection Programme for Participants in Criminal Proceedings issues opportunities for the smooth conduct of the proceedings and the protection of all actors whose safety is at risk.

In addition to the legal framework, an important legal source is various regulations, among which the National Strategy for the Fight against Corruption for the period 2024-2028 (Official Gazette of the RS, No. 63/24), action plans and other documents stand out.

6. INSTITUTIONAL MECHANISMS OF THE FIGHT AGAINST CORRUPTION IN THE REPUBLIC OF SERBIA

OCGL establishes new institutional mechanisms in the fight against corruption in the Republic of Serbia. Chapter III of the same regulation issues the organization and competence of state bodies in the fight against corruption (art. 13-18). Special bodies in the form of departments are foreseen at the level of the public prosecutor, the court and the police. According to Article 13, special departments of the Higher Public Prosecutor Office for combating corruption are foreseen, then a special police unit within the MoI of the RS and special departments of higher courts for combating corruption.

Special Anti-Corruption Departments of the High Court act in the first instance in relation to corrupt criminal acts prosecuted by the prosecution. These special departments exist in Belgrade, Kraljevo, Niš and Novi Sad. The work of the department is managed by the president of the special department, who is appointed by the president of the Higher Court (mandate of 4 years). The staffing of judges is done by the president of the Higher Court, who assigns the judges of the Higher Court, for a period of 6 years and with written consent. Also, in case of need, the High Council of the Judiciary can send a judge from another court to work in a special anti-corruption department, for a period of 6 years and with written consent. The president of the Higher Court regulates the work of the special anti-corruption department.

The Serbian public prosecutor acts in cases of corrupt felonies through Higher Public Prosecutor's Offices located in Belgrade, Kraljevo, Niš and Novi Sad, where special anti-corruption departments are formed. The work of each special anti-corruption department is managed by an appointed manager, who is appointed by the competent chief prosecutor. Acting prosecutors are assigned or referred to these departments from among former deputy prosecutors, now public prosecutors. Staffing is guided by the reasons for the needs of the service and the selection of candidates who have the necessary knowledge, skills and experience in combating crimes in the field of economic crime, acts against official duty and corruption. When appointing or referring to work in a special department for the fight against corruption, the consent of the deputy public prosecutor is necessary in case he is appointed or referred from a public prosecutor's office in which a special anti-corruption department has not been established.

The police have their own Special Anti-Corruption Department, which is part of the Criminal Police Directorate, but which is relatively independent in its work and related to cooperation with the Special Anti-Corruption Department of the Prosecutor's Office. At the headquarters of the criminal police in Belgrade, there is the Anti-Corruption Department, which coordinates work for the territory of entire Serbia, while at the level of the cities there are Sections (a total of 8) in the form of detachments, namely: Subotica,

Novi Sad, Belgrade, Kragujevac, Zaječar, Niš, Kraljevo and Užice (<https://informator.poverenik.rs>).

The work methodology (or Standard Operating Procedures) of these organizational units is the same as for other units within the criminal police, but specially adapted to the sensitive area they cover. The anti-corruption department and sections have close cooperation with the prosecution, especially because they act according to the direct orders of the prosecutor and in accordance with the law. For the sake of better cooperation, a coordinator for cooperation between the police and the prosecutor's office has been appointed within each department. Issues such as deadlines, procedures and official communication between the prosecutor's office and the police in the field of combating corruption are regulated by a joint legal act of the Minister of Justice and the Minister of the Interior. In addition, the Minister of the Interior issues a special act that more closely regulates the organization and policing of the special anti-corruption unit. Within the Combating Organized Crime Service, there is a special Department for High Corruption in cases involving elements of felonies of corruption in the context of organized crime, which is all under the jurisdiction of the Prosecutor's Office for Organized Crime (Further reading: Leštanin, Nikač 2016).

Specialized bodies for assistance and support to special anti-corruption departments of the prosecution are also issued by OCGL. Thus, the possibility of establishing a Financial Forensics Service is foreseen, within which expert work is performed by experts, as a rule, in the economic profession, who help prosecutors in the analysis of money flows and financial transactions. The law issues that financial forensic experts are experts who possess adequate knowledge in the field of finance, accounting, auditing, banking, stock exchange and business operations. The law also issues the mutual cooperation of all state authorities through liaison officers in order to achieve cooperation and provide data, with the aim of more efficient criminal prosecution for corrupt crimes. The next type of cooperation in the fight against corruption consists of strike groups, which represent a mechanism of cooperation, coordination and joint work formed by the decision of the competent prosecutor with the consent of the Supreme Public Prosecutor, with the aim of detecting and prosecuting crimes that are the subject of the work of the strike group. Other important elements of importance for the normal work and functioning of specialized bodies for the fight against corruption are the training of personnel, data on property status (property card), security checks and keeping data confidential.

7. RESULTS

Semantically, the word corruption originates from the Latin term *corruptio*, which in translation means corruption, depravity, debauchery; bribing, bribery; decay, decomposition; forgery (Vujaklija, 1980: 472). The definition of corruption is not uniquely determined in doctrine and practice because different – sociological, legal, mixed, etc. (Nikač, 2015: 32-38). Sociological definitions start from the broader social perception of corruption and undefined general good and public interest, while legal definitions start from corruption as a criminal act and specific criminal offences. In the author's opinion, the most expedient is a mixed (legal-sociological) determination that equally respects the social environment and the norms of positive law (Further readings in Milutinović, 1990: 34).

In modern society, primacy is given by functional definitions given by reference institutions, such as the World Bank, which considers corruption to be the abuse of a public position for the purpose of private gain (Teofilović, 2007: 23). A similar position is

taken by Transparency International, which under corruption means abuse of power for private gain (Further readings in Nikač, 2009: 408-424).

The most important elements of corruption are public authority (original or derived), abuse of authority and obtaining illegal (property) benefit for oneself or another (Poup, Skopjak, Nikolić, Nenadić, 2004: 3). The most important forms and types of corruption are: individual, systemic, indirect, competition, active and passive, and other forms – institutional and idiosyncratic; conventional and indirect; street, contractual and political; transactional, extortion and investment; nepotistic and autogenously (Derenčinović, 2000: 130-134).

The authors believe that the presented international documents are a good basis for establishing a joint fight against organized crime, corruption and other most serious forms of crime, as well as for establishing better international cooperation between states and international organizations. On the national level, these documents were important for the harmonization of norms and the adoption of good legal solutions, as well as for a more effective multi-agency approach of state authorities and bodies in the fight against organized crime and suppression of corruption.

The national legislation of Serbia in the field of combating corruption consists of several codes or laws that regulate criminal liability and the organization of public authorities. This legislation regulates the institutional mechanisms of each public authority in the fight against corruption. The system established in this way is in line with the most important international resolutions. In the practice of work of public authorities, cooperation on the internal level is very important, which takes place on a multi-sector, i.e. multi-agency level, while international cooperation with other countries and international organizations takes place on the external level. Multi-agency cooperation in the field of internal affairs, security and crime prevention takes place through the National Security Council, which is headed by the President of the Republic. The Council is significantly assisted in its work by the Bureau for Coordination, which operationally coordinates the work of the security services and executes the Council's conclusions on issues within its jurisdiction. In the work of these bodies, the relevant ministers (army, police, justice, etc.) and representatives of the police, intelligence agencies, military security services, the Supreme Court and the Supreme Public Prosecutor's Office and others, depending on the subject of consideration, participate in the work of these bodies as permanent members or by invitation. Representatives of these and other authorities exchange information and coordinate joint activities, potentially in the area of combating corruption in the community.

8. CONCLUSION

In addition to terrorism and organized crime, one of the most serious forms of criminality is certainly corruption, especially since it has gained the right of citizenship in numerous communities and has become a system of life. Today, corruption is a problem in a large number of countries in the world, especially less developed and countries in transition. This phenomenon seriously threatens to collapse the previous achievements of the developed world and human civilization, because the regular work and life of people in the community becomes meaningless. It also threatens to shake the foundations of a democratic society and undermine the work of all state bodies and citizens' trust in the state, its bodies and their work.

Corruption is significantly present in countries in transition, such as the countries of the former socialist bloc and ex SFRY, where it has successfully adapted to social, political and economic changes. In these countries, it took on some new forms and even more dangerous forms, because the transition environment significantly contributed to the development of corruption at all levels of society. Some of the ex-socialist countries managed to overcome the difficult time of transition, harmonize legislation with EU law and build institutional mechanisms to combat corruption. The best example is the Czech Republic, Slovakia, Hungary and Romania, which are equal EU member states today. The former YU republics of Slovenia and Croatia, which today are also equal members of the EU, had the same experience. Other member states of the former SFRY are currently in the process of transition and joining the EU, as is the case with North Macedonia, Montenegro and Bosnia and Herzegovina. The mentioned countries have also encountered organized crime, terrorism, and other most serious forms of crime and, of course, corruption.

Serbia is also an applicant country for admission to the EU, but with a lot of delays in the last 10-15 years, when the process of reforms in society seems to have stopped and admission to the EU is uncertain. Serbia has opened a lot of chapters or so-called clusters (groups of chapters) in different areas, among which Chapter no. 23 and 24 relating to defence and security, justice and internal affairs. The authors believe that Serbia has good legislative solutions based on verified international documents, but that in practice the desired results have not been achieved because the community is probably not yet ready for radical cuts. The situation is the same in the fight against crime and its most dangerous forms, especially against corruption. The formation of new organizational forms of the police, prosecutor's office and court in the form of specialized bodies for combating corruption is particularly important. These bodies have achieved good initial results, but it seems that there is a lack of greater support from the community and political structures.

A successful fight against corruption requires, first of all, a change of consciousness among citizens, then a change in the environment in society and the education of citizens in which the devastating consequences of corruption in the community would be constantly pointed out. Perhaps there is room for thinking to make some *de lege ferenda* changes in the existing framework, especially to adapt to the new ambient conditions and emerging forms of corruption in the public (state) sector. At the end, authors add that transparency in the work of all authorities is a necessary prerequisite for the successful suppression of corruption, while respecting the rules of criminal procedure and the secrecy of certain stages of the procedure.

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THE EROSION OF SMALL STATES – BETWEEN FOREIGN POLICY OPPORTUNISM AND INTERNAL OBSTACLES: CASE STUDY – WESTERN BALKANS

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Abstract

The main purpose of this paper is to put an emphasis on the internal institutional challenges, risks and threats on the path of creating sustainability at different levels. Thus, authors have decided to create a comparative analysis between internal, mostly institutional challenges, risks and threats, from one side, and foreign policy goals from the other side. Mentioned analysis would be, on the empirical example of Western Balkans, basis for proving the thesis that small states with limited political, economic, security and resource capacities should ensure their effective foreign policy positioning, thus ensuring sustainability, through strong, strategically directed and tactically adaptable institutional framework. In that context, the research question of the study would be: Does the weak institutional framework of small and microstates with limited capacities and resources constitute the main determinant of their stability and sustainability? The study will use internal challenges, risks, and threats as a variable in the process of concretizing and proving the promoted thesis.

Key words: small states, weak institutions, foreign policy, internal challenges, risks and threats, Western Balkans

1. INTRODUCTION

In the context of sustainability and sustainable development the institutional framework is positioned also as one of the goals of the whole process from the global perspective. But, the main issue of the discussion in this paper is the realization of the sustainable development agenda, thus reaching the declared goals, from the institutional perspective of small states. Precisely, how much small states in the group of weak ones, with a weak, unstable and unpredictable institutional system, could contribute to the mentioned agenda, thus securing sustainability as well for itself, and could play effective role on micro (national) level, if those group of countries produces internal (domestic and authentic) challenges, risks and threats with contrary consequences to the SDGs agenda? The authors leading question would be: on which grounds small and weak states could establish the sustainable development strategy framework if there is a lack of efficient institutional mechanism for the management and realization process? And it is closely connected to the declared foreign policy goals of small and weak states because their

foreign policy goals are defined on the national interests preservation basis. Analysed from that perspective, preservation of national interests is the basis for sustainability, which leads us to the finding that realization of foreign policy goals is in cause-and-effect relationship with national sustainable development. Namely, a weak domestic institutional framework is not able to perform strategically based and tactically focused diplomatic actions for the realization of foreign policy goals. Diplomatic failure on the side of foreign policy goals is questioning the national capabilities for the preservation of national interests. Without mechanism for preservation the long-term defined national interests, sustainable development of such groups of states is, by logical reasoning, unreachable. In fact, there is the essential importance of the paper, respectively, the explanation about the link between weak institutional framework and foreign policy failures which consequences are directly related to sustainability, including the development. From such perspective, on the concrete example of the Western Balkans states and political entities, authors will justify their thesis about the essential importance of internal institutional system and its effectiveness, as a precondition in the process of sustainable development, especially in the case of small states with limited economic, political, natural and military resources. From a theoretical perspective, authors will use the explanation of the representatives of neoclassical realism who are using the personal dimension of authorities/political and institutional representatives. Precisely on the case study of the Western Balkans, and through the mentioned theoretical dimension, the authors will explain how political and institutional authorities in the context of weak institutional framework are misusing their official capacities, working de facto against the foreign policy agenda and preservation of national/state interests, thus questioning the sustainability of the state they represent. The empirical example of foreign policy failure in the case study region, based on personal, instead of institutional decisions and guidelines, will serve as a pragmatic explanation of the authors' thesis, as well as empirical verifiable evidence about the importance of institutional system in the general context of sustainable development, as well as in the micro context of small states. This study also lead us to the wider discussion about the institutional efficiency and effectiveness, positioned as one of the sustainable development goals. Namely, the question that arises is whether the professional, predictable and stable institutional framework should still be set as one of the goals or they should be repositioned as one of the preconditions on the SDGs agenda?

2. METHODOLOGICAL FRAMEWORK

The research will be methodologically framed in qualitative methods, which refer to qualitative data analysis in order to determine behavioural patterns (Arežina, 2023:209) of the case study political entities in the context of foreign policy positioning. In fact, authors through the foreign policy activism are identifying the research problem which in this case is the issue of sustainability of small and weak states. Further, through the analysis of data (European Commission Annual Reports) they are establishing the description of the main phenomenon related to national/domestic institutional weakness as a dependent variable in the whole process of reaching strategic foreign policy goals, thus achieving effective foreign policy positioning which as a result means preservation of national/state interests and finally, securing sustainability. The research question (Creswell, 2012 :60) is structured so that the authors could be able to concretize the global sustainability phenomenon on a specific problem, respectively, to reach a specification of the problem of sustainable development from the perspective of small and at the same time weak states.

From a scientific perspective, the aim of this paper is to provide a scientific explanation (Arežina, 2021 :278) of the consequences that political decision-makers create in their personal and extra-institutional foreign policy activism in contemporary international relations, thus deepening the debate on the role of leaders in creating foreign policy from the perspective of neoclassical realists. On the other hand, in the context of societal goals, i.e. the applicability of this research (Arežina, 2021 :278), the authors provide a forecast based on existing tendencies derived from the annual reports of the European Commission, which further strengthens the value of the analysis itself, making it useful in identifying internal/domestic challenges, risks and threats and its implication to foreign policy positioning and sustainability as a de facto linked processes from the perspective of relationship between foreign policy goals and national/state interests. In the context of concretization and raising the question why the authors have decided to use European Commission Annual Reports as a sufficient data analysis basis, the explanation lies in the declarative foreign policy strategic goal of empirical example entities which is EU membership. From the perspective of the EU membership, as a goal which, in the context of case study entities, should contribute to further stability and development, authors have made quite a reasonable decision to use mentioned data of the reports as a qualitative explanation basis for dependent variable found in the institutional system and political framework. Methodologically, the paper is focused to internal dependent variables, isolating them on the case study of foreign policy decision-making process from the neoclassical realism theoretical approach, thus providing explanation about the sustainability of small and weak states.

3. POLITICAL POPULISM AND THE CAPTURE OF INSTITUTIONAL FRAMEWORK

In order to be clear during the process of analysing so-called small states, first we should clarify the difference between two subgroups of small states: small states with efficient and effective institutional framework and small states with captured institutional framework which, in practice, make those political entities weak and vulnerable. The goal of this paper is to analyse the process of so-called erosion of small and weak states from the institutional perspective, bearing in mind the limited capacities of resources that generally small states have. In fact, authors are focused to explain, on the Western Balkans case study, that lack of political, diplomatic, economic, natural and military resources could be on a certain way substituted with the strong, efficient, effective, resistant and reliable internal institutional framework, as a kind of an unlimited resource which could play a role of "fuel" in reaching defined foreign policy goals, thus securing sustainability of national interests, including the sustainability of the state.

The Western Balkans region has been chosen because there are states and political entities with enormous internal and regional issues, disputes and obstacles which, on a long-term basis, have negative effects not only in the process of creation sustainability, but in the rounding off statehood process. Empirical example serves twofold: to represent the characteristics of small and weak states, from one side; from the other side, to explain the role of institutional framework in the process of realization foreign policy goals and, consequently, securing sustainability.

As data for proving the thesis, the authors will use the European Commission Annual Reports for each of the so-called Western Balkans Six. The decision for analysis mentioned reports has twofold justification: first, those are annual documents which are strictly and precisely in different areas following the internal processes of Western Balkans

Six; second, EU membership represents a key, as well as strategic foreign policy goal of each of the Western Balkans Six, so there is logic connection between internal challenges, risks and threats, from one side, and foreign policy goals, from the other side.

Belgrade (Serbia 2024 Report, 2024)	
Internal challenges, risks and threats	
Political	political polarisation, existence of a list of “morally and politically unwelcome foreigners”, widespread pressure on public sector employees, EU integration process centralised and politically driven, political influence on the media
Economic	economic uncertainty, state-owned enterprises have a significant presence in the economy, economic influence on the media, private sector is hampered by weaknesses in the rule of law, in particular in tackling corruption and judicial inefficiency, the link between the strategic priorities and budget programmes is insufficient, and ad hoc priorities frequently crowd out resource allocation
Institutional	Serbia should address weaknesses in the investigation and prosecution of high-level corruption cases, the risk of corruption remains high for cases of exemptions from the Law on public procurement that are not in line with the EU acquis, Serbia ranked 104th out of 180 countries in the 2023 corruption perception index compiled by Transparency International, thus continuing the negative trend since 2018

Skopje (North Macedonia 2024 Report, 2024)	
Internal challenges, risks and threats	
Political	political polarisation in Parliament persisted, the situation was polarised during the period preceding the elections of April and May 2024, political support, leadership, supervision, and management of public administration reforms across the government remained insufficient, politicisation of the public service has continuously undermined the consistent application of provisions on merit-based and transparent processes and has further decreased trust in the administration and its work
Economic	post-pandemic economic recovery remained weak, economy remains vulnerable to a potential renewed surge in energy prices, given its high energy-intensity and still large reliance on imported energy, challenges posed by the large informal economy have not been addressed decisively, despite the urgent need to modernise the

	economy's infrastructure, investment in this area is low
Institutional	Health is one of the biggest national budget users, and the inspection services are vulnerable to corruption, corruption remains prevalent in many areas and is an issue of serious concern, track record in the fight against corruption has worsened, there are still concerning patterns regarding an increasing number of delays in court proceedings and an increase in reversals of court rulings on corruption and organised crime

Sarajevo (Bosnia and Herzegovina 2024 Report, 2024)	
Internal challenges, risks and threats	
Political	The reform dynamic stalled between April and October 2024, among political controversies and the political campaign for the October local election, political parties should respect the independence of the Central Election Commission, the conduct of the elections is negatively affected by the discriminatory elements of the constitutional system and by the lack of integrity of the electoral process, parliamentary oversight over the executives remains weak
Economic	Financial investigations and asset seizures and confiscations remain insufficient, Bosnia and Herzegovina is at an early stage of preparation and has made limited progress in establishing a functioning market economy, countrywide harmonisation remains insufficient, hindering progress towards a single economic space, the business environment continues to suffer from a weak rule of law, political uncertainty and the country's economic and institutional fragmentation
Institutional	Bosnia and Herzegovina needs to bring its constitutional framework in line with European standards and ensure the functionality of its institutions to be able to take on EU obligations, Bosnia and Herzegovina will need to reform its institutions to be able to effectively participate in EU decision-making and to fully implement and enforce the acquis, Bosnia and Herzegovina lacks strategic documents as it still needs to adopt a new justice sector reform strategy and related action plan

Tirana (Albania 2024 Report, 2024)	
Internal challenges, risks and threats	
Political	The functioning of democratic institutions is partially

	satisfactory, stemming mainly from the deeply polarised political situation, unaddressed shortcomings in the electoral process, limited effective parliamentary oversight over the executive and the lack of meaningful public consultations. Political scene continued to be marked by high political polarisation against the background of persistent divisions within the largest opposition party. This has further weakened the effectiveness, transparency and objectivity of parliamentary work
Economic	The business environment is hampered by a large informal economy. Informal economy remains widespread, impacting fair competition among businesses, inefficiencies in public administration, an excessive regulatory framework and corruption pose further challenges to the business environment
Institutional	Concerns remain about attempted interference and pressure on the judicial system from public officials and politicians, despite strong legal safeguards, merit-based appointments and career development are weakened in practice

Podgorica (Montenegro 2024 Report, 2024)	
Internal challenges, risks and threats	
Political	Persisting fragmentation of the parliamentary landscape, political instability, Montenegro should further strive to align its electoral processes to highest democratic standards
Economic	The dynamic development of local and foreign companies is hindered by the informal economy, inefficiencies and delays in dealings with the administration, excessive complexity of the legal framework and the administrative burden related to parafiscal charges as well as insufficient quality of e-services. Further obstacles are related to insufficient transparency in decision-making, arbitrary law interpretation and enforcement by public authorities and access to finance for small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs)
Institutional	Institutions are fragile and vulnerable to political crisis and potential institutional blockages, political instability as a main reason for the lack of public administration reform, selection processes for managerial positions are subject to political influence, the judiciary and the prosecution remain perceived as vulnerable to political interference

Priština (Kosovo* 2024 Report, 2024)	
Internal challenges, risks and threats	
Political	Domestic politics hampered the implementation of EU agenda, lack of demonstration of political commitment by aligning its legislation with the EU acquis, politicization of humanitarian issues, lack of political will, the functioning of democratic institutions is affected by some challenges, such as lack of cooperation on the line majority-opposition, boycott, issue of centralization of executive decision-making
Economic	Vulnerable to political influence and financial pressure, tax base continues to be weakened by numerous tax exemptions, preferential tax rates and special regimes, while public spending is burdened by category-based specific transfers, leaving little space for means-tested benefits and employment policies, lacks an independent monetary policy and does not have standard monetary policy tools at its disposal
Institutional	From the rule of law perspective, government officials tend to criticise decisions in individual cases or even target specific judges or prosecutors, which is of concern, The quality of justice remains insufficient, precisely, the quality of indictments and judgments in criminal law remains insufficient, the prosecution service to handle cases in a timely manner remains limited, particularly in high-level corruption cases

Referring to the findings of European Commission Annual Reports for each of the Western Balkans Six represent a sufficient twofold methodological approach: first, to explain the internal context between political populism and real flows; second, to create stable basis for connections between internal institutional flows and foreign policy opportunism. But the second variable will be explained in the next chapter.

When it comes to the findings of European Commission Annual Reports and internal populist discourse, it is quite a clear that there are substantive disagreements. While, on internal level, political representatives are promoting their political programmes for continuation of the development and sustainability, from the other side, based on the reports which are strictly connected to the strategic foreign policy goal of each of the six entities, there are data which show contrary flows.

- ***In the context of democratisation***, EU reports have confirmed the thesis about the lack of political will for realistic strengthening of democratic capacities while, at the same time, leading domestic and political representatives are placing themselves as generators of democratic and open societies

- ***In the context of rule of law and fight against corruption***, EU reports are confirming the thesis about the lack of efficient political and institutional mechanisms for dealing and resolving mentioned internal risks while, at the same time, leading domestic

and political representatives are de facto encouraging the wide spreading of the phenomena of corruption, thus marginalizing the rule of law standards.

- *In the context of market economy*, EU reports are confirming the thesis about the inefficient market economy while, at the same time, leading domestic and political representatives are, through legislative and political tools, contributing to the creation of a kind a politically-based economy which could not be interpreted as a planned economy, inherent to socialist or communist systems, but beneficial to the politically favourable groups and interests.

In fact, Western Balkans Six are facing structural internal (domestic) challenges, risks and threats, politically projected and institutionally applicable which are influencing to enhancing the process of complete internal inefficiency, which leads to unpredictability to whole process of sustainability, thus negatively contributing to the internal erosion. Within such scenario composed of public discourse based on the political populism, capture of institutional framework within the political interests and the lack of social and political awareness about the referred negative political, economic and institutional trends lead case study entities to the general twofold erosion: internal, by producing domestic challenges, risks and threats from institutional to social framework and vice-versa and foreign, lack of efficient political tools and institutional mechanisms for foreign policy positioning based on the foreign policy goals and defined national (state) interests. Data analysis based on the European Commission Annual Reports has shown concrete example about the dependence of foreign policy positioning to the internal (domestic) functionality. In the case study political subjects foreign policy positioning is absolutely released of their own material possibilities and resources and structurally based to the qualitative conditions framed in the domestic institutional system based on the political, economic and social frames. Such a context leads the authors to the conclusion that foreign policy opportunism is not a consequence of international developments, in this case within the European Union framework, but rather a “hostage” of domestic challenges, risks, and threats that generate structural contradictions within the political framework. While this framework formally insists on defined foreign policy goals, it simultaneously fails to contribute to domestic institutional functionality, which functions as a dependent variable in achieving the desired foreign policy positioning.

4. FOREIGN POLICY FAILURES FROM REGIONAL AND INTERNATIONAL PERSPECTIVE

This chapter serves to create a connection between the foreign policy goals of the political entities in the Western Balkans region and the institutional (domestic) challenges, risks and threats from the perspective of erosion of the state. Namely, each of Western Balkans Six declared the EU membership as a key and strategic foreign policy goal. In the case of Belgrade, the European integration and membership in the European Union are placed as a goals even above the foreign policy goals, stating that the both processes are "the national interest and strategic commitment of the Republic of Serbia, while the values of the European Union are precisely the values that the Republic of Serbia supports and wishes to further foster" (Republika Srbija, Ministarstvo spoljnih poslova, Politički odnosi Srbije i EU, 2025). In fact, Arnaudov explains, "Western Balkans exists as a political entity in which it is precisely European integration that determines such an whole, outside the real geographical framework on the ground" (Arnaudov, 2023 :124). But, the available data witness that the European integration and the EU membership are, in practice, just a

declarative or official goal of each of Western Balkans Six. Such thesis is empirically explained in the previous chapter where we have made short review of the political, economic and social flows within of each of the Western Balkans entities. Each of Western Balkans Six is facing intensive internal issues, risks and challenges, overspread in political, economic and institutional infrastructures, thus contributing to the national or precisely systematic inability to deal, manage and lead the foreign policy process in the context of European integration and EU membership.

Recalling the well-known Copenhagen criteria, each of Western Balkans Six has not established internal institutional infrastructure, thus political and economic grounds which will sustainably secure “stability of institutions guaranteeing democracy, the rule of law, human rights and respect for and protection of minorities, a functioning market economy and the ability to cope with competitive pressure and market forces within the EU, the ability to take on the obligations of membership, including the capacity to effectively implement the rules, standards and policies that make up the body of EU law (the ‘acquis’), and adherence to the aims of political, economic and monetary union” (EUR-Lex/Accession criteria (Copenhagen criteria):¹⁹⁹³).

On the contrary, there is a lack of an establishing framework for reaching the elementary criteria of European integration process and EU membership, although on the formal, official and legislative level there are visible results. But, the lack of consistency between legislative and implementation flows is the major obstacle. Political and institutional representatives in practice do not express realistic political will for the EU membership and integration process, thus questioning the so-called leading foreign policy goal. Consequently such scenario leads Western Balkans Six to the stage of unpredictability for two reasons: at internal (domestic) level, institutional, political and economic framework are instrumentalized in practice by political representatives, thus losing their main role and task to serve to the nation and the state; at international level, even in the current geostrategic momentum, Western Balkans Six are losing international and European support in the context of integration process because could not be positioned as reliable partners due their internal challenges, risks and threats, while, from the other side, all six entities are not making contribution to achieving defined criteria, thus not convincing the EU member states about their realistic dedication to integration process and membership.

Additional negative value in the whole process are current regional flows. Namely open issues and disputes since the civil wars from nineties and politization of the mentioned period, instrumentalization of bilateral issues in the European integration processes, continuation of the cross-border negative political rhetoric which raises animosities and reinforces the ground of distrust on a regional basis, including the lack of realistic understanding and political will about the Belgrade-Priština dialogue represent also important barriers to the foreign policy positioning of the Western Balkans Six entities, especially in the process of reaching key and strategic foreign policy goal of EU membership. The internal flows stated in this way remind us of the title of this paper, namely that it is about foreign policy opportunism, given that nothing substantial and concrete is being done in the process of achieving foreign policy goals, but rather that the actors in the politically defined region of the Western Balkans are preoccupied with internal and regional, primarily politically determined, trends and discourses that contribute to the destruction of the internal institutional infrastructure through its political instrumentalization, while at the same time distancing political entities from achieving foreign policy goals, and making them unsustainable if we strictly adhere to the theoretical

premise that achieving foreign policy goals serves the preservation and sustainability of national interests.

5. NEO-CLASSICAL REALISM AS AN APPROACH

Neoclassical realists argue that relative material power establishes the basic parameters of a country's foreign policy. They note, in Thucydides' formula, that "the strong do what they can and the weak suffer what they must" (Strassler, 1996 :5.89 op.cit. u: Rose, 1998 :146). Yet they point out that there is no immediate or perfect transmission belt linking material capabilities to foreign policy behaviour. Foreign policy choices are made by actual political leaders and elites, and so it is their perceptions of relative power that matter, not simply relative quantities of physical resources or forces in being. This means that over the short to medium term countries' foreign policies may not necessarily track objective material power trends closely or continuously (Rose, 1998 :147). Concretely, neoclassical realists believe, understanding the links between power and policy requires close examination of the contexts within which foreign policies are formulated and implemented (Steinmo et al., 1992 :11 op.cit. u: Rose, 1998 :147). The most common approach has been to assume that foreign policy has its sources in domestic politics (Rose, 1998 :148). It is the crucial theoretical approach, as a basis for making linkage between the functionality of domestic institutional framework and foreign policy positioning. Concretely, from the perspective of empirical examples in the second chapter of the paper, neoclassical realists are providing explanation about the cause-effect relationship between internal (domestic) challenges, risks and threats, from one side, and the process of achieving declared foreign policy goals – EU integration and membership. According to these stands, sustainability, as an issue closely dependent of foreign policy positioning, also is mostly determined by political decisions, respectively the behaviour of political and institutional representatives. Such thesis opens new debates for understanding the global phenomena of sustainability, thus placing the dependent variable of political decision-making process in the whole context of progressive sustainability. Unlike classical realists, who analyse foreign policy positioning exclusively from the perspective of the relationships between subjects in the international system (Rose, 1998 :146), neoclassical realists offer a more comprehensive understanding that significantly contributes, among other things, to the understanding of the foreign policy positioning of small and weak states. In this research by proving the linkage between domestic flows and foreign-policy positioning, at the same time released of the material variables, authors have opened a frame for new and qualitative discussion about the ongoing and future prospects of sustainability, thus sustainable development, basing the whole process on institutionality and political behaviour. Empirical paper is based to the so-called *Innenpolitik* theories which argue that internal factors such as political and economic ideology, national character, partisan politics, or socioeconomic structure determine how countries behave toward the world beyond their borders (Rose, 1998 :148). There are many variants of the *Innenpolitik* approach, each favouring a different specific domestic independent variable, but they all share a common assumption – that foreign policy is best understood at the product of country's internal dynamics (Rose, 1998 :148).

The author's assumption is that such theories are primarily applicable in the current chapter of international relations with the focus of small and microstates. Thus, making a clear twofold difference between material and qualitative variables in the foreign policy activism and positioning, while, from the other side, understanding about the small and microstates with strong institutional and personal (labour market) capacities and that one

positioned as a weak state. The first difference is classical one, from the perspective of classical realists, states with political power and military and economic strength could lead effective foreign policy activism, while, at the same time, there is a lack, from classical realists' perspective, understanding for qualitative variables, as those are personal (labour market) capacities, institutional strength and expertise based foreign policy strategies and tactics. From the small and microstates position, the difference between sustainable and weak states lies exclusively in the qualitative variables, respectively characteristics taking into account authors' assumption that small and microstates generally are facing limited resources and capacities, but still they have unlimited capacities and resources in the context of institutions functionality and personal solutions.

6. CLOSING REMARKS

Using the case study of the European integration process of Western Balkans Six, as well as the EU membership positioned as a key and strategic foreign policy goals of each of the Western Balkans political entities, paper' authors has significantly contributed to the understanding about the internal and substantial variables in the process of foreign policy positioning on the examples of small states. Authors have decided to use empirical example of small and weak states in order to create clearer picture about the domestic institutional factor, as a resource, in the process of foreign policy activism, thus reaching foreign policy goals as a mechanism for securing national/state interests. At the same time, on the side of sustainability, using the logic that defined foreign policy goals are serving as an instrument for preservation of national/state interests, authors have explained that without effective foreign policy positioning, thus losing the opportunities for reaching foreign policy goals, the national/state interests are directly endangered. By endangering the national/state interests, sustainability of the subject of the international system is as well questioned. Back to the title of the research, erosion of small states is directly dependent by internal institutional obstacles and the lack of synchronization between domestic political management and foreign policy approach. In fact, this is a characteristic of small but, first of all, weak states. Without domestic and foreign policy synchronization, followed by abusing foreign policy goals and national/state interests on daily political basis, instrumentalization of national institutional infrastructure for political, interest and personal needs, the foreign policy success would be missed, while, at the same time the erosion of the state infrastructure will be empowered due to the lack of mechanisms for preservation the national/state/social interests. Referring to the positions of neoclassical realists, small states cannot create effective and efficient strategic and tactic plans for their own foreign policy activism based exclusively on the international politics flows, behaviour of regional and big powers, current relations of regional and big powers, if they lack to include, as a variables, domestic institutional, political and social flows, including potential challenges, risks and threats. In fact, domestic functionality of small states is a key mechanism for their foreign policy visibility. Although those type of states are faced with a permanent lack of material resources, in the context of foreign policy positioning, as well as in the context of sustainable development, their domestic institutional reliability and political behaviour, including personal behaviour of political and state representatives, could play significant, even a crucial role in the process of reaching defined foreign policy goals, as a precondition for preserving national/state interests, thus securing sustainability.

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CORRUPTION AND ENVIRONMENTAL PROTECTION

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Abstract

Background: Environmental protection is an important segment of societal life, both nationally and internationally. Especially in conditions of climate change, environmental crimes and sustainable development, environmental protection is very important to create safe conditions for all living beings.

Environmental protection is directly related to the activities of the competent state bodies, but also of other institutions in the field. This includes many activities aimed at environmental protection, and activities to combat environmental crimes are especially important.

Within these activities, the presence of corruption in the field of environmental protection is notable, and hence the need to study anti-corruption measures in this area. Certain analyses in the Republic of North Macedonia indicate that corruption in the field of combating environmental crimes is significant, and there are examples of bribery of officials responsible for environmental protection.

Methods: These phenomena will be analysed with the method of content analysis. The author of the text explores these phenomena, with the aim to analyse and propose measures to combat corruption in the field of environmental protection in the Republic of North Macedonia.

Results: According to SOCTA and other research, corruption is directly related to environmental crimes in our country.

Conclusion: We need anti-corruption measures for combating environmental crimes without corruption.

Key words: corruption, environmental crimes etc.

1. INTRODUCTION

Corruption is a serious social problem that affects all spheres of social life. In the Republic of North Macedonia, this problem is most often represented as a criminal offence that is associated with receiving and giving bribes. There are numerous forms of committing these punishable behaviours, and numerous professions are represented, including: doctors, professors, police officers, customs officers, members of political parties, and many others. Although there are a certain number of institutions whose main activity, among others, is the suppression of this type of crime, this phenomenon is still on the rise.

According to certain research by the Faculty of Security in 2016 regarding bribery, 20.45% of the total number of respondents stated that they were exposed to the risk of corruption and gave a bribe, 60.86% stated that they were not in a position to give a bribe, and a part of the respondents – 18.69% did not want to state their opinion. It can be

concluded that a quarter of the total number of respondents gave a bribe (Mojanoski, Mališ Sazdovska, Nikolovski et al. 2016).

To monitor the current situation regarding corruption in the country, a special European Union Report is being prepared for the Republic of North Macedonia, so the Report for 2023 states that “The country is in between some and moderate level of preparation in preventing and fighting corruption. No progress has been made. Corruption remains widespread in many areas and this issue is of concern. The number of delays and reversals of trials in high-level corruption cases has increased, resulting in some cases with the statute of limitations expiring. The Criminal Code was amended following an accelerated parliamentary procedure. The maximum statutory penalty for specific corruption-related crimes was reduced, which had implications for the application of the statute of limitations and affected, halting or even terminating many high-level corruption cases, including those by the former Special Public Prosecutor's Office (SPO). The amendments also hinder the ability of the authorities to investigate and prosecute such crimes. This issue raises serious concerns”.

Based on the statements in the Report, it can be concluded that the country still faces major challenges in the field of anti-corruption measures and activities that need to be undertaken to suppress this negative social phenomenon.

The competent authorities for combating corruption are:

- The Government of the Republic of North Macedonia, which has developed an Action 21 plan to combat corruption. In August 2017, the Government of the Republic of North Macedonia also adopted a decision to adopt a Strategy for Strengthening the Capacities for Conducting Financial Investigations and Confiscation of Property with an Action Plan for its implementation in the period from 2018 to 2020.

- The Parliament of the Republic of North Macedonia adopts a national strategy, reviews and adopts reports from the SCPC, and adopts a budget for the SCPC.

- Ministry of Finance, SCPC submits a budget proposal to the ministry,

- Public prosecutor's offices and courts, processing criminal offences related to corruption and conflict of interest,

- State Commission for the Prevention of Corruption, is autonomous and independent in the performance of its duties and has the status of a legal entity. The Commission adopts a national strategy with an action plan, conducts anti-corruption inspections of laws and other acts, acts on reports, initiates initiatives, monitors the legality of operations, etc. The Commission submits a report to the Parliament, but also to the President of the Republic of Macedonia, the Government of the Republic of Macedonia and the media.

The State Commission for the Prevention of Corruption (SCPC) has a legal obligation to adopt a five-year National Strategy for the Prevention of Corruption and Conflict of Interest with an action plan for its implementation. This is the first document in the field of combating corruption to be adopted at the highest level, i.e. by the Assembly of the Republic of North Macedonia.

- Local self-government, municipalities adopt an Annual Plan for the Fight against Corruption and Conflict of Interest and an action plan for identified measures with activities and indicators.

- Ministry of Environment and Spatial Planning,

- State Inspectorate for Environment, cooperation with the business community, civil society associations, educational and scientific institutions and all stakeholders who can contribute with their activities to increase transparency, and emphasized cooperation with

the SCPC for the prevention of corruption in the area of transparency and integrity of the inspection service (Malish Szdovska, 2024).

In addition to these competent state and local government bodies, the Ministry of Interior, Ministry of Justice, Customs Administration, Financial Police, Inspection Council, Financial Intelligence Administration, Public Revenue Office, etc. have the competence and authority to act in the area of combating corruption.

The Basic Public Prosecutor's Office for Prosecution of Organized Crime and Corruption is responsible for the most complex forms of organized crime and high-level corruption and is responsible for handling cases related to organized crime and corruption throughout the territory of the Republic of North Macedonia. The Basic Public Prosecutor's Office for Prosecution of Organized Crime and Corruption is located in Skopje. It is accountable for its work to the Public Prosecutor of the Republic of North Macedonia, who supervises the work of this prosecutor's office, as well as to the Council of Public Prosecutors. The key guarantee for its functioning in accordance with the law is financial independence, which is the basic pillar and prerequisite for the independence of every institution, including the Public Prosecutor's Office.

Several competent authorities are responsible for financial investigations into environmental crimes related to giving and receiving bribes, among which the Financial Police, the Financial Intelligence Unit and the Public Revenue Office play a key role (Malish Szdovska, 2025).

2. Corruption and environmental protection

In addition to other areas in which corruption is evident, it can be concluded that there is also a serious presence of corruption in the area of environmental protection. According to the Serious and Organized Crime Threat Assessment 2021 (SOCTA, 2021) prepared by the Bureau of Public Security under the Ministry of Interior, it is concluded for environmental crimes that the number of detected crimes does not reflect the real situation, and in cases of environmental endangerment there are situations that are not fully documented and do not have a criminal-legal conclusion. The lack of the detection function of the competent authorities, which have difficulty recognizing crimes, is also highlighted as a problem. Forest devastation is a crime that, in its manifestations, in most cases represents organized crime. Illegal logging in the Republic of Macedonia is characterized as "highly threatening, with a large dark number, without indications of stopping criminal activity". Illegal logging and deforestation are directly linked to corruption, which is often used to facilitate the commission of these crimes (SOCTA, 2021).

Based on the results of SOCTA, corrupt abuse has been observed among:

- Employees of the Real Estate Cadastre Agency who carry out unfounded changes in the ownership of forest plots, from state ownership to private ownership of individuals, based on which logging permits are later issued,
- Employees of the PE National Forests for abuses in checking timber and issuing consignment notes for transport and sale,
- Employees of the Police and Forest Police for evading control by giving bribes.

Analysing the conclusions of the Assessment, it can be concluded that "corruption is a key driver of environmental crime, and it significantly affects the detection activity, which is why it is assumed that organized forms are not fully detected" (SOCTA, 2021).

The Serious and Organized Crime Threat Assessment, Mid-Term Review 2023, states that “environmental crime has increased by 26.3% compared to the previous period, with the increase being most pronounced in the threat to the environment and nature with waste, for which criminal acts have increased by 327.3%. In this Assessment, as in the previous one, the detection function is assessed as low and does not reflect the real situation on the ground” (SOCTA, 2023). The Assessment states that "environmental crime continues to be a current threat through the illegal use of natural resources, including the threat to the environment and nature with waste, which is increasing. Environmental crime is closely linked with the legal business sector, with criminal structures in the area managing to abuse legal loopholes and use legislative changes for new criminal activity. Also, in the concluding observations, it is concluded that environmental crime is often committed with elements of corruption and informal association of people, the possibility of organized action and cooperation with groups operating in the field of corruption and economic crime is assumed” (SOCTA, 2023).

Another document indicating the existence of corrupt activities in the field of the environment is the Annual Report on the Implementation of the Measures of the National Strategy for the Prevention of Corruption and Conflict of Interest, planned for implementation in 2021. The Report states that, "The environmental sector in the context of this Strategy consists of public institutions that are part of the central and local government, and with jurisdiction over issues in the field of environmental protection. This sector has gained importance in recent years due to the introduction of various environmental and other permits that business entities need to have in order to be able to start/carry out their operational activities (Annual Report, 2022).

The Report of the State Commission for the Prevention of Corruption, however, states that the commission acted in only 5 cases in the field of the environment during 2022, and that after receiving reports, and in no case on its own initiative.

2.1. Analysis of cases of environmental corruption

In the Republic of North Macedonia, there are several cases of bribery and corruption of persons in the field of ecology, i.e. environmental and nature protection (Analysis Florozon, 2024).

The Financial Police Directorate has filed a criminal complaint against a natural person in the capacity of an official - a Senior Civil Servant at the Ministry of Environment and Spatial Planning of the Republic of North Macedonia. The criminal complaint was filed due to the existence of a reasonable suspicion that during 2021 he abused his official position, i.e. acted contrary to Article 108, paragraph 1 and paragraph 8 of the Law on Environment, in such a way that, without inspecting the installation and its operation to determine the fulfilment of the requirements in accordance with legal regulations, he personally prepared and approved an A-integrated environmental permit for JPDKO Drisla Skopje, although they did not possess appropriate equipment and installations.

With the operation "Penta" in December 2014, the commander of the Police Station for Border Surveillance on Lake Ohrid was deprived of his liberty, due to the existence of a well-founded suspicion of committing the crime of Abuse of Official Position and Authority. In addition to the criminal charges against the commander, criminal charges were also filed against four individuals from Struga for committing crimes of "incitement" and "illegal fishing" under the Criminal Code. In this case, it is a senior manager in the Ministry of Internal Affairs who, for a long period of time, organized

a group that illegally caught fish and sold them to restaurants and other catering facilities and private individuals.

The nature of the crime consisted in the activities of the commander, who, in order to gain unlawful material benefit, enabled the other individuals charged to continuously commit the crime of Illegal Fishing in the waters of Lake Ohrid. The commander had to, but failed to, perform official actions in accordance with the legal regulations and did not take measures to carry out control in the waters of Lake Ohrid. He informed the other reported persons about the time and place of the police controls of the lake police, to avoid patrols, placing the nets in places where the lake police would not patrol, in order not to be discovered and not to have the equipment and nets with which they committed the crime of Illegal fishing confiscated. In return for this "service", the commander received monetary compensation or illegally caught fish.

The next case is the example of an employee of the Forest Police in Demir Hisar for accepting a bribe. The employee of the Forest Police from Demir Hisar was deprived of his liberty and suspected of committing a crime under Article 357 of the Criminal Code "accepting a bribe". The employee demanded money in return for not acting, that is, not sanctioning illegal operations. However, the person reported the case to the SVR Bitola and was given forensically processed money, which he gave to the employee of the Forest Police. After handing over the money, the person was deprived of his liberty and 18,000 denars were found on him, which originated from the crime, after which he was detained at the Bitola police station and criminal charges were filed against him.

In 2021, criminal charges were also filed against a state environmental inspector for accepting a bribe, after he received a bribe of 200 euros. He requested and received this money from the owner in Kičevo, and he also had an accomplice who will be prosecuted. The owner had a car lot, and the inspector for the return of the bribe was not supposed to inspect the lot. The criminal complaint was filed due to reasonable suspicion that the state environmental inspector committed a criminal offence of accepting a bribe, while performing his official duty. A criminal complaint was filed against the second defendant for reasonable suspicion of committing a criminal offence of aiding, because he enabled the inspector to take the money from the bribe in the premises of his office in Kičevo.

This occurrence of achieving material benefit from concealing legal violations by polluters was condemned by the State Inspectorate for Environmental Protection.

3. CONCLUSION

Based on the analysis of the above-mentioned cases of corruption in the field of the environment, it can be concluded that there is no effective action to suppress this phenomenon. Namely, there are numerous cases that confirm that employees in various institutions, at various levels of work from the lowest to the highest management positions, undertake corrupt actions and appear as perpetrators of crimes such as accepting a bribe, abuse of official position and authority, etc.

Hence, it can be concluded that this crime is prevalent in the field of the environment and that additional measures and activities are needed for preventive and repressive action in suppressing the crime.

The directions that can be proposed to improve the situation are: efficient criminal investigations into these crimes, increasing awareness among the population about reporting, strengthening the human and technical capacities of the competent authorities

under whose jurisdiction and authority this type of crime is, and perhaps the most important segment is strengthening the integrity of employees in these institutions.

In addition to the above measures, the following activities can be undertaken to prevent corruption, namely:

- strengthening of supervisory and control mechanisms,
- improving the standard and material well-being of the population,
- strengthening of the human and technical capacities of the competent authorities for the suppression of corruption,
- existence of an efficient judicial system and effective rule of law,
- introduction of digitalized procedures,
- education, training and strengthening of the integrity of employees in the competent authorities.

If these anti-corruption measures are implemented in the coming period, we can expect a reduction in the trend of corruption, as well as the creation of conditions for a society in which corruption will be reduced to the lowest level or we will have a state of zero corruption.

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HUMAN RIGHTS AS SECURITY ISSUE: THE CASE OF GREECE

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Abstract

The paper contributes to securitization theory by using its core concepts to argue that human rights of persons belonging to the Macedonian minority in Greece are securitized. It analyses the judgments of the European Court of Human Rights against Greece finding a violation of the right to freedom of association of Macedonians through the prism of securitization theory. And, based on this qualitative content analysis, it explains that Greece perceives and treats the associations of ethnic Macedonians in the country as a security issue. The measures against the associations, described by the Strasbourg Court as not necessary in a democratic society, are taken by the Greek authorities (as extraordinary measures) in response to the alleged threat to state and nation (national identity) coming from the association. By presenting the arguments advanced by the authorities to justify the interference with the right to freedom of association the paper provides a starting point for future research on how to desecuritize the issue.

Key words: securitization, human rights, Greece, Macedonians, right to freedom of association

1. INTRODUCTION

The paper stems out from the research project “Macedonian minority in Greece and Bulgaria and Council of Europe” designed at the Faculty of Security – Skopje and conducted in the period 2022–2024. The starting point of the research project was the significant body of literature that criticizes both Greece and Bulgaria for human rights violations against the members of the Macedonian minority, referring to the human rights mechanisms established within the Council of Europe (see, for instance: Stojkov, 2021; Daskalovski, 2002; Ringelheim, 2002; de Varennes, 2004; Anagnostou & Psychogiopoulou, 2010; Grigoriadis, 2008; Kyriakou, 2009; Ibraimi, 2013; Tacev, 2011; Triandafyllidou & Kokkali, 2010; Baltiotis & Embrikos, 2001). The research attempts to explain the causes of these violations using securitization theory. The initial findings from the research have already been published (Milenkovska & Gerasimoski, 2024: 13-22). This paper particularly discusses the securitization of human rights of Macedonians living in Greece.

Securitization theory has been discussed in the literature on security extensively. In spite of certain critiques regarding its theoretical coherence, its methodology or its

normative and critical status, many issues, such as religion, health, migration, energy, environment, etc., have been studied through the prism of securitization theory (Baele & Thomson, 2022; Balzacq & Leonard, 2016, Nasu, 2021; Nyman, 2013; Vuković, 2022; Balzacq, 2018; Славески, 2010; Charrett, 2009; Jutila, 2006; Buzan, et al. 1998; Waever, 1995). As a new analytical framework, the theory has been used in many ways, but mainly to describe the process of securitization. This paper applies it to explain that certain measures (violations of the right to freedom of association of ethnic Macedonians in Greece) are consequences of agreeing that something is a threat (Macedonian minority), and, on that grounds, tries to understand how the securitization process works regarding this issue.

To support the thesis that the rights of ethnic Macedonians in Greece are being securitized, the paper applies qualitative content analysis of the three judgments of the European Court of Human Rights against Greece, finding a violation of the rights of Macedonians. It analyses the judgments of the European Court of Human Rights available in the list of all judgments delivered by a Grand Chamber or Chamber, all advisory opinions and any related decisions as well as all decisions in key cases (Case-law references of judgments, advisory opinions and key case decisions) as updated until 25 November 2022).⁸ In other words, it analyses the following judgments: Sidiropoulos and Others v. Greece, from 1998; Ouranio Toxo and Others v. Greece, from 2005; and House of Macedonian Civilisation v. Greece, from 2015. The paper analyses these documents through the lenses of securitization theory.

Part I of the paper gives a short overview of the main concepts in the securitization theory. Using these concepts Part II of the paper provides arguments that the right to freedom of association of ethnic Macedonians in Greece is being securitized. The most salient findings of the paper, which contribute to securitization theory, are summarized in the conclusions.

2. SHORT ACCOUNT OF SECURITIZATION THEORY

Securitization theory⁹ is “conceptual framework explaining the process through which certain issues come to be perceived and treated as security threats” (Baele & Thomson, 2022, p. 174) to a designated referent object and “subsequently treated as an urgent matter to be dealt with outside normal political parameters” (Baele & Thomson, 2022, p. 184). Besides providing a constructivist operational method (Buzan et al. 1998; Nyman, 2013) “for understanding who can securitize what and under what conditions” (Buzan et al. 1998, p. vii), it embraced a wider security agenda (open to different types of threats) – introduced five security sectors (military, political, economic, environmental and societal) and thus “allowed recognition of new referent objects of security beyond the state” (Nyman, 2013, p. 56), such as nation and global market.

Securitization theory originates from the University of Copenhagen, and it’s been known as the Copenhagen school of security studies. However, its roots can be traced back to sociological constructivist theories inspired by the book “*The Social Construction of Reality: A Treatise in the Sociology of Knowledge*” (Berger & Luckmann, 1966). Also, as it uses the terminology characteristic of interactionist approach (such as actors, public etc.), the securitization theory is said to have drawn its roots from interactionist theory in sociology as well, in specific, from the so called dramaturgical interactionist approach in

⁸. Downloaded from the official web site of the Council of Europe

⁹ For the main concepts of securitization theory see also: Milenkovska & Gerasimoski, 2024.

the sociological theory developed by Irwin Goffman (Goffman, 1956; Тамева, 1999: 388-394). Later on, on the foundations of sociological constructivist approach in sociology, a group of social and cultural constructivist theories within the risk theories developed, which argue that the security risk is a result of social and cultural construction (Douglas, 1992; Douglas & Wildavsky, 1982). According to this group of risk theories the word construction has the meaning of creation, more precisely socio-cultural creation, creation through socio-cultural relations, not of invention. By the same token, any social and cultural issue can be constructed as security issue under certain circumstances. If the participants in a socio-cultural relation view, perceive and assess an issue as a security issue for them, it can be considered a security issue, such as threat or risk, justifying any further action of dealing with it. Unlike the socio-cultural sphere, which does this informally, securitization theory does the same formally, i.e., in the sphere of security policy.

According to the founders of securitization theory, Barry Buzan, Jaap de Wilde and Ole Weaver, (explained in their book “Security: A New Framework for Analysis”), “the exact definition and criteria of securitization is constituted by the intersubjective establishment of an existential threat with a saliency sufficient to have substantial political effects” (Buzan et al. 1998, p. 25). We have a case of securitization “when a securitizing actor uses a rhetoric of existential threat and thereby takes an issue out of what under those conditions is “normal politics” (Buzan et al. 1998, p.24–25). By shifting an issue from the political to the security realm through intersubjective process, the actor (e.g. government) claims a right to take extraordinary measures (e.g. to place limitation on inviolable rights). It does not necessarily mean that a threat objectively exists. The issue is presented as security issue justifying action beyond normal politics through speech act. The Copenhagen school focuses on speech act, but securitization theory has broadened since its first formulation at the University of Copenhagen, “integrating linguistic processes beyond speech acts as well as non-linguistic factors (such as images and practices) and emotional dynamics” (Baele & Thomson, 2022, p. 179). In any case securitization depends on audience assent (acceptance). If the audience does not accept that something is a threat one cannot talk of successful securitization (of securitized issue), but only of securitizing move, that is of presenting an issue as an existential threat to designated referent object (Buzan et al. 1998; Balzacq and al. 2016; Stepka, 2022). Due to the fact that securitization is intersubjective, it’s much easier to securitize an issue than to desecuritize it. The process of construction or deconstruction of security issues consist of subjective and objective aspects, with the subjective aspect dominating at the beginning, while objective aspect arising as the securitization process develops. In fact, the securitization process becomes objectified thanks to intersubjectivity.

The analysis provided below does not discuss the process of construction or deconstruction of security issues, but, rather, it contributes to the literature on securitization theory by applying the theory to explain that certain measures (human rights violations) are consequences of agreeing that something is a threat. It explains that the rights of ethnic Macedonians in Greece are being securitized using the original conceptual apparatus of the securitization theory: the securitization actor (in this case, the Greek state (authorities)), existential threat (in our case, Macedonian national minority living in Greece), referent object of threat (in this case, state as object of threat and national identity as object of threat) and undertaken extraordinary measures (in this specific case, restriction of freedom of association).

3. SECURITIZATION OF THE RIGHT TO FREEDOM OF ASSOCIATION: THE CASE OF THE MACEDONIAN MINORITY IN GREECE

The analysis of the judgments of the European Court of Human Rights against Greece finding a violation of the right to freedom of association of persons belonging to the Macedonian minority in the country (*Sidiropoulos and Others v. Greece, 1998; Ouranio Toxo and Others v. Greece, 2005; and House of Macedonian Civilisation v. Greece, 2015*) shows that the modern Greek state finds it adequate and justifiable to securitize the basic human rights of the Macedonian minority living mainly in their northern part. Acting as securitizing actor from the viewpoint of a typical nation-state, it perceives and treats the issue of the basic human rights of the Macedonian minority as a political and security one, and, on that grounds, justifies the implementation of extraordinary security, legal and political measures to what it deems to be a security risk, threat or danger to their values. The ECtHR's judgments clearly support the position that Greece is trying to base and justify their measures against the associations of ethnic Macedonians by referring to the alleged threat, or risk, to their national and cultural integrity, security and public order, thus, in fact securitizing the threat or risk, more precisely. It is important to note that most of the mentions that prove the securitization thesis found in these three judgments were direct, detailed, explicit and unambiguous and they contributed towards the verification of the securitization thesis.

The judgment of the ECHR *Ouranio Toxo and Others v. Greece* case from 2005, represents a peculiar example of violation of human rights of Macedonians living in Greece, in terms of violation of the right of their freedom of association. Ouranio Toxo, which means Rainbow in English and Vinožito in Macedonian, is the name of the only political party of the persons belonging to the Macedonian minority in Greece. The detailed qualitative content analysis of the ECHR *Ouranio Toxo and Others v. Greece* case from 2005, has shown clear securitization of the right of freedom of association of Macedonian minority, which was done by Greek state and Greek authorities in general, as securitization actor. We'll mention only one out of six instances within this ECHR judgment, which clearly and indisputably confirm the securitization of Macedonian minority human right to freedom of association.

An excerpt from the ECHR *Ouranio Toxo and Others v. Greece* case from 2005, states that "in the present case, the Court notes that the Ouranio Toxo party is a legally established party, one of whose aims is the defence of the Macedonian minority living in Greece. The placing of a sign on the front of the headquarters with the party's name written in Macedonian cannot be considered as condemnatory or as constituting in itself a present and imminent threat to public order. The Court accepts that the use of the term Vinožito certainly aroused hostile feelings among the local population. Its ambiguous connotations could offend the political or patriotic views of the majority of the population of Florina [the Macedonian form Lerin]. However, the risk of provoking tensions in the community by the use of political terms in public is not sufficient, in itself, to justify an interference with freedom of association" (*Ouranio Toxo and Others v. Greece, para. 41*). This clearly indicates that Greek state securitizes the right to freedom of association of Macedonians. Moreover, it actually securitizes not only the alleged and perceived threat, but, which is more interesting, it securitizes the risk. And while the reference to threat points out to some imminent danger, the reference to risk aims to indicate that, according to the Greek authorities, even when there is no real danger in the form of a threat, there is still a risk as a possibility that in a longer process it could become a threat to the values of the Greek state (in this case, public order).

The analysis of the other two cases under discussion in this paper, which concern the refusal of the Greek authorities to register a non-profit making association (House of Macedonian Civilization) asserting the Macedonian national consciousness, also supports the position that the Greek authorities treat the associations of persons belonging to the Macedonian minority living in Greece as a security issue. The aims of the association were: “(a) the cultural, intellectual and artistic development of its members and of the inhabitants of Florina in general and the fostering of a spirit of cooperation, solidarity and love between them; (b) cultural decentralisation and the preservation of intellectual and artistic endeavours and traditions and of the civilisation’s monuments and, more generally, the promotion and development of [their] folk culture; and (c) the protection of the region’s natural and cultural environment” (*Sidiropoulos and Others v. Greece, para.8.*) Although such aims were assessed by the ECtHR as perfectly clear and legitimate, it has not been registered yet.

As the Court’s judgment in the case *Sidiropoulos and Others v. Greece* (which concerns the initial rejection of the application for registration) reveals the national authorities in order to justify the interference with the right to freedom of association referred to “the maintenance of national security, the prevention of disorder and the upholding of Greece’s cultural traditions and historical and cultural symbols” (*Sidiropoulos and Others v. Greece, para.37.*) The Government defended the position of the domestic courts that the name of the organisation could cause confusion in the country and they had “good reasons ... to believe that the purpose of using the term ‘Macedonian’ [was] to dispute the Greek identity of Macedonia and its inhabitants by indirect and therefore underhand means, and discern[ed] in it an intention on the part of the founders to undermine Greece’s territorial integrity (*Sidiropoulos and Others v. Greece , para. 44.*) However, the ECtHR did not accept that the association represents a danger to Greek identity and Greece’s territorial integrity. According to the Court “the inhabitants of a region in a country are entitled to form associations in order to promote the region’s special characteristics, for historical as well as economic reasons” (*Sidiropoulos and Others v. Greece, para.44.*) And, as it explained “even supposing that the founders of an association like the one in the instant case assert a minority consciousness, the Document of the Copenhagen Meeting of the Conference on the Human Dimension of the CSCE (Section IV) of 29 June 1990 and the Charter of Paris for a New Europe of 21 November 1990 – which Greece has signed – allow them to form associations to protect their cultural and spiritual heritage” (*Sidiropoulos and Others v. Greece, para.44.*)

The ECtHR reiterated the same position in the case of *House of Macedonian Civilization v Greece*, emphasizing that the refusal to register the applicants’ association – “on the basis of more or less the same line of reasoning as that adopted by them in the *Sidiropoulos and Others* case” (*House of Macedonian Civilization v Greece, para. 38*) – was disproportionate to the objectives pursued (public safety and protection of public order). The Greek authorities again failed to convince the Court that the use of the term Macedonian – which according to the domestic courts in its historical sense was part of Greek civilization because “there was no Macedonian civilization or language” (*House of Macedonian Civilization v Greece, para. 38*) – in the name of the association could cause confusion within the country regarding the identity of the association and disturb the public order” (*House of Macedonian Civilization v Greece, para. 38*) .

The measures taken by the Greek authorities against the association asserting the Macedonian national consciousness named House of Macedonian Civilization (like the measures against the political party Rainbow (Vinožito)) did not pass the test of the

European Court of Human Rights of being necessary in a democratic society, so one can consider them as extraordinary, and argue that by interfering with the right to freedom of association in a manner which amounts to human rights violations, Greece breaks the normal political rules of the game within the meaning explained by the founders of the securitization theory (see Buzan et al. 1998).

As the analysis of the judgment of the European Court of Human Rights provided above shows the Greek authorities claimed a need for the interventions against the associations by referring to the alleged existential threat to certain referent object (Greek state and national identity (nation)) coming from them. The Greek state constructs the human rights as security issue, thereby trying to justify the usage of extraordinary political, legal and security measures against the members of Macedonian national minority in Greece. It takes out the issue of human rights, which normally belongs in the societal and cultural sphere, and constructs it as a security one. It is evident that the Greek authorities securitize not only what they consider to be real threat, but, moreover, they securitize the risk, the potentiality of future threat or endangerment. At the same time, this is the argument advanced in the ECtHR's judgments, which criticize Greece for violation and not respecting the right to freedom of association of Macedonian national minority, for, according to the law, no legal authority can restrict or deny any human right on the basis of assumed risk or threat, but only on their actual deeds undertaken in reality and in present time. Risk and threat are mere security assumptions and if not sustained by real acts of undermining or threatening the core values of state or society, cannot be considered as sufficient, justifiable and necessary reasons for securitization.

4. CONCLUSION

The paper puts forward that the rights of persons belonging to the Macedonian minority in Greece are being securitized, by referring to data collected within the research project "Macedonian minority in Greece and Bulgaria and Council of Europe" designed at the Faculty of Security – Skopje. More precisely, it referred to the judgments of the European Court of Human Rights against Greece collected within the research. The paper provided sound arguments that Greek authorities perceive and treat the Macedonian minority as source of threat to different referent objects (state and national identity) by analysing the judgments through the lens of securitization theory. The analysis showed that interventions against the associations asserting the Macedonian national consciousness in Greece (which did not pass the ECtHR's test of being necessary in a democratic society) are taken (as extraordinary measures) by the authorities (securitizing actor) in response to the alleged existential threat to state and/or nation (referent objects) coming from them. Greece takes out the issue of human rights, which normally belongs in societal and cultural sphere, and constructs it as a security one. Moreover, based on the analysis provided in this paper, one may argue that Greece securitizes not only what it considers to be real threat, but, also the risk, the potentiality of future threat or endangerment. This thesis deserves to be thoroughly and extensively researched and elaborated in the future.

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THE CONSTITUTIONAL-LEGAL APPROACH TO CLIMATE SECURITY: EVOLUTION FROM UNKNOWN TO EXISTENTIAL ISSUE

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Abstract

Natural conditions have always determined human existence. Climate, as some authors suggest, will lead warmer regions towards democracy while peoples from colder regions will be determined towards more autocratic rule. However, the most serious problem arises when natural disasters and climate crises make life impossible and devalue it, whether it is more democratic or autocratic. Droughts and floods lead to food and water shortages and new conflicts. The most vulnerable categories of society suffer the greatest consequences, which leads to instability and new migrations. This results in a large number of communities struggling to survive. Dealing with the consequences of climate change and disasters known under the term climate security raises the issue of the constitutional approach to it, which, appreciating the maxim *lex prospicit, non respicit*, must provide an up-to-date answer and set new guidelines in the legal and security order. The transition of this issue from a purely ecological to an existential issue elevates it to the position of a constitutional and security matter. Failure to recognize this concept will not only violate the rights and freedoms of current generations, but will also deprive future, unborn generations of the right to live in a safe and dignified environment. The constitutional and legal history of climate security brings an evolution that leads to clear legal recognition, emphasizing nevertheless judicial activism as crucial in bureaucratized systems.

Keywords: climate security, constitutional law, environmental law, climate change, constitutionalization

1. INTRODUCTION

When the environment experiences alarming and tectonic disturbances faced with unstoppable degrading processes, humanity has an obligation to stop the spiral of collapse, because otherwise – any life without conditions is a mere illusion. The data are more than worrying: the Amazon rainforest has already lost over 17% of its surface in the last 50 years, and over 50% of the world's coral reefs are dead or irreversibly damaged. Glaciers lose more than 600 billion tons of ice per year. The decline in pollinators directly threatens about 75% of agricultural production.

In the eyes of the insufficiently informed public, climate change seems like a phenomenon that is distant, that affects distant countries, that is not directly responsible for the emergence of emergencies, forced migrations and that does not pose a direct threat to any segment of human life. The reality is different (Simić, 2019, p. 41).

Climate change and disasters are no longer exclusively an ecological issue, but represent an existential challenge for the survival of society. What was previously unknown, in the 21st century is growing into a dominant and central issue of law and security. Climate security combines the concepts of environment and climate change, placing them in relation to human and global security, which raises the question of how constitutional systems respond to these threats? In a constellation of relations dominated by conflicts and migrations, security is violated, constitutional law is faced with the challenge of how to accept the concept of *salus publica suprema lex esto*¹⁰ – according to which the public good is the supreme law.

With the growth of European colonialism, the theory dedicated to climatic determinism¹¹ will serve as a "fig leaf"¹² to justify racism, eugenic policies and imperialism. From the 19th¹³ to the 20th century we record the greatest abuses of the climate, which through scientific racism and pseudoscience will legitimize colonial campaigns and slavery. In the last century Hitler, inspired by Haushofer's concept of Lebensraum – a natural right to expansion, will introduce the world to new wars and genocides. It is precisely this epilogue that will lead to a strong criticism of this type of determinism, which in the 21st century brings a new form of climate security. In contemporary concepts, we have a reconnection of man and nature (climate), but not as a justification or abuse, but in the direction of responsibility and an ethical approach. The transition from "climate that creates man" to "man who creates climate unsafe conditions" is already being noticed.

Climate security denotes the degree of systemic and institutional resilience of the order in conditions of climate instability. It represents a continuity in which the state is able to preserve its constitutional identity and social development, despite the escalation of climate risks that disrupt the natural and economic balance. Climate security is a new, modern social contract of the state and citizens with nature, in which a legal system is created as a resilient mechanism, and of course accompanied by a redefinition of relations in society.

The constitutionalization of climate security in the 21st century, which represents a new stage in constitutional evolution, through the transition from a political declaration to a constitutional guarantee, recognizes climate as the foundation of human dignity and the constitutional-legal system. The European continent is leading the process of

¹⁰ A Latin phrase originally used by Cicero, in order to emphasize that the interest of the state and the public should stand above personal or party interests.

¹¹ Geographical or ecological determinism is a theory according to which the natural environment, i.e. climate, geography, relief and resources, influence the development of society, culture and even the character of people. Ecological determinism shows a strong connection between nature and man, something that is again being actualized in this concept.

¹² The phrase "fig leaf" figuratively refers to something that conceals shame or guilt, a symbol for false concealment. As an expression, it comes from the Bible, specifically from the Book of Genesis 3:7, according to which "Then the eyes of both of them were opened, and they knew that they were naked; and they sewed fig leaves together and made themselves aprons". In Renaissance art, the leaf was often used to censor nudity. It is known that fig leaves were later added to some of Michelangelo's sculptures to depict modesty.

¹³ In the USA we have the concept of Manifest Destiny which claimed that they have a natural and divine right to expand their territory "from sea to sea".

constitutionalization, and European constitutional courts often compensate for the passivity of the legislative and executive branches.

This paper, through a comparative legal analysis, presents the evolutionary path of climate security, which from an unknown and ecological issue to an existential issue becomes a constitutional matter.

2. HISTORICAL AND THEORETICAL CONTEXT

2.1 Climate and security throughout history

The historical understanding of climate has evolved through different stages. The flood that we encounter in the “Epic of Gilgamesh” and later in the biblical story of Noah’s Ark represents the first climatic catastrophe that serves as a punishment for human corruption and immorality that disrupted the balance of nature and the gods.

Later, in the Code of Hammurabi, we already note the first provisions on irrigation systems, floods and droughts. In the provisions, we notice the first legal text that treats natural disasters as a legal consequence.

Hippocrates, the author after whom the most famous medical oath is named, in the work “Airs, Waters, and Places” first connects climate with the character and health of nations. Security in this context refers to the physical survival of the community. Aristotle, through his works “Politics” and “Meteorology”, connects climatic conditions with political order. According to him, climate affects the form of government and social morality.

In the Roman period, the concept of *res communes omnium* develops, which refers to the common goods of all (water, air, sea). Nature here becomes a legal category.

In the Middle Ages, natural disasters and climate change are considered divine punishment. Security in this time interval is perceived from a religious and moral aspect. Thomas Aquinas builds on Aristotle's work and Roman law, but introduces a Christian theological character. According to him, the law arises from the eternal law of God, and man must preserve that order, which also includes nature.

In the period of enlightenment, in the authors Montesquieu and Rousseau, we note the connection of climate with questions of moral balance and social stability, derived through the prism of the new political and legal orders of that time.

The period of the Industrial Revolution saw climate as a means of economic and imperial power. Industrial expansion led to enormous pollution, disease, and resource instability. After the mass pollutions in London, Manchester, and Paris, the process of passing laws that accepted the idea of state responsibility for nature was evident. The Public Health Act (1848, Great Britain) and the Forest Service (1905, USA) are examples of such anticipation. This period will also be known for the fact that many authors, including Thomas Jefferson, used environmental determinism to support and legitimize African colonization, arguing that tropical climates made people uncivilized.

In World War II, nature was slowly but surely brought into the realm of global security, in response to major environmental disasters and nuclear threats. The second half of the 20th century is particularly significant, as we see a growing number of international documents that enable the later acceptance of climate security (which will ultimately lead

to its constitutionalization¹⁴). Perhaps the most revolutionary impact will be achieved by the Stockholm Declaration of 1972, which will be reaffirmed and strengthened by the Rio de Janeiro Declaration of 1992. In 1987, the Brundtland Report will introduce the concept of sustainable development.

The 21st century, from its very beginning, heralds a kind of "golden age" for climate security. In 2007, the UN Security Council discussed climate as a security threat for the first time. The 2015 Paris Agreement, on the other hand, recognizes that climate change is a threat to human rights and global security. These key events will quickly multiply the new notion of security, and international organizations such as UNDP and IPCC will warn that climate crises lead to new conflicts, migrations and political instability. Climate is becoming an existential threat.

One of the most serious threats to humanity today and the leading security challenge in the world is climate change caused by global warming (Udovčić, 2024, p. 1).

2.2 The international character of climate security and its dependence on international law

One of the main characteristics of climate security is its international character, as well as its direct dependence on the development of international law. This concept is an example of a "top-down" concept, which is first developed internationally, and then these provisions are transposed into domestic legal systems.

Hugo Grotius' idea of *ius gentium* (law of nations) and *res communis* (common goods) creates a notion of global order, which has as a consequence the subsequent regulation of global resources and the environment. Although he does not mention climate and climate security directly, the principles he sets out will form the intellectual and legal basis for the concept of climate security. Grotius' elaborated principle "*sic utere tuo ut alienum non laedas*" which translates to "use your own so that you do not harm others", refers to the prohibition of causing harm to other states or common global goods, and was formalized as principle 21 of the 1972 Stockholm Declaration (also confirmed in the 1992 Rio Declaration).

We see the principle of common but differentiated responsibility in the 2015 Paris Agreement, which follows the logic of *res communis omnium*. This type of security today is not only a matter of protecting nature and the climate, but also of peace and global order, which is the essential message of Grotius' work "*De Jure Belli ac Pacis*" (1625).

In 1987, in the Brundtland Commission Report, we have the introduction of the concept of sustainable development, which connects the environment and global stability. This was followed by the 1992 UN Climate Change Convention, which was the first global framework for reducing greenhouse gas emissions. Of course, the 1997 Kyoto Protocol, which introduced legally binding targets for industrialized countries, is also important in this context.

The UN Security Council, for the first time in 2007, considered climate change as a potential threat to peace and security. Climate change and its risks were directly linked to

¹⁴ Constitutionalization is a process in which certain rights, norms, principles, values, or areas are elevated to the level of constitutional matter, giving them the highest degree of state and social protection. The term constitutionalism was coined in 1832 by the English poet R. Southey; along with English legal writers, O. Gierke is particularly responsible for its acceptance as a professional term. More: <https://www.enciklopedija.hr/clanak/konstitucionalizam>

food shortages¹⁵, which lead to migration and conflict, as well as to natural disasters, which lead to humanitarian crises and new instability.

The 2015 Paris Agreement set a goal of limiting global warming to well below 2°C above pre-industrial levels, with efforts to limit it to 1.5°C. The agreement aims to reduce the risks and consequences of climate change, which include climate disasters, migration, conflict and food and water shortages. The agreement recognizes climate change as a threat to peace and stability. The agreement also accepts that the countries that have historically contributed the most to climate change bear the greatest responsibility, while advocating solidarity with smaller and less developed countries, which are disproportionately affected by this threat.

2.2.1 European Union

In 2008, the EU, in the Climate and Energy Package, acknowledged that climate change affects security. Later, in 2013, the European Security Strategy (ESS) Update first mentioned climate change as a factor in global instability and a risk to peace. The 2016 EU Global Strategy (EUGS), for example, stated that climate change is a threat to security, while also creating new migration and conflicts. A particular step forward was noted in 2019 with the European Green Deal (a policy of climate neutrality by 2050 was introduced) and the EU Climate Diplomacy Action Plan of 2020, which integrated climate security into EU foreign policy, especially in the area of stabilization for Africa and the Middle East.

However, given the common goals and threats posed by climate change, cooperation between the EU and the USA remains crucial for global climate security¹⁶.

2.2.2 NATO

With regard to NATO, in 2009 we have the first official document linking climate to security. The following year, the Strategic Concept 2010 already acknowledged that climate change could cause instability in geopolitical frameworks and affect operations. Perhaps the most explicit recognition of climate security and its consequences is in the NATO Climate Change and Security Action Plan from 2021, which presents a concrete strategy for adapting bases, preparing for extreme weather conditions and integrating climate risks into mission planning.

2.3 Theoretical considerations on climate security

¹⁵ The World Food Programme (WFP) has made a worrying assessment that more than 80% of the world's food-insecure population live in countries with degraded environments prone to natural disasters. When climate-related events occur, the situation of already vulnerable people can quickly deteriorate, leading to famine. The problems of acute food insecurity and malnutrition are exacerbated where natural hazards such as droughts and floods are compounded by the effects of conflict. An example of such a situation is the Horn of Africa, where the rainy season failed for the first time in 2016. See Milosavljević (2019) for more details.

¹⁶ Is an international climate regime possible? Based on the research on realpolitik relations between states in the period between the Rio summits of 1992 and 2012, it seems that it is not. However, the essence of the problem is not mistrust between states or pragmatic exploitation of the situation for their own benefit (in which China is at the forefront), but the fact that economic development and the world market as such are the negation of climate awareness. For further discussion, see Popović (2014).

After the 1990s, we have seen a significant expansion of the concept of security. Especially after the Cold War, securitization has also encompassed new threats, which also incorporate the moment of nature and climate. The Copenhagen School has proven to be crucial, introducing the idea that climate and migration can be recognized as security threats.

In 1994, the UNDP introduced the framework for "human security", and as an integral part it includes ecological and climate stability.

The traditional (realist) approach to climate change sees it as a "threat multiplier". According to Thomas Homer-Dixon, known for his work "Environment, Scarcity and Violence" (1999), the lack of resources leads to conflicts.

Representatives of the liberal-institutional approach, such as Oran R. Young (author of "The Institutional Dimensions of Environmental Change: Fit, Interplay, and Scale"), emphasize the role of international institutions in dealing with climate risks and the need for global coordination.

Brauch and Hans Günter, as representatives of the human, social approach to climate security, cite climate as a human security issue.

3. CONCEPT AND FUNCTION OF CLIMATE SECURITY

Climate security is a new, interdisciplinary concept that connects the security, legal, political and economic dimensions of climate change. It is a state of protection of society, the state and nature from the risks and consequences of climate change (in order to preserve stability, health and international peace).

Problems with droughts, lack of food and water, floods, migrations and conflicts over resources, lead to a strong introduction of climate risks into national security strategies, because they are accepted as a threat to national and international security.

On the international level, this type of security is already integrated into international agreements, and is already widely accepted within the framework of the UN, the Security Council, the EU, NATO and others.

In terms of the legal function, climate security has the task of offering judicial protection and climate obligations (followed, of course, by its gradual constitutionalization). In terms of its function towards society, this type of security is aimed at human and social stability, and its function is to ensure climate justice¹⁷.

Especially after the major environmental disasters of the last century and after World War II, the need to include the environment in security is undeniable. The Cold War period requires an approach to security with a more rational and realpolitik approach, which would include elements that are not just part of the traditional understanding. The concept of environmental security was particularly developed in the 1960s and was accepted under that name 20 years later (Koprivnjak & Vidaček, 2024, p.162).

4. CONSTITUTIONAL-LEGAL DIMENSION OF CLIMATE SECURITY

4.1 Constitutional law as a traditional discipline

¹⁷ The term climate justice began to be used in the late 1980s, then within the framework of the environmental justice movement in the United States. It was first used by activists of African Americans and indigenous communities, who pointed out that environmental risks (especially waste and pollution) are concentrated in wider areas. Theoretical formulations for this term can be seen around 2002 by Mary Robinson, former president of Ireland.

Constitutional law has long been the subject of the odium of a conservative, traditional discipline that specifically accepts changes around it. Such a remark is quite justified, considering that initially and theoretically it defends and develops classical political rights, the subject of which is power and limitations.

Especially on the example of Great Britain we can see more of a classical conservative constitutional tradition, which does not know a constitution in written form, as a systematized act, but is a collection of several acts, judicial precedents and constitutional conventions and customs. In this way, the stability of the order is valued (which is both the basic function and task of constitutional law), and changes come along an evolutionary path, not through radical upheavals.

If the basic function of constitutional law is to maintain order, stability and security, then it must undoubtedly include the latest risks to life and well-being. It is in this field that the role of security is also seen, which together with constitutional law functions according to the principle of a coin with two sides.

As a counterweight to the popular originalism theory¹⁸ (according to which the constitution is strictly interpreted according to the will of the first framers of the constitution) the theory of the Constitution as a Living Constitution¹⁹, i.e. as *materia viva*²⁰, according to which it lives and develops with society.

4.2 Judicial Activism

Judicial activism as a legal doctrine and practice refers to judges who actively intervene in social and moral issues through their actions. The term was first used by Arthur Schlesinger Jr. in 1947, who used it to describe the US Supreme Court during the so-called Warren Court (1953–1969), whose composition actively protected human and civil rights. Under the leadership of Earl Warren, the court made a series of historic decisions. In the case of *Brown v. Board of Education* (1954), the principle of "separate but equal" was overturned and racial segregation in public schools was prohibited (which violated the 14th Amendment, which concerns equal protection under the law).

Furthermore, in 1961, under the leadership of Warren, in the case of *Mapp v. Ohio*, the Supreme Court decided that evidence obtained from an illegal search may not be used in court. In 1966, the Supreme Court, through its ruling in the case of *Miranda v. Arizona*, introduced the famous "Miranda rights" that refer to the obligation of the police to inform the accused of his rights upon arrest.

In this way, with its engagement (or rather activism²¹), the court has redefined American democracy, in a way that introduces new standards for freedom, equality and human rights.

¹⁸ Originalism is a legal theory according to which the constitution should be interpreted according to its original meaning or intention at the time of adoption. The main advocates in history are several American Supreme Court justices. The focus is on the text and historical context.

¹⁹ Contrary to the theory of the originalists, the theory of the Living Constitution is developing in the USA. Similar to the European version, the constitution as *materia viva*.

²⁰ The theory according to which the Constitution is *materia viva*, as a metaphor for the living, dynamic character of the constitution. The interpretation of the constitution is carried out according to contemporary needs and values. It originates from European soil, especially France and Italy. It is a counterbalance to traditional positivist constitutional law (following the example of Kelsen).

²¹ More in Ceranić (2010).

The theory of living constitutionality, accompanied by judicial activism as its emanation, creates a modern constitutional practice in which the constitution is not changed only through amendments, but constitutional courts, through extensive and dynamic interpretation, play an active role in the protection of freedoms and rights. They create an evolutionary and dynamic system from a static, traditional and conservative discipline of constitutional law. However, constitutional law has its own ability to independently complement and upgrade itself.

4.3 Climate trials before constitutional and supreme courts

Although the Netherlands does not have a constitutional court in the classical sense (as established in 1920, with the first Kelsen²² court in Austria²³), the judgment in the case *Urgenda v. Netherlands* (2019) shows how the Supreme Court protects constitutional principles even without having a formal constitutional status. This is a case in which the Urgenda Foundation sued the Dutch state for failure to fulfil its obligation to reduce greenhouse gas emissions. The Supreme Court, as the highest court, has ordered the state to reduce emissions by at least 25% by 2020 compared to 1990. This is actually the first case where a supreme court has ordered a state to take specific climate action, thereby indirectly exercising a constitutional function and setting an important legal precedent in terms of climate protection.

In the case *Neubauer v. Germany*, the German Federal Constitutional Court ruled on 24 March 2021 that part of the Federal Climate Protection Act (*Klimaschutzgesetz*) is unconstitutional because it “does not sufficiently protect people from future violations and restrictions of their freedoms as climate change intensifies”. The plaintiffs, including Laura Neubauer, have argued that the law’s goal of reducing greenhouse gas emissions by 55% by 2030 compared to 1990 is insufficient and does not protect their fundamental rights, such as the right to life²⁴, health and liberty. By ruling, the court recognizes climate rights, thereby accepting climate protection as part of fundamental rights (which also include the right to life and health). The court has emphasized the state’s obligation to protect the fundamental rights of future generations. In doing so, the court imposes an obligation to revise the legislation in order to ensure that emissions are as low as possible.

5. CONSTITUTIONALIZATION OF CLIMATE SECURITY

5.1 From unknown, through ecological, to existential issue

Until the middle of the last century, climate and climate change were practically unknown to the mainstream course in security sciences. Nature is a resource, and is perceived as such, but not as a factor that influences the types of security.

After the 1970s of the 21st century, when the process of constitutional acceptance of provisions on environmental law began, climate change began to be treated as an environmental issue and threat. The period from the 1980s to around 2000 can be spoken of as a kind of pre-period of green constitutionalism (considering that we already have acceptance of principles such as sustainable development, etc.).

Green constitutionalism, as a hybrid model between human rights, state obligations and environmental protection, is becoming a serious tendency in constitutional

²² More in Marković (2023).

²³ More in Kijevčanin (2022).

²⁴ More in Orlović (2014).

law in the 21st century. Climate security is an integral part of it, because otherwise this type of security cannot function in isolation. As stated in Vidacek and Ristovska (2025), green constitutionalism brings a much more mature and modern perspective – ecocentric, which elevates ecological sustainability above human needs.

5.2 Direct constitutionalization

With Amendment 20A to the German Basic Law (Grundgesetz), “the state, also in its responsibility towards future generations, shall protect the natural foundations of life and animals within the framework of the constitutional order, through legislation and, in accordance with law and justice, through the executive and judicial branches.” With this, since 1993, environmental protection has been directly rooted in German constitutional law. The court has used this as the basis for the Nuebauer v. Germany judgment from 2021.

Here we have a situation in which a right, or value, is explicitly inserted into the constitutional text (by means of new articles, amendments or a separate chapter, depending on the constitutional legal system and nomotechnics).

In terms of the strict mention of the term climate security, one should mention the case of France, 2021²⁵, when the request "to combat climate change" was proposed, but not fully adopted. Such possible acceptance would mean direct, explicit recognition of climate change in the Constitution. In the absence of such constitutionalization, one moves on to other forms of constitutionalization.

5.3 Indirect and judicial constitutionalization

When constitutional or supreme courts (with constitutional jurisdiction) interpret constitutional norms and through their actions create new constitutional law or expand the content of the existing one, it is judicial constitutionalization, which in turn is part of the broader concept of indirect constitutionalization.

This can be concluded that not every indirect constitutionalization is judicial. Following the example of Germany, there the constitutional doctrine has long before the courts accepted that human dignity has a material constitutional character. This is a broader concept because it can encompass a broader political and scientific interpretation, which is not always related to the court.

Indirect constitutionalization in general, especially in the area of climate security, is the most common. This is a situation in which although the right or value is not explicitly stated in the constitution, it is derived from existing constitutional norms, principles or case law.

If we look back at a Norwegian case from 2020, we see that the Norwegian constitution, in Article 112, states "Natural resources shall be managed on the basis of comprehensive long-term considerations that will protect this right for future generations", which is what the Supreme Court of Sweden referred to when advocating the state's obligation to prevent climate damage (Greenpeace Norway v. Ministry of Petroleum).

5.4 Other types of constitutionalization

²⁵ Following a proposal by the Convention citoyenne pour le climat, composed of 150 citizens, an amendment to Article 1 of the French constitution was proposed, according to which "The Republic guarantees the preservation of the environment and biological diversity and combats climate change". Although the lower house accepted the proposed amendment with 391 votes "for", 47 "against", in the further procedure a common text was not agreed upon.

The content of the preamble and the fundamental values are also important for the constitutionalization process. For example, the German Grundgesetz mentions “its responsibility to God and man” in its preamble, and on several occasions also to nature, natural resources, but even more importantly to future generations. The German Federal Constitutional Court has determined in its 2021 ruling that climate protection stems from the fundamental value and the connection with the preamble.

Similarly, Italy, for example, in Article 9 as a fundamental value, in 2022 made amendments, adding that “The Republic protects the environment, biodiversity and ecosystems, also in the interest of future generations”. Following this, judicial and constitutional practice already treats climate stability as part of the common good.

5.5 Green Constitutionalism

The acceptance of climate security as a constitutional matter, from a constitutional-legal perspective, can also be designated as part of the mosaic called “green constitutionalism”. This type of constitutionalism, which arises as a response to new global and security threats (especially in the area of the environment and nature²⁶) is a classic concept of the 21st century, which puts human rights, the environment and security in relation.

To a dominant extent, green constitutionalism is a process that includes the integration of environmental rights and obligations directly into constitutions (or basic laws, as is the case with Germany), as well as a clear recognition that the environment is a fundamental constitutional right, which is linked to human freedoms and rights, health and human development.

This type of constitutionalism is a product of the evolution we are witnessing from a classic constitutionalism (with a focus on political rights, organization of the state, etc.), towards a 21st century constitutionalism that recognizes nature and the environment as constitutional categories and protects them.

Green constitutionalism finds its practical application in Latin America, with the introduction of constitutional provisions in the constitutions of Ecuador (2008) and Bolivia (2009). The Ecuadorian constitution is the first to recognize the rights of nature (*derechos de la naturaleza*), while the Bolivian constitution constitutionalizes the term “Pachamama” (“Mother Earth”) as a living being. The United States and Europe are considered the theoretical cradles of this type of constitutionalism. (Marko Vidaček & Marika Ristovska, 2025, p.97)

²⁶ Although not to that extent, Yugoslavia also experienced some massive environmental damage and catastrophe, especially after the Second World War. In the fifties of the last century, massive pollution of the Vardar River was noticeable, as a result of industrial waste and mines in that area. Later, certain problems will arise with mining in the area of Kosovo and Metohija, where especially coal mines have caused great environmental pollution. The 1970s were also remembered for the pollution of the Danube, which, as one of the largest rivers in Europe, was exposed to a great deal of industrial pollution. This decade and the next (the 80's) also marked the spill of oil in the Adriatic Sea, which has especially actualized the question of protection and strengthening of the marine and coastal ecosystem. For more on the Constitution of the SFRY and the right to a healthy environment from 1974, see Ristovska, Akimovska Maletić and Vidaček (2025).

6. CLIMATE SECURITY CHALLENGES

6.1 Emergence of ecological populism

With the rise of green parties and globalization after 1980, the emergence of ecological, green populism²⁷ is noticeable, which is an approach in which ecology, the environment and climate change are used as a means of mobilizing the masses. Through simple, emotional and "catchy" messages, the government or certain institutions are accused of destroying nature.

This does not necessarily mean a negative phenomenon. The positive side is in the expression of dissatisfaction with anti-environmental and climate change policies, while the negative aspect is in the strengthening of demagoguery, the anti-scientific narrative.

6.2 Instrumentalization of climate security in politics

Just as Sophocles' "Antigone"²⁸ has two choices regarding her brother's death, so too, the issues of climate change, security and justice are unfortunately often posed antagonistically, as irreconcilable opposites. A dominant bloc division is created in the public sphere between pro and anti climate change advocates (and the concepts that come with them), which leads to even greater polarization in society.

Environmental and climate change issues are becoming issues for political debate, with the focus, unfortunately, shifting from the scientific field to social networks.

Climate change has been one of the most controversial topics on a global level for years. Although there is solid evidence of its genesis, manifestation and consequences, some scientists and authors deny the view that it disrupts and negatively affects human security (Simić, 2019, p. 35).

Instrumentalized in this way in daily political discourse, the climate can be used to justify certain economic, social or geopolitical interests, and ultimately turn into blockades and military intervention. This, in turn, raises the question of its militarization.

6.3 Militarization of climate policy

When climate is increasingly accepted as a security issue (and thus constitutionally and legally), following the example of the USA and other countries, it becomes part of military strategies. Climate is becoming an unavoidable part of national security (in addition to the fact that a new concept of climate security is being formed), so it is often given a militaristic²⁹ overtone. If climate events are accepted as a legitimate and rational

²⁷ As stated in the digital dictionary of the Macedonian language, populism is "opportunistic, demagogic politics with influence on the population through an apparent inclination towards the understandings, demands and spiritual needs of the broad masses of the people". As examples of left-wing ecological populism, we can cite Evo Morales in Bolivia and Rafael Correa in Ecuador. As right-wing ecological populism, we can cite Marine Le Pen in France (speaks about the ecology of nations) and Viktor Orbán in Hungary (believes that the protection of Hungarian land from foreign investment is an environmental issue).

²⁸ Antigone in Sophocles' play has to decide whether to respect the imperial decree and leave her brother's corpse unburied (which would mean "yes" to the law, but "no" to the brother) or to decide to bury her brother. She decides to bury him, thus following her moral and religious obligations. In the play, all the main characters suffer as a result of the conflict between law and morality.

²⁹ Militarization (from the Latin *militaris*: military), strengthening of military influence or introduction of a militaristic system. Strengthening militaristic values in society. Similar to militarism: dominance of military ideas, customs and interests, i.e. management of society in

threat, then there is a possibility that such a threat can be resolved through military intervention, rather than through diplomatic or legal means.

When climate events are treated as a threat, there is a danger of military intervention instead of a diplomatic or scientific solution. In the future, a large part of geopolitical actions under the guise of “fighting climate change” may lead to new military interventions.

Therefore, it is of particular importance that a state or international organization will subsume itself under climate security. Its overemphasis, and naturalization of not so natural elements, can easily make sense of the essence of the fight against climate change and serve as an alibi for some other fights. The bad experience of the 19th and 20th centuries can serve as a parallel and an appeal for caution.

6.4 Disproportionality in the effects of climate change

The disproportionate suffering of countries and peoples is one of the greatest challenges related to climate change and climate security. The underdeveloped and most vulnerable countries (especially in Africa, Southeast Asia, Kiribati) are increasingly affected by major droughts, floods, hurricanes. Although they contribute the least to the effects of climate change, they are the most pronounced – negatively. The fact that their resources for prevention, adaptation and other processes are limited further increases their vulnerability.

Especially in terms of economic and social aspects, we have a continuation of the cycle of poverty and insecurity. Therefore, future strategies for combating climate change and accepting climate security must also accept this challenge through mechanisms of international solidarity, followed by financial and technical support for the most vulnerable countries and peoples³⁰.

7. CLIMATE SECURITY IN THE REPUBLIC OF NORTH MACEDONIA

Climate security as a concept in this country is in its infancy. Despite the serious risks from climate disasters and conditions, legal and constitutional obligations still remain incomplete and fragmented.

As for the constitutional order, the constitution does not recognize climate security or this type of threat. However, there are several articles (primarily the fundamental provisions in Article 8 and Article 43 on the environment) that can serve as a basis for the introduction of this type of security in legal practice. In particular, constitutional courts and institutions, by way of a "derivative", can use these articles in a situation of absence.

As for the legal level, the media note that the Climate Action Law has been postponed for 5 years, and it is also noted that there is no National Plan for Adaptation to Climate Change. On the Electronic National Register of Regulations of the Republic of North Macedonia (ENER), it is visible that at the end of 2022, a notice was published to begin the process of preparing a Law on Climate Action, while a version of the draft law was published on 26.01.2023. Although the version does not directly talk about climate

accordance with the values of the military mentality. More: <https://www.enciklopedija.hr/clanak/militarizam>

³⁰ Due to the rise in sea levels, a large number of national and cultural minorities may lose their centuries-old habitat. This is especially true for nations or groups like the Caribbean, the Maldives, etc. This also applies to Arctic and subarctic peoples (such as the Inuit, the Saami, the Chukchi), but also to communities around the Ganges or Nile rivers (due to the desertification process).

security, the mention of the terms risks, hazards, and disasters provides a sufficient starting point for strengthening this concept and its greater recognition.

The competent authorities should take urgent and additional measures to deal with climate change, because the country lacks a clearly defined structure, coordination and communication between the parties involved, and a National Adaptation Plan has not yet been adopted, the State Audit Office concluded in its latest report on the country's readiness to face this global challenge, reports the web portal SDK.mk (2024).

However, it is worth noting that certain moves in a positive direction are evident. For example, President Siljanovska Davkova appointed Dr. Vlado Spiridonov, a professor of meteorology and climate change expert, to the Security Council in 2024. It is also important to emphasize that the adoption of the law has the support of the President, while the Government's position is unclear. "I eagerly await the day when I will sign the decree promulgating the Climate Action Law. I believe that this law, which is long overdue, will be a milestone in our climate action", the President stated on October 30, 2024, according to Media.mk (2024)

CONCLUSION

Climate security as a part of environmental security, which focuses exclusively on the damages from climate change and the establishment of a balance, is gaining more and more space in legal and security sciences. The constitutionalization of climate security is a new constitutional challenge in the 21st century.

The paper provides a historical overview of the concept of climate security, which is also accompanied by the process of constitutionalization. Analysing the various constitutional *modus vivendi*³¹, it is concluded that indirect constitutionalization is needed as the most adequate mechanism. The absence of a clearly direct constitutionalization (through new articles or paragraphs), which is not yet known for climate security in its most explicit form, is due to its theoretical and practical incompleteness. Climate security is in a complementary relationship with many similar categories (sustainable development, rights of future generations, rights to nature), and constitutions are not always able to promptly accept such concepts, especially those in development.

The court, in line with living constitutionalism, is obliged to interpret constitutional provisions and fundamental values in relation to the (dis)circumstances around it, and thus introducing climate security into the constitutional-legal framework will enable its existence in the foreseeable future.

The paper states that ecological populism followed by the instrumentalization of climate security, its attempt at militarization and the disproportionality in the effects of climate change are the key challenges towards its future development.

In the Republic of North Macedonia, for example, the constitutional court can easily indirectly constitutionalize climate security by referring to the fundamental values in the constitution and the special article 43. What is missing, however, is greater constitutional-judicial engagement and activity in the Macedonian case. The adoption of the long-awaited Climate Action Law will greatly improve the legal regulation on this issue and will seriously introduce the concept of climate security to a higher level.

³¹ The Latin expression "modus vivendi" translates to "way of living" or "way of coexistence".

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THE ROLE OF INDEPENDENT INSTITUTIONS IN ENVIRONMENTAL PROTECTION AND THE FIGHT AGAINST ENVIRONMENTAL CRIME

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Abstract

Beyond the classical separation of powers, which is predominantly linked to the protection and promotion of human freedoms and rights, a large number of institutions that are located between or almost outside Montesquieu's idea have an obligation to act promptly, especially when it comes to the environment and the fight against environmental crime. The evolution of the legal and political order, appreciating its virtues and flaws, has also given rise to a kind of sui generis institutions whose main domain is precisely the protection of rights and freedoms and the promotion of well-being. Although today the modern state can boast of a large number of creations, which are more or less called and ready for action, the constitutional courts and the institutions of the Ombudsman stand out, which, although different, find their connective tissue in the defence of freedoms, rights, and democracy. Especially when the "classical" institutions of the state, which are placed in strong bureaucratic constraints and procedures, cannot respond to the existing crises and challenges, it is necessary for institutions that have the ability for legal interpretation and reasoning (referring to fundamental values and natural law) to react in a timely manner and, to a certain extent, pre-emptively. This paper deals with the role and significance of institutions such as the Constitutional Court and the Ombudsman in the Republic of North Macedonia in the corpus of environmental protection and its advancement. It analyses the most modern actions and modifications of the Ombudsman, who is increasingly and more boldly entering this matter, making it inherent to this position.

Keywords: independent institutions, environmental protection, constitutional court, ombudsman

1. INTRODUCTION

In modern societies, the issue of environmental protection and the fight against environmental crime has quite justifiably become a matter of public interest, human rights, and dignity. Acting outside the classical separation of powers, the constitutional court and

the ombudsman as independent institutions have the role of key actors in the processes of greater integration of environmental rights. Deprived of the strict formalism, rigidity and bureaucracy of traditional authorities (legislative, executive and judicial), they can undoubtedly offer efficient and long-term solutions that are needed by societies at a given moment, using their flexibility and autonomy.

In a historical line, the concept of independent, impartial institutions and moral justice has followed humanity since ancient city-states to the modern, globalized state. The Athenians, at the place called "*The Hill of Ares*", where the god Ares was once tried, founded the Areopagus – an independent judicial institution that should continue the tradition of justice that will this time judge both people and rulers.

Medieval examples with the Forest Charter of 1217 and the ordinances of King Louis XIV show state forms of nature protection, while, somewhat later in the period of the Renaissance and the Enlightenment, we notice a shift in focus towards man and an order that is rational, connecting nature with morality, law and the social contract.

Natural disasters and urban crises of the 19th century formed a legal basis for the concept of environmental rights, examples of the great floods in London and the fires in the USA illustrate how the protection of nature became a public interest, and not just an economic or private issue.

In the 20th century, when at times the separation of powers became outdated and almost out of place and its shortcomings became visible (especially in the protection of human freedoms and rights and issues of mutual control), we witness two processes: **the establishment of constitutional courts** and **ombudsmen**. These are, in fact, chronologically the first independent institutions for the protection of human rights that appear outside of Montesquieu's concept of the separation of powers.

These institutions in the 21st century show that they have a central role in the sphere of environmental protection and the fight against environmental crime. By combining positive law and natural law principles (which, as civilizational developments, are "transmitted" into constitutions and laws), they function as a kind of "*instruments of the conscience*" of the state. The legal and continuous protection of the environment represents a logical and completely natural extension of the already established human rights, while the constitutional courts and the ombudsman become the "*voice*" of nature in the legal systems, striving to prevent environmental damage and protect future generations.

This does not mean that constitutional courts and ombudsmen are similar institutions. They are different in many ways, their role and function are different, but here we single them out and discuss them as two more relevant and most necessary institutions in the legal system (in a situation where there are several independent institutions), especially when the traditional separation of powers is late in anticipating changes. The key difference is certainly in their basic task: constitutional courts are guardians of the constitution and exercise constitutional control (they repeal or annul acts), while the ombudsman is a kind of administrative controller, who investigates and criticizes, but without executive power. This makes both institutions *sui generis*³², outside the legislative, executive and judicial branches. The paper does not compare their competencies (which

³² In Latin, it means "one of a kind". In the context of institutions, it refers to those who do not fit into the classical separation of powers. They have a specific, unique role.

would be “improper” at times), but rather emphasizes their importance and agility in protecting the environment and fighting environmental crime³³.

2. HISTORICAL DEVELOPMENT OF THE SEPARATION OF POWERS AND INDEPENDENT INSTITUTIONS

In Europe, during the period of absolutism, where kings were “*God's representatives on earth*” or where, according to the example of Louis XIV in France – “*I am the state*”, tyranny, religious persecution and wars became everyday life. Especially after the English Civil War (1642-1649), the Glorious Revolution (1688), as well as the French Revolution (1789), the need arose for power to be clearly limited by law, and for man to be protected from the state. In order to protect the individual from the arbitrariness of power, which would later form the basis of liberal democracy, John Locke was among the first to outline the limitation of power³⁴. He initially makes a separation of powers: he distinguishes between legislative and executive power. The former enacts laws, while the latter is responsible for their implementation. He also sporadically mentions the judicial power, but it is not tripartite as in Montesquieu. The complete and comprehensive theoretical basis for the concept of separation of powers is provided by Charles Montesquieu, a French philosopher who, especially through his work “*The Spirit of Law*” from 1748, will influence future constitutional processes. He speaks of three powers: legislative, executive and judicial power. For the third, which is not explicitly established by Locke, for example, he will state that it judges according to the laws (courts). These three must be separate, but also balanced, where we have the concept of “*checks and balances*”. Both theorists, one in England and the other in France, have personally experienced violent power and the cruel character of absolutism. Their reflections, guided by what they have witnessed, will form the foundation of modern constitutionalism and human rights.

In 1787, it was in the US Constitution that the previous theoretical concepts would be practically “revived” for the first time. The American founders would refer to Locke and Montesquieu, and the American Constitution would establish for the first time the separation of powers, accompanied by checks and balances, which would serve as a benchmark for modern democracies in Europe. However, the modern state at the turn of the 19th to the 20th century became truly complex, and in the period of increasing state role in the economy, public services and social issues, the separation of powers failed to control all segments. The existing three branches could not provide independent oversight, they closed each other in a circle, which would necessitate the need for new institutions that should fill, neutralize that vacuum and obvious shortcomings.

After the First World War, in Austria (1920) after the collapse of Austria-Hungary, we have the first Constitutional Court built on the theory of pure law of the creator

³³ According to the data of the Basic Criminal Court in Skopje, in the period 2018 to 2024, 29 final verdicts were pronounced for crimes against the environment and nature, of which the most pronounced were suspended sentences in 13 cases, a fine was pronounced in 9 cases, an effective prison sentence was pronounced in 2 verdicts, 1 verdict with a court warning and 1 verdict with a suspended sentence with protective supervision. During this period, 2 proceedings following a filed indictment were stopped, and the indictment was rejected for 1. The picture is similar for other courts in the country.

³⁴ Locke introduced the concept of philosophical legitimation of the separation of powers, according to which - the state exists to protect citizens, while it must be responsible and limited.

Kelsen³⁵. Later, the example of the Second World War illustrates how institutions can be subordinated to one person or one party, with which totalitarian regimes prove that the triadic separation of powers is not enough³⁶.

The Constitutional Court can be cited as the oldest independent institution. This group certainly includes the Ombudsman, who, although initially introduced in 1809, experienced its flowering after the Second World War. After the 1970s, there has been a noticeable trend of establishing various independent anti-corruption and media bodies.

3. THE CONCEPT AND CHARACTER OF INDEPENDENT INSTITUTIONS

Independent institutions appear as a reaction to the period in which the separation of powers in many matters is out of place and has been overcome. In particular, the courts become dependent on the authorities, and serious social and economic problems and challenges faced by the states and societies, the authorities are forced to step aside and form special, specialized institutions as independent mechanisms of control. Constitutional courts, following the example of the Austrian one, take on the role of constitutional control of laws, ombudsmen perform the role of protecting citizens from the administration and government in general, while audit institutions (Sweden, Great Britain, USA), election commissions (the example of India in 1950), anti-corruption bodies (Hong Kong in 1974), etc. also appear. Today, we distinguish a large number of such institutions, in which we clearly perceive the principles of independence, expertise (professionalism), specialization, publicity, etc. Independent institutions for human rights and freedoms are not a new branch of the separation of powers, but a modern extension of the idea of limiting power and the rule of law.

The following is a more detailed explanation of two of the oldest institutions (excluding the legislative, executive and judicial branches) in which their independent character, professionalism and specialization are most evident, and which have a **special, proactive role** in relation to the environment and environmental crime.

3.1 Constitutional Courts

Since their establishment, constitutional courts have been occupied for a long time with issues of “classical” rights, such as civil and political rights (right to life, freedom of speech, etc.). They are focused on what is embedded in the then constitutions of the 18th and 19th centuries. Environmental rights, together with social rights, only developed in the second half of the 20th century, and thus, being constitutionally unregulated, they are practically removed from the domain of constitutional court proceedings.

With the emergence of the first constitutional provisions on environmental protection and the formulation of the right to a healthy environment (SFRY, 1974), a new chapter opens in which the area of the environment becomes eligible for constitutional jurisdiction.

In addition to the need for these rights to be explicitly listed in the constitution (or somehow to be part of the constitutional text), an important moment is also ecological

³⁵ Hans Kelsen (1881–1973) was one of the most influential legal and constitutional theorists of the 20th century. He is best known for his *Reine Rechtslehre* / Pure Theory of Law. According to him, the constitution is the highest norm (*grundnorm*).

³⁶ Especially after the Second World War, many countries will accept the Austrian concept (unlike the American one - where there is no constitutional court, but the Supreme Court has established this jurisdiction itself with a precedent from 1803).

disasters and the increasing visibility of environmental damage. It is precisely the fatal consequences for the environment and nature that will force states and international organizations to pay special attention³⁷. Another point is also the strengthening of the civil sector and awareness of the existence of these problems and the rights related to them.

However, in this section it is of particular importance to point out the character and role of constitutional courts. They are not universal institutions, so their role depends on the constitutional-legal and political order. Their competencies are not “*carved in stone*”, no matter how much there are common characteristics³⁸.

In certain democratic states, they can literally be perceived as the fourth power (this can be understood from the constitutional text of some states, to some extent this solution is also present in the Macedonian constitution of 1991), while in others they are a kind of corrector of the authorities, an “inter-power”, but they can also be marginalized. There are still countries in the world where constitutional judicial control (and constitutional courts in general) is absent, but this is still reserved for absolute monarchies, authoritarian regimes or some micronations. The modern constitutional court of the 20th century is still the first example of an institutionalized, formally independent institution (although earlier forms of control can also be found in the Athenian Areopagus or in the medieval forest courts).

3.1.1. Constitutional Courts as guardians of the Constitution today

A functional constitutional judiciary, as former constitutional judge Šarin (2016) states, is one of the bearers of the democratic rule of law. Constitutional judges are “*neither gods nor servants*”. They are traditionally considered guardians of the constitution, which is their **first obligation**. However, in modern constitutional democracies their role continuously exceeds the control of constitutionality. They are not only the negative legislator as Kelsen believes (according to whom - these courts act negatively, only “erasing” norms from the legal order, and not creating new ones), but also become positive creators thanks to their judicial activism - giving new meaning.

In such a context, judicial activism gains a new, green dimension. When interpreting existing human rights (where, for example, environmental rights do not exist), these courts already include environmental rights, thereby bringing the constitution to life - turning it from a “*dead letter on paper*” into a living, moral instrument. In such a constellation, constitutional courts are not only guardians of the constitution, but they are also guardians of the planet in a legal sense. Such behaviour enters the era of green constitutionalism, and the constitutional court seemingly acts as a mediator between people and nature, advocating a balance between them³⁹.

³⁷ This is also linked to the formation of other concepts, such as environmental security. As authors Koprivnjak and Vidaček (2024) point out, the Cold War period required a more rational and “realpolitik” approach to security, which would include elements that are not only part of the traditional understanding.

³⁸ In the USA, for example, although there is no classic constitutional court, the Supreme Court itself assumes the jurisdiction for constitutional judicial protection and control, which is certainly one of the ways to establish this type of judicial powers.

³⁹ It can be concluded, appreciating the complex relations in society, and those that are yet to develop (digital rights, artificial intelligence, environmental rights, etc.), that we are talking about a “*functional spillover*”, where all institutions act outside their domain. Especially if we talk about the constitutional court and the ombudsman, then we see the positive effects in the rapid response (especially in environmental crime, for

Constitutional courts, as Đurić (2012) states, can also be an important actor in the process of European integration, which implies, among other things, the integration of the national order into the European one.

3.2 Ombudsman

The emergence of the ombudsman opens a new chapter in the relations between those who govern and those who are governed, between the state and citizens, between public servants and the public. The ombudsman appears in a dual role. He is equally an instrument for the protection of human rights and a unique mechanism for democratic control over the administration (Aviani, 1999, p. 67).

The authors Vidaček and Ristovska (2024) state that the ombudsman, as a “*megaphone*”, has the task of revealing legal problems and inappropriate actions of the administration and, with the help of professional and legal interventions, to try to restore justice and equality in the everyday system of legal relations. However, it is wrong to idealize this function and attribute to it some “*super-legal*” characteristics.

The Ombudsman, according to Akimovska Maletić and Vidaček (2025), as an informal, additional, non-repressive and non-judicial mechanism for the protection of human rights and freedoms, protects citizens from bad governance. Based on the mandate of the Ombudsman institutions, they have a significant role in the advancement and protection of human rights and fundamental freedoms, in promoting good governance and respect for the rule of law. The authors also recall the attempt from 1974, with the Yugoslav constitutional solution, to establish a “*public ombudsman of self-government*”, which is a kind of body to what is clearly called an ombudsman today.

Over time, specialized ombudsmen have also been established. They have been established for the environment, children, information, minorities, languages, etc. Appreciating that the world is moving towards specialized institutions, which as a process does not bypass the ombudsman, in a text from 2008, Professor Iskra Maletić Akimovska asks the question - *does Macedonia need an environmental ombudsman?* That, both then and today, would certainly yield better results in environmental protection by the Ombudsman.

4. THE INFLUENCE OF INTERNATIONAL STANDARDS

International law, after 1945, has been adopting new standards for human rights as a result of the need for people to be protected not only from the state, but also from the abuse of power and the neglect of public goods (including nature and the environment). The UN has approached the issue of the environment indirectly, and this is derived from the right to life, health, etc. Especially in the 1970s, the UN recommended the establishment of specialized institutions for human rights (and later for environmental protection). This gradually led to the ombudsman gaining powers in environmental issues, and constitutional courts having the legitimacy to protect the “new” rights.

example), the strengthening of moral interest and the enabling of synchronization of different policies and rights. Especially in the case of constitutional courts, their intention for a gap-filling function is noticeable.

4.1 Stockholm Declaration

In 1972, the Stockholm Declaration for the first time put the environment in relation to global challenges and human freedoms and rights. This declaration has 26 principles that form the future international environmental law.

According to Ristovska, Akimovska Maletić and Vidaček (2025), the declaration introduces the concept of the right to a clean environment, although it does not directly recognize it. It first formulates the right to the environment (of course not as clearly as it would be in the 1974 Constitution of the SFRY), advocates the rational use of natural resources and stipulates the principle of “no harm”, which would later become widely accepted in international law. Although the declaration is not legally binding, it has played a crucial role when it comes to environmental protection. It will pave the way for a new type of constitutionalism - titled “ecological” or “green” constitutionalism, which means integrating as many provisions for environmental protection as possible and clearly establishing the right to the environment. According to Vidaček and Ristovska (2025), the right to the environment is a vestibule of green constitutionalism.

Somewhat later, even constitutional courts begin to refer to the Stockholm Declaration. This is especially evident in the Indian Supreme Court, which, as one of the most active in environmental protection, has referred to the declaration in several judgments since the 1980s. The court in the case *Rural Litigation and Entitlement Kendra v. State of U.P.* (1985–1986) banned the exploitation of limestone in the Himalayas, because it threatened forests and watercourses. This is considered the first environmental decision in India in which the court directly mentioned the Stockholm Declaration, which as an international treaty obliges states to protect nature.

The court in India remained known for its activism in the following decades. For example, in a case from 1996, the court cited the Stockholm Declaration and the Rio Declaration (1992) and stated that they were also binding on India. The Supreme Court has ruled that the “precautionary principle”, the “polluter pays” principle and sustainable development are fundamental and inseparable from Indian national law. In doing so, it has incorporated the fundamental principles into its order. The court “takes” the Stockholm Convention as “soft law” and interprets constitutional norms through it. Through such judicial activism, this institution also becomes a “positive legislator” when it comes to environmental cases. This approach will also inspire courts in the Philippines, Bangladesh and Pakistan.

4.2 Paris Principles (1993)

The Paris Principles were adopted by UN General Assembly resolution 48/134 of 1993 (and were previously adopted in Paris in 1991). Their aim is to define minimum standards for the independence, mandate and operation of national human rights institutions (known as NHRIs)⁴⁰. They prescribe 6 key criteria. First, there must be a broad mandate in relation to universal human rights (this certainly includes “environmental” rights). Second, they must be independent of government - both organizationally and financially. Third, their composition is required to reflect social and professional pluralism. Furthermore, financial autonomy of these institutions is advocated. As a penultimate, these

⁴⁰ In this paper, we use the term independent institutions as a broader, more inclusive term than the abbreviation NHRI. The Ombudsman is, for example, a classic NHRI institution, while the constitutional court has a specific position in the entire legal system.

principles require the possibility of these institutions to investigate, recommend measures and advise. The last principle is the need for active international cooperation (Council of Europe, UN, etc.).

5. “FUNCTIONAL SPILLOVER” EFFECT

In the 21st century, when the traditional separation of powers is no longer absolute, we can increasingly speak of the spillover effect. It can be concluded, appreciating the complex relations in society, and those that are yet to develop (digital rights, artificial intelligence, environmental rights, etc.), that we are talking about a “*functional spillover*”, where all institutions act outside their domain. Especially if we talk about the constitutional court and the ombudsman, then we see the positive effects in the rapid response (especially in environmental crime, for example), the strengthening of moral interest and the enabling of synchronization of different policies and rights. Especially in the case of constitutional courts, their intention for a gap-filling function is noticeable.

No matter how positive we evaluate the activity of these two categories of independent institutions, we still need to foresee the danger that comes from this. These are actually side effects⁴¹, because behind these sometimes glorified institutions, there is still a human being, *errare humanum est*. It can be concluded that we distinguish among them preventive, reactive, educational, symbolic (moral) and other functions.

6. ENVIRONMENTAL PROTECTION IN THE REPUBLIC OF NORTH MACEDONIA

In the Republic of North Macedonia, “the regulation and humanization of space and the protection and improvement of the environment and nature” are part of the fundamental values, along with “respect for the generally accepted norms of international law” (stipulated in Article 8). In Article 43, the Macedonian Constitution establishes that “Every person has the right to a healthy environment. Everyone is obliged to improve and protect the environment and nature. The Republic provides conditions for the exercise of the right of citizens to a healthy environment”. This solution is similar to the solution of 1974, only that the then “social community” has now been replaced by “republic”. In this way, the constitution first gives an individual dimension (as a subjective right), and then a collective dimension (collective right) representing the environment as a *res communis omnium* – a public good that at the same time belongs to no one, and is common to all. It is a subjective - collective right, because the deprivation of any property would devastate the other moment. For the state, however, there is both an active and passive obligation. Such a constitutional framework⁴², further supplemented by the multitude of laws, creates an excellent basis for the actions of the constitutional court and the ombudsman.

⁴¹ Constitutional courts, and with them the Ombudsman, can easily play with their “extended” competencies, and consciously or unconsciously lead to a conflict of competencies. Such proactive actions (previously explained as “spillover”) can also lead to parallel decisions and recommendations, which would seriously burden the legal system and stability (example: the Ombudsman and the government may have different recommendations regarding forest management). In a situation of excessive, extensive understanding of competencies, these institutions can be defamed as those who want to subjugate democratic processes and declare themselves “superpowers” (when the court repeals/annuls an act due to environmental damage, and the other side claims that democratic principles are being violated).

⁴² With Amendment XVII, environmental protection also becomes an issue of local importance.

6.1 Constitutional Court of the Republic of North Macedonia

The constitutional judiciary in Macedonia began operating in 1964, and was first established with the Constitution of the Socialist Republic of Macedonia of 1963. The right to the environment is established in the 1974 constitutions of the Socialist Federal Republic of Yugoslavia and the Socialist Republic of Macedonia.

As can be seen from a statement by the former President of the Constitutional Court, Dobrila Kacarska from 2022⁴³, what is most often the case when the Court determines that there is a violation is in cases in which the constitutionality and legality of decisions on the adoption of urban plans are assessed. She then recalled the repeal of the Decision on Amendments and Supplements to the Urban Plan outside the Settlement Ski Centre Vodno – Block 3, Municipality of Karpoš from 2015 (U.br.36/2021), where a violation of constitutional and legal norms was found by the Municipality, which did not publish on its website the decisions on non-implementation, i.e. on conducting a strategic assessment of the impact of the planning document on the environment, although it has a legal obligation.

In 2000, for example, the Constitutional Court repealed an article from the Law on Amendments to the Law on Catering and Tourism Activities (112/2000-0-0) and annulled a paragraph that reads: “unless otherwise determined by the detailed urban plan”. Also, in 2005, the Constitutional Court (U.br.233/2005-1) repealed Article 85, paragraph 3, in the section on “compensation of costs” of the Law on Environment. Perhaps more interesting is the example of the repeal of the Decision (U.br.6/2013-1) on the adoption of an urban plan outside a populated area - part of the tourist complex "Sveti Stefan" in the Municipality of Ohrid, adopted by the Council of the Municipality of Ohrid in 2012. The court determined that this decision called into question the principle of the rule of law and the regulation and humanization of space and the protection and promotion of the environment and nature, as contrary to Article 8 paragraph 1 lines 3 and 10 of the Constitution, but also contrary to the provisions of the Law on Spatial and Urban Planning.

However, no matter how much it is accepted that the Constitutional Court has acted in the area of the environment, creating a solid practice, it is not too much along the lines of “living constitutionality” or judicial activism. It can be concluded that the Constitutional Court was not too brave in giving some kind of more extensive interpretation. “Revolutionary” actions that would give a different meaning to the environment are missing.

However, we can single out one decision from 2019 (U.br.130/2018), in which the Constitutional Court repealed provisions of the Law on Drinking Water Supply and Urban Wastewater Disposal, thus determining that it is unconstitutional to interrupt the supply of drinking water when the user does not fulfil the payment obligation. In the explanation, the Constitutional Court refers to the fundamental values, and among other things determines that according to Article 10, paragraph 1 of the Constitution, human life is inviolable. In this case, registered as U.br.130/2018 of 08.05.2019, we see that the Macedonian court is leaving its “comfort zone” and slightly entering the domain of “green constitutionalism”, appreciating that the right to water is closely correlated with the right to the environment and the fight against environmental crime (the environment also includes the water segment).

⁴³ The speech of the former President of the Constitutional Court entitled “To introduce a constitutional complaint, the right of citizens to a healthy environment is limited before the Constitutional Court” is available on the court's website. More at: www.ustavensud.mk/archives/21809

As even the constitutional judges themselves point out to some extent, at least those who are proponents of the “constitutional appeal” (which we do not know, or at least it is limited only to the rights and freedoms provided for in Article 110, paragraph 3), such a cross-section is to some extent a result of the non-coverage of the right to environment under the mechanism of requesting protection of freedoms and rights. It can be appreciated that, however, the Supreme Court, through a principled legal opinion⁴⁴ from 2024, which obliged the state to provide clean air and a healthy environment, has taken primacy before the Constitutional Court. Such “bolder” decisions, however, have not been observed at the Constitutional Court.

6.2 Ombudsman in the Republic of North Macedonia

The institution was established by the constitution in 1991. The institution began operating in 1997 (when the first law was adopted), and currently this matter is regulated by the new Law on the Ombudsman of 2003 ("Official Gazette of the Republic of Macedonia" No. 60/03 of 22.09.2003).

The Ombudsman is a recognized institution in the field of protection, promotion and advancement of human freedoms and rights. The large annual number of complaints from citizens confirms this position. However, the same cannot be said for the field of the environment.

In the period of 6 years (2019-2024), the Ombudsman reported⁴⁵ a total of 110 complaints through its reports, which is an exceptionally low number compared to other areas covered by the Ombudsman. If the average value is calculated, then it amounts to 18.3 complaints per year, which is certainly low. In addition, it is worth noting the share of complaints in the field of the environment in relation to the total number of complaints submitted. In 2019, the share was 0.52%, a decrease was recorded the following year and amounted to 0.41%, while in 2021 a share of 0.45% was recorded. In 2022, the share was 0.53 (which shows an increasing trend), which is also reflected in 2023 with a share of 0.75%. The largest share, which represents the only share above 1%, is the share from the last year, which amounted to 1.18%.

Complaints addressed to the Ombudsman are largely considered the dominant “input” in terms of his actions. Complaints serve as a source of information on possible irregularities, violations and restrictions of rights and freedoms, as well as the presence of maladministration. Based on such complaints, the institution initiates investigations, analyses, conducts direct inspections, provides recommendations and remarks, and in

⁴⁴ Following an initiative to establish a principled position submitted by the Law Firm "Godžo, Kičeev and Novakovski", the Supreme Court on 08.10.2024 discussed at a session whether the state is responsible for Macedonian citizens breathing polluted air, i.e. to what extent the state provides conditions for the realization of the right of citizens to a healthy environment, in accordance with the legally established duties and competencies in the field of the environment. The position of the Macedonian Supreme Court is that "in the realization of the rights to a healthy environment, the provisions of the Law on Administrative Disputes are applied, which provide judicial protection from illegal acts and actions (or failed actions) that violate the constitutionally guaranteed rights and freedoms of man and citizen, when that specific judicial protection is not provided for by the Constitution and other laws". Hence, the state is obliged to provide a healthy environment, and failure to take action is a violation of the rights of citizens.

⁴⁵ The Ombudsman's reports are available on the institution's official website. More at: www.ombudsman.mk

certain situations initiates changes to the legal regulations. Therefore, we observe complaints as an initial mechanism through which the Ombudsman is directed at specific problems.

The environment also has a very low share when it comes to cases initiated on its own initiative. It can be concluded that the Ombudsman initiates cases on its own initiative on an annual basis, but the environment is outside the dominant areas. There are years in which the Ombudsman did not initiate a single case related to the environment.

From media articles and appearances by representatives of the institution, it can be noted that in recent years the Ombudsman has been involved in a more active fight for environmental protection and environmental justice. A certain period of time is needed for his engagement to take effect.

The conclusion is that despite the acute but persistent environmental problems (air, soil, water pollution, problems with waste management and disposal, endangerment of flora and fauna...) citizens use the Ombudsman mechanism to a low extent. This can be attributed to some extent to the practice so far according to which the Ombudsman has built a somewhat greater authority in the areas of children's rights, persons with disabilities, consumer rights, health care, penal and correctional and educational-correctional homes, etc. On the other hand, it is worth highlighting the observation that although the Ombudsman provides a somewhat broader scope using the formulation "environment" (and not only environmental law), it can be noted from the cases handled that they are predominantly of a personal nature, related to several categories (air, water, soil, noise). It is not excluded that the Ombudsman will show a proactive stance where legal and by-laws are adopted contrary to the fundamental values of the constitutional order and environmental law. The Ombudsman can on many occasions ascertain a violation of the environment and actions contrary to these provisions.

The Ombudsman has the opportunity to act also in situations where some derived rights are obstructed, which, although not exhaustively listed, arise from the very essence and nature of the provisions, i.e. when such a ratio legis requires. Through his correct legal interpretation (when applying a broader and holistic interpretation of the law), he can establish such a legal practice that in the future, by means of (first) legal precedent, will provide even broader guarantees and respect for rights.

The environment (as a social and natural term, not necessarily a legal or security one) and environmental law, due to their polyvalent character, have a serious potential to develop rights and practices that the legal system has not yet accepted (which are not initially in contradiction to it). Therefore, it is really interesting to see the Ombudsman's actions appreciating its inherence with human freedoms and rights and democracy.

Given that the Ombudsman in this area shows weaker performance (compared to other "traditional" areas for him), there is an undoubted period of popularization and promotion of this institution in the field of the environment. In fact, here we have a strengthening of awareness through campaigns and activities on two issues, firstly on the issue of the environment and environmental law (which is under threat), and secondly on the Ombudsman as its protector (and the possibility of submitting complaints). However, the lack of initiative by the Ombudsman and other independent institutions may lead to seeking justice in Strasbourg⁴⁶ or to resort to other legal mechanisms⁴⁷ which have been unknown so far.

⁴⁶ There are a large number of applications submitted by Macedonian citizens to the Court of Human Rights in Strasbourg concerning the right to a healthy environment, on which no decisions

CONCLUSION

A state that protects the environment is not possible without independent and efficient institutions. In this millennium, it is noticeable how states are transforming into what the theory calls the “*ecological state*”, where environmental protection is not just a declaration, nor a political priority, but a clear constitutional obligation that projects a new, deconstructed system. In such a situation, constitutional courts and ombudsmen (as the first, oldest independent institutions outside the three branches of government) are the guardians of the new order that increasingly integrates provisions on environmental law, sustainable development, climate change and the rights of future generations.

Constitutional courts and ombudsmen act in a polyvalent manner, as legal, moral and educational mechanisms that stand as a bulwark against attacks on nature, creating an additional institutional framework for environmental protection and the fight against environmental crime. However, such a fight is largely conditioned by the activity of citizens. They must “feed” these institutions with information, complaints and lawsuits, because these institutions still predominantly work on the principle of “inputs”.

Citizens around the world are still largely oriented towards constitutional courts and ombudsmen, before whom they present their demands for the protection of both their rights and the rights of nature and future generations. Climate lawsuits are becoming a reality.

Especially in constitutional courts, the transition from a positivist to a natural-legal and ecological paradigm has been observed, linking the environment directly with man, his dignity, well-being, health.

However, this is not the case with the Republic of North Macedonia. In the practice of the Constitutional Court so far, it is noticeable that it has acted in environmental cases, but they are predominantly related to detailed urban plans or other legal/sub-legal acts. Apart from the decision related to the right to water, the court has not recorded any “more revolutionary” actions, which places it in the group of more conservative constitutional courts (which is not the case with the American, Indian or other).

Although the Ombudsman has been mentioning the environment and surroundings since its early years, it has also recorded “more modest” actions, which are mainly outside its dominant preoccupation.

After analysing the actions of both institutions in the country, it can be emphasized that strengthened constitutional control, accompanied by an expanded ombudsman mandate, as well as the possible establishment of a special department within the ombudsman, will contribute to more efficient protection of environmental rights.

However, both institutions are showing significant shifts and opportunities for change in the existing paradigm. Their louder appeals and speeches, in which they at least declaratively join the fight for environmental and climate justice, provide rational space for belief in their more extensive and revolutionary approach.

have yet been made. These decisions are of importance for further court proceedings that would be conducted in the Republic of North Macedonia, as well as the manner and mechanisms for taking action by the state, state and private entities for a healthy environment as a fundamental human right.

⁴⁷ The State Attorney's Office of the Republic of North Macedonia has filed a civil case in which the state is being sued over the right to clean air, it is in court proceedings and has not yet been legally concluded.

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TRAFFIC ACCIDENT RISK ANALYSIS AND POTENTIAL FOR ENHANCING ROAD SAFETY ON THE EXPRESS ROADS IN NORTH MACEDONIA

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Abstract

Official statistical data shows that in North Macedonia approximately 130 people die annually in road traffic accidents, and nearly 1000 are seriously injured. Road safety analysis plays an important role in the efforts to reduce the fatalities and serious injuries on roads. Traffic accident risk analysis is one of the most effective tools for assessing the current road safety level of a particular road. Express roads are a rather miscellaneous road category hierarchically situated between motorways and ordinary single carriageway interurban roads. Such roads have recently begun to be implemented in North Macedonia, but their impact on traffic safety has not yet been investigated. This research paper presents a comprehensive traffic accident risk analysis on the express roads in North Macedonia, with the primary objective of examining the road safety level of the express roads and proposing targeted interventions aimed at reducing accidents and fatalities on existing express roads and considerations for the future design of express roads. The findings of this research paper will enable transportation authorities to gain a clear understanding of the impacts of the express roads on road safety and considerations for the integration of safety into design.

Keywords: accidents, road safety, risk rate, express roads

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. Background

Over the past decade, road safety in Europe has been guided by the principles of the Safe System and the Vision Zero approach, with clear intermediate targets — to halve the number of fatalities and, for the first time, the number of seriously injured persons by 2030, as a step toward almost zero deaths by 2050. Road traffic accidents represent not only a global public health problem but also a major socio-economic challenge, particularly in low- and middle-income countries.

In 2024, road accidents in North Macedonia resulted in 142 fatalities and 1,085 serious injuries⁴⁸. Despite continued investments in road safety, the number of fatalities and serious injuries has increased compared to the previous two years, indicating an upward trend that is expected to continue into 2025. Moreover, the road mortality rate, expressed as the public risk of being killed in traffic, stands at 6.9 deaths per 100,000 inhabitants in North Macedonia — considerably higher than the European Union average of 4.6 deaths per 100,000 inhabitants.

In recent years, express roads have begun to be implemented in the Republic of North Macedonia; however, their impact on traffic safety has not yet been systematically investigated. This paper analyses the risk of road traffic accidents on express roads using indicators of collective risk (expressed through accident density) and individual risk (expressed through accident rate). The main deficiencies of express roads are identified, and proposals for improving their safety are provided.

The analysis focuses on the following express road sections: Štip – Kočani, Štip – Radoviš, and Veles – Kadrifakovo. These are newly built segments, constructed over the past decade, which have significantly improved connectivity in the central and eastern parts of the country.

1.2. Express roads

Express roads represent a rather heterogeneous road category, hierarchically positioned between motorways and ordinary single-carriageway interurban roads. An express road can be defined as a medium- to high-capacity road designed for long-distance connectivity, with limited access and closed to non-motorized traffic. Roads classified as express roads exist in a wide variety of types and formats, with substantial differences in both design and operational characteristics. In some cases, an express road is designed so that it can easily be upgraded to motorway standards.

Express roads may exist as dual carriageways (2×2 lanes with physical separation between directions, most often using an unpaved median) or as single carriageways — either 1×2 with standard lane width, 1×2 with wider lanes, or 2+1 configurations, where the middle lane alternately serves each direction for overtaking. Most express roads have shoulders (emergency stopping lanes). Single carriageways are more common, while dual carriageways tend to concentrate near urban areas and economic centres (Schagen, 1999). Express roads may include both grade-separated and at-grade intersections. Grade-separated intersections can be upgraded to full motorway standard but are sometimes designed with lower standards. In some countries, the use of grade-separated intersections on express roads is discouraged to maintain a clearer distinction from motorways. At-grade intersections are most often designed with right-in/right-out access, give-way or stop control, or traffic signals. Roundabouts are not very common but can be found — for instance, in France, they are often located at the beginning and end of an express road.

In the United Kingdom and Ireland, non-motorways – including express roads – are considered “all-purpose roads” and are therefore open to all traffic. In all other countries, however, most express roads are closed to non-motorized users, although Sweden and Portugal report a limited number of express roads where such traffic is permitted. The design speed for 2×2 express roads typically ranges from 100 to 120 km/h, while for single-carriageway express roads it ranges between 80 and 100 km/h. In general, speed limits vary between 80 and 120 km/h. Access control on express roads is less strict

⁴⁸ Ministry of Interior

than on motorways but stricter than on ordinary single-carriageway roads. For example, in France, the distance between access points on express roads is typically greater than 10 km (Schagen, 1999).

An express road is implemented, or an existing road is upgraded when the (expected) traffic volume exceeds a certain threshold, when higher speeds are desired, and when financial and/or environmental constraints prevent the construction of a full motorway. Another argument sometimes cited is better accessibility to major economic centres along the corridor compared to motorways. Safety, however, is rarely considered as a key factor in the decision-making process, even though some design standards and guidelines emphasize the need for uniformity and continuity with the adjacent network for safety reasons.

Overall, the safety performance of this “intermediate” road category is relatively poor. A detailed analysis of the Portuguese accident database found that the accident rate on express roads is roughly three times higher than that on motorways. The most common accident type on express roads involves single-vehicle run-off-road accidents (around 30%) (Hummel, 1999). Despite this poor safety record, express roads continue to be designed and built.

In the Republic of North Macedonia, express roads began to be introduced in 2016, when the Veles – Kadrifakovo express road (with at-grade intersections) was opened to traffic. This was followed by the Štip – Kočani, Štip – Radoviš, Kumanovo – Kriva Palanka, and Gradsko – Fariš express roads, all featuring grade-separated intersections. The total length of express roads in the country currently amounts to 145.2 kilometres⁴⁹.

1.3. Approaches for road traffic safety analysis

Road safety analysis plays an important role in the efforts to reduce fatalities and serious injuries on the roads. It is a process that allows the assessment of the safety level of a specific road or road network and can be carried out using two distinct approaches (Jolakoski et al., 2025; PIARC, 2025):

- Traditional approach, and
- Proactive approach.

The traditional approach to risk identification involves the analysis of historical accident data. This approach is often referred to as “reactive”, as the response is initiated only after accidents have occurred. Despite its reactive nature, it remains highly relevant and widely used.

The proactive approach (sometimes referred to as the systemic approach or the “in-built safety” approach) relies on the analysis of physical and operational characteristics of existing roads or planned road projects to identify current or potential future safety deficiencies. This approach is particularly useful in locations where accident data quality is low or where new infrastructure is being developed. Proactive approaches are increasingly being used to complement traditional accident-based analyses. Moreover, their added value lies in the possibility of improving road safety before accidents occur, thereby preventing fatalities and injuries from being recorded in the first place.

⁴⁹ WEB GIS Road Asset Management System (RAMS), Public Enterprise for State Roads

1. METHODOLOGY

2.1. Traffic accident risk estimation

2.1.1. Traffic accident density (Collective risk)

Accident density is a measure of collective risk. It refers to the number of accidents per unit length of road on each route (iRAP, 2024). This information can be used by road authorities and policy makers to:

- Help understand how the total risk to all road users is distributed across a road network
- Provide a valuable tool for estimating the total number of accidents that could potentially be avoided if safety on a route were improved
- Consider investment decisions.

As accidents typically increase with traffic flow, accident density is largely influenced by the number of vehicles using a particular route. For this reason, motorways and other high flow roads tend to have a relatively high collective risk. Accident density is calculated for each route in the analysis period as follows (PIARC, 2025):

$$D_j = \frac{f_j}{L_j}$$

where:

D_j = accident density of site j (accidents/km)

f_j = accident frequency at site j

L_j = section's length of site j (km)

2.1.2. Traffic accident rate (Individual risk)

Accident rate is a measure of individual risk. It is the number of accidents relative to the total number of vehicles using the road (iRAP, 2024). High volume roads, such as motorways, with a high number of overall accidents may have a low individual risk. On the other hand, low volume roads with occasional accidents may have a comparably higher individual risk. Accident rate mapping of individual risk aims to inform drivers about modifying behaviour on frequently used roads to reduce risk. This approach identifies a site where the accident frequency is unusually high relative to its traffic volume. The accident rate, which is the ratio of accident frequency to traffic volume, indicates the level of risk exposure. Traffic volume is the most commonly used exposure unit:

- At road intersections (nodes), the traffic considered is the sum of entering vehicles.
- On road links, it is the sum of vehicles travelling in both directions. The length of the link must also be accounted for.

Accident rate is calculated for each route in the analysis period as follows (PIARC, 2025):

$$R_j = \frac{f_j \times 10^6}{365.25 \times PL_j Q_j}$$

where:

R_j = accident rate of site j (accidents/Mveh-km)

R_p = average accident rate (accidents/Mveh-km)

f_j = accident frequency at site j

P = period of analysis (years)

L_j = section's length of site j (km)

Q_j = average annual daily traffic of site j (AADT)

The average accident rate is calculated for each route in the analysis period as follows (PIARC, 2025):

$$R_{rp} = \frac{\sum f_j \times 10^6}{365.25 \times P \times \sum L_j \times Q_w}$$

where:

R_{rp} = average accident rate of (accident/Mveh-km)

f_j = accident frequency at site j

P = period of analysis (years)

L_j = section's length of site j (km)

Q_w = weighted average annual daily traffic (AADT)

$$Q_w = \frac{\sum Q_j \times L_j}{\sum L_j}$$

Q_j = AADT of site j

As main advantages of this measure can be pointed out: it considers traffic exposure, it is the most widely used identification criterion, which facilitates comparisons, and it focuses on the probability of being involved in an accident (individual risk). The main disadvantages of this measure are: the traffic volume must be known at each site, it does not take into account the random nature of accidents, bias towards low-traffic roads (a random variation of a few accidents per period will significantly modify the accident rate value at such sites), it does not take into account accident severity, assumes a linear relationship between traffic volume and accidents; this may be a source of error.

2.2. Data collection

For the analysis of traffic accident risk on express roads, it is essential to have access to the following types of data:

- Data on the number of traffic accidents by severity,
- Traffic volumes, and
- Road characteristics.

The data on traffic accidents that occurred on express roads during the period 2022–2024 are presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Road Accident Data⁵⁰

Roadway	Year	Accidents with fatalities	Accidents with serious injuries	Accidents with injuries	Fatalities	Serious injuries	Injuries
Štip – Kočani	2022	2	7	7	2	8	18
	2023	0	2	7	0	2	17
	2024	4	3	6	6	10	23
	Total	6	12	20	8	20	58
Štip – Radoviš	2022	2	2	8	2	3	18
	2023	0	0	9	0	0	16
	2024	0	2	3	0	2	7
	Total	2	4	20	2	5	41
Veles – Kadrifakovo	2022	0	0	1	0	0	1
	2023	0	3	5	0	4	8
	2024	1	1	1	1	2	4
	Total	1	4	7	1	6	13
TOTAL		9	20	47	11	31	112

The traffic volume data for the express road sections are presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Traffic Flow Data⁵¹

Roadway	Year	AADT
Štip – Kočani	2022	6097
	2023	4845
	2024	5202
	Average	5381
Štip – Radoviš	2022	7674
	2023	9130
	2024	5373
	Average	7392
Veles – Kadrifakovo	2022	2152
	2023	2412
	2024	2551

⁵⁰ Ministry of Interior

⁵¹ Traffic Counting Data Processing System (TDPS), Public Enterprise for State Roads

	Average	2372
AVERAGE		5448

The road features data for the express road sections are presented in Table 3.

*Table 3: Road Features Data*⁵²

Roadway	Length (km)	Driving lanes	Emergency lanes	Crossing type	Speed limit (km/h)
Štip – Kočani	28.2	2	2	Grade-separated	110
Štip – Radoviš	37.2	2	2	Grade-separated	110
Veles Kadrifakovo	– 22.9	2	2	At level	110
TOTAL	88.3				

2.3. Traffic accident risk bands (classes)

In Europe, standard risk thresholds have been adopted based on expected distributions. These thresholds have been halved compared to the values initially established, in order to reflect the successful reduction in the number of fatalities.

A further reduction of these values is foreseen in the next set of risk thresholds, as road safety continues to improve. However, the decline in road fatalities has stagnated in many European countries over the past decade, and therefore, the planned adjustment has been postponed. The current range of risk thresholds is presented in Table 4.

Table 4: European Risk Bands (iRAP, 2024)

Risk level	Accident density (Accidents with fatalities per kilometre length of road in 3 years)	Accident rate (Accidents with fatalities per billion vehicle-kilometres)
Very low	0 – < 0.08	0 – < 1.2
Low	0.08 – < 0.16	1.2 – < 4.9
Medium	0.16 – < 0.24	4.9 – < 8.4
High	0.24 – < 0.32	8.4 – < 14.2
Very High	> = 0.32	> = 14.2

2.4. Highlighting persistently higher risk routes

Road sections with persistently higher risk are those that demonstrate a relatively high level of risk for road users during two consecutive analysis periods. For a particular section to be classified as a persistently high-risk road, it must be supported by robust data that meet the following criteria (iRAP, 2024):

- More than the average number of accidents across all road sections in both analysis periods,

⁵² WEB GIS Road Asset Management System (RAMS), Public Enterprise for State Roads

- At least one fatal or serious injury accident per kilometre of road length in both analysis periods,
- A minimum road length of 5 km,
- A minimum AADT (Average Annual Daily Traffic) of 2,000 vehicles and
- A risk classification of “*high*” or “*very high*” in two consecutive analysis periods.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results of the collective risk analysis of road traffic accidents on express roads, by road section and by year, are presented in Table 5.

Table 5: Accident density results

Roadway	Year	Accident density (Accidents with fatalities per km length of road)	Collective risk level
Štip – Kočani	2022	0.04	Very low
	2023	0.07	Very low
	2024	0.11	Low
	Total	0.21	Medium
Štip – Radoviš	2022	0.05	Very low
	2023	0.00	NA
	2024	0.00	NA
	Total	0.05	Very high
Veles – Kadrifakovo	2022	0.00	NA
	2023	0.00	NA
	2024	0.04	Very low
	Total	0.04	Very low
TOTAL		0.10	Low

From Table 5, it can be observed that the Štip – Kočani section has a medium level of collective accident risk, expressed as the density of accidents per kilometre. It is followed by the Veles – Kadrifakovo section, which shows a low level of collective risk, while the Štip – Radoviš section records a very low level of collective accident risk. The results of the individual accident risk analysis on express roads, by road section and by year, are presented in Table 6.

Table 6: Accident rate results

Roadway	Year	Accident rate (Accidents with fatalities per billion vehicle-km)	Individual risk level
Štip – Kočani	2022	15.92	Very high
	2023	40.08	Very high
	2024	55.99	Very high
	Total	36.09	Very high
Štip – Radoviš	2022	19.18	Very high
	2023	0.00	NA
	2024	0.00	NA
	Total	6.64	Medium
Veles – Kadrifakovo	2022	0.00	NA
	2023	0.00	NA
	2024	46.87	Very high
	Total	16.80	Very high
TOTAL		17.07	Very high

From Table 6, it can be observed that the Štip – Kočani and Veles – Kadrifakovo road sections exhibit a very high level of collective accident risk, expressed as the number of accidents per billion vehicle-kilometres, while the Štip – Radoviš section shows a medium level of individual accident risk. The Štip – Kočani road section demonstrates a consistently very high level of individual risk across three consecutive analysis periods, which highlights it as a persistently high-risk road section for road users.

The individual risk indicator focuses on the probability of an accident occurring and provides a more accurate measure of road safety risk, as it considers traffic exposure through the number of vehicle-kilometres travelled. The results obtained confirm that express roads are characterized by poor safety performance in terms of road traffic accidents.

3.1. Identification of main issues

The main deficiencies of single-carriageway express roads with one lane per direction (1+1) and emergency stopping lanes are as follows:

- Inadequate speed management combined with the potential for head-on collisions, and
- Misuse of emergency stopping lanes.

Head-on accidents, whether involving an oncoming vehicle or a roadside element, are the most common type of accident on express roads. In the case of a head-on collision at speeds of 110 km/h — the current speed limit on express roads — the probability of fatal consequences exceeds 100% (see Figure 1).

Figure 1: Risk of fatal outcome as a function of speed

The Safe System Approach (SSA) represents a new philosophy of thinking about road traffic safety, based on the understanding that humans are fallible and will inevitably make mistakes that can lead to fatal outcomes. It also acknowledges that the human body has a limited tolerance to accident forces before sustaining serious or fatal injuries, that fatalities and serious injuries resulting from road accidents are unacceptable, and that responsibility for safety is shared among all stakeholders. One of the key elements of the Safe System Approach is the concept of Safe Speeds (Aarts, 2023).

Within the Safe System Approach (SSA), speed limits are based on the principles of preventing accidents and reducing impact speeds to ensure that accidents do not result in serious injuries or fatalities. The objective of the Safe System is to establish appropriate speed limits that correspond to the function and characteristics of the road, as well as to the vulnerability of road users. (ITF, 2022).

A safe speed is defined as the speed at which the risk of a fatal outcome is below 10%. According to Figure 1, the safe speed for a head-on collision is 70 km/h. This means that, in line with the Safe System Approach, and in order to prevent fatalities and serious injuries, the speed limit should be set at 70 km/h. However, considering the lane width of 3.5 meters, it is unrealistic to expect drivers to comply with such a speed limit under current road design conditions.

The misuse of emergency stopping lanes is a frequent occurrence on express roads. It happens when drivers partially use the emergency lane while driving, thereby leaving insufficient space for safe overtaking in the main traffic lane. This situation becomes particularly critical when a vehicle from the opposite direction is also misusing its emergency lane, and two vehicles from opposing directions simultaneously attempt to overtake slower vehicles that are occupying the emergency lanes, assuming there is enough space to pass. At that moment, four vehicles appear side by side, and due to the limited available space, a head-on collision occurs between the two vehicles performing the overtaking manoeuvres.

3.2. Potential for enhancing road safety on express roads

Developing effective road safety measures requires a thorough understanding of the types of traffic accidents and the factors contributing to them, and, even more importantly, a clear comprehension of the traffic, roadway, and roadside characteristics that influence exposure, accident likelihood, and accident severity.

Given that express roads currently exist and will continue to exist in the future, it is essential to make continuous efforts to ensure that this road type becomes as safe as possible, with safety performance levels approaching those of motorways.

The safety of existing express road sections can be improved through infrastructure-based measures, including:

- Separation of opposing traffic directions using median barriers,
- Addition or widening of shoulders and
- Addition or widening of clear zones along the roadside.

Among the proposed and/or implemented safety measures for express roads, traffic calming measures are generally not considered, as the traffic function and the resulting high operating speeds of express roads make such measures inappropriate.

To overcome the deficiencies of existing express roads, the 2+1 road concept is recommended. This concept, originating in Sweden in 1998, has since been recognized and implemented in many other countries, including Finland, Norway, Denmark, Germany, Ireland, Estonia, Lithuania, Portugal, Romania, the Czech Republic, the United Kingdom, Australia, New Zealand, Canada, and the United States, among others. The 2+1 concept provides a third (alternating) overtaking lane and a physical or visual separation between opposing traffic directions. (Gazzini, 2008; Ray, 2003; Romana et al., 2018). This concept has been proven to be an effective intermediate solution between a 2+1 single-carriageway road and a motorway (Schagen, 1999). With this solution, the likelihood of head-on collisions is dramatically reduced, driver frustration decreases, and the speed dispersion becomes more stable. In practice, the 2+1 design is applied on corridors with medium to high traffic volumes (typically around 7,000–25,000 vehicles per day) and speed limits ranging from 80 to 100 km/h. (Romana et al., 2018). Figure 2 presents a schematic illustration of alternating 2+1 segments.

Figure 2. Schematic illustration of alternating “2+1” segments

The length of overtaking segments usually ranges from 1.0 to 2.5 km, depending on the AADT and terrain conditions. The length of critical merging sections varies between 180 and 500 meters and typically includes a protected “ghost island” zone, while the length of non-critical diverging sections ranges from 50 to 100 meters. (Romana et al., 2018) Figure 3 shows the critical and non-critical transitions.

Figure 3. Schematic illustration of critical and non-critical transitions

Intersections are designed either as grade-separated or at-grade with prohibited left turns. To separate opposing traffic directions, cable or steel safety barriers, delineator posts, or a painted median are used (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Cross-section of a 2+1 road with cable barrier and steel barrier (Sweden), painted median (Germany), and flexible delineator posts (Czech Republic)

On 2+1 roads, road markings and traffic signs are mandatory to provide advance notification of the beginning, length, and end of the overtaking lane (Figure 5).

Figure 5: Road markings and traffic signs for 2+1 segments

Studies show a significant reduction in fatalities and serious injuries on 2+1 road segments: in Sweden, reductions of 76–82% (with barriers) have been recorded; in Finland, around 46% (with barriers); and in Germany, a 36% decrease in injury accidents. In the United States, a 44% reduction in total accidents has been observed on sections with overtaking lanes. The average speed typically increases by 1–10 km/h across the entire segment, while the 85th percentile speed in the overtaking lane can reach 120–130 km/h, which requires effective closure design and strict driver discipline at critical transition zones. (Carlsson, 2009; Vadeby, 2016).

Research also indicates a reduction of fatalities and serious injuries by approximately 50% at the network level. On road segments without intersections, the reduction reaches about 63%, while total injury accidents decrease by 21–28%, and the severity of outcomes (FSI/PI ratio) drops by around 38%. For example, the Vanneberga section in Sweden (~2.4 km, ~14,700 vehicles/day) improved from a 2-star to a 3-star rating (and 4-star between intersections) according to the iRAP methodology, despite an increase in the speed limit from 90 to 100 km/h, showing a notable reduction in head-on collision risk. Typical benefit–cost ratios (BCR) for such interventions, according to iRAP, range between 3 and 6. (iRAP, 2020).

At critical transition zones, bottleneck effects may occur when traffic flow approaches capacity levels (1,400–1,900 vehicles per hour per direction). Additionally, increased acceleration and deceleration can be observed near the end of the overtaking segment. Therefore, it is recommended to maintain a balanced segment length and ensure careful speed management to minimize these effects. (Bergh et al., 2016; Romana et al., 2018).

The benefits of applying the 2+1 road concept include:

- Significantly higher traffic safety (compared to 1+1 roads with emergency stopping lanes):
 - o Lower accident risk
 - o Substantially fewer head-on collisions
- No need to ensure sufficient sight distance for overtaking:
 - o Opportunity for safe overtaking
 - o Reduced driver stress during overtaking manoeuvres
- Lower likelihood of driver errors and violations of traffic rules and regulations

4. CONCLUSION

The conducted analysis of express roads in North Macedonia reveals a clear discrepancy between collective and individual risk. While the overall accident density (collective risk) is low to medium, the accident rates by exposure (individual risk) are alarmingly high on certain road sections. Most notably, the Štip – Kočani section shows a “very high” individual risk for three consecutive years, standing out as a persistently high-risk corridor. The Veles – Kadrifakovo section recorded a very high risk in 2024, while Štip – Radoviš demonstrates a medium overall risk level, though with significant yearly fluctuations. These findings are consistent with international research, which confirms that road sections with high-speed limits and no physical separation are associated with a high probability of head-on collisions, and consequently, a high individual accident risk per vehicle-kilometre.

The main detected problems are: (a) Exposure to head-on collisions due to the absence of physical separation and the inherent possibility of risky overtaking under a

speed limit of 110 km/h; and (b) Misuse of emergency stopping lanes, which creates the illusion of a four-lane profile during simultaneous overtaking manoeuvres, thereby dramatically increasing the likelihood of conflict. Such a configuration is inconsistent with the principles of the Safe System Approach, particularly the principle of Safe Speeds for undivided traffic directions, which emphasizes the need to reduce the kinetic energy released in head-on accidents rather than relying solely on driver behaviour.

It can therefore be concluded that improving the safety of express roads cannot be achieved merely through local, low-cost “cosmetic” interventions, but rather through structural transformation aimed at reducing the overall accident risk. The most appropriate and cost-effective measure is the conversion to a 2+1 configuration with physical separation of traffic directions, applied to road sections that meet the criteria for persistently high risk and have sufficient traffic volumes.

To ensure a sustainable effect and transparent value for money, the implementation should be measurable, including a before–after evaluation using the Empirical Bayes method (with a minimum three-year period), monitoring of fatal accident rates per kilometre and per billion vehicle-kilometres, and analysis of speed profiles (85th percentile and dispersion), among other indicators.

This paper argues that express roads, as an “intermediate” road category, can significantly approach the safety performance of motorways only if their structural design is redefined. The conversion of critical sections into 2+1 configurations with physical separation, accompanied by harmonized speed limits, represents the most effective and cost-efficient approach to prevent further deterioration of traffic safety on express roads. In order to prevent further deterioration of traffic safety on express roads as well as the creation of conditions for the implementation of 2+1 roads, the definition for express roads was revised and it read as follows:

“An express road” is a public road designed and constructed for motor vehicle traffic, marked with the prescribed traffic sign, featuring two physically separated carriageways with two traffic lanes in each direction, or a single carriageway with at least one lane in one direction and two lanes in the other, alternating at short intervals according to road conditions, which may also be physically separated. The road shall have grade-separated intersections, no crossings with other roads, railways, or pedestrian and bicycle paths. Traffic may enter or exit only at designated points via specially constructed interchanges with acceleration and deceleration lanes. The road shall be protected from access outside these designated areas and shall include emergency stopping areas and rest areas for passengers.⁵³

⁵³ Law on Amendments to the Law on Public Roads (Official Gazette of the Republic of Macedonia No. 135/2025)

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THE IMPACT OF CORRUPTION ON THE ENVIRONMENT

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Abstract

According to the statements in the paper, the impact of corruption through its various forms on the environment is presented. Namely, the explanation of these criminalistic, criminal law, environmental, victimological, sociological, health, economic, and many other problems, is increasingly being talked about and written about worldwide because it is gaining momentum. The paper presents an overview of the problem of corruption in the environment, primarily through the processing of: introduction, legislative and legal framework, definition of the term corruption, types of corrupt behaviour, phenomenology of the occurrence of corruption in the environment, consequences of the impacts of corruption on the environment, prevention of future criminal activities, conclusion and used literature. To clarify the impact, several general research methods have been used and through the presentation of recent and older events that are directly related to this type of crime, an attempt has been made to present the phenomenological characteristics of the forms of manifestation encountered, the causal connections between the crime and the perpetrator versus the state response, as well as the failure to take the appropriate legally prescribed measures and activities of state institutions. To achieve the goal, explaining the impact of corruption on the environment, i.e. on persons with public functions and authorities who, through all their influences, obstruct justice and with their corrupt behaviour directly harm the environment, we use the following general research methods: comparative method, statistical method, descriptive method, causal method, method of document content analysis. All these activities have been carried out in a way that makes the illegal activities committed by employees in the environmental sector and other state institutions more accessible, more transparent, and collected in one place, as well as highlighting the inappropriate and irresponsible attitude – and, for unclear reasons, the impunity – of the judicial authorities, and the impact of this complex of illegal activities on the environment. At the same time, we also offer possible ways out of this situation and, above all, through prevention and then repression of corrupt activities in the environment and especially the negative impact of the same. However, we must emphasize that the small number of committed crimes indicates the existence of a huge dark figure.

Keywords: *corruption, environment, prevention, protection*

INTRODUCTION

Environmental pollution has emerged as one of the fastest-growing forms of organized crime globally, causing incalculable harm to ecosystems and, by extension, to humanity. The growth of such crimes often relies on organized networks, institutional protection, and impunity for perpetrators. To understand this phenomenon, it is essential to define key terms:

- **Environment:** the space containing all living organisms and natural resources, including natural and human-created values, their mutual relationships, and the total space in which humans live, including settlements, industrial facilities, and media (SSO, 2024).
- **Environment (alternative definition):** refers to physical and biological systems and their interconnections, distinct from political, economic, and social systems, including their feedback influence on human life (Bajagić, 2007).

To analyse the impact of corruption on the environment, this paper employs general research methods, including comparative, statistical, descriptive, causal, and document content analysis (Mojanoski, 2012).

1. LEGAL AND INSTITUTIONAL FRAMEWORK

Environmental crimes are codified as punishable offences in domestic legislation, including North Macedonia. However, despite legal provisions, institutional responses remain inefficient due to insufficient human resources, inadequate equipment, and corruption (Malish Szadovska, 2014; Fetai, 2021). Corruption, often described as a “disease of leaders”, occurs when public officials prioritize private interests over public duties (Mrvić-Petrović & Ćirić, 2004). Legislative instability, frequent amendments, and loopholes create opportunities for tailored laws favoring elites (Taseva, 2021).

These are exactly the cases with the SCPC and their president, as well as the decision of no confidence in members of the Republic Judicial Council, which, due to the adjusted and adapted laws, have no effect on the holders of functions. Here, we are primarily talking about ambiguities, legal loopholes and of course adapting or adjusting the criminal code to the needs of an elite. Regarding this phenomenon, we present the statement of the former President of the Republic of North Macedonia, Stevo Pendarovski, given on TV Telma, on October 15, 2020, **“The biggest problem in our country is high corruption. In all these years, there has been no conviction for a high-ranking official or other person involved in high corruption. Those in power always look to the past and do not pay attention to what is happening today. But even in those cases, there was no effective verdict or the sentences imposed were too low”** (Taseva 2021, 19). Macedonian criminal legislation defines 24 offences addressing corruption (Arnaudovski et al., 2007).

Such a range of criminal acts that prosecute corruption in state bodies necessitated the establishment of a special state body, the **State Commission for the Prevention of Corruption (SCPC)** is tasked with monitoring, prevention, and enforcement (Law on the Prevention of Corruption, Art. 49).

1.1 Systemic Corruption Risks in Environmental Governance

Environmental governance in North Macedonia exhibits structural vulnerabilities that enable corruption at all stages: strategic planning, environmental impact assessment (EIA), permitting, and enforcement (Florozon, 2023a).

High-risk stages include:

- Strategic documents: Susceptible to political and economic influence.
- EIA process: Lack of transparency and selective reporting of expert assessments.
- Permitting: Discretionary authority allows bribery and manipulation.
- Inspection and enforcement: Limited staffing, political interference, and weak reporting undermine compliance (Florozon, 2023a; 2023b).

Together, these risks form an interconnected system of vulnerabilities that facilitate corrupt behaviour in environmental governance.

2. ANTI-CORRUPTION RISKS IN THE ENVIRONMENTAL LEGISLATIVE FRAMEWORK

Recent analyses by the State Commission for the Prevention of Corruption (DKSK, 2021) identify significant corruption-exposure points within the Law on Environment and its associated bylaws. These insights deepen the understanding of how structural vulnerabilities in the legal system facilitate corrupt behaviour related to environmental governance.

2.1 Legal instability

The Law on Environment has undergone 23 amendments, averaging one modification every seven months. Frequent amendments to the Law on Environment create opportunities for selective application and regulatory capture.

2.2 Institutional fragmentation

SCPC notes serious inconsistencies in the distribution of institutional responsibilities. For example, Article 22 requires multiple ministries to jointly issue key environmental protection acts, meaning that the objection or inaction of a single actor can freeze an entire procedure. The Law does not prescribe deadlines for inter-institutional consultation, leaving procedural gaps that can be exploited for corrupt purposes.

2.3 Transparency and public participation gaps

Provisions governing public access to environmental information—such as Article 58 and several accompanying rulebooks (2006–2007)—are outdated and inconsistent with modern transparency standards. SCPC further identifies:

- absence of clear criteria for identifying interested public;
- lack of cross-border public consultation mechanisms for Environmental Impact Assessments (EIAs);
- duplication and contradiction with the Law on Free Access to Public Information.

These defects obstruct civil oversight and create space for non-transparent decision-making.

2.4 Environmental permitting as a high-risk process

A and B Integrated Environmental Permits (Arts. 95–129) are especially vulnerable to corruption. Municipalities are bound by a 30-day deadline, yet no corresponding obligations apply to the Ministry, generating exploitable procedural asymmetries. Rulebooks regulating permitting procedures (2006, 2014, 2016) contain unclear definitions of responsibilities and do not establish minimum standards for public hearings or expert participation.

2.5 Ministerial discretion and weak oversight

The SCPC report highlights the absence of standardized criteria for appointing environmental inspectors, committee members, and agency directors. This discretionary framework allows political influence, undermines accountability, and increases systemic exposure to corruption. Outdated inspection regulations further weaken institutional control mechanisms.

2.6 Alignment with EU acquis

As part of EU accession obligations under Chapter 27, the SCPC emphasizes the need to harmonize strategic environmental assessment (SEA), environmental impact assessment (EIA), and Best Available Techniques (BAT) methodologies. Gaps in SEA, EIA, and BAT implementation undermine transparency and regulatory effectiveness (Florozone, 2023a; 2023b).

3. DEFINING CORRUPTION

As in many other scientific and social fields, there is disagreement in the conceptual definition of corruption. It is very interesting that with the adoption of the first Law on the Prevention of Corruption (Official Gazette No.28/2002), the general concept of corruption was not defined, for which the entire law was composed, but rather two whole years were waited, when with the Law on Amendments and Supplements to the Law on the Prevention of Corruption (Official Gazette No.46/2004) in Article 2, the amendment of Article 1 with Article 1-a was made, which defines corruption as: *"using one's function, public authority, official duty and position to achieve any benefit for oneself or another"*.

According to another author, *"Corruption is the abuse of official position and authority, which is based on the unlawful acquisition of material or other benefits, represented in a narrow sense, and in a broader sense – the provision and use of services, privileges, benefits, as well as bribery, i.e. abuse of office or in another way"* (Miletic, 2001).

Corruption – (lat. corruption – corruption, bribery), in a general sense, neglect and abuse of official authority for personal gain, bribery, bribing of officials. In a broader sense – all forms of abuse of official authority and position through greed (bribery, abuse of position and authority, giving and using privileges, kickbacks, receiving commissions and gifts) and in a narrower sense, the crime of giving and receiving bribes (Aleksić et al. 2004, 134).

Corruption – is the abuse of one's own or someone else's position or function for the purpose of making a profit, obtaining an advantage or gain for oneself or others (Arnaudovski et al. 2007).

According to the *Civil Convention on the Prevention of Corruption*, *"corruption" means: the solicitation, offering or acceptance, directly or indirectly, of an unlawful act or of another undue advantage or promise of such an undue advantage which interferes with the normal performance of a function or prescribed conduct of the beneficiary of the unlawful act, or of the undue advantage or promise of such an advantage* (Official Gazette No.13/2002, Article 2, p.289).

On the other hand, there are authors who define the term corruption differently: *"corruption does not describe or include putting one's fingers in the coffers, but rather treats the abuse of function, position, authorization or disabling of the process of objectively making and implementing decisions and solutions"* (Tsigaridov, 2002, 169).

"Corruption and corrupt behaviour represent a cancer - a wound and a strong blow to the normal systemic state-legal and democratic functioning of the state apparatus. As a criminal phenomenon, it has a constant tendency to spread and create incompatibility with the state-legal structure, its belittling and devaluation, and the consequences are a direct blow to moral and ethical values and the trust of citizens in the institutions of the system" (Milkovski, 2002, 184).

Certain politicians have commented on corruption in certain public appearances, each in their own way, according to the former US president *"Corruption is a cancer: a*

cancer that feeds on citizen trust in democracy, a cancer that weakens the human instinct for innovation and creativity, Joe Biden” (Arifi, 2021).

The EU Ambassador to Macedonia, Rojas, commenting on the individuals involved in politics and the judiciary in high-level corruption, says: *“I think that the Public Prosecutor’s Office should always have the opportunity, in an independent judicial system, to conduct all investigations in the event that there are allegations of possible corruption in an institution, and for this, all mechanisms should be made available to it, all in order to be able to conduct an investigation into allegations of possible corruption” (SAKAMDAKAZAM.MK. 2024).*

4. TYPES OF CORRUPTIVE BEHAVIOUR

According to the majority of authors consulted, several types of corrupt behaviour are evident, which are divided according to where they appear, and are presented as follows:

- **corruption at the lowest level (street);**
- **medium-level corruption in the economic sphere (business);**
- **corruption at the highest level (top), so-called political corruption (Фетаи, 2021)**

We find an additional division in the following forms of corruption:

- **Black** - is the corruption for which the competent courts have rendered a verdict at all levels of the previous division;
- **Gray corruption** – are those corrupt behaviours that relate to misdemeanour matters and may or may not be punished, such behaviours are: nepotism, cronyism and political patronage.
- **Nepotism** – refers to the employment and/or promotion of close relatives in the state or public administration;
- **Cronyism** – refers to the employment and/or promotion of close friends in the state or public administration;
- **Political patronage** – refers to the employment and/or promotion of party members to high positions in the state or public administration. Clientelism and patronage are related to patronage and mean providing privileges to clients, favouring certain people for the sake of protection or a certain (most often party/political) merit;
- **White** – corruption encompasses those corrupt behaviours that in certain environments, due to the cultural matrix and value concepts, are not considered immoral, and therefore are not legally sanctioned. For example, giving items of small amount or value as a sign of gratitude for a successfully completed service (in an ambulance, hospital, at the counter, etc.) (Pecova Ilievska et al. 2020).

According to a study by the Institute for Communication Studies, a chart of the Most Burning Topics Related to Environmental Corruption has been prepared, from which the risks of environmental corruption are clearly mapped (FOSM, 2022):

Chart No. 1 - Most Burning Topics Related to Environmental Corruption:

Најгорливи теми поврзани со корупција во животната средина

According to this graph, at the very top are the construction mafia, air pollution from industrial complexes, illegal construction, and next to them are the misuse of mineral resources, illegal logging, construction in protected areas, and the opening of mines. Of course, the less risky categories of environmental corruption are also listed here, but no less significant, because this is a survey to which citizens responded.

Of course, in terms of divisions or forms of corruption, there are other types, but for the needs of the work, we believe that these are quite sufficient.

4.1 Corruption scenarios in environmental procedures

Recent assessments highlight several recurring corruption scenarios that undermine the integrity of environmental decision-making in North Macedonia. These scenarios reveal that corruption is not limited to individual wrongdoing but is embedded within procedural weaknesses, administrative discretion, and institutional fragmentation.

A common corruption scheme involves the manipulation of EIA reports, political interference in inspections, non-transparent public participation, and preferential treatment in permitting (Florozone, 2023a; 2023b).

5. PHENOMENOLOGY OF CORRUPTION IN THE ENVIRONMENT

Corruption in environmental governance involves employees, inspectors, judiciary, and politicians. Techniques include bribery, forgery, concealment of crimes, reassignment, and impunity through statutes of limitations. Examples include:

- **An employee forged permits for cutting wood – has charged 200 euros per truck** (Petrovska Rajović, 2024). An employee of PE Makedonski Shumi in Strumica issued forged wood-cutting permits for 12,000 denars per truckload to those transporting unstamped firewood, committing "abuse of official position", "forgery of an official document", and "embezzlement in office", causing a loss of 186,200 denars to the Subsidiary "Belasica".
- **Criminal case for an employee of "National Forests" forging an official document** (Makfax 2024). In July 2023, a clerk at PE National Forests, Karadžica – Skopje, falsified a delivery document, reporting 4 cubic meters of firewood while the truck carried a much larger amount.
- **Charges filed against the head of the Galičica Forestry Department and another person for felling an oak tree** (OHRIDPRES 2024). The Galičica Regional Forestry Department filed charges against an employee for "abuse of official position and authority" related to forest destruction (Art. 226 CC), causing damage of 1,434,510 denars.
- **Major action against wood thieves: Criminal charges for abuse of official position, obstruction of justice...**(2024). Criminal charges were filed against five individuals—three from Valandovo Forest Police and two from PE "National Forests" – Salandžak Valandovo—for "abuse of official position and authority" (Art. 353) and "obstruction of justice" (Art. 368-a). They had previously committed similar offences on three occasions without being detected.

Experts warn that pollution from industrial complexes can have severe consequences; accidents, especially on a large scale, pose a threat to land, rivers, lakes, groundwater, and human health, with flotation tailings ponds often referred to as "**flotation atomic bombs**" due to their potential environmental and health risks (Kostadinov et al., 2012). Perpetrators are often motivated by illegally acquired profits, while state representatives may be influenced by material or immaterial benefits, rights, privileges, or employment.

High-level corruption cases, such as the no-confidence vote of judges in the Republic Judicial Council and the president of the State Commission for the Prevention of Corruption, highlight systemic weaknesses in public office integrity, selection processes, and accountability. Although only the second case directly relates to environmental issues, both demonstrate how influence, impunity, and procedural delays allow corruption to persist, undermining public trust.

Networks of corruption involve coordinated activities affecting prosecution, judiciary, and public administration, often leading to impunity through legal loopholes, evidence gaps, reduced sentences, and statute of limitations. These examples illustrate that while many corrupt activities are known and sometimes investigated, the investigation and judicial processes are frequently compromised, resulting in cases ending without convictions.

The above-mentioned examples, and of course the 2020 SCPC Report supported by the OSCE, detect the weak points in the environment through which the "Rules of the Game" are circumvented:

- A broad legal framework and many sub-sectors that are differently aligned with European legislation, which leaves room to “turn a blind eye” to the full application of environmental standards;
- Insufficient implementation of the legislation;
- Impunity for corrupt behaviour, when the legislation is not applied at all;
- Different interpretations of the conditions and required documents;
- Delayed application of environmental measures for certain companies;
- Political influence and pressures from the private sector for delayed implementation of environmental permits and other environmental protection documents (Pushevski, 2024)

In addition to what has been presented by us about the causes and phenomenology of this phenomenon, we believe that there are still specific indicators that have not been discovered.

6. PREVENTION OF FUTURE CRIMINAL ACTIVITIES

Preventive mechanisms against corruption in environmental governance include trainings, workshops, media campaigns, short films, and highlighting prosecuted cases to demonstrate consequences. Strengthening public participation is essential: transparent access to Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA) and Strategic Environmental Assessment (SEA) documents, environmental permits, and inspection reports allows citizens meaningful engagement. Public hearings should be inclusive and well-advertised, while civil society organizations can monitor, provide legal support, and participate in oversight (Florozon, 2023b).

Secure and confidential reporting channels—such as hotlines, online platforms, and whistleblower protections—enable reporting without fear of retaliation. Capacity-building for local authorities, inspectors, and civil society enhances understanding of roles and responsibilities, ensuring governance is transparent, accountable, and resilient. Preventive activities should also target education, local communities, border regions, and employees within environmental, police, judicial, and penal institutions. By combining these measures, the deterrence effect is strengthened, and opportunities for corruption and environmental harm are significantly reduced (Marjanović, 2003; Sajkova Zafirovska, 2024; Florozon, 2023b).

7. CONSEQUENCES OF THE IMPACTS OF CORRUPTION ON THE ENVIRONMENT

Despite preventive mechanisms, corruption continues to profoundly affect environmental governance. Public officials responsible for legal action in environmental cases are often influenced through personal or family ties to polluting entities. Polluters exert pressure via politicians, claiming that punishment would cause mass job losses and social instability, while making substantial financial contributions disguised as donations or sponsorships. This allows officials to accumulate wealth far beyond that of ordinary citizens, often laundered through domestic or international investments. Notably, after nearly 35 years of independence, the Law on the Origin of Acquired Property has still not been passed—and as things stand, it is unlikely to be enacted for the next 135 years.

All participants in the fight against corruption must approach their work with the utmost seriousness, ensuring that processes progress efficiently toward court verdicts. This does not imply haste or superficiality, nor should it involve omissions, mistakes, or illegal

actions that allow perpetrators to evade responsibility. Such failures only enable the continuation of similar criminal activities in the environmental sector.

Meanwhile, citizens bear the most direct consequences: landslides, floods causing material damage and loss of life, pollution of air, water, and soil, and contamination of food. These factors increase mortality, cause diseases in humans, plants, and animals, and contribute to rising rates of malignant and unexplained health problems, particularly in highly polluted areas such as Skopje, Veles, Bitola, Kavadarci, and Negotino. These impacts strain the country's health, social, economic, and financial systems. According to UNICEF's *Breathless Beginnings* report (2024), air pollution in North Macedonia claims approximately 5,000 lives annually, comparable to wartime casualties (Mirčevska Jovanović et al., 2024).

Persistent corruption undermines public trust in institutions and disproportionately affects marginalized communities, highlighting social inequities and environmental injustice (Florozon, 2023b). Presenting this stark picture of environmental degradation and corruption underscores the urgent need for officials to responsibly perform the duties for which they are compensated by citizens' taxes.

CONCLUSIONS

If the main goal of the paper is to sublimate the impacts of corruption on the environment and through it an attempt is made to bring these activities closer to the scientific and professional public, the student population and the youth, but at the same time to reach every citizen of the country and the non-governmental sector, then this goal has been achieved by preparing the paper. It is precisely this goal that has enabled us to present more publicly available and research data that directly and indirectly improve our picture of the phenomenon that, from a professional perspective, has unimaginable and invaluable consequences. On the other hand, we sincerely hope that this paper would be an occasion and reason for future larger, more comprehensive, more detailed and certainly longer-term multi-scientific research. If, at least a little, we have raised awareness among the people who are directly responsible for the care and prevention of criminal activities in the environment and especially on corruption in it, then our goal has been achieved. But at the same time, raising awareness among the scientific and research population through our actualization of this problem and raising it to a higher level. The third element is raising awareness among citizens and civil society organizations regarding corruption and its impact on the environment. In order for all of this to be achievable, the following is necessary. No conclusion can be complete, but still, preventing and eliminating this phenomenon of environmental corruption must start from the youngest age so that it can continue throughout life. Namely, it is necessary to actively include topics of environmental protection and protection from corrupt activities from preschool age and then in school age from primary and secondary education, which would be upgraded in higher education, where all curricula would include subjects of environmental protection and measures and activities against corrupt activities. On the other hand, it is necessary to strengthen the controls, supervision and capacities of the competent inspection bodies, develop standard operating procedures for dealing with immediate harmful consequences, their connection and harmonization of activities with other bodies, expeditiousness and cooperation with other competent bodies in the field, leaving no possibility of omission of their legal activities in order to protect anyone's personal interests because there would be responsibility for the same. At the same time, it is necessary to tighten the penal policy that

would reflect both on the perpetrators and on the competent investigative and judicial bodies, which in any way and with any action help and enable the perpetrators not to be punished or to receive some symbolic punishment. Perhaps the most important thing is to unite the non-governmental sector, increase its cooperation so that evidence that has not been collected by the state authorities, which are obliged to do so, can be provided in a timely, accurate and appropriate manner, and to mobilize the public in a timely manner, which, through appropriate pressure, will force the state authorities to implement their legal competencies for which they were formed and paid, while at the same time assuming an obligation under international ratified conventions to act appropriately and provide information.

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DISRUPTIVE TECHNOLOGIES – CHALLENGES AND IMPLICATIONS FOR INTERNATIONAL LEGAL NORMS AND SECURITY OPERATIONS

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Abstract

The rapid advancement of disruptive technologies—such as artificial intelligence, autonomous systems, quantum computing, and cyber capabilities—is fundamentally reshaping the global security landscape and challenging the foundations of international legal norms. This paper explores the complex interplay between emerging technologies and the evolving missions of security services, with a particular focus on the legal, ethical, and operational dilemmas they introduce.

As state and non-state actors increasingly integrate disruptive technologies into defence, intelligence, and law enforcement strategies, traditional frameworks of international law—especially those governing sovereignty, the use of force, and human rights—are being tested. The paper critically examines how these technologies blur the lines between war and peace, civilian and combatant, and domestic and international spheres of action. It also investigates the adequacy of existing legal instruments in regulating novel threats such as autonomous weapons systems, algorithmic surveillance, and cyber operations.

Drawing on interdisciplinary research and recent case studies, the paper argues for a proactive and adaptive legal approach that balances innovation with accountability. It highlights the need for international cooperation, normative clarity, and institutional reform to ensure that security services can operate effectively while upholding the rule of law in an increasingly complex technological environment.

Key words: disruptive technologies, international law, conflict

1. INTRODUCTION

Geopolitical rivalries have not only led to a new arms race but have also provoked a global technology race. Technology will be the main feature of competition in the new geopolitical environment. A handful of critical and foundational technologies like AI, quantum, biotech, robotics, and hypersonic are key inputs for both long-term economic growth, and military pre-eminence. As such, technology diffusion for commercial purposes must be reconciled with more rigid technology ecosystems to advance national security objectives (European Commission & High Representative of the Union for Foreign Affairs and Security Policy, 2025).

Even the European Parliament report states that “Emerging disruptive technologies (EDTs) can potentially revolutionize warfare”. EDTs for military purposes are being developed globally, in particular in China, Russia and the US. This has led to an arms race in their weaponization, raising important ethical and legal concerns (Clapp, 2022). This confirms that disruptive technologies are not a distant future, but an emerging reality.

NATO stands at a crossroads where rapid adoption of cutting-edge technologies will determine its strategic edge. Modern conflicts, as seen in Ukraine, highlight how dual-use innovations—AI-powered logistics, cloud computing, cybersecurity, jamming, decentralized energy, and low-cost drones—are reshaping warfare. A tech race is now underway between autocratic and democratic regimes (DIGITALEUROPE, 2025).

At their meeting in February 2025, NATO Defence Ministers approved NATO’s Updated Defence Production Action Plan. NATO’s Rapid Adoption Action Plan substantially accelerates the adoption and integration of new technological products for defence, across all military domains. Allies commit to expedite adoption procedures, including fast-track procurement, and to allocate adequate resources to that end (NATO, 2025). Rapid Adoption Action Plan, including its political commitment and pilots, aims to significantly accelerate the pace at which the Alliance adopts new technological products, in general to within a maximum of 24 months. To accelerate the integration of new technological products into Allied Armed Forces, the Alliance will have to ensure that concept and doctrine development occurs at a commensurate pace. This needs to be anchored in a deliberate approach to transform the Alliance’s forces (NATO, 2025).

2. INTERNATIONAL LAW AND SECURITY OPERATIONS IN TRANSFORMED OPERATIVE ENVIRONMENT

In the era of technological expansion, disruptive technologies represent a fundamental challenge to existing international legal norms and security operations. These technologies not only change the way states wage war, communicate, and manage risks, but also call into question the capacity of international law to regulate new forms of power and influence.

The delineation of disruptive technologies as a security and operational term is a relatively recent phenomenon. However, although the term “disruptive technologies” is relatively new within the international community, this does not mean that their de facto existence and usage, or at least for some part of it has not already been regulated or addressed in an international context. For instance, international humanitarian law contains numerous provisions aimed at protecting civilian objects or dual-use facilities (such as hospitals, dams, and water supply systems), and while it does not explicitly classify them as disruptive technologies, they are de facto treated as such, which is why they enjoy special protection. Within the sources of international law, it is difficult to identify specific norms that address disruptive technologies as such.

In the context of national law, the situation is much simpler if an individual state directly regulates the matter of interest. However, it is still a matter of pioneering among states.

The scope of legal dilemmas and the range of perspectives on issues related to the use of disruptive technologies are vast. Understanding the many complexities involved in creating legal frameworks for regulating the use of disruptive technologies begins with understanding the environment and the benefits brought by technological progress, as all areas are continuously evolving. Therefore, the legal landscape is in constant flux. Many

legal and operational issues are currently amorphous and still developing, while technology does not wait.

Approaching the potential for definition of disruptive technologies, it is critically important to note that such technologies themselves might not be considered as disruptive per se – but the potential for (mis)use or unregulated use is huge.

The NATO report *Science & Technology Trends 2020–2040* stated that “emerging” refers to technologies that are expected to mature between 2020 and 2040 and whose effects are not expected to affect the alliance’s defence, security, and enterprise functions, while “disruptive” refers to technologies that will have a revolutionary impact. Yet the technologies that the report later outlines are not categorized in line with these descriptions. NATO defines nine technology priorities as EDTs, with no distinction between emerging and disruptive. These are artificial intelligence (AI), data, autonomy, quantum-enabled technologies, biotechnology, hypersonic technologies, space, novel materials and manufacturing, and energy and propulsion (Ricart, 2023).

International law has four vital functions: to precisely define the narrowly limited cases in which the use of force is permitted (self-defence and the preservation or restoration of world peace and security, in accordance with the Charter); to regulate and control the use of force even in situations where it is permitted; to assess whether the force that has been used was unlawful; and to regulate the consequences of the use of force, whether lawful or unlawful. Considering these four vital functions, and the fact that international law regulates the use of force through a prohibition on its use and exceptions to that prohibition, the efforts to maintain world peace and security have produced four aspects for regulating the use of force in international law. For all four aspects, the same sources of law apply in accordance with Article 38 of the ICJ Statute: international treaties, international customary law, state practice, the opinions of distinguished jurists, and judicial practice. The first of the four mentioned aspects is *ius contra bellum*, that is, the law against war or against the use of armed force. The second aspect is the body of legal rules known as *ius ad bellum* (“the right to war”), which regulates when a state or states may legally resort to the use of force. The third aspect is the body of legal rules known as *ius in bello*, which governs the principles, standards, and regulations that apply once force has already been used and an active conflict is taking place. The fourth aspect is *ius post bellum*, or the principles, standards, and obligations that apply after the end of major hostilities. Use of disruptive technologies can potentially challenge all four vital functions in different ways. The international legal position of security, at the current stage of development, lies primarily and fundamentally within the United Nations system of collective security. As contexts have shifted and new security challenges have emerged, so too has the need developed for new legal rules or the application of existing ones in a different context. In the absence of a built consensus at the level of an international treaty, states attempt to adhere to customary law or resort to analogy. At the heart of the norm are informal agreements among states and practices accumulated over time, while negotiations may later lead to formal and enforceable international treaties. Until then, the norms function as informal and non-binding standards of behaviour. Besides the absence of more concrete norms, the potential for their implementation in a landscape that goes beyond sovereignty and jurisdiction makes everything far more complicated (Poposka, 2022).

While the primary subjects of IHL are the parties to an armed conflict, the rules on the conduct of hostilities—notably the rules of distinction, proportionality and precautions in attack—are addressed to those who plan, decide upon and carry out an attack.

The core legal obligations for a commander or operator in the use of weapon systems include (anyhow) the following: to ensure distinction between military objectives and civilian objects, combatants and civilians, and active combatants and those hors de combat; to determine whether the attack may be expected to cause incidental civilian casualties and damage to civilian objects, or a combination thereof, which would be excessive in relation to the concrete and direct military advantage anticipated, as required by the rule of proportionality; and to cancel or suspend an attack if it becomes apparent that the target is not a military objective or is subject to special protection, or that the attack may be expected to violate the rule of proportionality, as required by the rules on precautions in attack (Davison, 2018).

Although international law has developed a robust framework to regulate the use of force and maintain collective security, the use of disruptive technologies for security and military purposes remains largely unregulated per se. Unlike traditional categories of weapons or military means, disruptive technologies are not defined by a singular legal classification, but rather by their very nature, which destabilizes existing norms and practices. This absence of explicit regulation does not necessarily imply a legal vacuum; instead, it highlights the difficulty of fitting rapidly evolving technologies into rigid normative frameworks. The disruptive character of such technologies stems from their capacity to blur established distinctions—between civilian and military domains, between peace and conflict, and between conventional and unconventional means of warfare. Therefore, it is not the fact of their use alone, but the manner in which they alter operational, strategic, and legal environments that renders them disruptive. Traditional international law mechanisms, grounded in treaty law and customary practices, struggle to keep pace with these transformations, as consensus-building lags behind technological innovation. In practice, this means that disruptive technologies challenge the adequacy of existing regimes such as *ius contra bellum*, *ius ad bellum*, and *ius in bello*. While these regimes regulate the use of force in principle, they do not specifically anticipate technologies that can reshape the very conditions under which force is deployed. As a result, the regulation of disruptive technologies stays implicit, indirect, and highly dependent on analogies drawn from broader international law principles, rather than explicit, detailed norms tailored to their unique characteristics.

The General Assembly's resolution 79/239, adopted in December 2024, had already affirmed that international law applies throughout the life cycle of military AI (United Nations General Assembly, 2024).

3. THE LANDSCAPE OF EMERGING DISRUPTIVE TECHNOLOGIES

The emerging disruptive technologies not only change the way operations are conducted but also pose serious challenges to the application of international law and principles of the law of armed conflict. In essence, the technological landscape is not merely technical, it is legal, ethical, and geopolitical. And while states compete to be the first in the technological race, international law struggles to run behind them, hoping to catch up before it is too late. Defence innovation and disruption no longer primarily stem from military labs, but from the usage the Armed Forces make of civil applications and services developed and marketed by private high-tech companies (European Defence Agency, 2023).

Emerging technologies such as AI are widely regarded to be a crucial element of future military effectiveness and advantage. The possession of cutting-edge militarily

relevant technologies equals more effective weapons systems, which in turn results in greater military power, which in turn translates into greater geopolitical power. In doing so, the utility of AI in military affairs seems virtually endless—from real-time analysis of sophisticated cyberattacks and detection of fraudulent imagery to directing autonomous platforms such as drones, to new forms of command and control such as automated battle management systems that analyse big data and provide recommendations for human action (Raska, 2019). It is highly likely that revealing the existence of new weapons during a crisis casts a shadow over modern great power competition and changes how states perceive the balance of military power. This shadow makes it difficult for the national security enterprise to align ends, ways, and means in pursuit of integrated deterrence (Jensen, Atalan, Mutlu, & Macias, 2024).

The European Defence Fund (EDF) Regulation defines a disruptive technology for defence as an 'enhanced or completely new technology that brings about a radical change, including a paradigm shift in the concept and conduct of defence affairs such as by replacing existing defence technologies or rendering them obsolete' (European Parliament & Council of the European Union, 2021). The European Defence Agency (EDA) identifies six particularly disruptive technologies: quantum-based technologies; artificial intelligence (AI); robotics and autonomous weapons systems; big data analytics; hypersonic weapons systems and space technologies; and new advanced materials (European Defence Agency, 2023).

In February 2021, NATO Defence Ministers endorsed “Foster and Protect: NATO’s Coherent Implementation Strategy on Emerging and Disruptive Technologies.” This is NATO’s overarching strategy to guide its relationship to EDTs. It has two main areas of focus:

fostering a coherent approach to the development and adoption of dual-use technologies (i.e., technologies that are focused on commercial markets and uses but also have defence and security applications) that will strengthen the Alliance’s technological edge, and creating a forum for Allies to help protect themselves from the use of EDTs by hostile actors, and protect their own EDTs and innovation ecosystems from interference and manipulation by potential adversaries and competitors.

This includes nine priority technology areas: artificial intelligence (AI), autonomous systems, quantum technologies, biotechnology and human enhancement technologies, space, hypersonic systems, novel materials and manufacturing, energy and propulsion, next-generation communications networks (The diffusion of hypersonic technology is under way in Europe, Japan, Australia, and India — with other nations beginning to explore such technology. Proliferation could cross multiple borders if hypersonic technology is offered on world markets (Morgan & Cohen, 2020).

In extremely dynamic security environment, disruptive technologies offer security and intelligence services strategic advantages that significantly transform the way information is collected, processed, and utilized, as well as the way operations are conducted. From autonomous drones to threat prediction systems, AI is already playing a role in military operations, intelligence, and data analysis. In everyday operations, AI can prove to be a useful tool in logistics and maintenance. It can optimize maintenance schedules by predicting equipment failures and streamlining supply chains, ensuring military assets are always ready to be deployed (FlySight, 2025).

The geopolitical significance of AI systems has gained increasing attention at EU level, where they are viewed as a key instrument of economic, political, and military

influence. This aspect has been particularly relevant in recent debates on enhancing Europe's 'strategic autonomy' and 'technological sovereignty', aligning with initiatives led by the current European Commission, which positions itself as 'geopolitical'. This focus is unsurprising, given the complexities of integrating critical technologies such as military AI into European security and defence frameworks. In recent years, the Commission has expanded its role in defence through market-driven and industrial initiatives aimed at enhancing the competitiveness and innovation of the European defence technological and industrial base (EDTIB). Additionally, it has increasingly integrated civilian science, technology, and innovation programs with the EU's security and defence policies, particularly in advancing critical dual-use technologies (European Parliamentary Research Service, 2025).

IMPLICATIONS FOR SECURITY OPERATIONS

Conceptually, changes in the security environment can be viewed in several ways, but they converge as: expanded, deepened, and multidimensional. Expansion refers to the increase in non-military threats, deepening to the evolution of existing threats, and multidimensionality to their interconnection and the influence of growing external factors. Armed forces face the challenge of having to adapt, develop, and innovate in order to adjust to an ambiguous, complex, and rapidly changing environment, often positioned in the grey zone between war and peace. Additionally, in order to meet the demands of the new era, they must drastically broaden their partnerships and open themselves to civil society. If the period between the end of the Second World War and the fall of the Berlin Wall was characterized by relative stability and predictability, the subsequent half-century we are living in and will continue to live through is a time of exceptional instability. In this context, disruptive technologies pose both a threat and a possibility for the operation of security services. New and disruptive technologies can be categorized as support, combat, and universal. Within the support category, of special significance are supercomputing and quantum technologies, which may increase productivity, including in research and design. Support technologies also include space-based assets (including 'mega constellations') employed for remote sensing, communication, or spacecraft surveillance; they can also be used to assist the targeting of offensive or defensive strikes against objects on land, in the sea, in the atmosphere, and eventually in orbit. Combat disruptive technologies include hypersonic ramjet engines (scramjets) and other types of propulsion systems that could become the basis for next-generation missiles, including (ultra-)long-range cruise missiles and anti-ship missiles, and those that could also be used as elements of guided re-entry vehicles of ballistic missiles (intercontinental and otherwise). Universal, fundamentally complex technologies include machine-learning for big data analysis and AI technologies in logistics (Stefanovich, 2025).

CONCLUSION

The exponential rise of disruptive technologies—ranging from autonomous weapons and quantum computing to biotechnology and cyber capabilities—has outpaced the evolution of international legal norms. On the other hand, in today's armed conflicts these technologies represent tactical-operational superiority. Science-based engineering, from fortifications to artillery and from communications to surveillance, has always assisted warfare (Suzen, 2020). Achieving this balance, between market-driven interests and global benefits, will require a multifaceted approach. The absence of a universally

accepted definition of autonomous weapons systems (AWS) remains one of the most pressing legal lacunae in the regulation of artificial intelligence in warfare. Despite ongoing deliberations within the framework of the United Nations and the Convention on

Certain Conventional Weapons (CCW), the lack of consensus has resulted in a fragmented normative landscape. This definitional ambiguity not only impedes the development of binding legal instruments but also enables states to exploit loopholes for strategic advantage. The principle of meaningful human control has emerged as a normative safeguard against the dehumanization of warfare. However, its operationalization remains inconsistent and largely rhetorical. Without codified standards mandating human oversight in the deployment, targeting, and decision-making processes of AI-enabled systems, the risk of algorithmic warfare devoid of moral agency becomes alarmingly real. The erosion of human judgment in life-and-death decisions undermines the foundational principles of international humanitarian law (IHL), particularly distinction, proportionality, and precaution. The diffusion of responsibility across developers, operators, and states in the context of autonomous systems presents a profound challenge to legal accountability. Current frameworks lack the granularity to attribute liability in cases of malfunction, unintended harm, or violations of IHL. The creation of a multilateral accountability regime—encompassing legal, ethical, and technical dimensions—is imperative to ensure that the deployment of autonomous systems does not operate in a normative vacuum. Quantum computing introduces a paradigm shift in encryption, surveillance, and strategic stability. The absence of a legal framework governing quantum advantage risks entrenching a new form of technological hegemony, wherein states with quantum capabilities dominate the informational and strategic domains.

This asymmetry threatens to destabilize existing deterrence models and erode trust in multilateral security arrangements. The normative architecture surrounding privacy and surveillance is fundamentally incompatible with the capabilities of quantum technologies. Existing human rights instruments, such as the ICCPR and the European Convention on Human Rights, lack provisions that anticipate the quantum disruption of data protection. The development of quantum-specific privacy standards is essential to safeguard individual rights in an era of pervasive and potentially unbreakable surveillance. Biotechnological advancements, particularly in synthetic biology and genetic engineering, pose dual-use risks that blur the line between civilian and military applications. The Biological Weapons Convention (BWC), while foundational, is outdated and insufficiently equipped to regulate emerging biotechnologies. The absence of a global oversight mechanism for dual-use research exacerbates the risk of weaponization and misuse, especially in contexts lacking transparency and ethical scrutiny.

Policymakers and hyper-scalers (i.e. Big Tech companies) today face the urgent task of learning from these precedents to ensure that disruptive technologies serve humanity's best interests. This includes nurturing global collaboration to prevent an arms race in AI or quantum applications, embedding ethics and accountability into their design, and developing safe and certified standards paths to protect vital services (Martino, 2025). An interdisciplinary approach would contribute to a better understanding of the co-production of material and social dimensions, as well as the entanglement between innovation, security, war, and global politics (Csernatoni & Martins, 2024).

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THE TERM 'WARFARE' IN A MODERN GLOBAL ENVIRONMENT

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Abstract

Within the paper, the author provides an interdisciplinary analysis of the terms "warfare", "asymmetric warfare" and "hybrid warfare". These forms of warfare have an impact on global, regional, and national security. In the final part of the paper, the author concludes: hybrid warfare is a characteristic of the 4th generation of warfare, with non-military means, such as diplomacy, economics, energy resources, information, and media are engaged to achieve goals. Terrorist organizations and criminal networks participate as the most important non-state actors. Non-state actors can have profound effects on the economic or political situation in nation-states, with the potential to exert both detrimental influence or undue control over the region. The use of asymmetric and hybrid threats arises from a disadvantageous military position, where non-state actors or weaker states must approach warfare through irregular and unexpected tactics to maintain victory.

For an effective national response to asymmetric threats, response mechanisms must be institutionalized by the national military and state institutions.

In the framework of preparing the content of the paper, the author uses the following research methods: the descriptive method, the normative method, the comparative method and the content analysis method as a special scientific method.

As a basic methodological procedure or technique for collecting data, the author uses content analysis of domestic and international references, research papers, publications, reports, conference proceedings, briefs, and analyses of various articles, journals and content analysis of websites, legal documents – regulations of the European Union, analysis of strategies, international documents, reports and Internet sources.

Keywords: warfare, asymmetric threats, hybrid warfare, state actors, non-state actors

1. INTRODUCTION

The post-Cold War period brought new low-intensity risks, such as: terrorism, civil wars, organized crime, insurgency, sabotage actions, cyber warfare, as well as other newer forms of threats, such as: warfare in urban environments, as well as the use of cruise, or ballistic missiles, to target areas that are otherwise inaccessible.

In short, post-Cold War society forced state and non-state actors to employ irregular tactics in warfare to combat the escalating arms race between opposing ideological blocs.

These conditions are directly responsible for the shift from conventional to unconventional warfare – and represent further encouragement for the use of asymmetric threats and hybrid tactics.

According to certain authors, asymmetry is an integral part of the history of society and warfare, that is, asymmetric issues have a history as long as humanity (Johnson, 2001).

In the last two decades, the buzzword "asymmetry" has been used to explain diverse and unpredictable threats that vary in intensity and common tactics and weapons (especially terrorism and crime). But when an adversary emerges that, in a planned and organized manner, simultaneously wages war symmetrically and asymmetrically, that combination necessitates a new definition: "hybrid warfare".

Scientific justification of the paper – exploring the terms "warfare", "hybrid warfare" is an important scientific content related to the struggle to tackle hybrid threats in order to achieve global stability and peace.

When preparing the paper, the author uses general methods, including descriptive, normative, comparative, and content analysis methods. The author uses the Descriptive Method – a general method that allows for a deeper insight and study of the nature of the phenomenon itself, which is the subject of the research; (this method contributes to the development of science). The subject of research is warfare, asymmetric threats, hybrid threats, etc. Dealing with these threats is an important condition for achieving global peace, security and stability.

Comparative method – the author analyses the term warfare through historical development (evolution) and comparative analysis of the terms asymmetric warfare (hybrid warfare).

Representatives from various academic disciplines are engaged in major debates over the definition of war; the types of warfare; and why wars occur.

As a basic methodological procedure or data collection technique, the author uses the analysis of the content of domestic and international references, research papers, publications, reports, conference materials, web content analysis, strategies analysis, international documents.

Through the Method of Analysis, the subject of research is broken down into its component parts, its factors, its connections and relationships in a specific space and at a specific time, thus enabling a more substantial understanding of the phenomenon being researched.

2. SCIENTIFIC DEFINITION OF THE TERMS "WAR" AND "WARFARE"

Throughout history, there has been a marked difference in the relative military, economic, political power, and warfare strategy of warring states. It is observed that the character and nature of war are changing, especially in wars between state and non-state actors.

There are major debates in academia about the definition of war; the types of warfare; and why wars happen. Representatives from various academic disciplines have separately attempted to provide answers to these questions.

War is defined as an armed conflict between two or more governments or states.

Carl von Clausewitz, a Prussian general and military theorist active during the Napoleonic Wars, provided several definitions of warfare: once as “[the] continuation of policy by other means”, while later as “...nothing but a duel on an extensive scale” and “... an act of violence intended to compel our opponent to fulfil our will” (Carl von Clausewitz, Colonel J.J. Graham, 1832).

Michael Walzer (2000), author of *Just and Unjust Wars*, defines war as “a legal state that equally permits two or more groups to engage in armed conflict” (Walzer, 2000:41).

When such conflicts become global in scope, they are known as world wars. War between different sections or factions within the same nation is called a civil war. Conflicts or wars in which major powers deliberately refrain from using all their armed power are often called limited wars (Singh, 1995). Interstate wars generally end with a treaty, and civil wars with a declaration of peace.

In the era of postmodern warfare, the character and nature of war are changing due to technological, social and cultural advances. At the same time, it is observed that warfare is dominated by the use of unconventional tactics. War and warfare have transformed from state-centric to a state where (state interest) no longer dictates combat (Creveld, 1991). Hence, there are two approaches to defining war in the postmodern era. One approach is based on technological advances and is state-centric in character. The second approach is based on the use of unconventional means and tactics and is more synonymous with non-state entities. Today, the action of a non-state actor against a state is loosely referred to as an act of asymmetric warfare. Such warfare is considered to pose a threat to become the leading instrument of strategic power (Lele, 2014).

In this context, the term asymmetry encompasses various tactics of war – fighting like guerrilla warfare, terrorism, irregular warfare, etc. these wars originate from conflicts over scarce resources, ethnic and religious issues, transnational crime (with its linkage to terrorism and insurgency), migration and illegal immigration, border disputes, famine and state collapse (Mendel, 1995-96).

"Conflict" can be described as a clash of opposing blocs, caused by ideological, territorial, economic, or other disagreements. We define the term "warfare" as "sustained, coordinated violence between political organizations" (Jack S. Levy and William R. Thompson, 2010).

This definition highlights several components of warfare.

First, war is violent. Warfare involves the use of force to kill people and destroy. This violence must be sustained to qualify as warfare, and is an exclusionary factor when classifying something as a conflict or war. Conflicts and disputes are common in international relations, but rarely do they escalate to war; such an escalation would require violence, the use of force, and then sustaining this violence for a period of time. A second component in identifying war emphasizes the "between" in our definition. Violence must be reciprocated to qualify as war; thus we treat war as the outcome of the behaviour of two or more actors.

In academic literature, warfare is classified into four distinct "generations". Each generation is characterized by a radically different strategy of warfare (Huseyin Kuru, 2018:13).

The "Classical Warfare" generation (Generation 1), and includes the Napoleonic Wars:

- The 1st generation prevails and is determined by the characteristics of the so-called Napoleonic Wars and the wars after them (the framework of the nineteenth century), where human potential and the number of armies in the conflict prevailed;

- The 2nd generation, which roughly dates back to the time around World War I (the first decade of the twentieth century), where the dominance was on the side of technology and technical innovations in armaments, i.e. firepower;

"All Along with Industry" (Generation 2), includes World War I: the Industrial Revolution and the wider availability of railways led to auxiliary and infantry units;

- The 3rd generation – "Manoeuvring wars" (Generation 3) – this is the era from World War II to the mid-1980s, where the dominant component was the ability to

manoeuvre; It is identified with the concept of national security developed by the United States in response to the terrorist attacks of September 11, 2001, aimed at non-governmental organizations (Hezbollah, Hamas, Al Qaeda).

The 4th generation represents the coordinated and simultaneous use of nonviolent and violent forms of civil protest, combined with special operations, with the intensive use of political, economic and social instruments, to break the enemy's combat capabilities, the morale of the organizational system. According to this theory, classical state conflicts have become a relic of the past.

This generation of wars is associated with the emergence of "Unconventional Wars" (including the aftermath of September 11 and the wars in Afghanistan and Iraq) (Renz, B., and Smith H., 2016:5).

As confirmed above, the fourth generation deviates considerably from the tactics of previous wars and encompasses asymmetric and hybrid methods unique to modern conflict.

This focuses on the ability of weaker forces to combine conventional and irregular tactics to pose a legitimate threat to the political will of the adversary. As such, fourth generation (which represents hybrid warfare) does not seek to win by defeating the enemy's military forces, but rather through hybrid tactics aimed at the enemy's political will (Mitrović, 2017).

Today, the modern geopolitical scene is a testing ground for hybrid warfare and its concept is very close to the 4th generation of warfare, - non-military means, such as diplomacy, economics, energy, information and intensive use of the media are engaged to achieve goals.

At the same time, current conflicts (hybrid wars) can also be called 5th generation of conflicts – although there is no clearly defined position of the scientific community, due to the increased form of conflict and the achieved deviation from 4th generation wars.

In the mid-20th century, British strategic theorist B.H. Liddell Hart advocated an "indirect approach" to strategy and determined that the wisest strategy avoids an enemy's strength and examines weakness (and exploits and abuses that weakness).

The complexity of the analyses of the concept of asymmetric security threats also contains deeper philosophical and socio-psychological roots.

According to Beyerchen – the very consideration of concepts such as periodicity, asymmetry, disproportionality is confusing and can cause logical repulsion, based on rootedness in cultural heritage – that is, linear concepts are far simpler and more acceptable than considerations of "unstable" concepts such as asymmetry and nonlinearity (Beyerchen, 1992).

Military historian John Keegan proposed this in his political-rational theory of war, saying that "[warfare] is assumed to be an orderly affair involving states, with declared beginnings and ends, easily identifiable combatants, and a high level of obedience on the part of subordinates" (Keegan, 1993). According to Keegan, this theory deals poorly with non-state and unconventional tactics.

Unlike nation-states (in the upper echelons of military spending), weaker parties to a conflict must bypass direct attacks in favour of unexpected tactics, due to their own shortcomings as well as the superiority of their adversary. These asymmetric approaches employ innovative, non-traditional tactics and weapons or technologies that are irregular in nature (Brzica, 2018:34).

3. SCIENTIFIC DEFINITION OF THE TERM ASYMMETRIC WARFARE

Asymmetry means the absence of a common basis for comparison in terms of some quality or, in operational terms, capability. All conflicts are asymmetrical to some extent, and the skilled fighter has always exploited this characteristic.

In war, there are always differences between the opponents. Sometimes, those differences are insignificant, fleeting – with no impact on the outcome.

There are situations in which the differences between opponents are important, putting one at an advantage and the other at a disadvantage. This is a very simple observation, but it raises one of the burning questions – and that is STRATEGIC ASYMMETRY:

Strategic asymmetry is the use of some difference to gain an advantage over the opponent. This is an idea as old as warfare itself (which appears in numerous forms, guises) (See: https://repository.ukim.mk/bitstream/20.500.12188/2308/1/acvetanovska2019_1.pdf).

Among strategic theorists, Sun Tzu Wu establishes "The basic concept of asymmetric warfare is a model through which a technologically and numerically weaker opponent enables the infliction of losses on the opposing side, presenting results in order to promote their views and goals, with the aim of motivating new like-minded people". According to this theorist, conducting indirect forms of warfare is one of the most effective ways to combat the enemy (Sun Tzu, 2000:9).

Asymmetric warfare can be defined as: "a form of warfare in which a non-state actor uses unconventional means and tactics against a state's vulnerabilities to achieve disproportionate effect, undermining the state's will to achieve its strategic goals".

Steven Metz, an American national security expert at the US Army War College, defines "asymmetry" as "acting, organizing, and thinking differently from adversaries to maximize relative strengths, exploit an adversary's weaknesses, or gain greater freedom of action" (Metz, S., Johnson, 2001).

Asymmetric warfare can be defined as: "a form of warfare in which a non-state actor uses unconventional means and tactics against a state's vulnerabilities to achieve disproportionate effect, undermining the state's will to achieve its strategic goals".

The successful asymmetric tactics used by non-state actors over the past few decades demonstrate that asymmetric warfare is a contest of wills. Psychological defeat is often much more serious and longer-lasting than battlefield defeat. The easiest way to achieve this is to attack the enemy where he feels most comfortable and secure (Goulding, 2000-01).

The goal is to achieve an advantage or defeat the enemy without directly engaging one's military operatives and expending one's own resources, which would inevitably cause direct conflict.

One of the main characteristics of asymmetric threats – avoiding the classical method of warfare – is seen in the fact that the organizers – the subjects of asymmetric action (organization, groups, states) avoid, through their actions, entering into a direct, open armed conflict with the state that is the target of the action. It acts indirectly – through the application of new tactics and the development of operational capabilities, as well as the use of technical and unconventional means.

These actions are coordinated, synchronized, and directed at the vulnerabilities, or weaknesses, of the chosen target. They can be directed at any domain of society – political, economic, military, civilian, or informational. Vulnerability is a qualitative characteristic of a state, which reflects the likelihood that the state will be attacked or harmed.

Based on certain analyses, it is possible to conditionally determine the determinants of asymmetric warfare: (Mitrović, 2017).

- an asymmetric threat to security is represented by phenomena that are new, unusual, surprising and unexpected threats;
- asymmetric threats are conditioned by the position and attitudes of certain nation states according to global foreign and security policy;
- the environment for the development of asymmetric threats is conditioned by the circumstances faced by institutions in the state – circumstances that have an impact on international security relations.
- the classical, conventional approach to organizing the defence and security system of a state (in the current dynamic movement) is relatively outdated and shows organizational weaknesses and shortcomings in the security system and the defence system; hence latent institutional weaknesses emerge in the current, classical way of responding to security threats and is predominantly focused on preventing and eliminating consequences, and less on prevention and building a protection system. According to certain authors, asymmetry aims to disrupt security forces – using their weaknesses – with an asymmetric approach based on psychological effects.
- the existence and application of new tactics and development of operational capabilities as well as technical and unconventional means of action by the adversary.

One of the main characteristics of asymmetric threats is to avoid the classical method of warfare, which is perceived through the fact that the organizers, the subjects of asymmetric action (the organization, the states) avoid, through their actions, entering into a direct, open armed conflict with the state that is the target of the action. There are situations when the bearers of asymmetric action are organized, supported or directed by other sponsoring states, acting against the victim state (according to perceived weaknesses in society, socio-economic and political life, as well as individual critical weak points of a particular state's infrastructure or defence and security system) (Mitrović, 2017).

In this way, the bearer of the asymmetric actions is placed in a position to implement the hybrid form of warfare that the sponsor implements, and they become an intermediary in the pursuit of other people's interests.

Practically, the asymmetric approach is based on exploiting an opponent's weakness, using innovative, non-traditional tactics, weapons and technology, and can be applied at all levels and types of warfare - strategic, operational and tactical, as well as across the entire spectrum of military operations (Staff, 1992:2). Asymmetric threats involve a variety of tactics, including disinformation campaigns, terrorism, and cyberattacks.

Asymmetric threats include a variety of tactics, including disinformation campaigns, terrorism, and cyberattacks. Importantly, these tactics exist under the threshold for conventional conflict while still de-stabilizing governments, alliances, or organizations (Beaulieu, and Salvo, 2018:1).

According to the Ministry of Defence in Serbia, certain characteristics are inherently asymmetric: 1. 2. 3. 4. 5. considered unusual from a conventional point of view (i.e. torture); irregular in the sense that they violate treaties or laws of armed conflict; depart from war as previously understood, (as in flying planes into buildings); leveraged or specialized against assets; difficult to respond to proportionally, creating a situation where

military intervention in response seems inhumane or cruel; 6. having unforeseen circumstances, typical of an event or attack not previously used. (Ćurčić, 2018).

Stephen Blank, a senior fellow at the Foreign Policy Research Institute, offers another interpretation of asymmetry, called "Blank's Theory" (Stephen Blank, 2020).

Blank's theory classifies asymmetric threats into five dimensions: 1. "they are threats of an unconventional nature; 2. 3. 4. 5. they are designed to mislead the adversary; they can be used by both state and non-state actors; they do not imply confrontation; and; they reflect the adversary's strategy". In both scenarios, these tactics are completely flexible, and create military action that is unpredictable, irregular, and difficult to combat.

4. SCIENTIFIC DEFINITION OF THE TERM HYBRID WARFARE

Hybrid warfare exists alongside asymmetric threats, mixing conventional and irregular tactics. In this sense, hybrid warfare "... combines military and non-military means, as well as covert and overt means, including disinformation, cyber-attacks, economic pressure [and] the deployment of irregular armed groups and the use of regular forces (Beaulieu and Salvo, 2018).

Franck Hoffman, a Distinguished Research Fellow with the Institute for National Strategic Studies, builds on this definition: he argues that hybrid warfare incorporates different modes of warfare (both conventional and asymmetric capabilities), thereby utilizing synergistic efforts that are simultaneous, fused, and subordinate to one command unit (Hoffman, 2007:8).

According to some military experts, this unconventional theatre of conflict can further be described as the "Gray Zone" of warfare, characterized by "...intense political, economic, informational and military competition more fervent than steady-state diplomacy, yet short of conventional war", and employing "small-footprint, low-visibility operations often of a covert or clandestine nature".

According to some military experts, hybrid warfare represents a "Gray Zone" of warfare, and is characterized by "...intense political, economic, informational, and military competition more fierce than steady-state diplomacy, yet less so than conventional warfare" and which utilizes "small-scale, low-visibility operations, often of a covert nature" (Joseph L. Votel, Charles T. Cleveland, Charles T. Connett, and Will Irwin, 2016:102).

The London-based International Institute for Strategic Studies in 2015 gave the following definition of "hybrid warfare": "The use of military and non-military instruments in an integrated campaign to achieve surprise, seize initiative, and gain psychological advantage used in diplomatic actions; large-scale and rapid information, electronic, and cyber operations; covert and covert military and intelligence activities; combined with economic pressure". The definition accurately reflects the key differences between hybrid wars and traditional conflicts.

The terrorist attacks of September 11 and the subsequent geopolitical consequences modelled a growing convergence of non-state and state forces. This created a void in contemporary military terminology and strategy, filled today by the widely used term "asymmetric and hybrid threats" (Ćurčić, 2018:23).

According to political experts, it is clear that hybrid warfare uses a combination of tactics – conventional tactics and asymmetric tactics are used, as well as strategic and simultaneously coordinated efforts that are different from those of previous wars.

Forms through which hybrid warfare manifests are (information operations, separatist and secessionist movements, "colour revolutions", institutionalized religious,

national and political extremism, counterterrorism, unconventional warfare, foreign internal defence (support of other countries in external aggression), stabilization operations, security transitions, reconstruction, strategic communications, psychological operations, information operations, civil-military operations, intelligence and counterintelligence operations, economic and energy sanctions and other general sanctions (in sports, culture, science).

5. DETERMINING THE TERMS STATE ACTORS AND NON-STATE ACTORS

Today, changes in global centres of power affect a number of regional and local events and processes. These changes also affect the challenges and threats to global and national security.

Today, in the realization of their interests, state and non-state entities are not guided by classic forms of conflict, are not guided by classical warfare. At the same time, the effects of the engagement of funds and forces lead to evident changes, in the field of real geopolitics on the ground, as well as in the fields of influence and effects of the effects of strategic advantage and positioning of powerful global and regional forces. Hence, the emergence of conflicts by applying unconventional means.

The strengthening of the power of non-state actors further complicates the security situation in the world. Non-state actors are (criminal groups, foreign-funded extremists, foreign fighters, returnees, terrorists, etc.). State actors are capable (and willing) to organize asymmetric efforts – their position regarding asymmetric conflict generally differs from that of non-state actors and is therefore considered separately.

The state contains traditional military and political authority that relies on its own economic and diplomatic power. In comparison, non-state actors use a non-hierarchical structure of motivated "cells" with shared motivations and political goals (Brzica, 2018:41).

State and non-state actors are inherently different, especially in terms of sovereignty: according to a report published by the National Intelligence Council, non-state actors are non-sovereign entities and therefore lack legitimacy on the global stage (See the contents on Non-State Actors: Impact on International Relations and Implications for the United States”, National Intelligence Council, National Intelligence Officer for Economics and Global Issues (August 23, 2007:2).

However, understanding both actors is vital to any discussion of asymmetric and hybrid warfare.

State actors

According to Timofey Bordachev, a professor at the Higher School of Economics, a state is a politically organized body of people in a defined territory with public authority and the legitimate use of force and violence. This monopoly on violence distinguishes sovereign states from other actors that lack similar territory or authority. State actors represent the traditional consolidation of authority and the central elements of the international system. Furthermore, a state must have public authority, governance tools, and a territory and population to govern (Timofei Bordachev and Dmitrii Suslov, 2018).

Beyond legality, some states conduct conflict beyond their borders, operating armies large enough to warrant conventional conflict or relying on hybrid and asymmetric means to circumvent international law with potential consequences.

In both states with conventional warfare capabilities and those waging proxy wars abroad, asymmetric threats have proven effective in causing massive disruptions to

national governments and supranational organizations. Every nation-state needs to create a defence strategy to fully address a specific asymmetric threat.

Non-state actors

Non-state actors are defined as "non-sovereign entities that exercise political, economic, or social" control at the national or international level (See: "Non-State Actors", National Intelligence Council, 2). These actors operate outside the boundaries of the conventional state, pursuing their political agendas through means that are more difficult to constrain or regulate. Building consensus on non-state actors has proven difficult for both scholars and national governments. However, a flexible list includes the following, according to the United States National Intelligence Council:

2. multinational corporations and organizations; non-governmental organizations (NGOs); 3. 4. 5. superpowers; terrorist organizations; criminal networks (See: "Non-State Actors", National Intelligence Council, 2).

Terrorist organizations and criminal networks participate as the most important non-state actors. When examining conflict, two main groups of non-state actors can be identified according to their operational tendencies. Non-violent non-state actors, including multinational corporations, can have profound effects on the economic or political state of a nation, with the potential to exert both detrimental influence or undue control over the region (See: "Non-State Actors", National Intelligence Council, 2).

Violent non-state actors generally cause national and international consequences of extreme magnitude and are characterized by their ability to rely on violence and force through asymmetric channels. Militias, warlords, insurgents, terrorist and criminal gangs, and transnational criminal groups all exemplify the range of violent non-state actors (Thomas Risse, Tanja A. Börzel, and Anke Draude, ed. 2018).

The use of asymmetric and hybrid threats arises from a military disadvantage, where non-state actors or weaker states must approach warfare through irregular and unexpected tactics to maintain victory. This is evident when examining specific examples of non-state actors and their methods, such as terrorist organizations operating in the Middle East, Africa, or Southeast Asia.

RUSSIA'S ATTACK ON UKRAINE – HYBRID WARFARE

By analysing the activities of the Russian Federation, Western military experts conclude that hybrid warfare is characterized by the following principles: (Janev, 2021)

- analysing the opponent - through the use of scientific methods (the goal is to identify and exploit the opponent's vulnerabilities, especially at a strategic level);
- developing a coherent strategy – by connecting all military instruments (conventional, irregular, nuclear) and civilian instruments of the state structure.
- applying strategies ambiguously. Be unpredictable in your actions and flexibly adapt your strategies to meet unforeseen opportunities and risks;
- refraining from publicly declaring and ending war. Conventional war should last as short as possible, while the hybrid threat can last indefinitely;
- using time as a strategic advantage - through the use of covert strategies, strategic deception, and strategic surprise;
- using armed forces regardless of strategic defeat – military assets are used, military actions are taken to threaten and pressure civilian actors on the opposing side, as well as to deter the opponent from possible military actions;

- striving to achieve dominance in the information space in relation to the enemy - at all levels of warfare (strategic, operational and tactical), through the application of complex information operations.

After Russia's invasion of Ukraine, the threat of so-called "hybrid warfare" has increased significantly. "Hybrid warfare" is the expansion of a purely military combat operation using espionage, sabotage, cyberattacks, election influence, propaganda or disinformation campaigns to weaken and destabilize the enemy from within. Experts warn that Russia has been continuously expanding its arsenal of hybrid warfare capabilities in recent years (See: <https://www.dw.com/mk/kako-funkcionira-ruskata-hibridna-vojna/a-70908400>).

In 2022, Germany was the target of a series of sabotage attacks: an arson attack at the Diehl factory that produces Iris-T air defence systems; an explosive device that caused a fire at the DHL hub in Leipzig; the destruction of parked military trucks in Erfurt; and sabotage of German warships, including damaged cables and contaminated water systems (See: <https://frontline.mk/2025/09/08/ruskata-hibridna-vo-na-protiv-evropa-1-evropa-konechno-priznava-deka-e- napadnata/>).

Poland was targeted with fires in shopping malls, warehouses, including an IKEA facility – operations that the investigation linked to Russian intelligence services. In the United Kingdom, a DHL warehouse in Birmingham was hit by an incendiary attack carried out by operatives of the Russian Main Intelligence Directorate (GRU – Главное разведывательное управление). France and Estonia have reported similar cases, accompanied by disinformation campaigns to sow fear and distrust.

Espionage – Since the beginning of the Russian invasion of Ukraine, European countries have expelled about 500 Russian diplomats. The British secret service MI5 classifies at least 400 of them as spies. There are speculations that many Russian embassies and consulates have state-of-the-art communications and spying technology. The claim cannot be confirmed with certainty because the facilities are considered Russian sovereign territory and enjoy diplomatic status and protection. The Dutch secret service has warned that Russia is providing false documents for spies and infiltrating Western institutions as businessmen.

Sabotage – A Chinese cargo ship commanded by a Russian captain damaged two submarine cables with the anchor it was dragging along the seabed. (November 2024). In October 2024, a fire was set at a warehouse in London storing aid for Ukraine. In July 2024, a package intended for air transport was set on fire at the DHL logistics centre in Leipzig. In these and numerous other cases, there are suspicions of Russian sabotage (however, nothing has been proven so far).

European intelligence services are warning that the number of acts of sabotage and arson in the EU and the UK has increased dramatically in the past 2024 year.

Cyber Attacks – The German Federal Office for Information Security warns that the spectrum of threats in cyberspace has expanded. “Before the Russian attack on Ukraine, groups linked to Russia were particularly active in Germany with cyber espionage and financially motivated attacks.

For example, there has been a sharp increase in the number of “DDoS attacks by pro-Russian hacktivists”, i.e. the flooding of institutional websites or servers to the point where they can no longer be managed due to overload. Hacker attacks aimed at penetrating the protected networks of companies or institutions are also on the rise.

Disinformation and Propaganda – Another area of hybrid warfare activity is the attempt to influence public opinion in the targeted country. False information, as well as pro-Russian or anti-Ukrainian narratives, are spread through so-called troll factories on social media or through Russian media abroad. In early 2024, the Ministry of Foreign Affairs uncovered a campaign in which 50,000 fake user accounts were spreading false allegations and pro-Russian opinions on social media, linked to fake websites. Some of them resembled well-known news outlets (except that they were spreading pro-Russian fake news).

Interference in elections and political processes - The primary goal of these disinformation campaigns is to undermine support for Ukraine among the population. Another goal is to undermine political stability in the (democratic) targeted country by strengthening extremist parties and their candidates - for example, through financial support. In April 2024, the Czech secret service uncovered the propaganda website "Voice of Europe", which was allegedly funded by Moscow and used to bribe various European lawmakers.

Western intelligence agencies accuse Russia of directly or indirectly interfering in dozens of elections in Europe and North and South America. For example, the Russian foreign broadcaster RT produced videos during the US presidential election campaign on controversial topics such as aid to Ukraine, migration or the economy. One can also cite Russian attacks with leaks of confidential data from politicians or parties, sometimes even mixed with forged documents, which are published shortly before elections. This happened in the 2016 US elections, or in the 2017 French presidential campaign.

For its hybrid war against Europe, Russia has created a network of agents, linking state agencies and the criminal underworld. Russian-speaking men with criminal records are also being recruited to carry out sabotage in Europe - This is the conclusion of experts from the NGO GLOBSEQ and the International Counter-Terrorism Centre (ICCT) in a joint study titled "Russian Criminal-Terrorist Network: Crime as a Tool for Hybrid Warfare in Europe". (See: <https://www.dw.com/mk/ruskata-mreza-za-hibridna-vojna-vo-evropa-kako-kreml-go-koristi-podzemjeto-za-sabotazi/a-74688707>).

The study places Moscow's tactics in the context of the war in Ukraine. It shows that "hybrid operations are not a sideshow, but a central pillar of Russian strategy". The researchers compare such tactics to the methods of the Islamic State (IS), a terrorist organization that once recruited criminals in Europe. "But this time it is not a terrorist organization, but a state actor that is driving recruitment and operations", the study emphasizes.

According to the study, from January 2022 to July 2025, there were 110 sabotage attempts and attacks with links to Russia in Europe, mostly in Poland and France. 89 of them were successful, and 21 were thwarted. The study authors emphasize that the number of thwarted sabotage attempts is likely significantly higher because intelligence agencies do not always disclose such information to the public. Furthermore, experts have identified

131 individuals who were involved in the incidents. At least 35 of them are former convicts and were recruited in prison or through criminal organizations.

According to the study, the Kremlin primarily recruits men in their 30s for sabotage operations in Europe – most often from post-Soviet countries, Russian-speaking, and in difficult living circumstances. Recruitment often takes place online, usually via Telegram, or through relatives and friends. The main incentive for saboteurs is money, with sums ranging from a few euros for distributing pro-Russian leaflets to significant sums for attempted attacks on critical infrastructure, the study states. To finance these activities, Moscow is also using illegal means to circumvent Western sanctions. "Russia's military campaign - bombings, arson, assassination attempts - should be seen as both a punishment for Europe's support for Ukraine, and a preparation for a potentially larger conflict".

GLOBSEC Recommendations for Defence Against Hybrid Threats - As a further step, the definition of “hybrid threats” should be expanded because the national doctrines and strategies of many countries do not adequately take into account the role of “non-state actors such as criminal organizations, ideologically motivated intermediaries, or individuals acting for personal gain”. It is precisely these “legal loopholes” that allow Russia to deny its guilt or involvement in attacks and acts of sabotage. It further states that close cooperation between public and private actors is crucial in combating this threat. "They must be partners, as private companies in Europe have more sophisticated mechanisms for detecting Russian criminal activities. It is necessary to create a platform for coordinating cooperation in order to prevent Russian hybrid attacks on European countries".

Russia’s war does not end at Ukraine’s borders. Hybrid warfare – a combination of conventional force and covert, unconventional tactics – has become a permanent feature of the Kremlin’s strategy to weaken European cohesion, disrupt critical infrastructure, undermine trust in democratic institutions, and influence political processes, all without crossing the line into open warfare (See: <https://frontline.mk/2025/09/08/ruskata-hibridna-vo-na-protiv-evropa-1-evropa-konechno-priznava-deka-e-napadnata/>).

The European Union continuously condemns Russia's hybrid campaigns against the EU, its Member States and partners, which encompass a deliberate and systematic pattern of malicious behaviour, including cyber and physical attacks, acts of sabotage, damage to critical infrastructure, manipulation, the spread of disinformation and other covert or violent activities, which have further escalated since the beginning of the Russian aggression against Ukraine (See: <https://www.brif.mk/sankciite-na-eu-poradi-ruskite-hibridni-zakani-prodolzheni-za-ushte-edna-godina/>).

Hybrid warfare is designed to disrupt and deplete societies politically, economically and psychologically. It aims to disintegrate alliances, undermine trust in democratic institutions and create divisions along ethnic, cultural or ideological lines. Recognizing and exposing strategies and tactics, their sources and objectives is essential to protecting democracy, stability and security of states (See: <https://frontline.mk/2025/09/08/ruskata-hibridna-vo-na-protiv-evropa-1-evropa-konechno-priznava-deka-e-napadnata/>).

As democratic institutions across Europe and the world face the growing threat of disinformation and the consequences of hybrid warfare, the fabric of European democracy is under threat. In addition to conventional warfare and brutal war crimes and destruction

of civilian targets in Ukraine, Russia's ongoing campaign to destabilize the West consists of infiltrating the economy, politics, and society.

CONCLUSION

The extreme differences in the military capabilities of actors have encouraged the use of asymmetric and hybrid threats. In other words, there is an inequality between actors with the capacity to accumulate large armies and those without the capacity to accumulate large armies. This has created an environment where less powerful actors must resort to employing hybrid tactics to reduce the inequality. Non-state actors can have profound effects on the economic or political situation in nation-states, with the potential to exert both detrimental influence or undue control over the region. The use of asymmetric and hybrid threats arises from a disadvantageous military position, where non-state actors or weaker states must approach warfare through irregular and unexpected tactics to maintain victory.

Modern national states still do not have functional hybrid threat response systems. These states need to face the challenge of hybrid, asymmetric threats of the 21st century in order to defend themselves against unconventional threats and maintain internal cohesion. These countries need to take greater responsibility for building resilience within their own societies to protect their security and sovereignty. It is necessary to adopt a national strategy for dealing with hybrid threats and building resistance.

The NATO Alliance also applies a strategy to counter hybrid warfare (See: https://www.nato.int/cps/en/natohq/topics_156338.htm?fbclid=IwAR2dS8IfODGxxr8B3RfenvBHdCsuetzj7aL9i4lFt-8GdUODX3GD-Mk).

The NATO Alliance is continuously collecting, sharing and evaluating information in order to detect and prescribe a certain current hybrid activity. The NATO Headquarters Joint Intelligence and Security Department improves the understanding and analysis of the Alliance for Hybrid Threats.

NATO also serves as a centre for expertise, providing support to allies in areas such as civilian readiness and response to chemical, biological, radiological and nuclear (CBRN) incidents; protection of critical infrastructure; strategic communications; protection of civilians; cyber defence; Energy security and the fight against terrorism. Training, exercises and education also play an important role in preparing for opposition to hybrid threats. This involves conducting decision-making processes and joint military and non-military responses in collaboration with other actors.

For an effective national response to asymmetrical threats, the response mechanisms must be institutionalized.

Integrated and institutionalized defence effort should include two basic efforts: threat protection and management. The answers must be institutionalized by the national army and state institutions. It is necessary to create a policy and strategy for dealing with hybrid threats and building resistance.

Through the Security Union Strategy – 2024, The European Union establishes activities aimed at achieving the strategic goal – strengthening the security of citizens in the European Union;

The European Union has continued to develop tools for effectively dealing with hybrid threats. These tools include: (According to Council document 7371/22).

- A European Union's hybrid box that is a framework in order to provide a coordinated and well-informed response to hybrid threats and campaigns;

- Hybrid teams for rapid response to the European Union have been formed in order to provide support to member states, countries and missions and operations of joint security and defence policy (CSDP);
 - EU protocol has been revised to counter hybrid threats ("The EU Protocol on Countering Hybrid Threats ("EU Play") that describes the processes and structures of the Union that deal with hybrid threats and campaigns
 - Instructions for the implementation of the EU Common Diplomatic Response Framework for malicious cyber activities have been revised, ("Cyber Diplomacy Tools") that enables the development of sustainable, adjustable, coherent and coordinated strategies against the constant actors of the cyber threat.
 - The existing tools of the Union for Prevention, Detection and Response to Manipulation and Mixing with Foreign Information (Jimmy) are also strengthened.
- Member States are taking action to continue and improve their cooperation in this area by ensuring effective implementation of the above tools. In this regard, regular exercises were carried out and hybrid teams were formed to give a quick response.

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ETHICAL USE OF DIGITAL AND OTHER TECHNOLOGIES BY THE POLICE AND CRIMINAL JUSTICE SYSTEM

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Abstract

We are living through the rise of a digitally networked society characterised by technological changes. For more than two centuries, we have faced urbanisation, factory work, labour migration, social dislocation, and a rising crime rate, that gave rise to the creation of professional public policing in the early nineteenth century. Something similar in scale may be happening nowadays and the implications for policing may be just as profound. In the modern digital era, police forces face new ethical challenges in how they use technology, requiring a focus on principles like transparency, fairness, and accountability to maintain public trust and to function as part of state authority at the same time. These principles should be embedded throughout the technology lifecycle, ensuring that innovation serves the public good and respects individual human rights.

Use of digital, scientific, and other technologies by the police and wider criminal justice system is a real challenge in today's societies. For the purposes of this research, the method of content analysis was used. It is time to face up to the challenge of policing in a digital era.

Keywords: policing; digital society; ethics; fourth industrial revolution; technology.

1. INTRODUCTION

Recently, the question has been raised **as to how** the police and wider criminal justice system can best balance the potential benefits and risks of using new digital technologies. A range of new technologies are increasingly available to police services and the wider criminal justice system (CJS). Police services are already making use of new technologies for: a) crime prevention, for example predictive policing using AI to predict hotspots for future crime; b) mobility, such as autonomous vehicles and drones; c) identification and tracing, for example, automatic number plate recognition; d) surveillance and sensing, including face recognition technologies; e) analytics, using AI-enabled approaches; f) communications and interconnectivity, such as automated updates for victims or AI technology used to support call and response routing (Chief Scientific Adviser to the Police, 2024).

It's been a decade since a government programme has introduced more technology to the courts service with the aim of making the system "more straightforward, accessible and efficient" (HM Courts & Tribunals Service, 2024). This includes bringing services

online, for example, HM Courts and Tribunal Service plan to move to a new video hearings service in 2024 (Law Society, 2024).

Online, cyber-enabled, and AI-enabled crime show an increasing tendency. For example, developments in fraud, grooming and ‘sextortion’, stalking, and ransomware incidents have direct implications for crime prevention, investigation and emphasized victim support. Perpetrators of online crimes may be harder to identify and can operate from any location. The Online Safety Act 2023 in the United Kingdom introduced new criminal offences from January 2024, including cyberflashing, threatening communications and intimate image abuse (Office for National Statistics (2022); The Times (2024); Todd, C. et al. (2020); Cross, C. et al. (2022); Horgan, S (2021); Correia, S. G. (2022); Scheurman, M.K. et al. Caton, S. and Landman, R. (2021); Ryan, F. (2019); Department for Science, Innovation & Technology (2024); Metropolitan Police, 2025).

Digitalization requires new spheres and ways of acting, a different nature of action in the work of state bodies engaged in crime prevention, and raising awareness about ethics in the application of technology today.

2. CHALLENGES AND OPPORTUNITIES IN TODAY'S TIME

Government, police forces, and other sector stakeholders have noted potential benefits to using new technologies in the criminal justice system: a) improving performance, for example, in preventing and detecting crime, using Facial Recognition Technology (FRT) to identify criminals; b) improving efficiency by freeing up police time and capacity for higher priority work; c) making it easier for individuals and communities to communicate and interact with the police services; d) supporting transparency, accountability and trust (House of Lords Justice and Home Affairs Committee (2022); Guzik, K. et al. (2019); Higgins, A. and Halkon, R. (2023); HM Courts & Tribunals Service (2024); The Standard (2023); McGuire, M. R. (2020); EAW Coalition (2023); Orell, C. (2023); Justice Committee (2022); Home Affairs Committee (2021); Lum, C. et al. (2020); Bradford, B., et al. (2022)).

Parliamentary, academic and sector stakeholders debate several areas of concern or risk arising from the introduction of new technologies. There has been public discussion about how the police and CJS must balance the rights of individuals with societal safety in introducing new technologies. An independent report for the Scottish government emphasised the importance of “a rights based, ethical, evidence-based, consultative approach to innovation and adoption of emerging technologies in policing, within a robust oversight framework” (Fontes, C. and Perrone, C. (2021); Aston, E. (2023)).

The aspects discussed relate to the following significant points:

- ethical and human rights, civil liberties and the right to a fair trial;
- data protection;
- validity and accuracy of technologies;
- risks around equality and discrimination;
- right to privacy, for example, from access to smart doorbell footage (Aston, E. (2023); Almeida, D. et al. (2022); BBC News (2020)).

Debate has already arisen in relation to police use of facial recognition technology (FRT). Academics and civil liberties groups have raised multiple concerns, including the imposition of FRT and its impact on privacy rights, and a lack of oversight, accountability and transparency. There is particular debate about the relative accuracy of FRT for different demographic groups, and the risk that its use exacerbates discrimination. A 2023

National Physical Laboratory evaluation for the Metropolitan Police Service (in the United Kingdom) found no differences in accuracy of identification by age, gender or ethnicity for Retrospective or Operator-Initiated FRT. However, for Live FRT, it found some differences in accuracy for people aged under 20 years old and for Black subjects, with lower face-match thresholds. (Lower thresholds mean the FRT system is less strict, increasing the risk of matching an innocent person with an individual on an offender watchlist) (McDonald, N. et al (2020); Radiya-Dixit, E (2022); Mansfield, T. (2023)).

The Chief Scientific Adviser to the Police, and academic commentators, have noted that maintaining public trust remains a major challenge to the introduction of technology and have emphasized the importance of public communication and transparency. Researchers have also highlighted the potential links between public trust in new technology and ‘policing by consent’, securing legitimacy and public compliance and cooperation. In particular, little is known about the impact of the existing use of technology in police-public interactions (for example, chatbots for crime reporting, social media engagement with communities, and body-worn cameras) on ‘policing by consent’ (Laufs, J. and Borrión, H. (2022); Aston, E. et al. (2021); Aston, E. et al. (2022); Wells, H. et al. (2022)).

A 2022 Justice and Home Affairs Committee report on the use of new technologies in the CJS also highlighted challenges around lack of oversight, regulation, scrutiny of application and information on what is being used, where, and how. It, supported by research, noted the potential role of data ethics committees. There are also existing challenges to AI governance, including around bias, privacy, consent and transparency of algorithms ([Artificial Intelligence in policing and security](#)). In 2023, the government proposed to abolish the role of the Biometrics and Surveillance Camera Commissioner (BSCC), and its governance and oversight responsibilities, through the Data Protection and Digital Information Bill. An independent report suggested that the abolition could leave gaps in future oversight. However, the bill did not progress before the July 2024 election. The incumbent BSCC resigned in mid-August 2024 (Charlesworth, A. et al. (2023); Oswald, M. et al (2024); Science, Innovation and Technology Committee (2024); Fussey, P. and Webster, W. (2023); Biometrics and Surveillance Camera Commissioner (2023); UK Parliament (2024); Biometrics and Surveillance Camera Commissioner (2023)).

The Justice and Home Affairs Committee, and other stakeholders, have raised concerns about how well procurement and the market for AI technologies work, for example in terms of consistency of purchasing, user knowledge of products, selling practices, and security concerns about suppliers. For example, a research study noted that a lack of consistent and transparent standards for the use of computer algorithms in technology used by the police could increase the risk of bias in their use, increase costs and inefficiencies, and lower public trust and acceptability.

In relation to digital forensics, another study found that the need to keep pace with technological advances had significant implications for purchase and maintenance costs, and ensuring user compliance and accreditation. It recommended a review of whether strategic investment in policing co-access to equipment and personnel would help address such challenges. The independent report for the Scottish government included recommendations around improving business cases and evidence assessments for new technologies, adopting appropriate standards, and developing a public operational practice code (Zilka, M., et al. (2023) & Griffiths, C. et al. (2024)).

There are also significant challenges around securing the right, and enough, workforce skills to deploy new technologies, whether operated by experts or non-specialists. The Justice and Home Affairs Committee recommended better training for staff on the legislative context, the risk of bias, and how to use the tools. Research studies note further internal barriers to adopting new technology, including migration to new systems, securing financial and political support, and unclear guidelines and procedures.

The growing role of technology in crime, and the increase in online, artificial intelligence- and cyber-enabled crime means the police must increasingly process and analyse digital material and evidence quickly. This can include text, media and metadata; footage from video, smart doorbells, smartphones, and social media; and materials from developing platforms such as virtual reality, online gaming, and the metaverse. Academic studies report challenges around the scale of demand for these digital forensic examinations and how best to manage the rising demand. For the court service, the Justice Committee noted in 2022 that there were delays to the government's programme, and a lack of data and analysis to establish the effectiveness of the programme. The Committee found that, despite potential benefits for efficiency and public/media access, the use of online procedures and digitisation in courts may have reduced transparency, and resulted in variations in accessibility and information quality (Griffiths, C. et al. (2024); Sandhu, A. and Fussey, P. (2020); Rappert, B. et al. (2020); Justice Committee (2022)).

3. THE "SAFE CITY" PROJECT IN NORTH MACEDONIA

The Safe City system and the installed cameras will start operating on 1 January of next year. The Ministry of Internal Affairs (MIA) will have enough time to record all newly registered vehicles and coordinate the data with other institutions, in order to precisely determine the method of punishment. Drivers who commit a violation will receive an SMS or e-mail with a photo of the violation within 24 hours. The police are already testing the installed cameras throughout Skopje. The most common violations are exceeding the speed limit and driving through a red light.

To establish the Safe City system, it was necessary to amend several laws, including:

- The Law on Road Traffic Safety, to enable automatic monitoring and sanctioning through cameras and sensors,
- The Law on Misdemeanours, to define a new method for recording and processing misdemeanours through digital systems,
- Law on Vehicles, to enable the collection of additional data during registration (phone number, email address),
- The Law on Enforcement of Sanctions, to enable the automatic enforcement of penalties and notifications through electronic systems, Criminal Code, to harmonize certain misdemeanours with criminal procedures, especially in cases of recurrence or dangerous behaviour.

The preparations for the start of operations are in their final phase, and estimates indicate that everything will be ready by the scheduled date for the launch of the new traffic penalty policy. At this very stage, all inconsistencies must be resolved, with particular attention given to ethical implementation and, above all, the respect for human freedoms and rights. Since this is a sensitive process being introduced for the first time in our country, it is essential that citizens are fully and timely informed and that they trust the system will operate without compromising any human rights.

Digital tools and video surveillance systems are useful instruments in police work and contribute to improving public safety. However, their use must remain strictly within

legally defined boundaries, as it is very easy for procedures to be initiated that could undermine the system and diminish public trust in these new practices of monitoring citizens' movements.

In addition to Skopje, the system will also be implemented in several other major urban areas, such as Kumanovo and Tetovo, and almost simultaneously along the highway section from Tabanovce to Bogorodica.

3.1. New traffic rules for fines for pedestrians and drivers for using phones and headphones will come into effect from September 26th.

The end of riding scooters with headphones in your ears or crossing pedestrians with a phone in your ear has come. The law has been published in the Official Gazette and from September 26th, stricter provisions will begin to apply to road users who will be fined for paying attention to electronic devices instead of driving. Crossing a pedestrian while using a mobile phone will be fined 40 euros, and for drivers of scooters, tractors, motorcycles who both drive and use electronic devices, the fine is 50 euros.

"Safe City" has been legalized and is already being used on a trial basis and for analysis, and with its help, striking numbers of traffic violations are being detected. Although it is included in the amendments to the Traffic Safety Law, the cameras from "Safe City" will be used for fines from the New Year. However, from September 26, the amendment will already apply to pedestrians who will not be allowed to cross streets with a mobile phone to their ear and talking because the law states that the fine is 40 euros for that violation.

"A pedestrian is obliged, when moving on a roadway under the conditions established by this law or when crossing the roadway and the bicycle path or bicycle lane, to move and cross carefully, without using electronic devices, such as headphones, a mobile phone, tablet, smart watch or other type of electronic device, which would reduce his attention while crossing the roadway and the bicycle path or bicycle lane," states Article 116-a of the Traffic Safety Law.

There will be fines for those who ride scooters, as well as for tractor drivers and cyclists if they use mobile devices or have headphones in their ears while driving. The fine for this is 50 euros.

Half a per mille of alcohol in the blood remains as the definition of drunk driving, except that for the most drunk, that is, those who have over one and a half per mille of alcohol, the fine will be 375 euros and a driving ban of 9 months to one year. The law allows the police to use much greater types of video surveillance, including "Safe City".

"The police are authorized to install technical means and devices for recording in public places where traffic is carried out and where road traffic offenses may be committed, i.e. the use of video surveillance and systems that use advanced technology in order to document traffic offenses, the manner of committing them, detect perpetrators and monitor safety and traffic flow, in accordance with the jurisdiction established by law," states Article 369 of the Traffic Safety Law. In order for Safe City to function, the law on misdemeanours, which has not yet been reviewed by the MPs and has not been fully written, should also be passed in the same package, and changes should also be made to three other laws.

CONCLUSION

The introduction of new technologies is a "double-edged sword." In the short term, the first results can be expected that will serve as a roadmap for the direction in which the security system should be organized so that society can function normally and safely, and thus the police service can perform its task without hindrance.

The Safe City system is not something new on a global scale. It also operates in other countries, especially in Europe (most countries have implemented similar systems over recent decades, including our neighbouring countries Serbia and Bulgaria) and on the Asian continent.

It must be noted that in this sphere, there is a thin line between normal and free on the one hand, and restrictive and illogical on the other, when it comes to the rules and algorithms according to which this system functions. The system itself, as such, is completely harmless, but in the hands of unethical professionals who would insert wrong algorithms that do not correspond to natural laws, it can very easily get out of control and contribute to unwanted effects.

Morality and ethics are an inseparable *conditio sine qua non* element of this issue.

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MALICIOUS USE OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE BY TERRORIST AND EXTREMIST GROUPS

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Abstract

The increasing integration of artificial intelligence (AI) technologies in various sectors presents a dual-use dilemma, offering transformative benefits while simultaneously posing significant risks. It has raised concerns about their potential misuse by terrorist and extremist organizations. This paper examines and analyses how these groups leverage AI across various operational spectra, including enhanced propaganda dissemination, targeted recruitment, and strategic planning. Specifically, the paper investigates the application of AI in micro-targeting vulnerable individuals for radicalization through predictive analytics and personalized content generation. We further explore the alarming use of generative AI, such as deepfakes and manipulated media, for disinformation campaigns, incitement to violence, and the creation of highly convincing deceptive narratives. Additionally, the role of AI-powered automation in bypassing content moderation systems and amplifying extremist ideologies across digital platforms is discussed. The paper also addresses the potential for AI to facilitate improved operational security, intelligence gathering, and even autonomous capabilities for these groups. Understanding these evolving threats is crucial for developing robust countermeasures, including advanced detection mechanisms, regulatory frameworks, and collaborative international strategies to mitigate the profound security implications of AI misuse by non-state actors.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence, misuse, terrorist and extremist organizations, terrorism, countermeasures

1. DEFINITION AND HISTORICAL CONTEXT OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE

Artificial intelligence (AI) refers to the capability of digital computers or computer-controlled robots to perform tasks typically associated with intelligent beings. This technology enables computers and machines to simulate human learning, comprehension, problem-solving, decision-making, creativity, and autonomy. Applications infused with AI can recognize objects, understand and respond to human language, learn from experience, make detailed recommendations to users, and act

independently, thereby reducing the need for human intervention (e.g., in self-driving cars).⁵⁴

The past decade has seen rapid adoption of AI solutions across various industries by both public and private sectors, contributing to societal well-being and safety. Although AI's emergence was first conceptualized during the Dartmouth Summer Research Project in 1956⁵⁵, pivotal advancements, such as IBM's Deep Blue defeating world chess champion Garry Kasparov in 1997, heralded a new era in computing. This victory signified not only a breakthrough in chess but also demonstrated AI's potential across diverse fields such as pharmaceuticals, financial risk assessment, and genetic research.⁵⁶

2. THE DUAL DILEMMA OF AI TECHNOLOGIES

As AI technologies become ubiquitous, they create both prosperity and vulnerability in modern societies. While advancements in AI significantly improve various aspects of life, they also present opportunities for malicious use. Various groups are actively seeking to exploit AI for destructive purposes, enhancing the intensity of terrorist attacks and amplifying the dissemination of extremist propaganda.

2.1 The Dark Side of AI

AI is general-purpose technology that can be employed for both beneficial and malicious purposes. The underexplored dark side of AI reveals its capacity for misuse in furthering terrorism and violent extremism. The dual nature of AI encompasses both the potential for enhanced offensive capabilities in cyberattacks and the risk of security breaches, underscoring the importance of securing AI systems.

AI as an Attack Surface and Attack Vector

1. **Attack Surface:** AI systems themselves can become targets for attacks. This can include adversarial attacks, where inputs are crafted to deceive AI models leading to incorrect outputs. Additionally, vulnerabilities in AI algorithms, models, or data they use can be exploited by attackers to compromise the integrity, confidentiality, or availability of the system.

The [attack surface](#) includes all the possible entry points a threat actor may exploit to compromise a system or network. It is a sum of all possible attack avenues, including exposed network ports, vulnerable applications, access points through physical contact, or even human error. Thus, the greater an attack surface, the greater the risk of a successful attack.

A cyberattack occurs approximately every 11 seconds, and nearly 60% of businesses have experienced a ransomware attack in 2023. Many of these attacks are successful due to attack surfaces that are large and poorly managed. The attack surface

⁵⁴Stryker, C., & Kavlakoglu, E. (2024, August 9). *What is artificial intelligence (AI)?* IBM. <https://www.ibm.com/think/topics/artificial-intelligence>

⁵⁵Dartmouth. (2025). *Artificial Intelligence (AI) Coined at Dartmouth | Dartmouth*. Home.dartmouth.edu. <https://home.dartmouth.edu/about/artificial-intelligence-ai-coined-dartmouth>

⁵⁶Stryker, C., & Kavlakoglu, E. (2024, August 9). *What is artificial intelligence (AI)?* IBM. <https://www.ibm.com/think/topics/artificial-intelligence>

changes constantly, it either grows or diminishes depending on what comes in the system or goes out, gets deployed or retired, or is somehow changed. An attack surface needs to be constantly assessed and mitigated. This calls for proactive management and monitoring of user behaviour and the IT infrastructure, and applications within your organization.

2. **Attack Vector:** In this context AI can be employed by malicious actors to automate and enhance their attacks. For example, AI can be used to create sophisticated phishing attacks, generate realistic deepfakes, or automate the discovery of vulnerabilities in systems. In this case AI acts as a tool or a method for carrying out attacks against targets.

*An **attack vector** is the way an attacker will take advantage of a vulnerability in an organization's attack surface.* An attack vector involves the precise path or method used to gain unauthorized access or the way through which damage is caused. Examples include phishing emails and malicious websites, exploiting software vulnerabilities, or compromised physical devices. The “**what**” here is the attack surface, while the “**how**” is the attack vectors.⁵⁷

Examples of common attack vectors:

- compromised/stolen credentials;
- weak/insufficient authentication;
- misconfigurations;
- phishing & malicious insiders;
- denial of service (DoS), malware & ransomware; and
- data breaches & exploited vulnerabilities⁵⁸.

MISUSE OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE BY MALICIOUS ACTORS

Historically, terrorists have exploited technology as a force multiplier, projecting strength that belies their actual capacity and instilling disproportionate fear. From dynamite to generative AI, the misuse of technology remains a persistent counter-terrorism challenge. Although terrorist groups tend to favor traditional weaponry, they are increasingly adapting to incorporate advanced communication and propaganda tools.⁵⁹

Terrorist groups and individuals have shown that they can adapt very well and have evolved considerably over the decades. They have demonstrated the potential to innovate, for instance, in their organizational structure, becoming decentralized, franchised, and global. They have also evolved significantly in terms of tactics, moving from irregular guerrilla warfare to indiscriminate attacks. Technology-wise, this trend to innovate is especially pronounced with respect to the Internet and social media, which

⁵⁷SentinelOne. (2025, July 22). *Attack Surface vs Attack Vector: Key Differences*. Sentinelone.com; SentinelOne. <https://www.sentinelone.com/cybersecurity-101/cybersecurity/attack-surface-vs-attack-vector/>

⁵⁸ Balbix. (2020, May 28). *Attack Vector vs Attack Surface*. Balbix. <https://www.balbix.com/insights/attack-vector-vs-attack-surface/>

⁵⁹ The Council of Europe. (2025, August 27). *Report on the emerging patterns of misuse of technology by terrorist actors - Council of Europe*. rm.coe.int; Council of Europe. <https://rm.coe.int/report-on-the-emerging-patterns-of-misuse-of-technology-by-terrorist-a/4880281a94>

have proven to be extremely valuable for terrorists. The Internet and social media, as well as by extension other ecosystems such as the online gaming platform, have become powerful tools for terrorist groups to radicalize, inspire, and incite violence; claim responsibility for attacks; recruit; raise and move funds; buy and transfer weapons; and make tutorials or instruments available to their members.⁶⁰

The interplay between technology and terrorism is broadly evident in three primary dimensions:

- **Weapon utilization:** Terrorists increasingly rely on technology as a means to execute their attacks. The nature of these attacks has evolved significantly alongside technological advancements. The arsenal of terrorist organizations has expanded from simple weapons such as knives and firearms to complex methodologies like aircraft hijackings and vehicle-based assaults. Some groups display intentions to acquire and utilize chemical, biological, or radiological materials, with the adoption of automatic rifles representing one of the most significant developments in their weaponry.
- **Transportation and logistics:** Technological advancements in transportation and logistics have greatly enhanced the capabilities of terrorist and criminal organizations. These developments have increased not only the speed and reach of their operations but have also transformed them into global threats rather than localized issues.
- **Communication and information dissemination:** Advances in information and communication technology have permitted terrorist groups to communicate more swiftly and covertly, transcending geographical barriers. This capability has enabled them to disseminate viral content, including videos and information that foster terror on a larger scale. Consequently, these technological tools enhance the efficiency and effectiveness of their operations, while simultaneously broadening their opportunities to engage with potential recruits via mobile communication devices, social media, and the dark web.

Through these dimensions, it is evident that the adaptation and utilization of technology by terrorist organizations complicate the landscape of modern counter-terrorism efforts, necessitating a strategic reassessment of responses to these evolving threats.⁶¹

This paper illustrates how terrorist and extremist groups misuse AI to enhance recruitment strategies, making their propaganda more effective by reaching a more extensive, often vulnerable audience:

- **Micro-targeting and profiling:** AI algorithms can analyse vast amounts of social media data to identify individuals who might be susceptible to radicalization. This includes looking for patterns in online behaviour, interests, expressed grievances, or exposure to certain types of content (e.g., violent or anti-establishment narratives). This allows them to "micro-profile" potential recruits and tailor their messaging accordingly.

⁶⁰ UNICRI. (2023). *Algorithms and Terrorism: the Malicious Use of Artificial Intelligence for Terrorist Purposes* | UNICRI : United Nations Interregional Crime and Justice Research Institute. Unicri.org. <https://unicri.org/News/Algorithms-Terrorism-UNICRI-UNOCCT>

⁶¹ United Nations Office of Counter-Terrorism. (2021). *ALGORITHMS AND TERRORISM: THE MALICIOUS USE OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE FOR TERRORIST PURPOSES*. <https://www.un.org/counterterrorism/sites/www.un.org.counterterrorism/files/malicious-use-of-ai-uncct-unicri-report-hd.pdf>

- Personalized propaganda and content generation: Once potential recruits are identified, generative AI tools can create highly personalized and persuasive content. This includes:
 - Tailored messages: AI can generate text that resonates with an individual's specific interests, beliefs, and vulnerabilities, making the extremist group's ideology seem more relevant and appealing.
 - Deepfakes and manipulated media: Advanced AI can create realistic fake images, audio, and videos (deepfakes) of individuals or events. This can be used to:
 - Produce fabricated news bulletins or "witness" accounts to spread disinformation and reinforce their narratives.
 - Show distorted versions of events to incite outrage or justify violence.
 - Create seemingly authentic endorsements from respected figures (real or fake) to lend credibility to their message.
 - Engaging visual content: AI can help generate short videos, memes, and other visual formats that are designed to appeal to specific demographics, including younger audiences, by incorporating elements like gaming aesthetics.
 - Automated Interaction and Chatbots: AI-powered chatbots can engage with potential recruits in interactive conversations, providing tailored information, answering questions, and slowly guiding them through radicalization pathways. These chatbots can adapt their responses based on an individual's inclinations and vulnerabilities, making the recruitment process feel more personal and less overtly manipulative.
 - Social Media Manipulation and Amplification:
 - AI-powered bots can be used to amplify propaganda content across multiple platforms, making it harder for moderation efforts to keep up.
 - They can manipulate social media trends, create artificial buzz around certain topics, and spread disinformation on a large scale.
 - Bypassing Security Measures:
 - Deepfakes can be used to bypass "Know Your Customer" (KYC) checks, facilitating illicit financial activities for funding terrorism.
 - AI can help in identifying vulnerabilities in content moderation systems, allowing extremist content to slip through.
 - Learning and Planning: Large Language Models (LLMs) can be used by terrorists to gather information, learn about vulnerabilities, plan operations, and improve their overall efficiency and impact.

In essence, AI allows terrorist groups to automate, personalize, and scale their recruitment and radicalization efforts, making them more sophisticated, targeted, and difficult to detect and counter⁶².

⁶² UNICRI. (2023). *Algorithms and Terrorism: the Malicious Use of Artificial Intelligence for Terrorist Purposes* | UNICRI : United Nations Interregional Crime and Justice Research Institute. Unicri.org. <https://unicri.org/News/Algorithms-Terrorism-UNICRI-UNOCCT>

RESPONSE OF THE NATIONAL INTELLIGENCE AND COUNTERINTELLIGENCE AGENCIES TO NEW TECHNOLOGIES

National intelligence and counterintelligence agencies are increasingly challenged by their inability to keep pace with the rapid technological advancements employed by extremist and terrorist organizations. These groups have adeptly harnessed emerging technologies, including artificial intelligence (AI), to enhance their operations, recruitment strategies, and propaganda dissemination. In light of these evolving threats, it is imperative that intelligence agencies proactively prepare and implement appropriate measures. By striving for necessary changes, these agencies can effectively combat the new risks and challenges posed by the misuse of AI and other advanced technologies.

National intelligence and counterintelligence agencies can adopt a multi-faceted approach to improve the effectiveness of their fight against terrorist and extremist organizations that misuse AI technology. In this paper, several key measures have been proposed:

1. Enhanced Surveillance and Monitoring

- **AI-Driven Analytical Tools:** Employ AI-based analytics to monitor online platforms for extremist content, facilitating the identification and assessment of threats in real-time.
- **Social Media Monitoring:** Utilize advanced algorithms to track the dissemination of extremist propaganda and recruitment activities on social media and dark web forums.

2. Collaboration and Information Sharing

- **Inter-Agency Cooperation:** Foster collaboration among national and international intelligence agencies to share data and insights regarding AI misuse by extremist groups.
- **Public-Private Partnerships:** Work with technology companies and social media platforms to develop systems for reporting and addressing AI-generated extremist content.

3. Investing in AI Capabilities

- **Development of Counter-AI Tools:** Invest in research and development of AI technologies that can detect, counter, and mitigate AI-driven threats from terrorist organizations.
- **Training Programs:** Provide specialized training for intelligence personnel on the implications and uses of AI in both counterterrorism efforts and extremist strategies.

4. Policy and Regulatory Frameworks

- **Establish Clear Guidelines:** Create regulations that govern the ethical use of AI in national security, ensuring a balance between security measures and civil liberties.
- **Dynamic Regulatory Responses:** Adapt policies quickly in response to emerging AI technologies used by terrorists, ensuring that countermeasures are proactive rather than reactive.

5. Enhancing Digital Literacy and Public Awareness

- **Awareness Campaigns:** Launch initiatives to educate the public about recognizing extremist content and misinformation, aiding grassroots efforts to combat extremist narratives.

- Training for Communities: Collaborate with community organizations to promote awareness of the ways AI can be used to spread extremist ideologies.

6. Research and Development

- Continuous Threat Assessment: Conduct ongoing research into the evolving uses of AI by terrorist organizations, establishing a comprehensive understanding of emerging threats.
- Cross-Disciplinary Research: Partner with academic institutions to analyze the implications of AI misuse in terrorism, leveraging insights from sociology, technology, and security studies.

7. Preventive Measures and Intervention

- Early Intervention Programs: Use AI analytics to identify at-risk individuals and implement targeted intervention programs aimed at preventing radicalization before it occurs.
- Monitoring Exiting Recruitment Channels: Scrutinize recruitment practices and implement counter-narratives to disrupt the processes by which individuals are radicalized.

8. Strengthening Legal Frameworks

- Legislation Against Misuse of Technology: Introduce or update legislation targeting the misuse of AI technologies for terrorism, ensuring that there are clear penalties and enforcement mechanisms.
- International Cooperation on Legal Standards: Work with international bodies to establish legal standards for addressing the misuse of AI in terrorism, facilitating cross-border cooperation in investigations and prosecutions.

9. Creating Ethical Use Guidelines for AI

- Ethical Frameworks: Develop ethical guidelines for the use of AI technologies in surveillance and counterterrorism, ensuring accountability and preventing misuse by intelligence agencies themselves.
- Human Oversight in AI Systems: Implement human oversight in AI systems used for counterterrorism, ensuring that automated processes are checked for bias and effectiveness.

10. Engagement with Tech Industry Experts

- Consultation with AI Experts: Regularly engage with technology experts and AI ethicists to stay informed of current AI advancements and potential countermeasures against extremist use.
- Joint Exercises: Conduct simulations and joint exercises with tech companies to identify vulnerabilities and develop cohesive response strategies.

4.1 AI-driven analytical tools as part of national intelligence and counterintelligence agencies preparedness

AI-driven analytical tools represent a powerful asset in the fight against extremist content and organizations. By leveraging their capabilities in data processing, pattern recognition,

and real-time analysis, intelligence agencies can significantly enhance their ability to monitor and counter extremist narratives effectively. Continuous improvement and ethical oversight of these technologies will be essential in ensuring they fulfil their potential while respecting individual rights and privacy. These kinds of tools have become increasingly effective in monitoring extremist content for several reasons. Here is a more detailed overview of their capabilities, methodologies, and the impact they have on countering extremist activities:

1. Data Processing and Scalability

- **Volume of Data:** AI algorithms can process and analyse vast amounts of data from numerous sources, including social media platforms, online forums, and websites. This scalability is crucial given the sheer volume of content generated every second.
- **Real-time Analysis:** AI tools can work in real-time, allowing for the prompt identification and categorization of extremist content as it emerges, which traditional human monitoring methods may struggle to achieve.

2. Natural Language Processing (NLP)

- **Text Analysis:** AI can employ NLP techniques to analyse textual content, identifying extremist themes, language patterns, and sentiment. This includes recognizing coded language or euphemisms used by extremist groups to bypass content moderation filters.
- **Contextual Understanding:** Advanced NLP models can assess the context surrounding the text, allowing for a more nuanced understanding of potential threats and motivations behind the communication.

3. Image and Video Analysis

- **Computer Vision Technologies:** AI-driven tools can analyse images and videos for extremist symbols, propaganda material, or even violent acts, enabling the detection of visual content that may not contain explicit text.
- **Deepfake Detection:** As generative AI tools create increasingly realistic deepfake content, AI systems can also be trained to recognize inconsistencies or manipulations in visual media, which can be used for misinformation or propaganda.

4. Pattern Recognition and Predictive Analytics

- **Behavioural Patterns:** AI can identify patterns in user behaviour that may indicate radicalization or recruitment efforts, analysing engagement metrics such as shares, likes, and comments to spot organizing trends.
- **Predictive Modelling:** By analysing historical data, AI can develop predictive models that foresee potential risks and emerging extremist narratives, allowing agencies to act pre-emptively.

5. Automated Reporting and Alerts

- **Alerts for High-Risk Content:** AI tools can be configured to automatically flag and report content that meets specific risk criteria, allowing human analysts to focus their attention on the most pressing threats.

- Integration with Monitoring Dashboards: These tools often connect with centralized monitoring systems, providing comprehensive dashboards that visualize data findings, making it easier for analysts to identify trends and hotspots.

6. Customization and Adaptability

- Tailored Algorithms: Agencies can customize AI algorithms to detect content specific to particular extremist groups or ideologies, enhancing the relevance and effectiveness of monitoring efforts.

- Machine Learning Improvements: Over time, AI systems learn from new data, continuously improving their accuracy and reducing false positives or negatives through machine learning techniques.

7. Cross-Platform Analysis

- Monitoring Multiple Channels: AI tools can simultaneously analyse data from multiple platforms, such as Twitter, Facebook, and Telegram, providing a broader view of extremist activities and networks.

- Network Analysis: AI can also help visualize connections between users and groups, revealing networks of individuals engaged in extremist activities and facilitating targeted interventions.

8. Ethical Considerations and Challenges

- Bias in Algorithms: One challenge is ensuring that AI tools do not perpetuate bias or infringe on civil liberties. Continuous monitoring and re-evaluation of these tools are necessary to address ethical concerns.

- Human Oversight: While AI can significantly enhance monitoring capabilities, human oversight remains essential to interpret findings accurately and make informed decisions based on the data analysed.

CONCLUSION

The malicious use of artificial intelligence by terrorist and extremist groups poses a significant threat to global security and societal stability. The capabilities offered by AI—such as automation, data analysis, and the ability to create sophisticated propaganda—can be exploited to enhance the operational effectiveness of these groups. It is imperative that policymakers, researchers, and technologists collaborate to develop robust countermeasures and ethical guidelines to mitigate these risks. Proactive measures, including increased surveillance, regulatory frameworks, and public awareness campaigns, are essential to prevent the misuse of AI technology. Here, the role of national intelligence and counterintelligence in addressing the misuse of artificial intelligence by malicious actors is indispensable in ensuring national security and public safety. National intelligence and counterintelligence agencies must enhance their capabilities to detect, predict, and respond to AI-driven threats through advanced analysis, collaboration across sectors, and the sharing of information. Additionally, investing in training and resources is essential for personnel to understand and counter the unique challenges posed by AI misuse. By fostering a proactive and adaptive approach, national intelligence and counterintelligence can play a pivotal role in

protecting society from the potential harms associated with the malicious application of AI technologies, ultimately ensuring a safer future for all.

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CHALLENGES FOR SECURITY AND INTELLIGENCE AGENCIES IN DEALING WITH HYBRID THREATS

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Abstract

Hybrid threats have emerged as one of the most pressing and multidimensional challenges for intelligence and security services worldwide. These threats blur the lines between war and peace, military and civilian domains, legality and illegality, and are increasingly shaped by digitalization, artificial intelligence (AI), cyber capabilities, and disinformation. This paper investigates the strategic, technological, and institutional challenges that hybrid threats pose to intelligence and security services, drawing on recent developments in the EU, NATO, and small- to medium-sized states.

Modern intelligence must move beyond traditional collection and analysis paradigms to integrate real-time OSINT, HUMINT, SOCMINT, and AI-driven analytical tools. The growing use of AI - ranging from automated decision-making to generative disinformation (deepfakes) - poses both opportunities and significant risks, especially when adversaries exploit algorithmic bias or target critical infrastructures.

Furthermore, the paper explores the institutional inertia and definitional ambiguities that undermine coordinated responses to hybrid threats, especially in the EU. It assesses operational platforms such as EMPACT and initiatives like the Radicalisation Awareness Network (RAN) to show both the potential and limitations of multilateral cooperation. Particular attention is given to the “grey zone” operations by state and non-state actors, where attribution is deliberately obscured, and legal thresholds are bypassed. The paper concludes by advocating for a whole-of-society approach that includes public-private partnerships, regulatory adaptation, and an intelligence doctrine resilient to emerging technologies and strategic deception. Intelligence services must enhance their anticipatory capacities, societal outreach, and cross-sectoral adaptability to remain effective in this rapidly evolving threat landscape.

Keywords: hybrid threats, intelligence services, artificial intelligence, disinformation, EU security, grey zone, cybersecurity, strategic resilience.

1. INTRODUCTION

Modern security and intelligence agencies are faced with a qualitatively new form of challenge — hybrid threats, which simultaneously combine the use of military, political, economic, informational and technological instruments. Hybrid actions are not limited to physical space, nor do they respect the classical concept of war and peace. On the contrary,

they operate in the so-called grey zone, where the boundary between legal and illegal, state and non-state, public and private sectors is blurred.⁶³

This phenomenon reflects a deeper restructuring of global power in the digital age. Networked connectivity, reliance on cyber infrastructure, and technological interdependence have created new opportunities for influence and control. Within this new dynamic, information becomes a weapon, and truth a battlefield.⁶⁴ This leads to the erosion of public trust and the creation of “pseudo-knowledge” – a condition in which information chaos undermines the ability of societies to make rational decisions.

According to the concept of complex interdependence, modern states face a network of security risks that cannot be addressed individually. Hybrid threats exploit precisely these interdependencies: digital platforms, trading systems, social media, and public narratives to create systemic disruptions.⁶⁵

This paper aims to analyse the strategic, technological, and institutional challenges that hybrid threats pose to intelligence and security agencies. The research is based on concepts and sources from contemporary international relations theory, cognitive security, and technological analysis.

2. The nature and complexity of hybrid threats

Hybrid threats are defined as coordinated activities that combine conventional and unconventional means of influence – political pressure, disinformation, cyberattacks, economic blackmail and the use of proxy actors – with the aim of achieving geopolitical goals without open military confrontation.⁶⁶ This type of strategy relies on the integrated use of all instruments of national power and focuses on exploiting weaknesses in democratic systems and global communication networks.

Hybrid operations are most often carried out in the cognitive and informational dimensions, where the goal is not physical destruction, but rather influencing the perception, trust, and behaviour of individuals and communities. This warns that the modern era of “information overload” creates space for the spread of falsehoods and “bullshit narratives” – deliberately created half-truths that replace facts with emotionally compelling constructs.⁶⁷

Research in the field of peace and conflict suggests that such cognitive manipulations lead to “structural violence” – a form of intangible aggression that undermines the integrity of society without visible armed action.⁶⁸ Hybrid threats, therefore, represent a new form of strategic warfare, in which the goal is the erosion of social cohesion and of trust in institutions.

One of the key aspects of this form of conflict is attribution – the ability to identify the source of an attack. Cyberspace and digital anonymity allow actors to operate without a clear signature, making it almost impossible to determine responsibility. This phenomenon

⁶³ Byman, D., & Waxman, M. (2002). *The Dynamics of Coercion: American Foreign Policy and the Limits of Military Might*. Cambridge University Press.

⁶⁴ Frankfurt, H. (2005). *On Bullshit*. Princeton University Press.

⁶⁵ Keohane, R. O., & Nye, J. S. (2011). *Power and Interdependence: World Politics in Transition* (4th ed.). Longman.

⁶⁶ Byman, D., & Waxman, M. (2002). *The Dynamics of Coercion: American Foreign Policy and the Limits of Military Might*. Cambridge University Press.

⁶⁷ Frankfurt, H. (2005). *On Bullshit*. Princeton University Press.

⁶⁸ Galtung, J. (1996). *Peace by Peaceful Means: Peace and Conflict, Development and Civilization*. Sage Publications.

has been documented in numerous cases, including attacks on political institutions and media infrastructures by advanced persistent threats (APTs).⁶⁹

Modern analyses, such as those of Hybrid CoE⁷⁰ and MCDC⁷¹, warn that hybrid threats should not be seen as exclusively military or technological, but as social and institutional processes that draw on cultural symbolism, historical narratives, and ideological divisions. Their complexity therefore stems from the fact that they are embedded in the very fabric of society.

At the same time, research in the area of critical infrastructure and the management of unknown risks shows that modern security systems must develop analysis models that integrate uncertainty.⁷² Hybrid threats often operate in the realm of "unknown unknowns", where traditional assessment methods are not applicable.

Finally, as the concept of soft power suggests, influence in international politics is increasingly based on narratives, cultural dominance, and media perception.⁷³ Hybrid actors, exploiting this dynamic, seek to change the social meaning of truth and redefine reality according to their own interests.

Thus, hybrid threats should be understood not as a new form of warfare, but as a postmodern form of strategic influence, where information, technology, and the cognitive environment become the central battlefield.

3. Technological and digital challenges for intelligence services

Modern security and intelligence systems operate in an era of accelerated digitalization, global connectivity, and mass data production. These changes are creating a paradigm shift in the way information is collected, analysed, and interpreted. Intelligence services, which have traditionally relied on human (HUMINT) and technical (SIGINT) sources, must now integrate new forms of data sources such as open intelligence (OSINT), social media (SOCMINT), and automated analytical systems based on artificial intelligence (AI).⁷⁴

3.1. Bulk data and processing restrictions

The digital age has created a phenomenon of an "information explosion", where the amount of available data grows exponentially, while the capacity to process it rationally remains limited. This imbalance leads to the creation of "analytical black holes" – zones in which huge amounts of data exist but cannot be effectively converted into usable knowledge. This phenomenon creates a serious challenge for intelligence agencies, which must develop new models of selecting, filtering, and prioritizing information.

⁶⁹ CrowdStrike. (2016). *APT29: The Dukes Cozy Bear and the Russian Government's Cyber Espionage Campaign*.

⁷⁰ Hybrid Centre of Excellence (Hybrid CoE). (2022). *The Role of Cognitive Security in Countering Hybrid Threats: Insights from the European Context*. Helsinki: European Centre of Excellence for Countering Hybrid Threats.

⁷¹ MCDC (Multinational Capability Development Campaign). (2019). *Understanding and Countering Hybrid Warfare*. NATO Allied Command Transformation.

⁷² Rumsfeld, D. (2002). *DoD News Briefing – Secretary Rumsfeld and Gen. Myers*. U.S. Department of Defense.

⁷³ Nye, J. S. (2004). *Soft Power: The Means to Success in World Politics*. PublicAffairs.

⁷⁴ U.S. Department of Defense. (2015). *The DoD Cyber Strategy*. Washington, D.C.: U.S. Government Printing Office.

Modern intelligence must deal with "known unknowns" and "unknown unknowns" – a concept derived from the famous Rumsfeld matrix.⁷⁵ This means that some threats exist beyond the capacity of traditional perception and that agencies must develop predictive algorithms that can detect latent patterns and trends in data before they manifest themselves as specific risks.

3.2. Artificial intelligence and algorithmic risks

The integration of artificial intelligence into intelligence processes is a double-edged sword: it provides greater efficiency in analysis and prediction, but at the same time creates new risks. First, there is the threat of algorithmic bias – a phenomenon where machine learning systems replicate or amplify existing prejudices present in data sets. Second, generative artificial intelligence enables the creation of credible but false content (deepfakes), which can be used for disinformation operations and undermine public trust.⁷⁶

Modern media systems are already mediatized within conflicts – the example of the Ukrainian campaign “Be Brave Like Ukraine” shows that digital communication has become a form of strategic defence, but at the same time it represents a potential field for cognitive attacks.

Therefore, artificial intelligence must be treated not only as a technological resource, but as a new subject of security regulation. Intelligence agencies should develop AI-ethical frameworks that ensure transparency, accountability, and protection against abuse.

3.3. Cyberspace as a battlefield

Cyberspace is today the primary theatre of hybrid operations. It represents a "fifth operational domain" in addition to land, sea, air, and space.⁷⁷ It involves constant interactions between state and non-state actors, with hacker groups, cyber militias, and private companies carrying out attacks or defending themselves. Such attacks are often part of broader strategic operations, as in the case of APT29, in which state-backed actors use cyber infrastructure for political influence, espionage, and sabotage.

The problem of attribution remains a central point of weakness. In many cases it is impossible to reliably prove the origin of an attack, creating a "grey zone" in which states can act without direct consequences.⁷⁸ It is this legal and operational ambiguity that undermines the possibility of a traditional response and requires the development of innovative mechanisms of detection, prevention and deterrence.

3.4. Information dominance and cognitive security

Modern hybrid strategies go beyond the technical dimension of cyberwarfare and enter the cognitive realm – the control of information, perception and interpretation.

⁷⁵ de Valk, G. (2022). *Knowledge, Power, and the Intelligence Profession: Reflexivity and the Future of Analysis*. *Intelligence and National Security*, 37(5), 681–698.

⁷⁶ Nilsson, M., & Ekman, J. (2024). *Cognitive Warfare and Information Influence in the Digital Age: Lessons from Ukraine*. *Defence Studies*, 24(2), 156–179.

⁷⁷ Rumsfeld, D. (2002). *DoD News Briefing – Secretary Rumsfeld and Gen. Myers*. U.S. Department of Defense.

⁷⁸ Hybrid Centre of Excellence (Hybrid CoE). (2022). *The Role of Cognitive Security in Countering Hybrid Threats: Insights from the European Context*. Helsinki: European Centre of Excellence for Countering Hybrid Threats.

Information dominance is achieved through the synchronized use of cyber operations, propaganda and manipulation of public narratives.⁷⁹

These methods confirm the thesis of soft power – influence through values, information and communication, rather than through direct force.⁸⁰ Intelligence services must learn to operate in this environment, not just as observers but also as active actors in cognitive defence. This means integrating psychological, media, and technological expertise into intelligence analysis.

These forms of interdependence create "asymmetric vulnerability" - countries that are more digitally developed are simultaneously more vulnerable.⁸¹ Therefore, security systems must combine technological innovation with building resilience, which implies the readiness of society to face shocks and misinformation without losing functional stability.

Hybrid threats, seen from a technological perspective, are not just a matter of defence, but also of adaptation and transformation of the entire intelligence system.

4. Intelligence analysis and knowledge creation

The process of knowledge creation in intelligence services is one of the most delicate and complex aspects of their work. In the context of hybrid threats, this process takes on even greater weight, as analysts are faced not only with unknown facts, but also with deliberately created false narratives, manipulated data, and information paradoxes.

Modern intelligence theory attempts to explain this process through multi-layered models such as the DIKIW framework (Data–Information–Knowledge–Intelligence–Wisdom), the Rumsfeld matrix ("known knowns", "known unknowns", "unknown unknowns"), and the concept of cognitive epistemology of knowledge.⁸²

4.1. From data to intelligence

The DIKIW model describes the path from raw data to intellectual wisdom,⁸³

- Data – unprocessed facts without context;
- Information – a selection of data with structured meaning;
- Knowledge – is created through analysis, comparison and interpretation;
- Intelligence – applicable knowledge that serves to make decisions;
- Wisdom – the ability to assess the broader context, values and ethical implications of that knowledge.

This model emphasizes the importance of interpretation and contextualization – without them, data remains empty of meaning. In the context of hybrid threats, where hostile actors actively create “noise” in the information system, the task of intelligence analysts is to separate the “signal from the noise” and create epistemological resilience – the ability to recognize what is true and what is a constructed reality.

Modern society suffers from "information inflation" in which truth becomes a relative category, replaced by plausibility and repetition.⁸⁴ For intelligence services, this

⁷⁹ MCDC (Multinational Capability Development Campaign). (2019). *Understanding and Countering Hybrid Warfare*. NATO Allied Command Transformation.

⁸⁰ Nye, J. S. (2004). *Soft Power: The Means to Success in World Politics*. PublicAffairs.

⁸¹ Keohane, R. O., & Nye, J. S. (2011). *Power and Interdependence: World Politics in Transition* (4th ed.). Longman.

⁸² de Valk, G. (2022). *Knowledge, Power, and the Intelligence Profession: Reflexivity and the Future of Analysis*. *Intelligence and National Security*, 37(5), 681–698.

⁸³ de Valk, G. (2021). *Epistemology of Intelligence Analysis: Knowledge, Uncertainty, and Analytical Culture*. *International Journal of Intelligence and CounterIntelligence*, 34(3), 451–473.

creates the danger of being drawn into a process of “pseudo-analysis” – creating reports that are formally accurate but essentially empty. Hence the need to develop an analytical culture of doubt, where all knowledge is subject to verification and contextual scrutiny.

4.2. Managing the unknown: the Rumsfeld Matrix

The concept of "known and unknown unknowns" is applicable not only to military strategy, but also to intelligence analysis. The matrix divides threats and knowledge into four categories:⁸⁵

- Known knowns – What is known to be known (facts and confirmed information).
- Known unknowns – What is known to be unknown (identified knowledge gaps).
- Unknown knowns – Information that exists but is not recognized or integrated.
- Unknown unknowns – Threats and factors that are not known to exist.

In the context of hybrid threats, the most dangerous category are the “unknown unknowns”, as they are often the result of systemic self-confidence and institutional routines that suppress creative thinking. It is precisely these “epistemological gaps” that are exploited by hybrid actors – they directly influence precisely in areas where the system does not see risk.

Hence, intelligence analysis must develop a predictive awareness, based on scenarios and simulations that are not limited by existing assumptions. This requires institutional courage to accept alternative interpretations, even when they run counter to political expectations.

4.3. Knowledge, power and interpretation

Knowledge is a form of power – whoever controls the process of creating knowledge also controls the perception of reality.⁸⁶ In the context of hybrid threats, this means that the struggle for information is simultaneously a struggle for interpretation.

Intelligence institutions are not just observers, but also participants in an epistemological conflict where truth is negotiated between different actors. Power today does not only derive from military force, but also from the ability to shape ideas, narratives and values.⁸⁷

Modern conflicts are not resolved by destroying the adversary, but by controlling the flow of information and dominating the cognitive environment. This shift transforms the traditional role of intelligence from an instrument of discovery to an instrument of strategic interpretation.

4.4. Critical epistemology and cognitive resilience

Contemporary research in the field of cognitive science emphasizes the need to develop a critical epistemology – a system that not only collects data, but also questions its own methods of knowledge. This new intelligence paradigm is based on three principles:⁸⁸

- metacognitive awareness – recognizing one’s own analytical limitations;

⁸⁴ Frankfurt, H. (2005). *On Bullshit*. Princeton University Press.

⁸⁵ Rumsfeld, D. (2002). DoD News Briefing – Secretary Rumsfeld and Gen. Myers. U.S. Department of Defense.

⁸⁶ Galtung, J. (1996). *Peace by Peaceful Means: Peace and Conflict, Development and Civilization*. Sage Publications.

⁸⁷ Nye, J. S. (2004). *Soft Power: The Means to Success in World Politics*. PublicAffairs.

⁸⁸ Hybrid Centre of Excellence (Hybrid CoE). (2022). *The Role of Cognitive Security in Countering Hybrid Threats: Insights from the European Context*. Helsinki: European Centre of Excellence for Countering Hybrid Threats.

- interdisciplinarity – integrating psychological, technological and sociological approaches; and
- reflexivity – constantly adapting analytical models to new circumstances.

By applying these principles, intelligence services can move from a reactive to a predictive function, where the goal is not only to detect the threat, but also to predict the possible directions of its development.

In this framework, knowledge creation is not a technical process, but a strategic act that determines the ability of states to cope with hybrid influences.

5. Integrated approach and multilateral cooperation

Hybrid threats, by their nature, transcend the jurisdiction and capacities of single institutions. They operate across sectors, states and levels of governance, combining military, political, economic and psychological elements. This character requires an integrated, multilateral and societal approach that will involve all relevant actors — state institutions, the private sector, academia, the media and civil society.

5.1. The concept of a "whole-of-society" approach

Contemporary analyses emphasize that countering hybrid threats cannot be a matter of military or intelligence activity alone. It requires a “whole-of-society” model, in which every segment of society has a role to play in countering disinformation, cognitive manipulation, and digital attacks.

This approach is based on the idea that societal resilience is as important as technological or institutional protection. If the public is informed, critically literate, and resistant to manipulation, the effects of hybrid operations are significantly reduced.

The concept of complex interdependence, according to which security cannot be built in isolation, applies here. Due to global connectivity, weaknesses in one sector can have a domino effect on the entire system. Hence, an integrated strategy requires horizontal coordination between all societal actors and continuous communication between the public and private sectors.⁸⁹

5.2. The European and Euro-Atlantic framework

Within the European Union, the institutional response to hybrid threats is based on several key mechanisms:

- The Hybrid Fusion Cell in the European External Action Service (EEAS) serves as a central point for collecting and analysing information related to hybrid activities.
- EMPACT (European Multidisciplinary Platform Against Criminal Threats) promotes cross-border cooperation between intelligence and police services.
- The Radicalisation Awareness Network (RAN) works on prevention through educational and collaborative projects targeting local communities.

These instruments represent an attempt to create systemic synergy between national and European capabilities. But coordination is still limited due to definitional

⁸⁹ Keohane, R. O., & Nye, J. S. (2011). *Power and Interdependence: World Politics in Transition* (4th ed.). Longman

ambiguities over what exactly constitutes hybrid threats, as well as the different approaches of member states to their recognition and response.⁹⁰

Within NATO, the strategic framework for dealing with hybrid influences is formulated as the Enhanced Resilience Commitment, which obliges member states to develop common standards for the resilience of critical infrastructure, information systems and public communication.

Additionally, the creation of the NATO Strategic Communications Centre of Excellence (STRATCOM COE) and cooperation with the Hybrid CoE in Helsinki strengthen the transatlantic system of cognitive and information defence.

5.3. Institutional constraints and international coordination

Although the EU and NATO have developed relevant mechanisms, their effectiveness depends on interoperability and trust between members. Numerous reports indicate that differences in national legislation, different intelligence cultures and limited exchange of sensitive information pose serious challenges.

Multilateral coordination is most difficult in the face of asymmetric threats, where each state has a different level of exposure and different priorities. Therefore, to ensure long-term effectiveness, it is necessary to develop a common operational doctrine and shared analytical standards among allies.⁹¹

The notion of structural peace, in which cooperation is not based solely on interest, but also on shared values and trust, is relevant here. Without establishing such a cultural and moral consensus, institutional integration remains superficial and formal.

5.4. Public diplomacy and strategic communication

One of the most important aspects of an integrated approach is strategic communication – the process through which states, institutions and societies create narratives that strengthen trust and neutralize disinformation.

Soft power comes from the ability to communicate values and vision in a way that inspires, rather than intimidates.⁹² This is especially important in the fight against hybrid influences, where propaganda and manipulation cannot be defeated with censorship, but with truthfulness, transparency and credibility.

In this sense, communication becomes a form of defence. Effective strategic communication must combine institutional messages, academic knowledge, and media creativity to create immunity against cognitive manipulation. Examples of successful coordination, such as the Baltic countries' public campaigns on media literacy and counter-disinformation, show that social participation is a key factor for stability.

5.5. The path to strategic resilience

⁹⁰ Hybrid Centre of Excellence (Hybrid CoE). (2022). *The Role of Cognitive Security in Countering Hybrid Threats: Insights from the European Context*. Helsinki: European Centre of Excellence for Countering Hybrid Threats.

⁹¹ Byman, D., & Waxman, M. (2002). *The Dynamics of Coercion: American Foreign Policy and the Limits of Military Might*. Cambridge University Press.

⁹² Nye, J. S. (2004). *Soft Power: The Means to Success in World Politics*. PublicAffairs.

The concept of strategic resilience is emerging as a fundamental pillar of integrated security. It represents the ability of a state and society to absorb shocks, adapt to change, and continue to function under pressure.⁹³

This model requires vertical and horizontal coordination – from local to international levels, and from the public to the private sector. It is a long-term process that combines education, critical thinking, digital literacy and institutional trust.

Future power will be based on the ability to combine technological means with moral authority. Only societies that can think critically, believe in the truth, and communicate openly will be resilient to hybrid threats.⁹⁴

The integrated approach, therefore, is not just administrative coordination, but a new philosophy of security — based on trust, knowledge, and collective responsibility.

6. CONCLUSION

Hybrid threats are changing the fundamental understanding of security and redefining the role of intelligence services. They are not limited to physical attacks or classic espionage operations, but encompass a complex spectrum of activities that take place in the digital, cognitive and institutional space.

The main challenge for intelligence and security agencies lies in the blurring of boundaries — between truth and disinformation, state and non-state, war and peace. In such a context, traditional methods of data collection and analysis prove insufficient. It is necessary to adopt integrated models of analysis, which combine technological precision (AI, OSINT, SOCMINT) and cognitive and ethical depth.

Artificial intelligence is becoming a key factor in modern intelligence, enabling automated processing and analysis, but at the same time creating new risks related to algorithmic bias and manipulation of synthetic content.

Cyberspace is transforming into a strategic arena, where battles for influence are fought through information, symbols, and perceptions.

European and Euro-Atlantic agreements provide a basis for multilateral coordination, but their effectiveness depends on definitional clarity, trust and interoperability among member states.

The integrated approach – "whole-of-society" – is proving to be the most promising model, where security is understood as a shared social responsibility, not just an institutional function.

Ultimately, the future of security-intelligence systems will be measured not only by their technological superiority, but also by their intellectual and moral adaptability.

Societies that succeed in building structural peace, soft power and moral authority, and cognitive resilience will be best prepared to face the new era of hybrid threats.

⁹³ Hybrid Centre of Excellence (Hybrid CoE). (2022). *The Role of Cognitive Security in Countering Hybrid Threats: Insights from the European Context*. Helsinki: European Centre of Excellence for Countering Hybrid Threats.

⁹⁴ Nye, J. S. (2004). *Soft Power: The Means to Success in World Politics*. PublicAffairs.

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FIGHTING AI-DRIVEN CYBERCRIME IN THE REPUBLIC OF SERBIA

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Abstract

The paper explores the complexities of attribution and accountability in AI-enabled cybercrimes, focusing on cases when AI technologies are used for illegal activities like hacking, identity theft, cyber fraud, cyber terrorism, prevention or limitation of access to public computer networks, cyberbullying, hate speech, or malware distribution. The primary research questions include: Which forms of cybercrime are dominant and, as far as possible, use artificial intelligence? How can the legal system attribute liability in cases of AI-driven cybercrime? What role do AI developers play in preventing the misuse of their technologies? And can AI systems themselves be considered autonomous actors, thus complicating accountability? To address these questions, the paper will present case studies of AI-driven cybercrime incidents and how they can be treated in Serbia's legal system. A comparative analysis will be employed to examine how different international frameworks approach liability for AI-related offenses and how they can be used to improve legal treatment of this type of cybercrime in the Republic of Serbia. The crucial aim is to identify key patterns in liability attribution, with an emphasis on the responsibilities of different stakeholders, as well as to provide insights into the challenges of processing AI-driven cybercrime. The conclusions will offer practical recommendations for how legal systems should handle the increasing use of AI in cybercrime, contributing to the development of more robust cyber laws and AI ethics regulations.

Keywords: *cybercrime, artificial intelligence, AI-driven crime, regulation, liability*

1 INTRODUCTION

The expansion of information-communication technologies and the integration of artificial intelligence into everyday life have significantly transformed the nature of cyber threats. While AI-driven tools can enhance cybersecurity defences, they also empower offenders to design and execute sophisticated attacks with minimal human intervention.

From automated malware generation to deepfake-based frauds, AI has redefined the boundaries between traditional and emerging forms of cybercrime.

Cybercrime, often referred to as computer crime, internet crime, digital crime, or high-tech crime, represents one of the fastest-growing areas of transnational criminal activity (Drakulić & Drakulić, 2014). The Republic of Serbia, aligned with international standards such as the *Budapest Convention on Cybercrime* (2001), legally defines and prosecutes these offenses under the term high-tech crime. According to the Serbian Ministry of Interior and the National CERT, the number and complexity of cyber incidents have increased dramatically in recent years, correlating with the global surge in AI utilization. This crime, like the COVID pandemic, covers vast areas and affects various and numerous victims. Thus, in China alone, almost every second computer is infected and the infection rate is 47%, with a tendency for widespread vulnerability in individual and business systems (Deepstrike, 2025). It is estimated that global cybercrime costs will reach 14 trillion USD by 2028, while average data breach expenses in 2025 already exceed 4.88 million USD, a 10% annual increase (VikingCloud Team, 2025).

The concern is fully justified if one takes into account the use of AI in the darknet, or dark web. They are increasingly using AI to reach their victims more easily, to better conceal their activities and, above all, to make detection of their 'deeds' more difficult. There are increasingly frequent and alarming warnings that AI is increasingly strengthening the dark web ecosystem (Telefonica Teh, 2025). Although it occupies only 0.1% of the Internet, this space records according to Pangarkar (2025) huge daily traffic. As of March 2025, over 3 million visitors access dark web platforms daily, with illegal websites accounting for about 60% of all domains; it is estimated to generate enormous illegal income about 1.5 billion dollars annual income from the sale of stolen data, counterfeit goods and other illegal products; rise in credentials - stolen credentials for accounts available on the dark web grew 82% in 2022, reaching an estimated 15 billion credentials - a major enabler of subsequent cyber-attacks. Bitcoin is the most used cryptocurrency on the dark web, accounting for over 98% of transactions; it is estimated that the number of active hidden services on the dark web is around 30,000. The USA is the country with the largest number of users of this web, followed by Germany, France and the United Kingdom. In such conditions, the application of AI is justifiably scary, as shown by the fact that in just one year, sales of AI-based tools (Wang, Arief & Castro, 2025) on the dark web have increased by over 200%, especially frequent identity theft scams that have quadrupled, and 73% of companies worldwide have experienced some form of AI-related data compromise (Telefonica Teh, 2025). Also, artificial intelligence is increasingly used as a response to various systems, especially government and business, in managing the risks of cyber-attacks or as support for security "patches", but also forensic techniques and tools (Vaadata, 2024).

The emergence of AI as both an instrument and a target of cybercrime adds unprecedented complexity to legal and forensic frameworks. Unlike conventional software tools, AI systems possess varying degrees of autonomy and learning capabilities. This is precisely why attributing responsibility to either human operators, programmers, or the AI system itself poses a profound legal and ethical dilemma. These challenges are especially pressing in jurisdictions such as Serbia, where rapid technological adoption coincides with evolving but still maturing cyber-legal structures.

This paper aims to analyse: (1) the role that AI developers play in preventing misuse (AI-driven cybercrime in Serbian practice) (2) the establishment of the capacity to respond to AI-driven cyber incidents (combating AI-driven cybercrime, possible or not?),

and (3) the ways in which liability can be attributed under current Serbian law (regulation as a presumption for the success of the fight against cybercrime in the Republic of Serbia). The structure follows a logical progression: conceptual definitions, legal frameworks, typology of AI-enabled crimes, national case studies, and policy recommendations.

2 AI-DRIVEN CYBERCRIME IN SERBIAN PRACTICE

The emergence of artificial intelligence as a tool for cybercriminal activities has significantly altered the landscape of digital threats in Serbia. Although there is still no official statistical category of “AI-driven crime,” several documented incidents and patterns confirm the presence of such phenomena. These crimes primarily include AI-assisted phishing and smishing, AI-based malware and ransomware, deepfake frauds, voice cloning (vishing), and automated hacking attempts.

Serbia’s National CERT and Ministry of Interior have repeatedly warned about phishing and fraud campaigns written in grammatically correct Serbian language, suggesting the use of Large Language Models (LLMs) such as ChatGPT, FraudGPT, or WormGPT for automated message creation. Similar to global trends, these AI systems can generate deceptive, credible messages mimicking official institutions or well-known brands (Naveed, et al., 2025).

Between 2023 and 2025, Serbia experienced multiple large-scale phishing campaigns targeting users of Telecom Serbia, Netflix, and the Serbian Treasury Administration (CERT, 2025). The sophistication of these campaigns, reflected in language fluency and personalized targeting, strongly suggests AI involvement.

In the Telecom Serbia campaign, users received fraudulent SMS messages inviting them to claim loyalty points by logging into a fake domain (MTS, 2025). Once credentials were entered, attackers withdrew funds from victims’ accounts. Similarly, the Netflix campaign used authentic logos and style to obtain payment information, while the Treasury Administration campaign distributed malware disguised as government notifications.

Voice phishing (vishing) campaigns have also emerged in Serbia, where attackers use AI voice cloning to impersonate officials or company representatives. According to the Ministry of Interior, citizens received calls from spoofed numbers where cloned voices urged them to “**verify bank information.**” Research by Azzuni & Saddik (2025) indicates that as little as 30 seconds of recorded speech is sufficient for realistic voice replication.

The most alarming case of AI-driven cybercrime globally – and one serving as a reference for Serbian analysis – occurred in 2024, when the British engineering company Arup lost \$25 million in a deepfake video scam ([Magramo K., 2025](#)). Deepfake frauds use AI algorithms to synthetically create realistic yet false video or audio material, often for extortion, political manipulation, or financial deception (Abbas & Taeihagh, 2024).

In Serbia, similar attempts have been detected through fake Facebook investment ads falsely attributing interviews to high-ranking officials, including the current Prime Minister. These deep fake campaigns used authentic visual and linguistic cues to persuade citizens to invest in fraudulent platforms. Though under investigation, they are presumed to have been developed with **GAN (Generative Adversarial Network)** technology.

AI has also revolutionized malware creation. Tools such as **WormGPT** and **FraudGPT** can autonomously generate malicious code, select attack vectors, and adapt to defensive systems in real time (Falade, 2023). According to RATEL and the National CERT (2020–2024), incidents involving unauthorized data collection, malware installation, and phishing remain dominant in Serbia. A steady annual increase demonstrates the growing sophistication of attacks, partly driven by AI technologies.

The use of AI in cybercrime challenges traditional criminal law doctrines. When AI systems autonomously generate malicious code or execute decisions, establishing *mens rea* and *causality* becomes difficult. Moreover, the ethical responsibility of AI developers is a growing concern, particularly when tools are designed without ethical constraints (e.g., WormGPT). Serbian legal scholars advocate introducing provisions for developer liability and mandatory ethical AI certification.

The Republic of Serbia has made notable progress in establishing a structured and comprehensive framework for combating cybercrime, including offenses potentially involving artificial intelligence. Through the adoption of specialized legislation, ratification of international conventions, and creation of institutional mechanisms, Serbia has positioned itself among the regional leaders in addressing high-tech and AI-related offenses. However, the dynamic evolution of AI technologies poses challenges that exceed the scope of existing regulatory mechanisms.

The integration of AI into cybercrime introduces numerous procedural and evidentiary difficulties:

- a) **Attribution and evidence collection:** AI-generated content (text, video, audio) often lacks unique digital fingerprints, complicating proof of authorship.
- b) **Cross-border complexity:** AI-driven attacks frequently rely on distributed cloud infrastructures located in multiple jurisdictions, necessitating international cooperation under the Budapest Convention and its additional protocols.
- c) **Forensic limitations:** Existing digital forensic tools are insufficient for analysing machine learning models or identifying algorithmic decision-making paths.
- d) **Lack of expertise:** Despite ongoing training programs, there remains a shortage of AI-savvy investigators and forensic experts capable of interpreting algorithmic behaviour.

Serbia's *Strategy for the Development of Artificial Intelligence 2025–2030* emphasizes the importance of AI safety, ethics, and responsible innovation. It advocates the creation of a National AI Ethics Committee and proposes guidelines for AI accountability. In parallel, *The Strategy for Combating High-Tech Crime 2019–2023*, currently undergoing revision, is expected to integrate new measures specific to AI-driven threats, including:

- **Development** of AI-assisted forensic tools;
- **Introduction** of algorithmic liability provisions;
- **Enhanced** cooperation between academia, law enforcement, and the private sector;
- **Continuous** capacity building through education and international partnerships.

Despite these initiatives, the absence of explicit provisions on AI criminal liability remains a critical gap. Current interpretations rely on extending traditional criminal law principles (intent, negligence, causation) to AI-mediated scenarios, but such analogies are often insufficient when AI systems act autonomously or unpredictably.

In the European Union, instruments such as the AI Act (European Parliament and of the Council, 2024) and the Digital Services Act (European Commission, 2023) introduce obligations on transparency, explainability, and accountability for high-risk AI systems. Serbia, though not yet an EU member, follows these developments closely and aims to align its domestic legislation accordingly. The ongoing adoption of these norms represents both a challenge and an opportunity to modernize Serbian criminal law and cyber governance frameworks.

3 COMBATING AI-DRIVEN CYBERCRIME, POSSIBLE OR NOT?

It is, although it is often with little success and weak effects. Previous practice has shown great complexity and countless attempts. What is certain is that the fight against AI-driven cybercrime can be diverse, which depends on the criteria for classifying methods, techniques, measures, mechanisms and tools. Given the complexity and scope of this crime, the fight must be well-planned, long-term, comprehensive, systemic and systematic. Thus, based on the mechanisms of struggle, it can be: social, political, legal-ethical, criminalistics, organizational, procedural, technical-technological and/or educational. If the way of working is taken as a criterion, the fight can be individual and/or team. According to the length of action: short-term, medium-term and/or long-term, and according to the method of action: spontaneous or organized. The selected mechanisms can be undertaken preventively or subsequently, while according to the time of intervention they can be primary, secondary and tertiary. In any case, it is necessary to remove or mitigate the consequences that affect individuals, groups or en masse, and the measures taken will be individual, group or en masse. It would be optimal for the fight to be unified in such a way as to suppress the causes and remove the consequences. And, of course, enable the recovery of the attacked system.

Back in 2012, the American Standards Institute published a special guideline for computer security (NIST, 2012), revised it several times. It specifically stated that "effectively responding to incidents is a complex undertaking, establishing a successful incident response capacity that requires significant planning and resources". Establishing the capacity to respond (organization, society, government, etc.) to incidents is related to computer/cyber security, and it is the efficient and effective resolution of incidents. Achieving these requirements is made possible by a timely and high-quality incident response plan, which is implemented in at least four phases and requires the selection and complete preparation of the teams that will implement it, as well as the selection of appropriate tools and resources. Broadly speaking, the response plan must encompass and elaborate various forms of combat, synchronizing and harmonizing them with each other. It is important that all phases are included, that is, that each of them is well organized, managed and realized. The stages are: **preparation; detection and analysis; suppression and eradication; and recovery.**

In order for the response plan to be successful, not only preparation, detection and analysis are important, but also its extremely good knowledge, on the one hand, and for suppression, eradication and then recovery of the system, timely and effective identification of the response, on the other. All the more so because it, like any other phenomenon, has its own **life cycle**. Studying the life cycle is extremely important for understanding its essence and deciding what forms of struggle should be undertaken. Often the struggle is focused on eliminating the consequences instead of identifying the causes, methods, techniques and tools that have been applied. Such an approach makes it difficult to see the characteristics of the perpetrators and victims of this crime, as well as avoiding the interpretation of the space in which it takes place.

The new generation of cybercriminals, subtle and secretive, not only requires a new approach to cyber security, but also imposes the need to treat a new type of cyber threat differently due to the possibility of using AI. They simultaneously change the *modus operandi*, as well as give a new dimension to the life cycle of this crime. The life cycle of AI-driven cybercrime itself includes (Paloalto, 2023; Vidal E. R., 2025; GeeksforGeeks, 2025):

1. **examination**/reconnaissance;
2. **planning**/"arming";
3. **delivery**/transition from preparation to action;
4. **attack**/implementation and use/exploitation/transition from potential threat to actual intrusion;
5. **installation**/validation/verification of fulfilment of set goals, effects/establishment of permanent presence within the compromised system;
6. **command and control**/adjust external communication channel to send instructions, receive stolen data and operate in a compromised environment with full control;
7. **effect** on the goal.

Each stage of the life cycle carries specificities and special modalities. They need to be looked at and analysed in order for the cyber security response to be appropriate and effective. Therefore, the *modus operandi*, AI must be investigated. The *modus operandi* of AI-driven cybercrime is increasingly linked to organized crime and indicates that increasing the efficiency of criminal operations requires increasing their speed, reach and sophistication. Perpetrators, actors, threats use criminal and social criminal networks as tools for disruption (The SHERLOC, 2022; Wall D, 2017).

In order to determine the *modus operandi* of the perpetrators of this crime, their approach and forms of behaviour are analysed, that is, how and whether: a) preparation was undertaken; b) which methods were chosen for the execution of the crime, c) how many perpetrators there were, that is, suspects; and d) where they "operated".

- a) In the analysis of AI-supported cybercrime, unlike any other crime, it is determined how and which software and hardware was chosen to carry out the act. It is also part of a **serious and serious preparation** in order to find out whether these are premeditated acts and/or organized by several persons. It is increasingly evident that perpetrators of cybercrime prepare extensively and systematically, as well as investigators. The preparation consists of: choosing the victim; obtaining electronic addresses and other data related to the victim; collecting data on system weaknesses; locating materials, documents, data that you want to access; digging through the deepnet and the darknet to find the best tools and methods of execution, the nodes of the criminal network; choosing the way to destroy evidence; choice of ways of concealing and covering identity; choice of partners (accomplices). The choice of the victim, or goal depends on the motivation of the offender and the degree of vulnerability of the system. The existence of a large number of victims, of different profiles, is connected to this crime. The most effective way is vulnerability scanning because everyone (state, organization, group, individual) presents their services to the public, and they could be a channel for an attack. Frank Smith and Graham Ingram (2017) warn that threats to individuals are growing "almost exponentially" and that "government has lost the battle".
- b) Perpetrators of cybercrime **use special methods, tools, skills, and knowledge** to commit crimes (Drakulić & Drakulić, 2014) and are constantly improving. One of

these new methods/tools is deep fake (AI is behind the rise of deep fake and enables hyper-realistic fake audio or video recordings that can fool almost anyone) (Vazdar, 2025). Methods undergo numerous modifications, becoming more complex and sophisticated. Studying the methodology of committing the crime is doubly important: **for perpetrators profiling** (United States Government, 2024) and **victim profiling** (Havers, Tripathi, Burton, McManus, & Cooper, 2024). Changes and modifications in the characteristics of the victims are especially present, but two are particularly significant - age and number. The number of older people is increasing, with the fact that they are less likely to report "cybercrime to the police, bank or other authorities", but that is why, according to the FBI (2024) "people over the age of 60 report the highest losses from various forms of cybercrime, which is almost 5 billion dollars out of a total of 16 billion dollars lost in 2024." The mass of victims is an increasingly frequent feature of this crime (e.g. 353,027,892 victims in 2023, and the majority of incidents resulted from cyber-attacks) (Fox, 2024), especially since as a rule these crimes are concurring and affect a large number of victims. Also, victims from areas that were previously avoided for ethical reasons, such as health, are mentally ill persons (Monteith, Glenn, Geddes, Achtyes, Whybrow, & Bauer, 2024). The most vivid statement is for this second category: "The use of artificial intelligence to deceive individuals is of particular importance to psychiatry, because mental illness can increase vulnerability to cybercrime. Factors that can increase vulnerability to online deception include severe mental illness, emotional instability, poorer short-term memory, cognitive impairment, and lack of technical skills. In addition, impulsivity and overconfidence in information technology knowledge and skills can increase susceptibility to cybercrime. Psychiatrists should be aware that artificial intelligence is increasing the quantity and quality of cybercrime against individuals and to be able to recommend reliable sources of cyber security education to their patients..."

- c) The **number of perpetrators** (and associates/accomplices) and suspects is a characteristic of this crime. The most dangerous and attractive category are organized criminal groups. They are particularly related to AI-generated phishing, AI-driven malware and ransomware, AI-driven social engineering attacks, AI-based cyber espionage (Shoeb Ali Syed, 2022), AI cryptocrimes, but also certain acts of child abuse (Wang, 2020), thus the Internet Watch Foundation, IWF, identified a significant and growing threat of using AI for the production of child sexual abuse material, noting that "an initial report in October 2023 revealed the presence of over 20,000 AI-generated images on a dark web forum in one month, with more than 3,000 depicting criminal child sexual abuse activity. Since then, the problem has worsened and continues to evolve". Further, they warn that the reports from April 2023 to March 2024 (IWF, 2024), "contain a total of 375 reports that contained AI-generated content and child-assisted child abuse, peaking at 60 reports in February 2024". Many of these acts are the result of the "work" of criminal groups (e.g. members of "Scattered Spider" started the breach with a ten-minute vishing attack (voice phishing) posing as an employee in a phone call to the IT department asking for help and access to data). In a Trend Micro (2024) survey of cybercrime group categories, a distinction is made between: **small groups** with 1-5 members and revenues of less than \$500,000 per year (e.g. Scan4You); **medium groups** of 6-49 members, with annual revenues up to 50 million dollars (e.g. MaxiDed); and **large groups** with more than 50 members, and earnings over 50 million dollars per year

(e.g. Conti). The problem, of course, is the analysis of their structure and activities because they are anonymous, "invisible" and inaccessible, well hidden in the dark net. In any case, the activities of cyber groups are extremely present and often supported by national governments (primarily for intelligence and espionage purposes, as was the case with the North Korean group Lazarus). Governments themselves support organized cyber criminal groups through direct sponsorship, indirect support (hiding perpetrators) and/or through defensive cyber warfare (developing sophisticated cyber operations to protect their own networks and systems from attack) (UNODOC, 2020).

- d) The **location/scene of the crime** (Saqib, Faheem, India, Nituja, & India, 2025) is the fourth essential component of the modus operandi. The analysis of the crime scene of this form of cybercrime indicates its specificity, as well as a different approach to hiding evidence and the identity of the perpetrator. This analysis enables investigators to establish timelines of events, identify patterns, and overcome the challenges of adapting to the growing complexity and volume of data. The emergence of artificial intelligence technologies is transforming the processing of evidence, on the one hand, improving efficiency, precision and scalability, and the complex concealment of evidence and perpetrators, on the other. "*AI is also being used to reconstruct crime scenes through sophisticated 3D modelling techniques, which provide investigators with a detailed perspective of events and enhance courtroom presentations.*" In any case, AI is changing almost the entire picture of crime and forensic tools, especially cyber forensics, for detection, monitoring, analysis and presentation, as well as locating crime scenes. The changes are broad, deep, all-encompassing and in some ways terrifying. That is why specific experts are necessary whose knowledge can ensure the identification of the crime scene, the tools used, as well as the identification of the victims and the perpetrator (FBI, 2025).

4 REGULATION AS A PRESUMPTION FOR THE SUCCESS OF THE FIGHT AGAINST CYBERCRIME IN THE REPUBLIC OF SERBIA

In the process of the ratification of *The Convention on Cybercrime* (Budapest Convention, 2001) and additional protocols (*Law on the Ratification of the Additional Protocol to the Convention*, 2009, and *Law on Ratification of the Second Additional Protocol to the Convention on Cybercrime on Enhanced Cooperation and Discovery of Electronic Evidence*, 2022), the legislator in the Republic of Serbia decided to use term **high-tech crime** (hi-tech crime) for the crimes that are happening in the cyberspace. This led to introduction of criminal acts **against security of computer data** (Arts. 298–304a), **sexual offenses** committed through computer networks (Arts. 185, 185b); as well as criminal acts **against intellectual property** (Arts. 198–202) into Criminal Code of the Republic of Serbia but also gives possibility to process other criminal acts (such as crime against property, against economy, against legal instruments, against public peace, against constitutional order and security) under the jurisdiction of the Prosecutor for High-Tech Crime.

Each of these areas can be directly influenced by the use of AI. For instance, Articles 298–304a criminalize unauthorized access to protected computers, networks and digital data processing, computer data and programs destruction, computer sabotage, computer fraud, development and introduction of malicious software (viruses), as well as prevention and limitation of access to a public network, unauthorized use of a computer or

networks, etc. Sexual offenses such as the production or distribution of child pornography (Art. 185) and the abuse of communication technologies to target minors (Art. 185b) are increasingly linked to AI-generated deepfake materials. Furthermore, the use of copyrighted or patented works for AI training without authorization may violate Articles 199–202 concerning intellectual property.

It is expected that these three groups of criminal offenses could be directly influenced by mass usage of AI in the crimes, thus these ones will be further explored in the context of AI driven cyber-attacks that are currently happening in the Republic of Serbia, as well as potential usage of AI to conduct them if they are not detected in the wild. Furthermore, Serbia in 2023 adopted the *Law on the Organization and Competence of State Bodies for the Fight against High-Tech Crime*, which regulates the formation, organization, jurisdiction and powers of special organizational units of state bodies for the purpose of detection, prosecution and trial for criminal offenses determined as hi-tech crime.

Institutionally, Serbia has established a strong organizational framework for addressing cybercrime:

- The **Special Prosecutor’s Office for High-Tech Crime**, responsible for prosecuting all cases falling under the defined categories (with possibility that other criminal acts that potentially fall under jurisdiction could be influenced by AI);
- The **Department for the Fight against High-Tech Crime** within the Ministry of Interior;
- The **National CERT** (Computer Emergency Response Team), part of the **Regulatory Agency for Electronic Communications and Postal Services** (RATEL); and
- The **Information Security Inspectorate**, responsible for oversight of critical ICT systems.

The Statistical Bulletin of the Special Prosecutor’s Office for High-Tech Crime (2024) indicates a 10.31% increase in registered cases between 2023 and 2024, reaching a total of 7,198 cases, of which 3,888 involved unknown perpetrators. These data highlight both the rise of digital threats and the complexity of identifying offenders operating in or through AI-assisted mechanisms. Additional data show that 93 indictments and 8 full indictments were filed in 2024, with 39 plea agreements concluded. Although AI-specific cases are not yet statistically isolated, prosecutors report a growing number of offenses involving AI-generated phishing, voice cloning, and AI-assisted fraud (Vrhovno javno tužilaštvo, 2025).

Despite the extensive legal framework, AI-driven cybercrime presents unique challenges to regulation and enforcement. Traditional provisions are built on the assumption of direct human agency, while AI-enabled attacks often involve systems capable of self-learning, decision-making, and autonomous adaptation. This raises several legal questions:

- **Attribution:** Who is responsible—the user, the developer, or the AI system itself?
- **Mens rea:** Can intent be established when an AI independently adapts or modifies its actions?
- **Jurisdiction:** How to prosecute transnational AI attacks executed through cloud-based infrastructures?

While Serbian law currently lacks explicit norms addressing these specific dilemmas, the *Strategy for the Development of Artificial Intelligence 2025–2030* outlines the need for a coordinated response integrating technological, organizational, legal, and ethical

safeguards. Future legislative amendments are expected to incorporate provisions on algorithmic accountability, data transparency, and explainability.

5 CONCLUSION – WHAT’S NEXT?

The continuous advancement of artificial intelligence technologies has transformed both the scale and sophistication of cybercrime, presenting unprecedented challenges for legal systems worldwide. The Republic of Serbia, while maintaining a robust institutional and legislative foundation, must now adapt its criminal law and cybersecurity frameworks to reflect the autonomous and adaptive nature of AI-driven threats.

This research identified that AI influences nearly every domain of cybercrime – from data manipulation and fraud to sexual exploitation and intellectual property violations. Serbian criminal law currently provides mechanisms to prosecute most of these offenses under existing provisions (Arts. 298–304a of the Criminal Code), yet the rise of autonomous AI systems calls for a more nuanced legal understanding of intent and liability.

Three critical conclusions emerge from the analysis:

1. **Legal adaptation is essential.** The Serbian criminal justice system needs to expand definitions of digital offenses to explicitly include AI-assisted and AI-generated cybercrimes. Concepts such as algorithmic accountability, explainability, and developer liability must be integrated into statutory law.
2. **Institutional and technical capacity must evolve.** Specialized training for prosecutors, judges, and forensic experts in AI technologies is necessary. The introduction of AI-powered forensic tools capable of analysing machine learning models, recognizing synthetic media, and identifying behavioural anomalies will enhance investigative efficiency.
3. **Ethical and preventive frameworks must accompany enforcement.** As AI technologies continue to develop, their misuse can only be mitigated through ethical governance, transparency obligations for AI developers, and cross-sectoral cooperation. Establishing an independent *AI Ethics Council* and implementing risk-based certification systems could help ensure the responsible use of AI across industries.

Looking forward, Serbia’s position as a regional leader in cybersecurity gives it an opportunity to shape normative standards that balance technological progress with human rights and rule of law. Future legislation should focus on proactive prevention, international cooperation, and education, ensuring that the benefits of AI outweigh its potential for misuse.

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THE HYBRID CHARACTER OF COLOUR REVOLUTIONS

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Abstract

According to their characteristics, it can be said that colour revolutions are a kind of "hybrid", i.e. a combination of a coup d'état and a classical revolution. That is, as in the case of a coup d'état, there is a change in the holder of supreme power, without broader social changes (without changes to the state system and the economic and political system), with a certain role of the national army and other security bodies (this time more passive), as well as with support from an external factor. The similarity with classical revolutions, apart from the name, is also represented by the significant role of the masses in the realization of this type of coup. The term "revolution" is used because it evokes positive feelings and expectations of progressive change. As in other types of coups, a large number of actors in colour revolutions, primarily protesters in the streets, are not fully aware of their true role and the events that are taking place. Without taking all this into account, they are used as evidence of mass anti-government sentiment, and if necessary, in the event of intervention by government security forces, they can also serve as a living wall and protection for the real bearers and leaders of the movement.

Keywords: hybrid threats, colour revolutions, security situation.

Introduction

In the 21st century, states cope well with security threats from other states. Even when there was an interstate war in which there was a large difference in the balance of power, such as Iraq's invasion of Kuwait, the international community, with joint forces, prevented such behaviour of states. However, another type of war has become relevant in the 21st century, and these are hybrid wars, which have shown the unwillingness of international bodies to identify and deal with them. Therefore, we can freely say that a global recognition and rearrangement is underway, characterized by conflict between the leading actors on the political, religious or social scene.

Hybrid wars are not characteristic only of the strongest, they are also used by other countries, primarily those that fight to maintain the status of regional powers, and are even used by non-state organizations, such as ISIS, to achieve their own goals.

Hybrid war

The efforts to give a clear seal and recognition of phenomena and processes in social relations, especially as our interest in the sphere of security requires us to consider the emerging forms, methods, means and modalities of the relatively new concept of hybrid war from several aspects. However, the concept of hybrid warfare is not new, as

states and intelligence services have used emerging forms, methods, means and modalities of hybrid action in the past, especially expressed through subversive techniques and tools, to achieve their goals. The KGB used disinformation and propaganda as a means of asymmetric warfare in the Cold War due to the large borders of its population and the regions that were under its sphere of influence, just as the CIA used them to prevent the spread of communism in the United States and Western countries⁹⁵.

With the development of technology, hybrid warfare takes on a completely new dimension, where the overall space could be manipulated by using various "weapons" in the form of an unnoticeable, but persistent and purposeful action in the direction of weakening the supporting elements of a social community. Hybrid warfare, by combining conventional military techniques and unconventional technologies with conventional methods, has become the leading generation of tools that the world is slowly facing⁹⁶. If there is no use of conventional weapons, then there is no war. Everything can be reduced to conflict, to clash and ultimately to war. So, conflict does not always have to lead to clash, and clash does not always have to cause war, but war is always a consequence of the existence of conflicts and clashes.

The remarkable growth of hybrid wars in the 21st century does not mean the end of classic, conventional wars, which we are particularly witnessing with the war between Russia and Ukraine. However, the increasing role of hybrid wars in achieving the geopolitical goals of the opposing sides means that a different approach is needed when creating the defence strategy of the states that are the target of this type of war.

In hybrid warfare, the role of non-military means of a subversive nature is emphasized. Ideally, the state that plans and carries out the "attack" should not use military force and conventional weapons. The goal of the attackers is to control the actions of the political leadership and population of the attacked state and direct them in the desired direction for them, a direction contrary to the determinations of the state⁹⁷. If military force is used, it is used secretly, covertly, with a good alibi. However, although the role of the use of non-military means is particularly emphasized, according to many authors, both in classical wars and in hybrid wars, the basis is the armed conflict as a last resort.

As a working definition in the paper, this will be used: hybrid war as an armed conflict that is carried out in combination with military and non-military means in order to force the enemy to take such steps that he would not do voluntarily, with their synergistic effect, and where at least one party to the conflict is a state. The main role in achieving the goals of the operations is the use of non-military means, such as psychological and propaganda operations, economic sanctions, embargoes, criminal activities, terrorist activities and other subversive activities of a similar nature. As secondary are the military actions of the aggressor, which are carried out in secret, with irregular forces, in combination with symmetrical and asymmetrical methods of combat operations against the entire society and especially against its political structures, state bodies and local self-government, the state economy, the morale of the population, and against the armed forces.

⁹⁵ Davor M. Milošević, Pojmovno određenje fenomena hibridnog ratovanja, *Војно Дело*, 3/2018, стр. 301.

⁹⁶ *Ibid*, str.303

⁹⁷ Hybrid warfare: A new phenomenon in Europe's security environment, Jagello 2000 for NATO Information Centre in Prague, 2015.

The basis of the concept of hybrid war is found in subversion⁹⁸. Thus, according to the above, it can be seen that armed struggle is the essence of war, by quite explicitly emphasizing its reduced role in relation to the other elements of war. It is considered that hybrid war is essentially the achievement of set goals with little or no direct fighting⁹⁹. Therefore, in hybrid wars it is almost impossible to say when the real fight or organized violence begins, which is actually war, conflict, in its classic form. One of the key ideas of hybrid wars is that the difference between the separate categories of war and peace, as well as civilian and military operations, is deliberately blurred. This obfuscation is achieved by using a wider range of means: violent and non-violent, military and civilian, in a carefully planned manner without unnecessarily crossing the threshold for war and direct conflict, even if the level of escalation varies.

The concept of "hybrid warfare" consists of three phases, and each phase consists of three sub-phases¹⁰⁰:

Preparation phase

The preparation phase is aimed at identifying or discovering, recording and studying the strategic, political, economic, social and infrastructural weaknesses and vulnerabilities of a particular state, as well as setting up and developing the necessary means in order to exploit them to achieve the goals of the "attacker". The means for identifying and studying the indicated weaknesses and vulnerabilities basically include traditional diplomatic and non-diplomatic activities and the activities of "soft - coercion - persuasion", such as the establishment of political cultural societies, the exercise of economic influence, ensuring a significant media presence, support for separatist movements and other anti-government activities. During this phase, there is no open conflict using violent methods, and measures are taken that do not violate the political and legal threshold, which would serve as an indicator to the target state that aggression is imminent.

Attack phase

In this phase, there is an open and organized use of violence. Unmarked, mostly secretly armed units appear, which set up barricades and checkpoints on key communication routes, ostensibly as an expression of certain dissatisfaction and non-fulfilment of the requirements for the appropriately imposed problem. Institutions at the central or local level are blocked in order to prevent their functioning and to prevent the adoption of political decisions that are not in accordance with the "persuasion" of the attackers. At the same time, well-organized, often armed protesters, dressed in civilian clothes, occupy less important local government buildings, media outlets (radio and TV stations, news agencies) and critical elements of the civilian infrastructure. The seizure of

⁹⁸ Milinko S. Vračar, Razmatranje adekvatnog teorijsko-epistemološkog pristupa u istraživanju fenomena hibridnog ratovanja, dostupno na http://www.isi.mod.gov.rs/multimedia/dodaci/69_2017_7_20_vracar_1534761013.pdf

⁹⁹ Fiona Hill, "Hybrid War: The Real Reason Fighting Stopped in Ukraine – for Now," Reuters, February 26, 2015, <http://blogs.reuters.com/great-debate/2015/02/26/hybrid-war-the-real-reason-fighting-stopped-in-ukraine-for-now/>.

¹⁰⁰ Давор М. Милошевић, Перцепција савремених оружаних сукоба као индикатора хибридног концепта рата - модели, превенције и супростављања хибридним претњима, Војно Дело, 6, 2019, стр. 273.

radio and TV stations prevents the broadcasting of information by the central government and enables the broadcasting of their own targeted information/disinformation. The offensive operations are supported by an intensive information operation aimed at paralyzing decision-makers, causing despair, fear and dissatisfaction among citizens with the official government, weakening the possible resistance of local armed forces and police units by weakening their morale. The command system of a particular state is devastated, disrupted and obstructed through electronic interference, sabotage and the placement of disinformation or through the animation of corrupt statesmen. At the same time, the aggressor state constantly denies its own participation in the crisis that has arisen.

Although most actions in this phase are carried out using non-military means, the use of military forces is also significant. Military forces are deployed near the state border and thus cause psychological pressure on citizens and authorities, as an immediate threat of a possible conventional attack. This influences the central government of the attacked state to abandon the possible use of violent methods to suppress demonstrations, riots and prevent the onset of armed rebellion and secession.

Stabilization phase

In order to consolidate the achieved results, the aggressor state takes additional steps, which, presented as a way out of the situation, are positioned as the most appropriate and expedient for calming the situation. Various forms of supposedly democratic processes are organized, such as referendums, declarations, resignations for moral reasons, etc. after which, and if some element does not fit into their plans, there may be specific military-police attacks or the use of informal units as special forces formed for that purpose by the aggressor state. The ultimate political goal of this type of warfare is to prevent the independent existence of the attacked state in that format of social order and with that political and economic capacity. The attacked state is no longer able to conduct an independent foreign policy at a time when it loses territory, population, resources and credibility. Hybrid war is a conceptual departure from the classical theory of armed conflicts and in its conceptual definition contains positions that are found in postmodernist theories of war. The essence of the new observation is that the dominant use of armed force, which means the destruction and annihilation of the enemy, is losing its importance.

The focus of action is on "taking over the enemy" and engaging him in fulfilling one's own interests. This approach is significantly conditioned by globalization, the technological revolution and the general dominance of the neoliberal concept, where the imperative is actually economic interest and market expansion. It has been shown that hybrid warfare includes traditional and non-traditional, i.e. military and non-military ways of waging war, with the expansion of its action into a sphere that is not exclusively military. It is also a new view of such an important social phenomenon as war. Given the wide range of actions that can be used in a hybrid military operation, it is quite certain that non-military forms will initially be given priority over options that involve the direct engagement of military capacities¹⁰¹. Their diversity and flexibility in application indicate the need for constant monitoring and study of this type of action, so that the state can develop the ability to early recognize and quickly find an appropriate response to non-military hybrid threats. It is clear that larger and richer states have an advantage in this, and therefore weaker ones must make greater efforts and demonstrate institutional readiness,

¹⁰¹ Мирослав Митровиќ, „Економски и енергетски аспекти на хибридната закана за националната безбедност“, Воено дело 6/2017, 304-315.

which implies the integration of all state and social capacities, for a correct and timely reaction.¹⁰²

Possible ways of managing the masses, i.e. public opinion, in order to achieve the goals of certain interest groups that can be identified with hybrid action against a certain state, are recognized through:

(1) Influence on the value system and insistence on dominant positions that glorify new "democratic" values in the image of developed Western democracies;

(2) Formation of various groups of like-minded people (civic groups, cultural centres, political parties, non-governmental organizations, etc.) who represent the protagonists of certain values that are common or formulate them as common for the purpose of a controlled appearance in order to emphasize the "difference" in relation to public opinion that supports the current regime and problematizing all those issues on which the "difference" is established;

(3) Strong propaganda activity and increased action through all media forms, constantly emphasizing the difference and deviation from the regime and its supporters, which leads to increased antagonism towards dissenters (clearer establishment of the relations between the old and the new, the undemocratic and the democratic, the backward and the progressive, etc.);

(4) Establishment of "democratic" public opinion as the main driver of political change, based on the demonization of the current regime and the trivialization of the existing value system that created or supports the current regime.

"Colour revolutions", as an element of hybrid war

"Colour revolutions" are also an element of hybrid wars. "Colour revolutions" in fact, represent a type of coup, which is mainly realized with a non-violent type of resistance to the regime, with the active participation of the masses in street demonstrations, with political and financial support from outside¹⁰³.

"Colour revolutions" are essentially special operations of hybrid warfare aimed at carrying out a coup d'état, which are carried out using political, information, communication, sabotage-terrorist and moral-psychological methods of influence in gross violation of international law¹⁰⁴. The goals of such illegal activities can be the complete or partial disintegration of the state, a qualitative change in its internal or foreign policy, the replacement of the state leadership with loyal regimes, the establishment of external

¹⁰² The challenges faced by weaker states, as noted, are further compounded by conditions of systemic, endemic corruption and organized crime. Addressing these challenges requires qualitatively radical, structural reforms within key systems and subsystems, as emphasized by Miodrag Labović in his scholarly study, "Системско владеење на правото против системската корупција и организираниот криминал- Стратешка визија со конкретни реално одржливи и практично спроведливи решенија за нашите најголеми проблеми- Како Македонија може да стане функционална држава"., Култура Скопје, 2024 Integrating insights from this work could provide valuable guidance for designing effective institutional strategies and ensuring timely and comprehensive state responses.

¹⁰³ Милош Р. Миленковиќ*, Мирослав Митровиќ, Обојене револуције у парадигми хибридног рата

¹⁰⁴ Игор Н. Панарин, Хибридни рат, теорија и пракса, Београд 2019 година, стр.325.

control over the state, its criminalization and subordination to the dictates of other states or transnational corporations.¹⁰⁵

This type of revolution most often occurs in such a way that first certain so-called non-governmental organizations and intelligence services in certain countries form political and civil associations and strengthen them to the point where they become strong enough to oppose the legal government¹⁰⁶. Such strength is not valued through the prism of strength expressed through conventional or unconventional capacities and resources, but through the ability to impose opinions, spread disinformation, build awareness of powerlessness, lethargy and hopelessness. Such conditions correspond to the imposition of opinions that the current government is not competent, does not work in the interest of the citizens, but rather the opposite. The conditions of hopelessness and apathy among citizens do not provide an opportunity to identify threats that are imposed. Therefore, most often the people accept such conditions and believe that they will succeed in obtaining positive power and favourable conditions for a normal life.

However, one of the characteristics of "colour revolutions" is that the level of explicit violence is relatively low. That is why today the Internet, social networks and modern electronic devices are used to mobilize the masses. Mass communication, based on modern technologies, is particularly suitable for managing public opinion as the broadest generator of group motivation. The masses, or public opinion, represent a social category prone to management, significantly less stable than the value system and political culture. It can be assumed that certain foreign or domestic factors can raise a certain issue that would raise it high in the focus of public opinion in the countries that are objects of hybrid action, especially those that relate to poverty reduction, "democratization of society", reduction of corruption, etc. In this way, they manage public opinion according to their interests, seducing the group that is the object of action, by inducing or manipulating their attitudes and interests. The processes of managing the motivation and action of the masses are influenced by several factors, and among them they differ and manifest themselves as leaders or creators of public opinion, political events, mass media, personal contacts, group or party indoctrination. By managing the above-mentioned actors and processes, an efficient and targeted reaction of the target population is achieved, in accordance with their dominant public opinion that is created or tense.

The role of modern technologies and social networks available via the Internet has greatly facilitated the preparation, animation of individuals and the organization of protests, starting from mobilizing as many members as possible by distributing pamphlets, ideas and propaganda messages, to developing detailed action plans. In the past, actors of conspiratorial, subversive actions gathered in public buildings or private apartments, in order to avoid identification, but today such "meetings" are mainly organized in the virtual world. In the example of the "colour revolutions", this could look like the widespread social network Facebook, especially among younger people, which is the most common target group in this type of "warfare", and would be used to distribute ideas, recruit members and strive for more massive support for the movement to change the current

¹⁰⁵ Broader consideration about "colored revolutions", their role and practical consequences, see in: Миодраг Лабовиќ, "Системско владеење на правото против системската корупција и организираниот криминал- Стратешка визија со конкретни реално одржливи и практично спроведливи решенија за нашите најголеми проблеми- Како Македонија може да стане функционална држава", Култура Скопје, 2024, стр. 249-259

¹⁰⁶ <http://www.ceopom-istina.rs/politika-i-drustvo/hibridni-rat-tehnologije-protiv-obojenih-revolutsija/?lang=lat>

government. In this way, modern technology and social networks enable easier and faster formation of a movement for reaction and mobilization of citizens. Indeed, their importance and role have been confirmed in practice, in the Arab Spring and the events in Kiev, Ukraine.

Considering the various forms of violent regime change, starting from traditional methods of regime change, to the “colour revolution”, which is considered a more modern action, we can conclude that “colour revolutions” represent the most logical and likely choice for changing the current government in a certain country, implemented as a segment of the hybrid war. There are claims that the “colour revolution”, i.e. the change of government, is actually the last phase of the hybrid war: “In fact, the “colour revolution” is the last phase of the hybrid war, the phase in which the change of government in the country, which is subjected to hybrid aggression, takes place”¹⁰⁷.

If the colour revolutions fail, the next stage follows in which certain victims of such a revolution become rebels or terrorists, and armed intervention begins against such groups. For example, after the failure of the "Arab Spring" in Syria, the fight against terrorism began, with the US and its allies providing open support to certain rebel groups, calling them "moderate rebels", with the aim of overthrowing the then current president Bashar al-Assad¹⁰⁸. The same thing happened with the rebels in Ukraine in the Donbass, who received covert support from Russia.

According to their characteristics, it can be said that colour revolutions are a kind of "hybrids", that is, a combination of a coup d'état and a classic revolution. Just like a coup d'état, there is a change in the holder of state power, without broader social changes (without changes to the state system and the economic and political system), with a certain role of the national army and other bodies from the security and intelligence sphere (this time more passive), as well as with support from an external factor. The similarity with classical revolutions, apart from the name, is also the significant role of citizens in the realization of this type of action.

The name "revolution" is used because it arouses positive feelings and expectations of progressive change. For the success of "colour revolutions", the ability of the main "players" of the coup, the inspirers and organizers is also very important. The constant need for messages and information that are placed in the public, should ideologically, and not only technically, be able to easily reach as many citizens as possible, and success is assessed through the degree of persuasiveness of them to animate and put under control as many people as possible. Of course, colour revolutions do not represent spontaneous animating of citizens, but rather a well-thought-out and planned campaign with clear and well-targeted messages. As in other types of coups, a large number of actors in colour revolutions, primarily street protesters, are not fully aware of their true role in the events taking place, due to the different forms of understanding the messages and the different interests they want to achieve¹⁰⁹. Without taking all this into account, they are used in numbers as evidence of mass anti-government sentiment, and if necessary, in the event of intervention by government security forces, they can also serve as a living wall and protection for the true bearers and leaders of the movement, driven by the euphoria of

¹⁰⁷ See in: Итан Буено де Мескита, Промена на режимот и револуционерни претприемачи, Американски преглед на политички науки, том 104, бр. 3 (август 2010), стр. 446.

¹⁰⁸ Кире Јанев – „Хибридни војни“ – Партизан Проект Тетово, 2021

¹⁰⁹ Милош Р. Миленковић* , Мирослав Митровић, Обојене револуције у парадигми хибридног рата, достапно на: <file:///C:/Users/Kire/Downloads/71-2019-6-17-MilenkovicMitrovic%20.pdf>

the crowd. The factors on which the success of colour revolutions depends can be divided into external and internal. External factors are proportionally equal to the interests at the geopolitical and geostrategic level of perception of the great powers, while internal factors are perceived through the conditions, events and social power of the state, primarily the economic and political power of the state in which the colour revolution takes place¹¹⁰. Internal factors include:

- weakness and small number of forces of the central government;
- corruption;¹¹¹
- pronounced economic inequality and tensions;
- interethnic and interreligious conflicts within the country;
- lack of vision for the future (especially pronounced among young people).

How often these so-called colour revolutions occur can be seen from the claim of the American journalist and publicist Wayne Madsen, who claims that as many as 64 colour revolutions were organized by the United States alone¹¹²¹¹³. Such examples are: the "Rose" Revolution in Georgia, the "Orange Revolution" in Ukraine, the Lebanese "Kedra" Revolution, the "Olive Revolution" in Palestine, the "Tulip Revolution" in Kyrgyzstan, and the list also includes coups in Yugoslavia, Kuwait, Libya, Burma, Tibet, Iran, Egypt, Tunisia, Syria and other countries, and similar revolutions were also predicted in Moldova, Mongolia, Uzbekistan, Ecuador, Bolivia and Belarus.

The most serious consequences were left by the "Euromaidan" colour revolution in Ukraine, with the coup in 2013-14, which was followed in 2014 by an internal civil war between the government and the Russian minority in Ukraine. The demonstrators, "democratically" called "Euromaidan" on one hand, and the opponents of the demonstrators called "Antimaidan".

Protests or Euromaidans in support of the "colourful revolution" in Ukraine were organized in parallel starting on November 24, 2013 by countries such as Poland, Great Britain, Germany, France, Italy, Sweden, Austria, Czech Republic, Bulgaria, the United States and Canada¹¹⁴.

New "colour revolution" followed. In that region, a "colourful revolution" was taking place in Georgia, which failed to overthrow the elected government there. The President of Georgia, Salome Zourabichvili, who is a French citizen and an associate of Zbigniew Brzezinski, an advisor in the American governments of Reagan and Jimmy Carter, and strongly supported by the EU, did not recognize the elected government of the "Georgian Dream" party in 2023 after the elections, and then the presidential elections in 2024, which were won by Mikhail Kavelashvili, and called for protests that took place.

¹¹⁰ Andrew Korybko, *Hybrid Wars: The Indirect Adaptive Approach to Regime Change*, Peoples Friendship University of Russia, Moscow, 2015, p. 35.

¹¹¹ Miodrag Labovic: *Policing in Central and Eastern Europe – Social Control of Unconventional Deviance*, Conference Proceedings, Social control of institutional organized crime, 2011, стр. 194, 200, 208 <https://www.ncjrs.gov/pdffiles1/nij/Mesko/235122.pdf>

¹¹² Милош Р. Миленковић* , Мирослав Митровић, *Обојене револуције у парадигми хибридног рата*, достапно на: <///C:/Users/Kire/Downloads/71-2019-6-17-MilenkovicMitrovic%20.pdf>

¹¹³ Илья Вадимович Максимов, *«Цветная» революция – социальный процесс или сетевая технология?*, Монография, Москва, 2010, стр. 8.

¹¹⁴ <https://www.blic.rs/vesti/svet/svet/vejn-medsen-amerika-sirom-sveta-organizovala-64-obojene-revolucije-medu-kojima-je-i/stnnqk7>

The first to appear at the protests, as usual, were schoolchildren and students, and then people organized into violent groups and people from other countries appeared.

Unlike Ukraine, there were no armed clashes in Georgia, no paramilitary units formed by the two opposing sides. The European Union, which granted Georgia candidate status for accession in 2023, withdrew its decision, and the new Georgian government, after the protests, decided to freeze its application for EU membership until 2028.

The bloody fist and the bloody hand, the symbol of the coloured (colourful) revolutions, we are seeing up close now in Serbia with the blockades for more than a year, were seen all over the world. The pattern is the same, as with all "colourful revolutions", the last initiative of the Serbian blockaders, after the unsuccessful ten-month demonstrations, blockades and violence, is the public call to act as in Nepal.

In Nepal, the bloody "colour revolution" took over 30 people in 48 hours, half of whom, not in riots, but in public, mass murders of political opponents. Officially, 22 murders and a dozen "disappearances" were reported. During the protests in Bangladesh, on Capitol Hill and during the riots in Kathmandu, it is estimated that it was the work of such colour revolutions. This choreography was also seen in 2003 in Albania, when the non-governmental organization "mjaft!", which translates as enough, launched a campaign against corruption with violence.

The initial cause, the death of 15 people from a canopy collapse at the Novi Sad railway station, is no longer mentioned by anyone. They are demanding a government without elections or elections organized by the blockaders, the secession of Vojvodina and the recognition of Kosovo.

In Portugal, in Lisbon, 21 people recently died from a cable car collapse, but there was no "colour revolution". Portugal is not yet ripe for "democracy".

This form of hybrid action also existed in our country, namely, on May 5, 2016, the so-called "Colourful Revolution" took place. Through the publication of the so-called "bombs" of the largest opposition party, SDSM. A large number of journalists and civic activists were given "folders" with their wiretapped conversations¹¹⁵. The Colourful Revolution took place under the slogan "No Justice, No Peace" and had eight demands:

- withdrawal of the decision to abolish;
- resignation of President Ivanov;
- pronouncement of the Constitutional Court on the constitutionality of the SPO;
- establishment of a special department of the Criminal Court competent for SPO cases;
- withdrawal of the decision to hold parliamentary elections on June 5, 2016;
- participation of independent representatives of civil society in resolving the crisis;
- the crisis to be resolved on the territory of Macedonia; and
- formation of a transitional government that will implement the urgent reform priorities from the Priebe Report.

In the following period, civil protests for the resignation of the Government continued, and with the mediation of the European Union and the United States, political

¹¹⁵ Од Букурешт до Преспа, Сведоштва на едно време Македонија 2008 - 2018, Фондација Отворено општество – Македонија, Скопје, 2020, стр242, достапно на: <https://fosm.mk/wp-content/uploads/2020/02/foom-od-bukurest-do-prespa-mk-za-web.pdf>

talks began to resolve the political crisis and to ensure conditions for fair and democratic elections, which ended with the signing of the Pržino Agreement on June 2 and its annex on July 15. An important feature of the "colourful" protests was the absence of any party symbols, but also the presence of tens of thousands of independent citizens and members of various opposition parties. Over time, some protesters became visible and recognizable faces of the resistance, but it had no leader. The operation was conducted in 4 phases¹¹⁶:

- creation of a crisis and destabilization of the state;
- compromising the government and institutions;
- change of government and bringing in a new one;
- realization of the set goals.

All the facts support the thesis that the "colour revolution" and the events of April 27, 2017 are the result of a hybrid war¹¹⁷.

"Colour revolutions" or insurgency

We have examined the basis of the "coloured" or "colourful" revolutions. Due to their development into a possible direct conflict expressed with the use of conventional weapons, it is necessary to make a distinction from insurgency or to show where "coloured" revolutions merge or distance themselves from insurgency. Insurgency is presented as a set of activities of an organized, often ideologically motivated group or movement, which aims to cause or prevent political change by the ruling authorities, focusing on persuading and intimidating the population using violence or subversion. Insurgency uses violent and non-violent tactics to achieve the goals of the organization that "rebelled". Nonviolent tactics are used to achieve political goals without the use of force. Violent tactics are usually used in combination with nonviolent tactics. Using a combination of these two tactics, supported by propaganda, helps recruit new fighters, as well as gain popular support. Insurgency is inherently an asymmetric threat. Asymmetric warfare is a conflict in which a weaker adversary uses unusual surprise tactics to attack the weak points of a stronger adversary. Such tactics include: terrorism, guerrilla warfare, criminal activities, subversion or propaganda¹¹⁸. Violent tactics of insurgency include: terrorism, guerrilla warfare, sabotage, or conventional operations. Rebels often use terrorism and guerrilla warfare as tactics to achieve their goals, because they do not have the ability to oppose the government or counterinsurgency forces with conventional operations. Subversion and propaganda are the two most common forms of nonviolent struggle. Terrorism, due to the diversity of forms and methods that can be used, is an acceptable tool for action of the insurgent group, which independently chooses the goals of action, makes decisive plans and uses maximum conspiratoriality to realize the tasks¹¹⁹. Later, in order to cause fear, unrest, panic, distrust in the institutions of the system, publicly through the media, they take responsibility for the event and thereby identify themselves in the public, often with a clear interpretation of the goals and demands, and also advertise themselves for the effect of possible massification and expansion of their ranks through quality and gradual selection.

¹¹⁶ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=liSc995tSQM&feature=youtu.be>

¹¹⁷ Нормално конкретни докази за инволвираност тешко дека ќе може да се пронајдат, ниту пак посочените држави би го признале евентуалното учество во овие настани, нешто што е карактеристично токму за хибридните војни

¹¹⁸ FM 3-24.2, Tactics in counterinsurgency, Headquarters Department of the Army, Washington, DC, 2009, p. 2-20.

¹¹⁹ З. Димовски, Тероризам, Графотранс, Скопје, 2007

A common denominator for most rebel groups is their goal of gaining control over the population or a certain territory, including its resources. This goal distinguishes rebel groups from terrorist organizations. According to Bard O'Neill, insurgency is probably the most widespread type of armed conflict since the creation of organized political communities. He defines insurgency as "a comprehensive concept that refers to a conflict between a government and a group or opponent that uses both political resources and violence to change, reformulate, or adhere to the legitimacy of one or more of four key aspects of politics". The four key aspects are¹²⁰:

- integrity of the borders and composition of the nation-state;
- the political system;
- the government;
- the policies that determine who gets what in society.

A very important segment for politicians and security agencies in preventing insurgency is the concept of incipient insurgency. The concept of incipient insurgency covers the period before the insurgency and the organizational phases of the insurgent conflict¹²¹. It refers to situations in which subversive activity by an undeveloped insurgent group is only a potential threat to governments where anti-government incidents occur frequently, where the organization is recognizable to the public, and its activities in the future can be recognized and predicted. A revolutionary group that aims to become an insurgent must, at a minimum, aim to build the organization, carry out selection and recruitment, train people, obtain material and other values, present its beliefs and goals, etc. The group may also choose to incite riots or work stoppages, infiltrate the legitimate political apparatus, and engage in terrorism as a means of promotion. If more than one of these signs is present and their magnitude is high, it can be concluded that the group has engaged in these activities and poses a more serious threat. These are classified as preparatory activities. The most alarming signs – those that will almost certainly signal the beginning of a serious insurgency threat – include significant foreign aid, either from governments or from other insurgent or extremist groups, receiving guerrilla training, acquiring large amounts of resources for carrying out actions, and creating an organization that is most often composed of two wings: a political and a conspiratorial military wing. The difference with "coloured" revolutions is obvious, and especially concerns the inspirers, the members of the group, the way of "working", intergroup relations and the way of communicating with the people, plans, goals, and methods of action. According to these characteristics, insurgency stands out as a special way of acting, although the goals are identical to the emergence of "coloured" revolutions, but it represents support for certain initiatives and the achievement of an appropriate goal.

¹²⁰ Aaron M Young, David H. Gray, *Insurgency, Guerilla Warfare and Terrorism: Conflict and its Application for the Future*, стр.2, достапно на:
<http://globalsecuritystudies.com/Young%20Insurgency%20FINAL.pdf>

¹²¹ Кире Јанев- „Хибридни војни„-Партизан Проект Тетово, 2021

CONCLUSION

From the above, we can conclude that "colour revolutions" and according to the content of the measures and goals represent a hybrid form of action. They actually represent a type of coup d'état that is carried out mainly through "non-violent" resistance to the current government, with the active participation of groups of citizens through street demonstrations, but also with political and financial support from outside from other states, institutions, terrorist organizations. According to their characteristics, "colour revolutions" can be said to be a type of "hybrid" or a combination of a coup d'état and a classic revolution. Given that "colour revolutions" emphasize the importance of citizen participation as one of the dominant actors, they are essentially reduced to a measure of populist dominance. However, their success does not depend on that and whether the majority of the population in a country or city actively supports the idea of a "color revolution", but rather the fact that the inspirers and organizers of mass protests gather a sufficiently large number of people who, with their actions, messages and activities, pose a security challenge to the government. The size depends on each individual country, on the characteristics of its leadership, the economic and political strength of the government and the ability of its security apparatus (police, army, judiciary) to face these types of security risks. Social dominance is achieved at the moment when this "critical mass", which has risen to overthrow the current government, expects an inadequate and "chaotic" reaction from the government. After that, the initiative is on the side of the protesters, who, with active help from abroad, more easily manage to bring about a change of government. The ability of coup supporters, instigators and organizers to convey certain messages and information to the public and for them to easily reach as many citizens as possible, ideologically and not just technically, is extremely important for the success of "colour revolutions". In creating and managing information, all the knowledge and skills of propaganda and public relations are used, supported by the Internet and modern means of communication. "Colour revolutions" are therefore not spontaneous gatherings of citizens, but a well-thought-out and planned campaign with clear and very focused messages. As with many types of coups, a large number of actors in "colour revolutions", primarily street demonstrators, are not fully aware of their true role in the events taking place. Regardless, they are used as evidence of mass anti-government sentiment, and if necessary, in the event of intervention by government security forces, they can also serve as a "human wall" and protection for the true bearers and leaders of the movement.

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TEAMWORK IN THE CUSTOMS ADMINISTRATION

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Abstract

Teamwork is a formal organizational approach that aligns the predefined goals and tasks of the Customs Administration with its overarching mission. As a work arrangement, teamwork fosters a collaborative environment, generates positive energy, and enhances organizational performance – particularly in terms of productivity and efficiency among customs officers.

A core rationale for promoting teamwork within the Customs Administration is the concept of synergy phenomenon in which the combined efforts of multiple elements result in a greater impact than the sum of their individual contributions. Customs teams can achieve synergy through various channels, including technological, managerial, psychological, and market-based sources.

- **Technological synergy** arises from the transfer of knowledge between different operational or functional domains.
- **Managerial synergy** is achieved by applying expertise from one area of work to another, often relying on “consulting knowledge”, which is particularly adaptable and transferable across teams.

This paper examines the role of teamwork in the Customs Administration and emphasizes its significance in achieving the institution’s vision and mission.

Keywords: teamwork, teams, human resources, customs officer performance

1. INTRODUCTION

Human resource management in the Customs Administration is a complex and demanding function, as each customs officer possesses distinct characteristics, competencies, and motivations. Human resources form the foundation of the Administration’s success, and managerial effectiveness is reflected in the degree to which customs teams are cohesive, adaptable, and efficient. In this context, successful management depends on the ability to recruit and develop highly capable, flexible, and talented officers who, through effective organization and coordination, can substantially enhance the institution’s overall productivity and performance.

Complex challenges in contemporary customs operations cannot be addressed by individuals alone; they require the coordinated efforts of cohesive teams. Consequently, the team-based approach is widely recognized as one of the most effective solutions to the organizational and operational challenges that arise in today’s dynamic and globalized environment. Human individuality and collective identity are expressed and reinforced through participation in groups and organizations. Historically, the majority of significant

human achievements have been realized through collective action, while the notion that outstanding results stem solely from individual effort is increasingly challenged as a myth (Battaglini & Palfrey, 2024).

2. TEAMWORK IN CUSTOMS

The concept of teamwork, rooted in Western business philosophy, represents an effective mechanism for addressing complex organizational problems, provided it is managed professionally. Core managerial competence lies not merely in forming a group, but in establishing a cohesive team that integrates the activities of the entire organization and contributes to the achievement of its strategic objectives. A team can be defined as a collective of individuals who collaborate in pursuit of a clearly defined goal (Poleac, 2023).

Within the Customs Administration, teams are capable of performing a diverse range of functions, including developing professional relationships, providing services, negotiating contracts, conducting market research, coordinating projects, offering advisory support, and facilitating decision-making processes. Compared with traditional hierarchical departments, teams demonstrate greater flexibility and responsiveness to change, thereby enhancing institutional adaptability.

Recent empirical evidence indicates that effective teamwork significantly improves organizational productivity, accelerates the exchange of knowledge and ideas, enhances the execution of operational tasks, boosts motivation and achievement, and increases workforce flexibility (Saud & Rice, 2024).

Similar effects have been observed in Japan and the United Kingdom, where multidisciplinary teams increase organizational creativity by 30–40% (Thelwall & Maflahi, 2019).

The inherent complexity of customs operations, combined with the broad spectrum of challenges to be addressed, necessitates a reliance on teamwork. The rapidly evolving external environment requires prompt and comprehensive institutional responses, grounded in interdisciplinary expertise, which can only be achieved through coordinated team efforts.

2.1 Criteria for Selecting Team Members in the Customs Administration

The effectiveness of teamwork within the Customs Administration largely depends on the careful selection of suitable members. This process must be guided by well-defined criteria to ensure both competence and cohesion. General criteria for selecting team members include (Salas, 2006):

- Required technical knowledge and expertise
- Previous experience in teamwork
- Strong communication skills
- Relevant professional experience
- Willingness to accept responsibility
- Appropriate formal qualifications
- Psycho-physical capability

2.2 Criteria for Selecting Team Leaders

The criteria for selecting a team leader extend beyond those applied to regular team members. In addition to possessing technical knowledge and formal qualifications, a leader must demonstrate:

- Managerial skills, including coordination, communication, decision-making, risk-taking, and accountability,
- Comprehensive professional knowledge and expertise,
- Interpersonal and motivational skills necessary for effectively leading people (Salas, 2006).

While a leader should not differ substantially from team members in terms of intelligence, values, or education, they must embody superior qualities that secure authority and legitimacy. The leader serves both as a point of identification for the team and as a key instrument in achieving the team's objectives.

Within the team structure, the leader occupies a central position and performs multiple functions, which may include: executive authority, strategist, planner, ideologist, expert, organizer, controller, arbitrator.

Although these responsibilities primarily rest with the leader, many must be shared with the team, as the collective success ultimately depends on all members. Therefore, the role of a leader within a customs team closely parallels the role of managers in formal organizational structures, combining authority, guidance, and collaboration to ensure the team's effectiveness. In Germany, research shows that leaders who actively share responsibilities improve team outcomes by 15–20% compared with strictly hierarchical approaches (Müller & Turner, 2010).

2.3 Teamwork as an Organizational Response

The Customs Programme 2021–2027 of the European Commission emphasizes capacity building, staff training, and cross-border cooperation among customs administrations (European Commission, 2021). In the Western Balkans region, customs leaders from multiple countries reaffirmed in 2025 their commitment to deeper integration, real-time data exchange, and inter-agency cooperation under the theme “Customs Partnership for a Connected Europe”.

At the global level, the World Customs Organization (WCO)'s 2020–2021 Annual Report highlights knowledge sharing, joint operations, and institutional cooperation as core elements in modern customs administrations. Hence, teamwork within customs administrations is not only an internal organizational strategy but also a key mechanism to align with supranational programmes and regional cooperation frameworks.

2.4 Team Categories

Within the Customs Administration, teams can be characterized and managed along multiple dimensions, such as functional scope, temporal duration, leadership structure, and membership expertise. The selection of an appropriate team type depends on task complexity, organizational structure, and the composition of team members (Choi & Miller, 2023).

Depending on their purpose, teams can be configured in various ways. In practice, the following categories are most frequently identified:

- **Problem-Solving Teams** – Typically established to resolve internal issues within a limited timeframe (usually less than one year). Membership is mandatory, and these teams tend to be reactive and tactical in nature.
- **Task Teams** – Composed of highly specialized members drawn from different organizational functions, convened to address complex problems requiring advanced expertise.
- **Cross-Functional Teams** – Include members from diverse functional areas of the organization. Their primary role is to analyse issues, recommend alternatives, and solve complex problems. Unlike advisory teams, cross-functional teams are also responsible for implementing their recommendations. Members are often narrowly specialized or highly qualified.
- **Self-Managing Teams** – Responsible for managing their own internal processes and operations. These teams exhibit the highest degree of autonomy and development, often exercising control over decisions typically reserved for human resources (e.g., recruitment, dismissal, scheduling, remuneration). They may also manage budgets, interact with customers, and possess authority to improve work methods.
- **Research and Development (R&D) Teams** – Generally temporary in nature, these teams focus on developing new systems, methods, or products. They are often cross-functional and consist of experts with diverse backgrounds and specialized experience.

In South Korea and Singapore, R&D teams in customs and public administration have led to faster adoption of digital systems and process innovation (Lee & Kim, 2021).

3. SYNERGY IN TEAMWORK

One of the primary foundations and justifications for teamwork within the Customs Administration is synergy. Synergy can be defined as the phenomenon whereby two or more elements working together produce a greater effect than the sum of their individual contributions. Within a team, synergy emerges because discussions among members generate more alternatives, eliminate weaker options, reduce errors, and foster creative thinking (Rakicevic, 2007).

Synergy is often illustrated as the “2+2=5 effect.”

Customs teams can achieve synergy from several sources, most notably: technological, managerial, psychological, and market synergy.

- Technological synergy arises from transferring knowledge from one type of production or process to another, enhancing efficiency and innovation.
- Managerial synergy occurs when knowledge is shared across different areas of work. This is often facilitated by consulting expertise, which can be easily disseminated among teams, thereby generating managerial synergy.
- Psychological synergy is achieved when team members’ interactions promote mutual support, trust, and motivation, leading to higher engagement and collective problem-solving capabilities.

- Market synergy results from combining insights from various departments or functions to better understand customer needs, adapt services, and improve institutional responsiveness to market trends.

By effectively harnessing these sources of synergy, customs teams can significantly enhance organizational performance, foster innovation, and improve decision-making.

4. MANAGEMENT TEAMS

Within the Customs Administration, a **management team** refers to a group of managers at the same organizational level who report to a common supervisor. These teams convene regularly to share information, coordinate decisions, and address issues that affect either the entire organization or a specific department. They constitute an essential component of the formal management structure.

The number of management teams depends on the size of the organization. Small organizations may have only one team, whereas larger institutions typically have several teams operating at different levels of the hierarchy. According to McIntyre (2000), there are three main types of management teams:

- **Low-level management teams** focus on the day-to-day supervision of employees responsible for executing specific operational tasks required to produce and deliver goods and services.
- **Middle-level management teams** supervise lower-level managers and determine how to best utilize personnel and other resources to achieve organizational goals. These teams often include managers with specialized expertise in areas such as finance, marketing, or human resources.
- **Top-level management teams** consist of senior leaders who set organizational strategies, define long-term goals, and provide direction for the entire institution. Typically composed of five to seven members, these teams function most effectively when they encompass diverse expertise and perspectives—from finance, marketing, production, and engineering—because such diversity strengthens decision-making and mitigates the risk of groupthink, in which the desire for consensus overrides critical evaluation.

Building a high-performing management team requires time and sustained effort. Members must develop mutual understanding, establish trust, and cultivate shared working practices. Given the pivotal role these teams play in organizational success, understanding the factors that contribute to their effectiveness remains both a practical imperative for leaders and a significant challenge for researchers.

5. MEASURING TEAM PERFORMANCE

Accurately measuring the performance of customs teams is of critical importance to the Customs Administration. This process demands substantial time and effort, as the success of individual teams ultimately influences the overall effectiveness of the organization. Consequently, effective managers—those capable of fostering strong relationships among team members and establishing clear channels of communication—play a decisive role in the success of any project undertaken by a team. In such an environment, team members are better positioned to acquire new skills and knowledge that can be applied in future tasks.

A fundamental aspect of performance assessment is the opportunity it provides for team members to receive feedback on their contributions. Feedback serves to identify errors, facilitates their correction, and helps prevent their recurrence. As a result, team members continuously enhance their individual skills and knowledge, thereby raising overall performance levels to meet the expectations of managers, the organization, and the broader professional environment.

Managers must establish appropriate performance benchmarks for their teams and possess the expertise to evaluate both individual and collective performance against these benchmarks. Achieving this requires not only strong managerial skills but also a comprehensive understanding of the specific challenges the team is tasked with addressing. Comparative studies in France and Denmark show that teams with clearly defined performance metrics report higher efficiency, reduced errors, and greater job satisfaction (Larsen & Dubois, 2016).

6. CONCLUSION

There is no longer any doubt regarding the positive impact of teamwork on the efficiency of the Customs Administration. Teamwork is recognized globally as a highly valuable professional competence. Both scholars studying the phenomenon and practitioners applying it in organizations consistently emphasize its beneficial effects. This confirms that teamwork provides numerous advantages for employees, the organization as a whole, and the stakeholders it serves.

Within the Customs Administration, teamwork fosters greater creativity, enhances employee motivation, accelerates task execution, and encourages shared responsibility. It contributes to workforce flexibility, generates synergy of ideas and skills, and promotes innovative approaches to problem-solving. Teamwork also strengthens decision-making by improving the acceptance, understanding, and implementation of decisions, while enhancing autonomy, diversity, and commitment to achieving common goals. Ultimately, these factors translate into increased organizational productivity.

Beyond measurable outcomes, teamwork improves communication among customs officers, builds unity and team spirit, and cultivates a stronger sense of enthusiasm and energy. These qualities, in turn, elevate motivation levels and overall performance. The mutual support and assistance that team members provide one another, particularly in challenging situations, further contribute to superior results.

In essence, teamwork is not only a practical instrument but also a strategic necessity, enabling the Customs Administration to pursue and achieve its vision and mission more effectively.

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